

**PERCEPTIONS OF HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS OF
INFECTION PREVENTION AND CONTROL PRACTICES IN
KINGDOM OF SAUDI ARABIA:**

A MIXED METHODS STUDY.

BY

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ABHRs	Alcohol-Based Hand Rubs
AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
APIC	Association of Professional in Infection Control
BI	blood infections
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
CNS	Coagulase Negative Staphylococcal
COREQ	Consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative research
E. coli	Escherichia Coli
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
ENT	Ear, Nose, and Throat Department
ER	Emergency department
GCC	Gulf Cooperation Countries
H1N1	Influenza A
H5N1	Avian flu
HAIs	Healthcare-Associated Infections
HBM	The Health Belief Model
HCWs	Healthcare Workers
HIS	Healthcare Improvement Scotland
HIV	Immunodeficiency Virus
HOSPITAL 1	King Fahad Specialised Hospital
HOSPITAL 2	Buraidah Central Hospital
ICU	Intensive care unit
IPC	Infection Prevention and Control
KP	Klebsiella pneumoniae
KSA	Kingdom of Saudi Arabia
MENA	Middle East & North Africa
MERS-CoV	Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus
MOH	Ministry of Health
MRSA	methicillin resistant Staphylococcal aureus
MSSA	methicillin-sensitive S. aureus
NHS	National Services Scotland
NHSN	National Health Safety Network
OC	Organisational Culture
PA	Pseudomonas Areoginosa
PD	Positive Deviance
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
RTI	respiratory tract infection
SA	Staphylococcal aureus
SAR	Saudi Arabian Riyal
SARS	Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome
SEIPS	Systems Engineering Initiative for Patient Safety
SENIC	Study on the Efficacy of Nosocomial Infection Control
SFDA	Saudi Health and Food Authority
SICPs	Standard Infection Control Precautions
SPIDER	Sample, Phenomena of Interest, Design, Evaluation and Research type framework
SSI	Surgical Site Infections
TB	Tuberculosis
TBPs	Transmission-Based Precautions
TPB	Theory of planned behaviour
TST	Tuberculin Skin Test
UTI	Urinary Tract Infections
VRE	vancomycin-resistant enterococcus
WHO	World Health Organisation

DECLARATION

I declare that this thesis and the research upon which it is based to be my own work and testify that it has not been accepted in any previous application for a degree, that all verbatim extracts have been distinguished by quotation marks, and that all sources of information have been acknowledged specifically.

Date: 19/08/2019

Signed: Adil Abalkhail

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

Papers

- Redefined model for semi-dry biofilms to assess enhanced tolerance to antibiotics and the environment. Amaeze N, Akinbobola A, **Abalkhail A**, Ramage G, Kean R, Williams C, Mackay.
- Prevalence and mortality of chronic lung diseases associated with COVID-19: a systematic review and meta-analysis Alkathami M, Advani S, **Abalkhail A**, Alshehri M, Alsalamah J, Alkathami F, Albeashy E. *In preparing*

Conference proceedings

- Infection Prevention and Control IPS Scottish Branch Conference 2017 on Wednesday 25th October 2017 at the DoubleTree by Hilton Hotel Glasgow Central. (**Oral +Poster presentation**).
- SHAIPI (Scottish Healthcare Associated Infection Prevention Institute): future collaboration and capacity building day Govan Mbeki Building, Glasgow Caledonian University as best poster Friday 10 March 2017 (**Poster presentation and prize for best poster in the event**).
- Conferences on challenges of Public Health for middle east in the United Arab Emirates UAE - Organized by Cleveland Clinic (**Poster presentation**).
- Infection Prevention and Control KSA conference which held place at the Al Faisaliah Center, in the heart of Riyadh, KSA. In October 2018 to learn about the latest research, science, innovation and discover real-world solutions in the challenge against improvements within Infection Prevention (**Oral presentation**).

Appreciation

- Certification of appreciation from the Saudi Culture Mission after choosing my project one of the best researchers of Saudi students in UK - 2017.
- Certification of appreciation from the Saudi Embassy as one of 50 Saudi best students in UK - 2018.
- Certification of appreciation from Ministry of Health MOH - KSA for the valuable support for the improvement of the infection and control program in during period data collection-2016.

PERSONAL STATEMENT

For many years, I have worked as a medical microbiologist with MOH and also worked as a clinical infection prevention and control practitioner. My interest in IPC and public health was initiated by my readings in this field, but in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA), infection control is a young, rapidly growing speciality. Therefore, I seek to pursue this highly professional and attractive field for my ambition to specialise in it.

My plans for my career have set this major as my priority because IPC public health specialists are very scarce in KSA. This area of study will help me contribute to filling this professional and academic gap in KSA. I hope to achieve this after I obtain my PhD degree. When I graduate, I plan to go back to KSA and work in this field in the Department of Public Health at my university. Among the other methods of doing this, I plan to establish a university level undergraduate and postgraduate training programmes such as BSc/MPH and recruit students from KSA and the Arab region into these degree and postgraduate degree programmes.

It is known that HAIs pose a significant clinical and economic burden worldwide and KSA faces unique challenges when addressing infection control especially due to Hajj and other factors. Infection prevention and control practices in my country (KSA) have not been explored in detail and this might be due to the stress and burden or lack of professionals among other factors. I therefore chose to research this area in particular in order to better understand the influence of perceptions on compliance with infection control practices and to identify factors which might further inform infection prevention and control practices there.

DEDICATION

In the name of Allah, the Most Gracious, the Most Merciful

الحمد لله الذي بنعمته تتم الصالحات هذه الرسالة أهديتها بكل الحب والعرفان إلى والدي الغالي ومعلمي
وقدوتي عالي المقام عبد الرحمن بن محمد أبا الخيل (رحمة الله عليه) وإلى والدتي الحبيبة وشمعة حياتي
الجوهرة بنت عبد العزيز المعتق ألبسها الله ثياب الصحة والعافية،
محبكم/ عادل بن عبد الرحمن أبا الخيل

This PhD thesis is dedicated to my mother for her love and emotional and material support throughout my life and my studies here in the United Kingdom. Also, this PhD thesis is dedicated to my late father, it has been more than 11 years since you departed. Every situation that I find myself in, I imagine your presence, sharing the happy moments with you. Thank you for everything. I appreciate your love. You have left me with great memories. You did great by encouraging me to do the right thing and commit myself in every undertaking as the only way of realizing achievement. I really miss your presence.

With Love

Adil

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ABSTRACT

Healthcare-Associated Infections (HAIs) lead to considerable morbidity, a prolonged hospital stay, antibiotic resistance, long-term disability, mortality and increased healthcare costs. Based on the literature, some individual and socio-demographic factors including knowledge, age and length of service or work experience, gender and type of profession influence compliance with infection prevention and control (IPC) procedures. In addition, organisational culture (OC), which refers to the assumptions, values, and norms shared among colleagues (Robbins et al., 2018) can influence an individual's thinking and behaviour either positively or negatively. This study aims to investigate the role of perceptions and socio-demographic and institutional factors in promoting infection control in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA).

To understand the perceptions of healthcare workers' (HCWs) of infection prevention and control and identify the factors associated with compliance with IPC practices in two tertiary hospitals in the Qassim region of KSA, a quantitative self-administered survey, semi-structured interviews and non-participatory structured observations were used. The findings from quantitative and qualitative data collected in a concurrent mixed methods research design were integrated to facilitate gaining a comprehensive understanding of infection control strategies, influences and challenges in two healthcare facilities in KSA.

The findings from the three sources of data show disagreements regarding the ways HCWs perceived the quality of IPC practices at their respective hospitals as they expressed their perceptions in the semi-structured interviews and the quantitative survey and the ways HCWs were observed implementing infection control practices in both hospitals. One of the key findings of qualitative interviews and quantitative survey indicates that the quality of infection control is good in both hospitals. However, the results of observation show poor infection control practices as demonstrated by implementing poor hand hygiene and cough hygiene practices as well as improper use of PPEs. Therefore, a key finding that observation suggests is having a gap between

HCWs' perceptions and the actual application of IPC practices as compliance with the recommended IPC practices was suboptimal in the hospitals included in this study.

Triangulating the results from the three data sources also shows some points of agreements. For example, the triangulated findings suggest that HCWs are aware of barriers and gaps in infection control and prevention in the two hospitals which need to be addressed to improve compliance with recommended IPC guidelines and policies. A number of factors were identified as contributing to HCWs' non-compliance with IPC practices primarily including the lack of sufficient supplies, the need for sustained high-quality training, shortage of IPC specialists and ineffective surveillance systems which are essential to improve infection control practices. A number of individual factors such as education, gender, profession, nationality and self-efficacy were associated with HCWs' perceptions of infection control quality. An important recommendation the study suggests is providing more investment in the provision of supplies, high quality training, proper staffing and effective monitoring mechanisms such as providing electronic monitoring in KSA hospitals.

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The purposes of this introductory chapter are to present the topic of this research study, clarify the study's aims and how it is organised as well as provide some background information on the research context. First, the chapter begins with presenting the statement of the problem. Second, the study's aims and significance will be highlighted. Third, the research questions and methodology will be provided. Fourth, the thesis structure will be explained. This will be followed by an examination of the global epidemiology of Healthcare-Associated Infections (HAIs) with a focus on developing countries. Some background information on the context of this study will be also provided such as the people, culture and healthcare system of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA). Finally, while discussing the status of infection control both globally and locally in KSA, this chapter outlines the strategies and challenges associated with the control of HAIs.

1.2 RESEARCH AIMS AND SIGNIFICANCE

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), there has been an overall increase in the incidences of HAIs around the world in both developed and developing countries, with an annual average prevalence of about 5%–10% in patients. Therefore, there are approximately 1.4 million people worldwide suffering from HAIs annually (Haque et al., 2018). It has been reported that the developing nations are 25% more at risk of acquiring HAIs compared to developed countries (Hassan et al., 2017; Mandoh et al., 2018) with high-income countries such as KSA having a prevalence of 7.1% (Colet et al., 2018).

As an example, the study conducted by Nofal et al., (2017) shows that healthcare workers (HCWs) may demonstrate a low level of knowledge of infection prevention and Control (IPC) measures. Many factors have been associated with non-compliance with infection control procedures globally including uncertainty among HCWs about infection prevention-related issues such as institution-specific problems, monitoring and reporting standards, readiness and competence to implement policies and countering outbreaks (Aboshaiqah and Baker, 2013). Socio-demographic factors are also considered among the contributing factors such as age and length of clinical experience (Timilshina et al., 2011; Desta et al., 2018). For instance, based on Desta et al., (2018), IPC knowledge and practices are affected by having years of experience in the hospital and older age. However, the role of other factors such as knowledge and HCWs' perceptions and attitudes on compliance with IPC practices have not been clearly demonstrated. For instance, while some studies have reported an association between knowledge and education and compliance with infection control practices in Hong Kong (Chang et al., 2014), Nepal, (Paudyal et al., 2008) and Jordan (Hassan, 2018), other studies such as Vaz et al., (2010), which is focused on Jamaica, found no significant relationship. Similarly, there is conflicting evidence regarding the association between perceptions and attitudes and compliance with hospital infection control.

Some studies have reported an association between HCWs' perceptions and compliance to various precautions (Suchitra and Devi, 2007; Darawad et al., 2012; Honarbakhsh et al., 2017). However, other studies such as Vaz et al., (2010) and Jain et al., (2012) showed no such association. For instance, Jain et al., (2012) which assessed the perception and practice of infection control measures among HCWs in Mangalore indicated that 85.8% of HCWs showed awareness of IPC measures, but only 55.7% were practicing it. Therefore, although HCWs showed good knowledge of IPC measures, their practices were poor (Jain et al., 2012).

In KSA, the local context of this study, increased cases of occupational infections observed among healthcare workers have been reported. For example, chicken pox was acquired when healthcare professionals, primarily nurses, did not follow established IPC guidelines appropriately, highlighting the need for procedures that aim to change the perceptions of HAIs in the KSA among nurses (Assiri et al., 2013). Furthermore, statistics from the Ministry of Health (MOH) indicate that in recent years, HAIs have increased in KSA and have presented a significant economic burden on the country (Balkhy et al., 2006; Gupta et al., 2017).

The MOH have embarked on efforts to achieve universal health coverage in KSA since the 1960s. Inclusive healthcare provision was a directive initiated by HM King Faisal in the 1960s that provided free healthcare of the highest standards to all citizens. Pathogens remain a principal cause of morbidity and mortality in KSA and pose a substantial medical and economic problem. However, most of the diseases are highly avoidable or curable (Aboshaiqah and Baker, 2013).

In KSA, very few studies have been carried out. The factors contributing to the lack of adherence to infection control protocols among HCWs are still under-researched and not clearly understood. For example, in some studies, it was reported that most participants in the KSA were aware of various infection control measures, but only a few adhered to them (Elrggal, 2018; Binalrimal et al., 2019). Similarly, in the UK, a study by Stein et al., (2003) was conducted to determine doctors' and nurses' knowledge, attitudes and compliance with infection control guidelines in Birmingham teaching hospitals. The study indicates that significant variation exists with respect to many variables with nurses having better adherence to infection control guidelines in the process of delivering care compared to doctors. The knowledge on blood-borne virus transmission through contact with blood and other body fluids was found to be below 50% among both doctors and nurses. More importantly, Stein et al., (2003) argue that doctors consistently de-emphasised the relevance of the existing infection control guidelines with

consequent poor compliance with the requirements of their guidelines. In addition, the study showed that compared to nurses, doctors were more likely to say that they re-sheath used needles manually. Examples of the reasons that doctors provided for poor compliance with infection control measures include time constraints, wearing gloves, lack of conveniently located sharps containers, age and training (Stein et al., 2003).

In a study conducted by the secondary care hospital in KSA, it was found that health practitioners were not entirely aware of the significance of IPC programme guidelines within hospitals (Assiri et al., 2013). Therefore, there is a need to understand in greater depth the influences on compliance or non-compliance with infection control practices in KSA. In response to this need, this mixed-methods study was designed and undertaken.

The significance of this study, therefore, lies in its overall aims to understand in depth the perceptions of HCWs of IPC practices and how these perceptions among other individual and institutional factors influence compliance with the recommended infection control practices. These aims are achieved through exploring HCWs' points of view and observing their IPC practices in two tertiary care hospitals located in the Qassim region in the centre of KSA. In other words, the three main objectives which guided the design of the study are:

- to examine HCWs' perceptions of IPC practices in the two research hospitals;
- to determine other factors influencing IPC practices; and
- to explore how HCWs' perceptions and other factors play a role in compliance with IPC practices.

Therefore, one of the contributions of this study is understanding in depth HCWs' perceptions and the role which these perceptions and other factors play in affecting compliance with infection prevention and control practices in KSA. The results of this study will help inform

the policy on infection control in KSA particularly as the reduction in HAIs infections has the potential to decrease suffering for patients and reduce medical and economic burdens.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND METHODOLOGY

Since the aim of this research is to provide a comprehensive understanding of HCWs' perceptions of infection control practice in KSA, with a particular focus on the role of perceptions in influencing the implementation of recommended IPC policies and guidelines, the key research questions are:

1. What are healthcare workers' perceptions of infection prevention and control practices within the two research hospitals in KSA?
2. What institutional factors influence healthcare workers' compliance with infection prevention and control practices within the two hospitals in KSA?
3. How do the individual factors influence healthcare workers' compliance with infection prevention and control practices within the two hospitals in KSA?

To facilitate investigating the factors associated with compliance with IPC and respond to the main research questions, the concurrent mixed methods approach was used. A structured questionnaire survey was developed to explore and explain HCWs' perceptions of IPC practices and how their perceptions among other individual and institutional factors play a role in affecting HCWs' compliance with recommended IPC practices. To better understand the views of HCWs in depth based on their own perceptions, semi-structured qualitative interviews were conducted. The use of the quantitative survey and qualitative interview was complemented by using

structured observations to comprehensively investigate compliance with IPC practices in the two research hospitals in KSA.

1.4 THESIS STRUCTURE

To understand the perceptions of HCWs of IPC practices and identify the factors associated with compliance with recommended IPC practices in two tertiary hospitals in the Qassim region of KSA, the thesis is organised into seven chapters as Table 1.1 below shows:

Table 1.1: Thesis Structure

In **Chapter One**, the research aims and significance are explained. The structure of the thesis is presented. The epidemiology of HAIs is examined at global and local levels with a specific focus on developing countries. Some background information on the people, culture and

healthcare system of the KSA is introduced. A brief review of the literature on Saudi healthcare workers' perceptions of IPC practices is also provided. In **Chapter Two** a detailed review of literature on the factors associated with non-compliance with infection control procedures is provided. One of the aims of the literature review is to identify gaps in the existing research which inform the direction and design for this study such as the lack of studies carried out in specific locations as in KSA, the local context of this study.

Chapter Three provides a detailed review of the conceptual framework on which the study is based. First, a review of the WHO framework for the design of infection control programmes is provided in order to justify the selected conceptual model. The Systems Engineering Initiatives for Patient Safety (SEIPS) Framework is also explored. In **Chapter Four**, the research philosophy and methods used for this research are analysed. Taking a pragmatic approach, both the positivist and realist approaches are employed for quantitative and qualitative studies in order to understand how perceptions can influence compliance with infection control practices among HCWs at two healthcare facilities in KSA.

In **Chapter Five**, the results obtained from both quantitative and qualitative data in this mixed methods research are examined in detail. **Chapter Six** discusses the analysis of the results from the quantitative and qualitative data in relation to the literature and research questions. In addition, the chapter identifies the research gaps and describes the study's strengths, challenges and limitations. Finally, in **Chapter Seven**, the main findings are summarised and recommendations for practice, policy makers, future research are proposed.

1.5 RESEARCH BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

1.5.1 Prevalence of Healthcare-Associated Infections (HAIs)

HAIs, also known as hospital infections or nosocomial infections, refer to infectious diseases that occur within 48 hours of hospital admission, within three days of discharge or 30

days after having received health care. These infections were not present at the time of a patient's admission. Infections can be acquired anywhere within a healthcare setting, including long-term care, home care or ambulatory care (Haque et al., 2018). In addition, HAIs include epidemics associated with the use of devices or healthcare practices and procedures (Bénet et al., 2015) such as the outbreaks of carbapenem-resistant *Enterobacteriaceae* infections that were associated with the use of duodenoscopes (used for endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography), even when the manufacturer's instructions and professional guidelines were strictly followed (Rutala and Weber, 2016).

HAIs are a major issue for healthcare providers, infection control specialists, public health authorities, and patients. It is estimated that approximately 6% of patients admitted in acute-care hospitals in developed countries acquire at least one infection (Kritsotakis et al., 2017). In developing countries, the risk of contracting HAIs is estimated to be up to 20 times higher (Ayed et al., 2019); equivalent to an infection rate of up to 25% (Cheng et al., 2007). A recent Centre for Disease Control (CDC) report indicated that nursing homes report over 3 million HAIs per annum, some of which lead to patient death or disability (Garett, 2016). HAIs are associated with an increase in mortality and morbidity, prolonged hospital stays, antibiotic resistance and increased healthcare costs (Allegranzi et al., 2013; Tan and Jeffrey, 2015; Ng et al., 2017). It is estimated that HAIs result in between 44,000 and 98,000 unexpected deaths in the United States and the cost of dealing with these infections is estimated at US \$17–29 billion (Kurtz, 2017).

Data from national and multicentre studies show rates of HAIs in high-income countries ranging from between 3.5% and 12% (Fineschi, 2019) and rates of between 5.7% and 19.1% in low income countries as Figure 1.1 and Figure 1.2 show below:

Prevalence of health care-associated infection in high-income countries, 1995-2010*

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Figure 1.1: Prevalence of HAIs in high-income countries. (Source, WHO Apps.who.int. (2011). [online] Available at: https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/80135/9789241501507_eng.pdf;sequence=1) [Accessed 7 Apr. 2019].

Prevalence of health care-associated infection in low- and middle-income countries, 1995-2010

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Figure 1.2: Prevalence of HAIs in Low Income countries. (Source WHO Apps.who.int. (2011). [online] Available at: https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/80135/9789241501507_eng.pdf;sequence=1) [Accessed 7 Apr. 2019].

Zingg et al., (2014) analysed data collected between 2006 and 2012 in annual HAIs prevalence surveys at the University of Geneva Hospitals, finding a pooled point and period prevalence of 7.46% and 9.84% (+32%) respectively. When analysed by infection sites, data indicated that 32% of HAIs were primarily attributable to infections of the lower respiratory tract (2.42% vs 3.20% [+32%]); the urinary tract (1.76% vs 2.62% [+49%]); surgical site infections (1.02% vs 1.20% [+19%]); and bloodstream infections (0.76% vs 0.86% [+13%]) (see Table 1.2 below). This study shows the types of infection that are most likely to occur. Furthermore, the study indicates the potential causes of infection. Routes of transmission include, for example, direct, fomite, aerosol, oral, vector-borne and zoonotic.

Table 1.2: Prevalence of different types of HAIs at the University of Geneva Hospital

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Source: Zingg, W., Huttner, BD., Sax, H., Pittet, D. (2014) Assessing the burden of HAIs through prevalence studies: what is the best method? *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiol.* 2014 Jun;35(6):674-84. doi: 10.1086/676424. Epub 2014 Apr 17.

The CDC has classified nosocomial infection sites into 13 types with 50 infection sites based on biological and clinical criteria. Common infections include urinary tract infections (UTIs), surgical and soft tissue infections, skin infections, bacteraemia, gastroenteritis, meningitis and respiratory infections (Khan et al., 2015). The pathogens that most commonly cause nosocomial infections are *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *E. coli*. However, HAIs are not only caused by bacteria, but they can be also caused by fungi such as *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus* spp., and by viruses such as the respiratory syncytial virus and influenza virus (Suleyman et al., 2018). Common pathogens associated with HAIs and their favoured sites of colonization include *Methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), *meticillin-sensitive Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA), vancomycin-resistant *Enterococci* (VRE) and multidrug-resistant *Acintobacter* spp. (Elstrøm et al., 2019). Table 1.3 below shows common pathogens associated with HAIs in ICU patients:

Table: 1.3: Common pathogens associated with HAIs in ICU patients

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Source: Dasgupta, S., Das, S., Chawan, N. S. & Hazra, A. 2015. Nosocomial infections in the intensive care unit: Incidence, risk factors, outcome and associated pathogens in a public tertiary teaching hospital of Eastern India. *Indian journal of critical care medicine: peer-reviewed, official publication of Indian Society of Critical Care Medicine*, 19, 14.

Few studies have reported the prevalence of different types of HAIs in KSA. For example, Sabra and Abdel-Fattah (2012) conducted a study of HAIs in Taif Hospitals in KSA, indicating that 32.3% of HAIs cases were of respiratory tract infection (RTI), 25.3% UTI, 18.2% were blood infections (BI) and 12.9% were surgical site infections (SSI). As for the type of biological agents, the most predominant Gram-positive isolates (31.7%) were methicillin resistant *Staphylococcal aureus* (MRSA) 10.2%, coagulase negative *Staphylococci* (CNS) 8.5% and *Staphylococcal aureus* (SA) 7.4%. The predominant Gram-negative isolates (66.3%) were *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) 22.3%, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (PA) 17.6% and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (KP) 9.9%. *Candida* spp. represented 2% of total isolates. *E. coli* was the commonest isolate from UTI (47.7%), followed by KP (15.1%) and PA (8.1%). RTI isolates were PA (44.4%), MRSA (14.8%) and *Acinetobacter spp* (12%). BI isolates were KP 23.3%, CNS 16.7% and *E. coli* 15%. SSI isolates were *E. coli* 25.6%, MRSA 18.6% and MSSA 14%.

1.5.2 The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

1.5.2.1 Historical Background and Geographical Location

KSA is situated in the Middle East region. The Middle East region covers approximately 9,000,000 square kilometres, stretching between the East of the Atlantic Ocean and Afghanistan, with a population of approximately 355 million people (The World Bank, 2017). Several countries lie within this expansive region including Iran, Turkey, Iraq, Yemen, Oman, the United Arab Emirates, Qatar, Bahrain, Kuwait, KSA, Jordan, Syria, Lebanon, Israel, Egypt, Libya, Tunisia, Algeria and Morocco. As Figure 1.3 below shows, KSA occupies most of the Arabian Peninsula. It is bounded by the Red Sea to the south, the Arabian Sea to the East, and the Arabic Gulf to the northeast. KSA is bordered by Iraq, Qatar, Oman, Yemen, Jordan, Kuwait and the United Arab Emirates (General Authority for Statistics, 2016).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Figure 1.3. Map of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia showing all regions. Source: <https://i.pinimg.com/736x/de/45/5c/de455c797c69daa97d6a0957a0862534.jpg>

1.5.2.2 Demographic Characteristics of KSA

KSA occupies an area of approximately 2,150,000 km² (830,000 sq. mi). In terms of geographic size, KSA is the largest country in the Middle East, and the second-largest country in the Arab world after Algeria (The World Bank, 2017). In 2016, KSA had a total population of 33,413,660 (The World Bank, 2017). KSA's population is characterised by rapid growth of around 1.63% per annum. The majority of the population is male (57.4%). A large proportion of population are under the age of 25 (0–14 years: 25.74%, 15–24 years: 15.58%). The majority of KSA's population comprises Arabs (90%), with 10% of the population being Afro-Asian (KSA Statistical Office, 2019). A significant percentage of the population (37%) is made up of immigrants seeking economic opportunities (The World Bank, 2017; General Authority for Statistics, 2016).

1.5.2.3 Culture in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

There are five distinct cultures that characterise the Middle East region: Iranian, Arab, Turkish, Israeli, and Middle East North African (MENA). As Figure 1.4 below shows, the culture of KSA has been shaped by Bedouin, Arab and Islamic identities:

Figure: 1.4: The building blocks of the Saudi Arabian Culture

The culture of KSA is shaped by language, economy, government and traditions. It is also defined by its Islamic heritage, its historical role as an ancient trade centre, and the Bedouin tradition. KSA's society has evolved from traditional values, customs, hospitality and styles of dressing and now adopts current forms of modernisation. However, traditional values are deeply rooted in Islamic teachings and Arab customs and are thus learned at an early age within families and in schools. (Saudi Arabian Cultural Mission, 2017).

1.5.2.3.1 The Saudi and Religious Identity

Language is a crucial element that defines the culture of the people living in KSA as it is an essential element of the sharing of information in any culture. Verbal and non-verbal communication are important in the delivery of information. Religion is also a defining characteristic of Saudi Arabian culture, with KSA adhering to Islamic religious culture. Governance of the country is built on religious beliefs which cannot be ignored when examining

the political structure of the country. Nevertheless, decisions made by political leaders should consider the issues that matter to the majority of the population. Traditions form the strongest element of a country's culture, and are drawn from religion, governance and language through the sharing of information (Ministry of Health, 2013). The culture of KSA presents a significant challenge for expatriate nurses, doctors and other healthcare workers, as the native cultural paradigm aims to provide KSA patients with the best treatment approach based on their beliefs (Nazar et al., 2015). Healthcare sectors in KSA allow native individuals to learn other languages in order to help foreign nurses translate in cases where there is a language barrier, whilst offering infection prevention and treatment. The difference in the cultural and psychological attitudes of patients and nurses reflects the consideration of religious preferences, stereotypes and ethnocentric orientation (World Health Organization, 2014). These cultural differences may create barriers that impact on healthcare in KSA. Although the government provides education and orientation programmes for expatriate healthcare workers, there is a need to further improve these programmes to take account of the culture and language in KSA. With the increasing number of expatriate healthcare workers, effective communication is essential to ensure the quality and safety of patient care (Almutairi, 2015).

1.5.2.3.2 The Arab Identity

Middle Eastern societies are made up primarily of Arab populations. The Arab culture is characterised by four dimensions: uncertainty avoidance, power distance, masculinity vs. femininity and individualism vs. collectivism. (Hofstede et al., 2011). Uncertainty avoidance refers to the degree to which members of a society feel comfortable with ambiguity and uncertainty. Countries that score highly on uncertainty avoidance are assumed to be societies with rigid ideas and codes of behaviours. Power distance refers to the extent to which the least powerful members of society accept and expect an unequal distribution of power. Societies that accept a

large degree of power distance tend to accept a hierarchical order in which individuals do not typically strive to equalise the distribution of power (Strychalska-Rudzewicz, 2016).

Individualism vs. collectivism refers to the extent to which a society shows a preference for a loose-knit social framework individualist or for a framework in which group care is exchanged for unquestioned loyalty collectivist (Ljunge, 2016). A society's position on this dimension can often be recognized by whether members' self-image is defined in terms of 'I' or 'we'. Masculinity vs. femininity refers to the extent to which a society values achievement, assertiveness, heroism, and material rewards masculinity, and cooperation and quality of life femininity. Arab societies tend to score highly for power distance, uncertainty avoidance and collectivism. These dimensions may play a role in the extent to which the society as a whole is resistant to change, including an at an organizational level.

Arab families are traditionally organised as extended families, with a single-family unit often comprising up to three generations of grandparents, first cousins, nephews, nieces and other relatives living in the same place. However, recent urbanisation and migration has led to the breakdown of extended family units and an increase in the number of nuclear families (Alajmi, et al., 2011). Furthermore, Middle Eastern culture is traditionally characterised by power distance and masculinity. Male chauvinism is common, and women have little say in the matters that affect their lives. For instance, women are not permitted to trade with men, drive cars or even choose their own life partner (Al-Omari, 2008). However, with the introduction of cell phones, television and the internet, these traditional cultures are gradually fading. Moreover, women are now studying at the highest levels possible, and business space is quickly opening for all citizens, including women. Globalisation and the increasing influence of the western world has brought a range of changes in a number of areas including diet, education, entertainment and clothing (Hammad and Hallinger, 2017).

Adherence to Arabic and Islamic practices may play an influential role in infection control in KSA. Arab families have developed a culture of being directly involved in the care of a family

member through constant presence and support on matters pertaining to IPC. Additionally, individuals' cultural perceptions affect activities such as visiting patients, the maintenance of modernity and the approved communication process that should be followed by nurses in the process of offering IPC, and supporting the spiritual needs of patients (Zumla, et al., 2016).

1.5.2.3.3 The African Culture

Cultural diversity is a primary aspect of African culture and has developed in response to the handling of internal affairs and in response to dealing with external encounters with other continents. African cultures are integrated and bonded within particular groups that stress local identity, as opposed to a collective continental perspective (Ghaemi, 2010). However, these cultures were destroyed by the colonial invasions of the last century, which imposed foreign languages and significantly altered African religious beliefs. This led to confusion around the political, religious, social and cultural identities of the African people (Kauser and Tlaiss, 2011).

In some parts of Africa, traditional rituals, supernatural beings, witchcraft and ancestral spirits are still followed and worshipped. A visitor to Africa is likely to encounter three different groups of present-day inhabitants. The first group are little or not affected by modernisation, and hence engage within the boundaries of the same ethnic group (Pendleton, 2017). The second group, of transitional Africans, combine western culture with traditional beliefs. The third group consists of modern Africans who are educated, use modern technology and have fewer social boundaries. Therefore, the cultural setup of the Africans is diverse and changing and is influenced by internal and external factors (Ghaemi, 2010).

1.5.2.3.4 Asian Culture

The Asian culture comprises several nationalities of diverse heritage, ethnicity and religion. Asian culture is exhibited through customs expressed in cuisine, art, music and literature. Although not a culturally distinct continent, Asian history highlights some common

characteristics shared between the people from the region. The most complex aspect of Asian culture is the integration of the western culture into traditional Asian culture (Dixon-Woods et al., 2014).

Most Asian nations tend to accept authority or power from higher office without question. However, Asian countries, except for South Korea, Japan, Iraq and Iran, tend to score below average on the uncertainty avoidance index, indicating that they are not comfortable with threatening situations. As regards the masculinity versus femininity index, most Asian nations are 'masculine'; meaning that they prefer to work to live than to live to work. Asian countries tend to score highly on collectivism, indicating that group care is prized over individuality for survival (Dixon-Woods et al., 2014).

1.6. INFECTION CONTROL STRATEGIES AND CHALLENGES

1.6.1 Global Infection Prevention and Control strategies and Challenges

Measures to prevent the spread of infection are an essential component of healthcare. The spread of infection is prevented by the implementation of transmission-based precautions (TBPs) that involve standard infection control precautions (SICP) such as regular hand hygiene, the use of personal protective equipment including gloves, gowns and eye protection, and vaccinations to reduce the risk associated with the transmission of blood-borne microorganisms and pathogens (Assiri et al., 2013).

Adherence to preventative measures is imperative to prevent infection transmission. In this regard, a literature review conducted by Moralejo et al., (2018) assessed adherence to IPC practices among individuals and organisations. The review found significant variations in baseline adherence and the extent of changes both between and within studies as well by the specific behaviour assessed. Education and peer evaluation were found to improve adherence to standard procedures, whilst education alone and education with additional infection control support were

found to slightly improve adherence to infection prevention measures. However, education showing respiratory particle dispersion was found to lead to little or no difference in knowledge. Education with additional infection control support was also found to lead to little or no difference in rates of adherence to preventative measures.

TBPs are categorised based on the route of transmission of the infectious agent and include contact precautions, droplets precautions and airborne precautions (NIPCM, 2015). Contact precautions involve the prevention and control of the acquisition of infection through direct contact with an infected individual or through indirect contact with patients in the immediate care environment. Contact precautions include wearing gloves, the proper disposal of sharps and clinical waste, and minimising the number of people coming into contact with patients. Droplet precautions aim to prevent and control infection from spreading over short distances of 3 feet to 1 metre via droplets arising from the respiratory tract of one individual and travelling directly to another individual's mucosal surface or conjunctivae. Examples of droplet precautions include the use of routine environmental decontamination such as sterilisation and organised cleaning regimens, wearing eye protection and bed spacing. Airborne precautions aim to prevent and control infections that spread widely without close contact with patients. Airborne infections travel in the form of aerosols arising from the respiratory system of an infected individual and coming in contact with the mucosal surface of another individual. In a similar way to droplets, aerosols enter the respiratory system of another individual to the point that they reach the alveolar level (McCloskey et al., 2013). Examples of airborne precautions include wearing face masks and respirators, the use of Airborne Infection Isolation Rooms (AIIR) with monitored negative air pressure, and the provision of adequate ventilation (Minnesota Health Assessment, 2017).

Multiple infection prevention and control strategies are used in the healthcare environment and each strategy comes with a specific protocol to which healthcare practitioners must adhere. Healthcare workers are expected to follow standard infection control practices when dealing with

recognised and unrecognised sources of infection such as blood and other body fluids (Rim and Lim, 2014). Lack of adherence to infection control protocols may indicate a lack of staff training, a lack of perceived risk or a lack of interest in infection control amongst staff. In order to determine if this is the case, it is important to examine the factors that determine the successful implementation of new infection control strategies. For instance, additional infection control strategies can include surveillance with the aim of detecting and treating infections before they escalate. Khuan and Springhorn (2012) found that monitoring of HAIs is a significant component of an effective IPC programme. Moreover, training and education of all new and existing staff, irrespective of their position, ensures that staff are well informed about new IPC methods (Memish et al., 2013). This study suggests that the extent to which an infection prevention strategy is successfully implemented, at least in its initial stages, depends to a significant extent on staff training and supervision.

The World Health Organisation (WHO, 2016) states that regulatory implementation, in the form of an IPC programme, is a critical step towards the prevention of HAIs and indicates an organisation's level of preparedness and responsiveness to a communicable disease crises. The WHO (2016) also defines the essential core components for IPC programmes as follows:

- Organisation of IPC programmes
- Technical guidelines
- Human resources (training, staffing, occupational health)
- Surveillance of diseases and of compliance with IPC practices
- Microbiology laboratory support
- Clean and safe environment
- Monitoring and evaluation of IPC programmes
- Links with public health and other services

The WHO is concerned with averting HAIs at a worldwide level. To ensure patient safety and infection control, the WHO created the World Alliance for Patient Safety in 2005 and identified HAIs as a priority topic in patient safety. The programme entitled ‘Clean Care is Safer Care’ includes several measures to minimise the occurrence of infectious diseases and HAIs (Mukerji et al., 2013). All healthcare workers who are in direct contact with patients, or in direct contact with items used in patient care, are required to observe and adhere to established rules by participating in infection control and thus reduce the risk of infection between staff and patients (Mehta et al., 2014). Healthcare workers are encouraged to embrace preventive disease strategies such as hygiene through hand washing and are also required to monitor and report any outbreaks to ensure proper treatment.

The WHO global infection control strategy emphasises that every healthcare facility should recruit a person or a team to ensure that infection control procedures are adhered to when handling patients. In every country, there should be appointed trained professionals in charge of infection control at local and national levels, including healthcare professionals, qualified nurses and others who are responsible for implementing IPC activities across the healthcare system. These professionals should be highly skilled and possess a high level of knowledge of the general principles of IPC, the surveillance of disease and outbreak management, and the monitoring of clinical practice (Storr et al., 2017). Other healthcare workers who should be included in the infection control structure include dentists, medical assistants, laboratory workers, managerial staff and housekeeping employees that provide patient care at any level. These professionals should collaborate with public health departments and create a connection between local and provincial health departments in order to report instances of infectious diseases and find solutions to control them.

The WHO also recommends that healthcare facilities implement infection control guidelines to reduce the occurrence and spread of disease as well as ensure the early detection and isolation of infection. However, practices may differ across healthcare facilities, depending on the

type of care offered. The WHO recommends that priority should be given to the most frequent or risky practices such as injection safety, surgical processes and use of indwelling catheters on the basis of regulations that ensure a uniform implementation of welfare strategies to prevent HAIs on a global level. The efficacy of global infection control can be exemplified by the ‘Save Lives’ campaign in Australia (2009–2015), a hand hygiene campaign which resulted in more than 80% of hospitals complying with infection control strategies (Allegranzi et al., 2016).

1.6.2 Factors Associated with Non-Adherence with Infection Control Practices

Many institutional and sociocultural factors can pose constraints on adherence to safe infection control practices by healthcare workers. Based on the literature, institutional factors that constrain adherence can include the following:

- lack of infection control policies and guidelines;
- lack of education and knowledge on infection control;
- ineffective surveillance;
- antibiotic control policies leading to antibiotic resistance;
- inadequate supplies and facilities, including hand washing facilities, good water and food hygiene, waste disposal facilities, and personal protective equipment (such as masks, gloves, gowns, etc), and
- inadequate infrastructure - mostly faced by developing countries, due to poverty and poor financing. This is evidenced by poorly functioning and equipped laboratory services, poor infrastructure such as few wards and intensive care rooms and a lack of single and isolation rooms, and lack of personnel and well-trained infection control experts (Allegranzi and Pittet, 2009; Ayub et al., 2013; Bai, 2015; Tan and Jeffrey, 2015; Edet et al., 2017).

Examples of the sociocultural and political factors that can constrain adherence include resource and budgetary allocations, culture and religious beliefs and organisational culture.

1.6.3. Institutional Factors Associated with Infection Control

1.6.3.1 Infection Control Policies, Knowledge and Education

Infection prevention policies and guidelines have been found to enhance professional nurses' experiences and understanding of infection control practices (Edet et al., 2017). Edet et al., (2017) conducted a qualitative study which aimed to understand and explain behaviours that occur in everyday infection control practice from the perspective of healthcare workers. The study used vignettes developed from nurses' account of practice in order to assess behaviours related to infection prevention. Workplace policy and infection surveillance were found to enhance professionals' perception of infection control practices as they focus on organisational factors in order to develop a positive orientation towards compliance, and to develop long-lasting strategies for infection control practices. However, although participants showed a clear intention to present themselves as being knowledgeable practitioners, they did not always follow infection control policy and procedures. An important finding of this work is that it reveals reasons for non-adherence to procedures, even if practitioners were aware of them. For example, some nurses made judgements about their own behaviours which allowed not following guidelines while describing infection prevention behaviour in terms of "a show" to appear in a good light. The study highlights the need for multifaceted interventions which the current policy and guidance do not completely provide. Therefore, the study suggests that infection control behaviour is controlled by a constellation of variables, and that a lack of infection control training cannot fully explain why nurses do not always follow standard procedures. As such, educational interventions should not only consider scientific knowledge but also beliefs, values, and social understandings of infection.

The Health Belief Model (HBM), first developed in the 1950s by social psychologists working in the US Public Health Services (Hochbaum 1956; Becker, 1974; Champion and Skinner, 2008; Rosenstock, 1974), suggests that individuals adopt a health behaviour, such as wearing gloves whilst drawing blood, based on the satisfaction of several factors, including beliefs, values and social understandings. First, the level of knowledge that an individual has of the disease or health issue in question will affect their perception of their susceptibility to that disease (e.g. HIV/AIDS). Second, a range of contextual factors act to modify the likelihood of adopting a healthy behaviour, as for example, the extent to which the health threat or disease is perceived to be severe enough to harm or kill them if acquired. Demographic and sociocultural factors include age, gender, ethnicity, personality, socio-economic status, and other cues to action, such as knowing somebody who caught the disease and died from it. Third, the perceived benefits of compliance with the health behaviour contributes to the likelihood of it being adopted. As such, the HBM is based on the understanding that a person will undertake a health-related behaviour such as wearing gloves whilst drawing blood, if that person:

- believes that a negative health condition (e.g. hospital-acquired Hepatitis B or C, HIV) can be avoided by doing so;
- has a positive expectation that taking the recommended action (i.e., wearing gloves) will be effective in preventing the transmission of hospital-acquired Hepatitis B or C, HIV infection; and
- believes that they can successfully take a recommended health action (i.e., they can use gloves comfortably and with confidence) - also known as self-efficacy.

The HBM can be used to understand observed behaviour and predict expected behaviours based on a classification of healthcare workers perceived susceptibility, beliefs and cues to action.

As will be discussed in detail in the next chapter, the HBM has been applied to an extensive range of health behaviours and subject populations. For instance, the HBM has been used in health promotion to encourage preventive health behaviours such as adherence to good diet, exercise, vaccination and contraceptive practices; in avoiding risky behaviours such as smoking; in understanding sick-role behaviours, such as clinic use and physician visits; and for compliance with recommended medical regimens following the professional diagnosis of illness (Romano, 2015).

Evidence on the role of knowledge, education and attitudes with respect to infection control is contradictory. Some researchers have argued that level of education determines level of knowledge, and that a higher level of knowledge positively influences attitudes and orientation towards compliance with hospital infection control practices. Therefore, compliance amongst more highly educated professionals would be expected to be higher than amongst new graduates. However, these assumptions are mostly based on qualitative studies conducted in the United States (Quan, et al., 2015; Sodhi et al., 2013), and studies conducted in other contexts and settings may contribute to existing knowledge by showing the extent to which these findings can be more broadly generalized. For instance, a study conducted in KSA found that a significant percentage of healthcare practitioners do not adhere to pneumonia (VAP) prevention guidelines, with factors related to the organization, management protocol, and healthcare providers being identified as the main cause of lack of adherence, rather than a lack of education (Wahabi and Alziedan, 2012). However, a study by Yaseen and Salameh (2015) assessed the barriers that affect nurses' adherence to infection control guidelines, finding that hospital education and the nursing curriculum were the main barriers to adherence to VAP guidelines. Finally, a study by Bassuni and Bayoumi (2015) found a need for continuous education programs for ICU nursing staff in KSA to increase knowledge and skill levels on the importance of improving patient safety measures in a complex care context (Bassuni and Bayoumi, 2015). However, factors other than levels of education and knowledge can also have an impact on adherence to infection control

measures. A study by Jain et al., (2012) found that despite the majority (76%) of participants being aware of infection control measures, only 56% complied with the requirement to dispose of used needles and syringes in puncture-resistant containers. In addition, only 50% of participants observed the requirement not to recap needles, despite only 19% of participants having been immunised against Hepatitis B (Jain et al., 2012). Given that these findings are based on self-report accounts, it is possible that actual adherence rates may be much lower. Another limitation of this study is that no attempt was made to determine the way in which practitioners rationalized their lack of commitment to policies and procedures. Future studies in this area could provide valuable insights to inform policymaking.

1.6.3.2 Inadequate Infrastructure and Personnel

An additional challenge that can impact on adherence with infection control practices is the availability of adequate infection control infrastructure and adequate supply chains for products such as hand disinfectants, and protective equipment such as gloves and vaccines. A lack of infection control infrastructure can also be compounded by the performance of high-risk procedures in facilities lacking trained personnel.

In second world countries, adequate funds tend to be directed to health institutions within urban areas which have more speciality hospitals. Rural healthcare institutions tend to lack the supplies required to mitigate infections associated with sterile body sites and mucous membranes (Andreassen et al., 2017). Most hospitals have inadequate supplies of gloves, facemasks, disposable and non-disposable aprons, culture bottles, soap dispensers, waste disposal plastics and bins, hand sanitisers and other supplies vital for compliance with infection control practices (Nakarmi et al., 2018). Most hospital wards have few single rooms, and most are not equipped with specific isolation rooms. Wards are often inadequate for purpose, with medical wards, including intensive care units (ICUs) being used for surgical purposes. Wards often lack temperature and humidity control equipment and have little in the way of diagnostic

microbiology services. In many cases, wards are cramped with insufficient bed to bed space and a very high turnaround time for patients, leading to a prevalence of pathogens such as viral and bacterial infections. Bed-to-bed distance is at least 150 cm in ICUs in the Netherlands, whereas it is generally only 100 cm in most hospitals in Turkey (Alp, 2011). A lack of proper staffing within ICUs also compromises hand hygiene as continuous in-service training is required to ensure compliance. Increased movement of patients and practitioners within and between wards increases the chances of the spread of multi drug resistant (MDR) microorganisms (Barbier et al., 2016).

The growth and spread of MDR microorganisms are mostly associated with overcrowding, the sharing of beds between patients, overuse of antibiotics and poor air quality. Furthermore, inadequate infrastructure, overcrowding and a lack of resources for isolation and disinfection have been found to result in a high prevalence of HIV, MDR tuberculosis and other widespread antimicrobial resistant pathogen in government hospitals in Bangladesh (Shears, 2007; Rimi et al., 2014). A systematic review by Mesfin et al., (2014) that included a meta-analysis of 24 observational studies found a high prevalence of HIV and MDR tuberculosis in poor resource settings (see Table 1.4 below). Uncomfortable conditions such as high temperatures during summer have also been found to affect work performance (Andreassen et al., 2017). The peak in tuberculosis cases recorded during spring and summer has been found to be the consequence of *M. tuberculosis* transmission during the winter months, particularly in overcrowded and poorly ventilated settings (Álvaro-Meca et al., 2016).

Inadequate personnel, and a shortage of trained staff who can deliver adequate and effective infection control guidelines can also pose a challenge for the effective implementation of infection control measures. Trained staff minimise the risk of HAIs by assisting with the maintenance and operation of equipment, the use of aseptic techniques or safe injection practices, the performance of phlebotomy procedures, and the use of correct and safe injection practices

(Andreassen et al., 2017). Education and training are essential to ensure that staff have the knowledge and skills to protect patients, visitors, colleagues and themselves. Defining core knowledge and skills will assist service managers to identify training required and assist educators to evaluate and update current education and training programmes and e-learning resources.

Table 1.4: The association between poor hospital environment HIV/AIDS and multi-drug resistance tuberculosis**Table 1.** Summary of the 24 observational studies assessing the association between HIV/AIDS and multi-drug resistance tuberculosis included in the meta-analysis.

First author, year, country	Design	Sample size	MDR-type	Number HIV+	MDR-TB HIV+	Number HIV-	MDR-TB HIV-	AOR	CI
Dubrovina. et al, 2008 (Ukraine)	Cross-sectional ^a	1540	Any	307	31.6%	1143	23.8%	1.7	1.3–2.3
Valerieschoeel et al, 1998 (France)	Case-control ^a	1334	Primary	893	1.2%	5864	0.3%	3.3	1.5–7.3
		4	secondary	107	11.2%	868	6.6%	1	0.5–2.0
Robert M.Granchi. et al, 2005 (California)	Cross-sectional ^a	2871	Any	2031	4%	2736	1.4%		0.78–1.23
		2				2		0.98	
Patrice Josephe. et al, 2006 (Haiti)	Cross-sectional ^a	330	primary	115	10%	166	3%	3.2	1.1–8.9
Andrew C.weltman. et al, 1994(newyork city)	Case-control ^a	172	any	78	26.9%	25	4%	2.7	1.1–6.8
Nino Mdivani. et al, 2008 (Georgia)	cross-sectional ^a	996	any	5	40%	227	28.6%	1.4*	0.47–4.17
Catharina Hendrika. tal,2007(Netherlands)	Cross-sectional ^a	7090	primary	308	1.6%	646	0.6%	2.78	1.09–7.1
Kliiman K. 2009 (Estonia)	Cross sectional ^a	1163	any	54	16.7%	914	18.8%	1.57	0.80–3.11
S.J conaty. et al,2004 (England Wales)	Case-control ^b	9541	Primary	274	3.6%	7936	1%	2.5	1.2–5.20
			secondary	19	21.4%	611	8.2%	2.8	0.6–11.9
k.weyer. et al, 2007 (s/Africa)	Cross-sectional ^b	5866	any	2700	3.4%	1939	2.9%	1.3	1.0–1.70
			Secondary	501	7.9%	418	5.7%	1.46	1.04–2.07

N.B:

^arepresents institution based studies and.^brepresents population studies.

*represents unknown HIV status patients or individuals considered as HIV negative.

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Source: Mesfin YM, Hailemariam D, Biadgign S, Kibret KT (2014) Association between HIV/AIDS and Multi-Drug Resistance Tuberculosis: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. PLoS ONE 9(1): e8223

1.6.3.3 Ineffective Antibiotic Policies

A serious public health concern is antimicrobial resistance (AMR). AMR refers to the pharmaceutical agent that kills or prevents the growth of microbes, as for example, antibiotic, antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal and antiparasitic. AMR is a threat to the efficiency of antimicrobials in the treatment of infections. Therefore, the excessive consumption, increased frequency and careless use of antimicrobials are likely to result in antimicrobial resistance (Reilly et al., 2016). The concern that the WHO raised is that antibiotic resistance can prevent effective infection control (WHO, 2018).

In developing nations there is an extensive and uncontrolled use of antibiotic and antimicrobial drugs, which are readily available over the counter in pharmacies. There are many questions regarding the effectiveness and the quality of antibiotics due to improper regulation of registration and distribution (Monnier et al., 2018). According to Venugopalan et al., (2016), between 20% and 50% of a healthcare facility's funds is spent on antimicrobial drugs that are used to treat more than half of patients. Despite evidence showing that education programs have been efficient in facilitating changes in antimicrobial prescribing that result in a reduction in use, such programs are minimised in developing countries. According to Al-Tawfiq and Memish (2015) in Mecca and Medina during Hajj, people tend to carry a 3-day course of antibiotic medication, which contributes to increased cases of resistance. Pilgrims come from 184 nations, many of which freely provide antibiotics over the counter. This overuse causes an increase in antibiotic resistance and causes strain on the healthcare system in KSA, with associated difficulties in communicating the risk due to language and culture barriers. (Zowawi, 2016; Al-Tawfiq and Memish, 2015).

Issues around antimicrobial and antibiotic resistance highlight the importance of the input of clinical microbiology laboratory services that identify the prevalence of and concerns about new resistant organisms, and the emergence of new infectious bacteria that cause disease.

1.6.3.4 Infection Surveillance Systems

Surveillance in the healthcare environment refers to the continued, systematic collection, analysis and interpretation of healthcare data. This is required in order to effectively plan, implement and evaluate public healthcare practices and systems in a timely and consistent manner, and so that dissemination of data to those who need it can be guaranteed (Bansal et al., 2016). Surveillance in a healthcare setting first requires an assessment of the types of patients/residents that it serves, the key medical interventions and procedures that patients/residents undergo, and the types of infections patients/residents are most at risk of contracting. This assessment should be carried out in order to establish key priorities for the surveillance system. In selecting outcomes for surveillance, hospitals and long-term care homes should consider the full range of potential infections as well as the frequency, impact and preventability of infection (Bansal et al., 2016).

HAIs surveillance and control programmes are critical to ensuring effective surveillance and control of infections through activities including data collection, analysis, interpretation and dissemination of results. Moreover, HAIs surveillance involves the monitoring and reviewing of infection data, thus enabling the tracking of trends and the identification of appropriate actions that can be adopted to control and/or reduce HAIs, in addition to providing data for quality outcome indicators (Mitchell et al., 2016). According to WHO (2016), surveillance is a significant component of HAIs prevention as it is used to identify outbreaks, establish endemic baseline rates of disease and evaluate control measures.

However, despite the significance of HAIs surveillance programmes, many healthcare systems in developed and developing countries still use manual surveillance methods, meaning that infection prevention teams have to spend a considerable time assessing reports with the aim of identifying potential HAIs and patient isolation interventions. A lack of automated disease surveillance technology makes it challenging to collect and analyse patient data in real time to increase surveillance efficiency. Manual surveillance leads to inefficiencies and delays in reporting, thereby limiting opportunities for effective and timely HAIs mediation (Mitchell et al., 2016). These inefficiencies in reporting prevent the collection of data that can be used to identify

preventable infections among high-risk patients, implying that resources are not directed to high-priority areas.

The finding of the study on the Efficacy of Nosocomial Infection Control (SENIC), undertaken in US hospitals in 1985 clearly indicated that HAIs surveillance when complemented with immediate feedback and effective and efficient infection control programmes significantly controlled the prevalence of HAIs (Rosenthal et al., 2013). The study found that 25 hospitals that employed the three key elements and involved microbiologists and physicians were able to reduce the nosocomial infection rates by 32% (Rosenthal et al., 2013). These findings are supported by results from nosocomial infection surveillance programmes implemented across Germany that were shown to significantly reduce the rate of HAIs (Korniewicz, 2013). Inefficiencies in surveillance systems are another major challenge that limit infection control within healthcare facilities (Thompson and Workman, 2014). For instance, ensuring the efficient and proper recording of the vaccination status of new and existing hospital staff enables healthcare organisations to effectively monitor and improve healthcare practices (Korniewicz, 2013) and to positively impact on the control of HAIs.

1.6.4 Other Factors Associated with Non-Adherence with Infection Control

Non-compliance with safe codes of practice poses significant challenges for infection control practices in healthcare facilities. Safe codes of practice cover a wide range of healthcare activities and include the following:

- those concerned with sustaining good hand washing practices;
- those ensuring the safe disposal of waste (such as sharp cutting and piercing objects such as needles);
- codes of practice around good water and food hygiene;
- the proper sterilisation of patient's wounds in the cases of open cuts;
- safety codes concerned with the use of injecting needles and syringes, and
- nursing standards for administering intravenous (IV) fluids (Perry et al., 2010).

The following subsections will explore the more common forms of non-compliance with IPC measures, and the factors influencing these non-compliant behaviours.

1.6.4.1 Non-Compliance with Hand Washing

Ignaz Semmelweis established the importance of hand washing more than 150 years ago when he discovered that the incidence of puerperal fever could be drastically cut using hand disinfection in obstetrical clinics. Non-adherence to hand washing practices in the healthcare setting is a key cause of the spread of multidrug-resistance organisms (WHO, 2016). However, despite its acknowledged importance, experts agree that improving and sustaining good hand washing practices is an ever-present challenge. Compliance with hand washing practices among healthcare workers rarely exceeds 40% on a global level (Septimus et al., 2014). Numerous factors have been found to contribute to the lack of compliance including the lack of time, being too busy, negligence or forgetfulness, inadequate facilities such as few or no sinks inconveniently located or non-functional sinks, inadequacy of supplies such as soap and paper towels, and cultural factors (Odell, 2015). Nevertheless, in developing countries, few strategies have been implemented on hygiene, process surveillance and performance feedback, which have significantly helped efforts to facilitate compliance with IPC practices.

1.6.4.2 Poor Waste Management

Clinical and health waste comprise various materials that can cause infection to those handling them. Healthcare facilities must have strict policies regarding the handling and disposal of dangerous hospital waste including infectious waste, cutting objects and other sharp items such as needles. A study conducted by the WHO in twenty-two developing countries reported that the percentage of facilities not using proper waste disposal methods ranged from 18–64%. Recent studies have also shown that the quantity of healthcare waste has risen sharply in recent years accompanied by inadequate approaches to waste management caused by lack of training, lack of adequate resources, staff resistance, awareness, negligence, poor leadership and unfavourable attitude (Yazie, et al., 2019). Furthermore, a recent report from the United States

CDC indicated that there are approximately 385,000 needle stick and sharp object-related injuries amongst healthcare workers annually in the US (CDC, 2016). Such injuries have been associated with the hospital-based transmission of HIV and the Hepatitis B and C viruses. According to the data provided by WHO, there are approximately 36 million healthcare workers worldwide, of whom around 3 million per year receive an injury with a sharp instrument, resulting in 2,000,000 subjects contaminated with HBV and 1,000,000 with HCV (Coppola, 2016).

1.6.4.3 Poor Nursing Practices

Several poor nursing practices have been associated with the transmission of HAIs. These include not wearing gloves before touching a patient with an infectious disease, not wearing face masks or aprons, and not disposing of used gloves, disposable aprons and other infectious waste in proper bins. Other examples of poor nursing practices include recapping needles, reuse of unsterilized needles, infusing unscreened blood or blood products, and inappropriate use of medical devices. According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), nurses are exposed to needle stick injuries more than other healthcare workers, and needle stick injuries are the most frequent occupational injury amongst nurses (Kahrman et al., 2016).

Inappropriate and outdated injection practices such as the re-use of needles and syringes and the use of multi-dose vials have been implicated in the transmission of HAIs. Despite the availability of needle safe systems and disposal sharp containers, needle stick injuries are still common even in resource-rich settings (Godfrey and Schouten, 2015).

An examination of the prevalence of death and disability from injection-associated infections caused by hepatitis B virus (HBV), Hepatitis C virus (HCV) and HIV found that patients received an average of 3.4 injections per year. A total of 39.3% of these injections were found to be administered with reused equipment (Foda et al., 2018). Furthermore, the WHO has identified more than 70 countries which do not test all donated blood for HIV, Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C and syphilis (WHO, 2016).

The majority of HAIs are associated with inappropriate use of medical devices. For instance, pneumonia has been linked with mechanical ventilation, and UTIs are associated with use of urinary catheters. Surgical Site Infections (SSIs) are caused primarily by surgery, and bacteraemia mainly occurs after the use of intravascular devices (Khan et al., 2017). Khan et al. found that UTIs constitute 30–40% of all nosocomial infections, and that $\geq 25\%$ of patients admitted to ICUs in developed countries develop a HAI, with mortality from HAIs running at $> 25\%$. In developing countries, 66% of patients admitted to ICUs develop an HAI (Khan et al., 2017).

1.6.4.4 Poor Food Hygiene and Access to Portable Water

Tap water and food can function as potential reservoirs of nosocomial pathogens. Studies have reported that in most developing countries, hospital water supply is contaminated or interrupted. Waterborne diseases are primarily caused by faecal pollution of water sources. However, in hospitals this problem is compounded due to the nature of the patients and the invasive surgical procedures that occur, which leads to the pollution of water with non-faecal Gram-negative bacteria and Legionella (Dilnessa and Demeke, 2016). Food pollution can also occur, with many hospitals failing to monitor the quality of food. Lapses in food-handling are common including, for instance, cooking or storing food at the wrong temperature and the cross-contamination of raw and cooked food, resulting in nosocomial food-borne infections. Research has estimated that the incidence of nosocomial diarrhoea in developing countries may be higher than generally believed (Islam et al., 2018).

1.6.5 National Strategies and Challenges for Infection Control

1.6.5.1 Organisation of the Healthcare System in KSA

KSA healthcare amenities have evolved over time. The first public health department was established in Mecca in 1925 (Almalki et al., 2011). The Ministry of Health of KSA was instituted in 1950. The Saudi healthcare system is comprised of government-owned, public sector hospitals

and privately-owned hospitals. The Ministry of Health is responsible for providing and financing government healthcare services. Hospitals and primary healthcare centres comprise 26% of Saudi Arabian health services.

In addition to the Ministry of Health, other state bodies provide healthcare services to the general population, in addition to serving their employees and dependents. These bodies include the security forces (e.g. the National Guard health affairs, the security forces and the army), the Royal Commission for Jubail and Yanbu health services, Johns Hopkins Aramco Healthcare, and school health units run by the Ministry of Education and the Red Crescent Society. State bodies cooperatively run 39 government-owned hospitals with a total of 10,822 beds providing the majority (59.9%) of Saudi Arabian healthcare (see Figure 1.5 below).

The country also has many private sector healthcare services. The private sector runs 125 hospitals in total with 11, 833 beds and 2,218 dispensaries and clinics which are primarily located in major towns and cities (MOH, 2019). Overall, KSA currently boasts over 53,000 hospital beds per 1000 residents. When combined with the public sector, KSA's bed per population has risen to over 70,000 beds (MOH, 2015).

KSA healthcare system is divided into primary, secondary and tertiary healthcare. Primary healthcare provides basic healthcare services to all people in KSA. Specialised treatment is offered at some private and public facilities, with referrals being made to hospitals such as the King Faisal Specialist Hospital, higher education hospitals (teaching hospitals) and research centres (Alkhamis, 2012; MOH, 2019). The public sector runs across all levels of healthcare, from primary healthcare to tertiary healthcare and high-risk and emergency services. Some government hospitals are specifically designed to complement each other instead of competing, with some hospitals being solely devoted to cancer, and others to paediatric and maternity care for example.

Saudi Arabians are afforded free treatment as are government contractors such as Aramco employees and their families (Almalki et al., 2011; Alkabba et al., 2012). The services offered by the public sector are incomparable with general hospital healthcare services afforded by the private sector as public sector healthcare is given free at the point of delivery to all Saudi citizens. The WHO has ranked the KSA health system as being the 25th best system in the world, ahead of most

developed nations (Al-Hanawi et al., 2019). Figure 1.5 below shows the structures of the healthcare sectors in KSA:

Figure 1.5: Structures of the healthcare sectors in KSA. Source: Almalki et al., (2011) Healthcare system in Saudi Arabia: An overview. *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal*17: 784–93.

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KSA's healthcare workforce (HCW) is made up of 423,940 healthcare workers, of which 248,000 are physicians and nurses. However, a large percentage of physicians (73.4%) and nurses (49.7%) are foreigners from other Middle Eastern countries, Africa and Asia as Table 1.5 below shows (Almalki et al., 2011).

Table 1.5: Healthcare Professionals Employed in the KSA as of 2017 (MOH, 2017).

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The KSA government is determined to establish a healthcare system which would eliminate the need for Saudi citizens to seek treatment outside of the kingdom because treatment for their condition exists in KSA.

1.6.5.2 Healthcare Human Resource Development, Vision 2030 and National Transformation

The quality of the national healthcare system in KSA has improved rapidly over recent years (Al-Hanawi, 2017). According to a recent report published by The Ministry of Health (MOH, 2017) healthcare provision consumed 7% of the total governmental budget in 2013. However, with the population of KSA growing at a rate of 2.65% per annum, the 32.6 million population, recorded in 2018, is projected to double by 2050, reaching 77.2 million (World Bank, 2018). This rapid population growth is expected to fuel demand for healthcare services in KSA. However, despite improvements in healthcare, KSA is currently facing an increasing number of emerging illnesses associated with modern and urban lifestyles, and a growing middle-income population. Responding to these challenges, the government launched Vision 2030 (NTP, 2016). KSA's Vision 2030, hereafter referred to as Vision (2030) is a strategy for healthcare that aims to privatise various services of the KSA government specifically in the health sector. Vision (2030) aims to encourage more private sector participation in healthcare provision, with the government gradually assuming a more regulatory role, rather than acting as a healthcare provider. Vision (2030) is highlighted in the National Transformation Plan (NTP) and the privatisation plan (NTP, 2016). The Vision aims to improve the quality of therapeutic and preventive healthcare services through improved healthcare training, the enhancement of efficiency, the improvement of medical facility standards and the implementation of a private medical insurance enhancement plan (NTP, 2016). It is hoped that these improvements will enable people to easily access appropriate medical services and reduce waiting times.

As part of improving the quality of healthcare training, Vision (2030) aims to implement an elite training programme for healthcare professionals aimed at improving the treatment and prevention of infectious and chronic diseases such as cancer, heart diseases and diabetes, through prevention-related care including infection control. Remarkably, Vision (2030) advocates for a

landmark diversification of the Saudi Arabian economy to let loose the abilities of the auspicious sectors of the economy. Furthermore, Vision (2030) plans to advance the competitiveness of the health sector to the top ten from its current position (NTP, 2016). Based on Vision (2030) promotion for the privatisation of most government services, the private sector is envisaged to increase its current contribution to GDP from 40% to 65% by 2030. There are also targets to reduce unemployment rates in the KSA from the current 11.6% to 7%, and to increase the participation of women in the Saudi workforce from 22% to 33%.

1.6.5.3 The Challenges and Opportunities of HCW Human Resources Department in KSA

As at the last quarter of 2014, the KSA healthcare sector employed a total of 600,000 workers, of which more than half (350,000) were healthcare professionals, with the remainder (250,000) being comprised of management and support workers. With a growing and ageing population, KSA will have to spend extensively on healthcare facilities in order to meet the expected increase in demand for healthcare from individuals aged 65 years and over. The NTP report (2016) indicated that the percentage of the population aged over 65 years is expected to double from 3% to 6% over the next ten years. This increase in life expectancy is expected to result in a 25% increase in healthcare workforce requirements (Al-jedai et al., 2016). As such, KSA needs to focus on increasing the supply of employees in the health sector in a bid to meet the needs of an ageing population. Currently, there are around 11 healthcare employees to serve every 1000 individuals. To maintain this up to this benchmark by 2030, KSA needs to maintain approximately 710,000 healthcare workers, meaning that KSA has to employ 360,000 more workers to the current workforce.

In order to meet the goals of Vision (2030), there is a need to employ more Saudi nationals in the healthcare sector as specified by the Saudinization initiative (NTP, 2016). The number of students currently graduating from medical schools is not even sufficient to replace the specialists who are currently retiring or leaving. Based on the expected increase in the number of elderly nationals, KSA will need to replace at least 100,000 healthcare positions by 2030 (NTP, 2016), equating to between 6,000, and 7,000 new nurses being employed every year. There is also a

severe inadequacy of family doctors in KSA. Saudi Arabian physicians tend to overspecialise, and only 5% specialise in family medicine, which is less than Vision (2030) target. With approximately 24% of hospital beds and 32% of health facilities in KSA in the ownership of the private sector, KSA needs to increase the participation of the private sector in the health industry in order to meet the Vision (2030) objectives.

1.6.5.4 Infection Prevention and Control in Healthcare System in KSA

Infectious diseases have claimed many lives in KSA, although most infectious diseases can be treated or prevented. According to reports published by the MOH, brucellosis, chickenpox and amoebic dysentery are the most chronic infections most easily transmitted among people in KSA (Albejaidi, 2010).

There are IPC quality assurance departments that are established at a healthcare facility or institution with the task of implementing infection control programmes and guidelines. IPC is a new but growing discipline in KSA, and at the national level, the Saudi MOH is responsible for establishing several centres for disease control and prevention. For instance, the Command and Control Centre (CCC) was set up with the aims of enhancing the prevention of infections and establishing systems to track infections in KSA and worldwide. Agencies such as the Centres for Medicare and Medicaid use hospital data to track hospital performance on matters pertaining to IPC (MOH, 2013). Every Saudi healthcare facility is also required to design, establish and coordinate an IPC programme to identify, and reduce the risk of, infection acquisition and transmission amongst patients, staff, and visitors (Colet et al., 2018). The MOH facilitated the establishment of infection control services in all its hospitals. Moreover, the MOH provides in-house training and field epidemiology training on infection control to all healthcare workers. The Saudi Council for Health Specialties also established a subspecialty training institution in infectious disease in internal medicine and paediatrics to fulfil extensive domestic demands. Therefore, there are now a large number of nationally trained Saudi internists and paediatricians (Ronald and Memish, 2001).

Assiri et al., (2014) conducted a cross-sectional interview-based study to describe and assess the status of IPC programmes in KSA. The study focused on the status of the eight core components of IPC programmes that are deemed essential in strengthening capacity for the prevention of HAIs. The study calculated a combined score for the eight components for each healthcare facility. These eight core components include the organisation of IPC programmes, technical guidelines, human resources, surveillance of HAIs, microbiology lab support, environment, monitoring and evaluation, and public health links. The results indicated that the facilities' combined scores ranged from 42% to 57% as shown below in Figure 1.6:

Figure 1.6: Total facility scores of IPC components at national level (MOH, 2017).

Examining the status of IPC programmes in different regions in KSA indicated that the combined scores for core components ranged from 42% to 67% as shown in Table 1.6 below:

Table 1.6: Illustration of key IPC components and their values in different parts of the KSA (MOH, 2017).

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Please contact the thesis author for further
information.

facilities have established infection control measures, their performance is suboptimal. IPC programmes have been shown to be clinically cost-effective (Assiri et al., 2014). Furthermore, they can provide significant cost savings through a reduction in HAIs, less time spent in hospital, and a reduction in microbial infection rates and treatments costs (Al-jedai et al., 2016). Based on the economic and human costs of HAIs, there is a need to implement relevant and sufficient resources for IPC initiatives.

1.6.5.5 Challenges in Hospital Infection Control in KSA

Based on some studies, KSA faces several challenges, limitations and barriers to efficient infection control, all of which increase the number of health issues in the country leading to increased mortality and morbidity rates (Mazi et al., 2013; Assiri et al., 2014; Haridi et al., 2016; Rabaan et al., 2017). Most hospitals in KSA lack the required trained professionals to deal with infection control, and there is a need for awareness initiatives to deal with this deficiency.

However, human resources, particularly those associated infectious diseases, are insufficient in KSA (Assiri et al., 2014).

The infrastructure to aid infection control programmes in KSA is underdeveloped in comparison to global standards as Rabaan et al., (2017) indicate. Many hospitals have limited capacity with which to develop the core components required to build an effective IPC programme. As such, there is a need to increase investment in resources to develop IPC components in accordance with acceptable standards. Such investments will reduce the costs of treating HAIs and decrease associated mortality and morbidity rates (Assiri et al., 2014). Accordingly, KSA healthcare facilities should evaluate the needs for infection control and establish an active infection control programme in order to reduce the various risks associated with HAIs and improve the safety of healthcare.

1.6.5.5.1 Hajj and Pilgrimages as a Challenge

KSA's culture is defined by its Islamic heritage, its historical role as an ancient trade centre and the Bedouin tradition. KSA's society has evolved from traditional values, customs, hospitality, and styles of dressing to adapt to current forms of modernisation. However, traditional values are deeply rooted in Islamic teachings and Arab customs and are thus learned at an early age within families and in schools.

The religious and cultural heritage of KSA poses particular challenges for the management of HAIs. The Hajj pilgrimage, which is an annual customary journey to the sacred location of Mecca, presents a major challenge to infection control in KSA. The Hajj event lasts for five days, involving around 3 million pilgrims and spanning several different locations. Hajj has been associated with the increased prevalence and spread of infectious diseases. Communicable diseases that have been found to increase in occurrence during the Hajj event include respiratory infections such as the MERS-CoV, influenza virus infections, meningococcal meningitis infection, tuberculosis, and blood-borne diseases including Hepatitis B, C and HIV (Khan et al., 2009; Azizkhan, 2015). Extended stays at each pilgrimage site, hot atmospheric temperatures, crowded accommodation, traffic jams and dust, and inadequate food preparation and storage all facilitate

the transmission of airborne and waterborne infections. The increased risk of contracting infectious diseases during Hajj has been associated with a wide range of factors including extreme overcrowding, fatigue from travel and movement, high temperature and excessive humidity, dense dust air pollution, inadequate and contaminated nutrition, water scarcity, inadequate sewage management and improper sanitary habits (Azizkhan, 2015).

Congestion of people during Hajj has been found to increase carrier rates for *Neisseria meningitidis* to 80% of the population, which increases the risk of an epidemic outbreak (Memish, 2010). For example, during the Hajj event in 1989 there was a massive outbreak of meningitis in KSA. This prompted the Saudi government to demand that all attendees were vaccinated against meningitis before attending the annual Hajj event. Outbreaks of the serogroup W135 strain of meningococcal infection amongst 2000 and 2001 Hajj pilgrims and their families, both within the country and internationally, necessitated a change from a bivalent to quadrivalent vaccine (Ahmed et al., 2006).

The Ministry of Health reports a 57% increase in infectious disease related hospital admissions during the Hajj event every year, with pneumonia accounting for up to 39% of all hospital admissions during this time (Memish, 2010). The influx of large numbers of temporary and permanent immigrants to KSA has contributed to continuingly high levels of tuberculosis (TB). The high percentage of elderly Hajj participants, and the high prevalence of TB in countries such as Singapore and Malaysia where many of the pilgrims come from, have led to the resurgence of TB in the KSA (Shibl et al., 2012). The high volume and secondary transmission rates of these infections pose a challenge for the management of nosocomial infections. For instance, most of the infections that occur during and immediately after the Hajj are preventable through proper vaccinations and protective hygiene measures.

Seasonal influenza vaccination is recommended for people moving within the country, for individuals with pre-existing health conditions and for all healthcare staff working in healthcare facilities that serve Hajj participants (Badahdah et al., 2018). Ensuring that all Hajj pilgrims are vaccinated against meningitis, pneumonia and influenza remains a challenge for the Saudi government, as a result of the sheer number of participants and the remoteness of the country's

rural areas (Abalkhail et al., 2017). The financial and personnel resources necessary to increase the desired level of coverage, accessibility and preparedness for free healthcare and vaccination services for the Hajj participants is enormous and a significant challenge for the Saudi government.

The annual change in date for the Hajj festival further compounds the challenges faced by the government in preparing to handle infectious diseases common during the Hajj and other pilgrimages to religious sites in the country (Benkouiten et al., 2013). Challenges related to water scarcity for countries in the Gulf Peninsula continue to hamper efforts by the Saudi government towards instilling better hygiene practices for the Hajj season as well as improving public health standards, especially within urban areas (Cruz and Bashtawi, 2016).

1.6.5.5.2 The Increasing Burden of Emerging Infectious Diseases

Over time, infectious diseases have spread widely across populations, regions and across the world. Existing theories note that new infectious diseases will continue to be identified in the world (WHO, 2018). Many infectious diseases arise from animal reservoirs and only affect human beings under certain circumstances. There are numerous factors that are associated with the emergence and spread of infectious diseases (Zumla et al., 2016). These factors include changes in human demographics and behaviour, the effect of new technologies and industries, an increase in international travel and commerce, and breakdown resulting from public health measures. Other factors include humans sharing the same environment as domestic and wild animals, as discussed by The Coronavirus Study Group of the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses (2013).

The emergence of new infectious diseases poses a challenge for healthcare facilities in controlling nosocomial infections. Sampathkumar (2014) describes a severe viral illness caused by a newly discovered coronavirus found in Middle Eastern countries, including KSA, and which was subsequently named the Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV). The MERS-CoV caused epidemics in the Middle East region and among Hajj participants. By May 2014, the number of laboratory-confirmed cases of MERS-CoV infection worldwide had reached 665 with 205 fatalities as shown in Figure 1.7 below.

Figure 1.7: Confirmed cases of Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (MERS-CoV) in the KSA and other countries. Source: Who.int. (2018). [online] Available at: <https://www.who.int/emergencies/mers-cov/epi-20-april-2018.png?ua=1> [Accessed 16 Apr. 2019].

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Based on the literature, 90% of MERS-CoV cases occurred in the Middle East region, with cases outside the region being reported only in people who had recently travelled to the Middle East, or had come into direct contact with someone who had recently travelled to the region (Pavli et al., 2014; Al-Tawfiq et al., 2014). The MERS-CoV illness has a high mortality rate as it is a communicable disease that can be easily transmitted between humans (Sampathkumar, 2014).

Fever and mild cough are among the first symptoms of the MERS-CoV illness. The breathing difficulties progress either rapidly or over several days based on the pre-medical conditions of infected patients resulting in dyspnoea and hypoxia, that is, inability to maintain oxygenation. The lungs, kidneys, and heart can be also infected by the virus which leads to disruption in their functioning. The reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) test

is used to diagnose the MERS-CoV illness. Using tests such as X-ray and CT-Scans may also be diagnostic (CDC, 2020; WHO, 2020).

Because of the lack of experimental data there is no curative approach to treat the MERS-CoV infection other than offering support for disorders, as for example, oxygen supplementation and mechanical ventilation. The treatment should be adjusted based on the patients' pre-medical conditions and there have been different medications on trials. However, there have not been conclusive benefits yet. As MERS-CoV does not spread rapidly it is possible to take protective measures to prevent further outbreaks of the disease such as avoiding close contact with infected people, wearing masks and gloves, washing hands regularly and avoiding bodily fluid exchanges. Nevertheless, in hospitals and care centres infected patients should be kept in airborne isolation rooms. Healthcare workers have to wear masks and gloves as well as cover their eyes when treating patients (CDC, 2020; WHO, 2020).

The MERS-CoV disease has become a major challenge for IPC in KSA as the foundation of the virus and the method of transmission have not yet been completely identified. However, studies show that the virus originates from single-humped camels in Egypt, Qatar and KSA (Sampathkumar, 2014). Such infections constitute a major barrier for prevention and control strategies in KSA.

1.6.5.5.3 Limited Budget Resources

The most difficult challenge faced by the Saudi Ministry of Health is the funding of healthcare services. Overall public health service expenditure originates from the administration and services which are provided free of charge to all Saudi citizens. This leads to substantial cost strain on the government, especially in the current context of population growth, the high cost of technology and increasing awareness of health and disease (Almalki et al., 2011). According to the WHO, KSA allocates 22.75% of total GDP to the healthcare sector (WHO, 2015), although resources are unevenly distributed with a substantial percentage (51.34%) of spending going to bigger communities (WHO, 2015).

Although born of the desert two generations ago, KSA has made tremendous progress in both its private and public healthcare system. Fully aware of the exigencies of establishing a strong healthcare system, budget allocations to healthcare have consistently increased. Despite continued efforts to become globally competitive and meet the highest of standards, this goal has not yet been achieved. Nevertheless, KSA has become a recognised healthcare leader within the Arab Middle East region. The Saudi Ministry of Health continues to evolve and develop in its aim to meet the highest global healthcare quality levels (Alomi, 2015).

According to a report published by the MOH, over the period from 2015 to 2016 the Ministry of Finance allocated SAR 59.985.36019 for healthcare spending, rising to SAR 62.342.539 in 2016 (MOH, 2016). However, as Kingdom Of Saudi Arabia Budget Report (KPMG, 2018) notes, neither of the figures were enough to fulfil the Ministry's plan to make KSA the regional centre for healthcare. Therefore, starting in 2017, the Ministry of Finance started allocating 19% of the national budget to healthcare and education. This translated into \$26.3 billion for 2017 and as it was still considered insufficient, the 2018 budget was increased to \$34.3 billion (MoH, 2016; KPMG, 2018). Saudi Arabians receive free treatment in all public hospitals, clinics and outpatient centres but foreigners cannot enter the kingdom for work purposes or for any length of time, if they do not have health coverage with a major insurer (Almalki et al., 2011).

1.7 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER ONE

Highlighting the purposes of this study, which mainly include investigating the factors associated with adherence to IPC practices, Chapter One has focused on the global epidemiology of HAIs and explored differences in the prevalence of HAIs in developed and developing countries. It has been indicated that between 5.4% and 20% of patients admitted to acute-care hospitals in developing countries acquire at least one or more HAIs. As this study investigates infection control in KSA, some background information is provided on the people, culture and healthcare system of KSA, including population trends and demographic profile.

The chapter also discussed the status of infection control, both globally and locally in KSA, outlining the strategies for, and challenges associated with the implementation of IPC programmes. Furthermore, the chapter outlined the WHO core components for the implementation of IPC programmes, exploring the factors that affect non-adherence to infection control practices from a holistic perspective.

Chapter One described the organisation of the Saudi healthcare system in general, and the organisation of infection control services in particular. Although the MOH has established IPC programmes at every healthcare institution, performance has been found to be suboptimal as a result of the many challenges faced by the MOH in running effective IPC programmes. Challenges include the existence of defunct or understaffed IPC programmes, the increasing burden of emerging infectious diseases exacerbated by pilgrimages, poor health financing, and a range of other factors that lead to poor compliance with IPC procedures. Against the above-mentioned research background and context, this mixed-methods study is set. The purpose of the next chapter is to present the literature review on infection prevention and control to situate infection control in KSA in the global context internationally.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The literature review is defined as the identification and analysis or review of the literature and information related to what is intended to be studied (Terre Blanche et al., 2006, p. 480). Therefore, the purpose of this chapter is to provide an in-depth exploration of the healthcare literature to review articles of direct relevance to the current study. In particular, the focus of the review will be on barriers and enablers to infection prevention and control (IPC) in healthcare facilities. The chapter begins with some background information on healthcare-associated infections (HAIs). A rationale for conducting this literature review and the main review questions will be provided next. The chapter also presents in detail the procedures of identifying the literature including the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the search strategy and selection, methods for data analysis and synthesis and the critical appraisal tools used to assess the quality of the articles included in the review. Finally, the findings of the literature review are presented thematically and gaps in the literature are identified.

2.2 BACKGROUND INFORMATION

Data from the World Health Organisation (WHO) show that globally about 5% -10% of patients admitted to inpatient wards of hospitals acquire HAIs annually (WHO, 2008; Sydnor and Perl, 2011). It has also been suggested that the incidence of HAIs has been on the increase in the past 20 years in both developed and developing countries worldwide (WHO, 2008). The burden of HAIs is higher in developing countries compared to developed countries, with developing countries having up to 20 times more the risk of acquiring HAIs compared to developed countries (Cheng et al., 2007; Hopmans et al., 2007; WHO, 2008). For example, utilising data from national and multicentre studies, the report published by WHO in 2011 indicates that from 3.5–12% of hospitalised patients in high-income countries such as the UK and France acquire HAIs compared

to 5.7–19.1% of hospitalised patients in developing countries such as the Islamic Republic of Iran or KSA (WHO, 2011).

As mentioned previously in Chapter One (section 1.2), in KSA, there have been reports of increased cases of occupational infections observed among healthcare workers when healthcare professionals, primarily nurses, did not follow established guidelines of infection prevention and control appropriately (Assiri et al., 2013). This emphasises the need for procedures that aim to change the perceptions of HAIs in KSA among nurses (Assiri et al., 2013). Furthermore, based on Gupta et al., (2017), statistics from the MOH indicate that in recent years, healthcare-associated infections have increased in KSA and placed a heavy economic burden on the country. Therefore, HAIs is still a challenge in KSA as in many developing countries because of many reasons primarily HCWs' non-compliance with IPC measures (Nofal et al., 2017).

Several factors have been associated with non-compliance with infection control procedures globally. Based on the literature, these factors can be grouped into two major categories including individual or socio-demographic factors and institutional factors. Socio-demographic factors include knowledge, age, gender, education, and HCWs' attitudes and perceptions. For example, some studies investigated the association between knowledge and education (Paudyal et al., 2008; Vaz et al., 2010; Chang et al., 2014; Hassan, 2018), age and length of clinical experience (Chan et al., 2002; Osborne, 2003; Timilshina et al., 2011), and compliance with infection control practices, while other studies such as Vaz et al. (2010) found no significant relationship. Similarly, some studies (Suchitra and Devi, 2007; Darawad et al., 2012; Honarbakhsh et al., 2017) reported an association between HCWs' perceptions to various precautions and compliance, whereas others, such as Vaz et al., (2010) and Jain et al., (2012) found no such association. On the other hand, among instructional factors, some studies have reported that availability of monitoring and reporting standards, supplies and materials, surveillance and readiness and competence to implement policies and counter to outbreaks, among other factors, to be associated with compliance with IPC practices (Aboshaiqah and Baker, 2013).

2.3. RATIONALE FOR CONDUCTING THIS REVIEW

While some reviews have attempted to summarise evidence on factors associated with infection control, most of these reviews have focused on the importance of hand hygiene on prevention of hospital infections (Allegranzi and Pittet, 2009; WHO, 2011; Ng et al., 2017). The WHO (2011) report defined a set of essential core components for IPC programmes, which suggested that implementing an IPC programme within a healthcare setting is crucial for avoiding HAIs and preparing for and responding to communicable diseases crises. In addition to the above, reviews by Allegranzi and Pittet, (2009) and Hale et al., (2015) from the UK reported that multi-modal IPC programmes which incorporate electronic hand hygiene monitoring and performance feedback, for example, were associated with increased compliance with recommended IPC practices. However, to the researcher's knowledge, no review has investigated the effectiveness of both individual and institutional factors in reducing infections in healthcare practices.

Conducting a comprehensive review encompassing an understanding of both the individual and institutional factors associated with adherence with infection control practices in hospitals would facilitate the formulation of guidelines, identification of gaps in practice, institutional strengths and weaknesses and the development of strong and sustainable infection control programmes and procedures in all hospitals across the world. A reduction in healthcare-associated infections may lead to less suffering of patients and would translate into a lessened medical and economic burden, hence the importance of this study. Therefore, the aim of this review and the review questions which were used to design and conduct this systematic review are provided in the next section.

2.4 REVIEW QUESTIONS

The aim of the systematic review is to analyse evidence of barriers and enablers to compliance with IPC procedures in hospitals. The two main review questions defined in this study are the following:

- What is the role of institutional factors, including availability of guidelines, training, surveillance, supplies, and organisational culture in facilitating or hindering adherence with IPC procedures in healthcare facilities?
- What is the role of individual factors, including socio-demographic factors such as age, education, gender, nationality, individual attitudes and perceptions and self-esteem in facilitating or impeding infection control practices in healthcare facilities worldwide?

The results of this review were used to identify gaps in knowledge in relation to the factors which act as barriers and facilitators to infections prevention and control. In addition, the results informed formulating the aims and objectives of this research study as well as the research questions to address the knowledge gaps in infection prevention and control practices in healthcare facilities.

2.5 METHODS

2.5.1 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

This review was conducted following the recommendations in the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis (PRISMA) statement (Liberati et al., 2009). The three tools considered to facilitate carrying out the review were the PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison, and Outcome), PICOS (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcomes and Study Design) and SPIDER (Sample, Phenomena of Interest, Design, Evaluation and Research type) tools. As Methley et al., (2014) and Cooke et al., (2015) indicate, the PICO tool is used to define quantitative research questions and search terms, whereas the PICOS and SPIDER tools are used as search strategies for qualitative and mixed methods research studies. To facilitate conducting this research while including qualitative evidence synthesis, the PICOS tool was used to focus the review question and design the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The PICOS tool was chosen due to the limitations of the PICO framework which excludes qualitative studies

and the limitations of the SPIDER framework which may show a limited number of relevant articles (Methley et al., 2014). The inclusion and exclusion criteria are presented in detail below:

Table 2.1: Inclusion and exclusion criteria of the review on barriers of compliance with hospital infection control procedures

Domain	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Population	Hospitals, tertiary hospitals, referral hospitals, teaching hospitals, clinics, dispensaries, medical centres, intensive care units (ICU), cardiac ward, paediatric ward, medical ward, female ward, male ward, internal medical ward, neurology ward, infectious diseases ward,	1. Community settings, environmental settings 2. Articles that were not done in a clinical setup
Intervention	Studies that investigated the Institutional barriers e.g. Policy barriers such as institution of infection control programme, leadership, education and training, supplies and equipment, Physical Environment factors e.g. availability of bins, hospital layout and proximity of hand dispensers or hand wash sinks, Technological barriers, e.g. electronic hand wash monitoring system, Studies that investigated the Personal barriers such as Task oriented barriers (e.g. being a nurse or doctor), attitude and perceptions, demographic factors (such as gender, age, nationality), self-efficacy Studies that investigated interpersonal barriers (organisational cultural barriers; e.g. teamwork, existence of a supportive or unsupportive culture, careless or caring culture)	1. Articles that talk about the attitude and perception of the general public and not those of HCWs 2. Articles that measure levels of perceptions or knowledge but do not link their significance with compliance with infection control
Outcomes	Compliance with infection control measures (adherence to hand hygiene, wearing PPEs such as gloves, aprons, face masks; proper disposal of hazardous waste; good nursing practices such as not reusing or recapping needles)	Levels of knowledge, or perceptions, prevalence of infection control behaviours, perceptions of the general public on what causes HAIs
Study design	Quantitative studies (cross-sectional studies or surveys, descriptive surveys, prospective studies, audits) Qualitative studies (surveys, semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions) Systematic reviews	Narrative studies or reviews which did not include studies that investigated factors of IPC adherence among healthcare workers

Based on the literature reviewed in Chapter One, it was envisaged that demographic and other individual factors (such as beliefs and attitudes), perceptions (such as perceived susceptibility and threat), and institutional factors such as physical or environmental, technological, personal and task associated factors would potentially facilitate or hinder compliance with IPC procedures. Furthermore, organisational culture, that is, the existence of a supportive or unsupportive culture was considered another factor influencing compliance with IPC guidance. Therefore, these factors were used to narrow the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

2.5.2 Search Strategy and Study Selection

The literature was sourced from databases including MEDLINE (Ovid), CINAHL (EBSCOhost), Web of Science and other sources of grey literature. Government and healthcare body websites were also sourced for grey literature or other relevant references.

The search involved combining of key words and text words in MeSH, title, abstract, and full text and the use of Boolean operators such as OR and AND, or *. These test words and MeSH used were chosen following guidance obtained from previous reviews published in peer reviewed journals and national infection control guidelines. Search terms for quantitative studies were based on the search terms used in the review by Price et al., (2018) because of their relevance to this study, whereas those used to capture qualitative studies were based on the terms used by Currie et al.,'s (2018) review.

It was envisaged that the search should identify evidence from both qualitative and quantitative surveys (both primary studies and systematic reviews) on barriers and enablers to compliance with infection control practices globally, not only locally from KSA. Therefore, the search was not limited to primary studies only nor the KSA context specifically. The search was made comprehensive because the aim of the review was to understand any barriers or enablers to compliance with IPC procedures. Therefore, evidence should be drawn from any published studies, whether primary or systematic reviews, to give a comprehensive picture of these enablers

and barriers. In addition, the aim was to identify all published studies irrespective of their date of publication. Therefore, no publication date limitation was applied to the search.

As the researcher comes from KSA, the search also aimed at identifying any studies that might have been conducted in KSA or any Arab or Middle East countries. Therefore, no language filters were applied. Details of an example of the search strategy are provided in Table 2.2 below:

Table 2.2: Search Strategy

Search No	Query
#1	'healthcare associated infection*:exp' OR 'hospital-acquired infection*:ti,ab' OR 'nosocomial infection*:ti,ab' OR 'hospital infection*:ti,ab' OR 'Hospital-acquired infections.mp.' OR 'Cross Infection*' OR 'hospital acquired infection* outbreaks.mp.' OR 'Iatrogenic Disease:ti,ab' OR 'Bacterial Infections: exp' OR 'Clostridium Difficile Infections.mp' OR 'methicillin resistant hospital infections.mp.' OR 'Methicillin-Resistant Staphylococcus aureus.mp' OR 'Vancomycin Resistant Enterococci:ti,ab'
#2	"demographic factors:ti,ab' OR 'health care worker Age:ti,ab' OR 'Age.mp' OR 'gender.mp' OR 'education.mp' OR 'nationality:ti,ab' 'qualification.mp' OR 'experience:ti,ab' OR 'work experience.mp' OR 'profession:ti,ab' OR 'nurse*:ti,ab' OR 'doctor*:ti,ab' OR 'dentist*:ti,ab' OR 'ophthalmologist*:ti,ab' OR 'attitude*:ti,ab' OR 'perception*:ti,ab' OR '(attitudes AND perceptions)' OR 'work load' OR 'self-efficacy'
#3	'institutional support: exp' OR 'technological barriers:ti,ab' OR 'socio-demographic barriers:ti,ab' OR 'policy:ti,ab' OR 'policy barriers:ti,ab' OR 'leadership:ti,ab' OR 'education.mp' OR 'training.mp' OR 'supplies.mp' OR 'equipment.mp' OR 'gloves.mp' OR 'availability of gloves' OR 'face masks.mp' or 'availability of face masks.mp' OR '(aprons AND gown*)' OR '(availability of apron* AND gown*)' OR 'physical environment.mp' OR 'bins:ti,ab' OR 'availability of bins' OR 'hospital layout.mp' OR 'hand wash sinks:ti,ab' OR 'availability of hand wash sinks:ti,ab' OR 'proximity of hand dispensers' OR 'automatic soap dispensers' OR 'medical trollies.mp' OR 'Laboratory:ti,ab' OR 'availability of infection control Laboratory' OR 'electronic hand wash monitoring system' OR 'surveillance' OR 'organisational culture' OR 'being a nurse' OR 'being a doctor' OR '(being a nurse OR doctor AND health care culture)'
#4	#2 AND #3
#5	'adherence to infection control procedures:ti,ab' OR 'adherence to IC guidelines:ti,ab' OR 'hand washing.mp' or 'washing hands before touching patient:ab' OR 'wearing gloves:ti,ab' 'needle capping:ab' 'environmental cleaning' OR 'cohorting.mp' OR 'patient cohorting' OR 'isolation:ti,ab' OR 'environmental cleaning:ab' OR 'precautions:ab' OR 'infection outbreaks: exp' OR 'outbreak of multi-drug resistant organisms' OR 'outbreak of hospital acquired infections.mp'
#6	#1 AND #4 AND #5

Illustrative examples of search outputs on MEDLINE, CINAHL and Web of Science are provided in Appendices I to III.

2.5.3 Quality Assessment

Several tools were used to assess the quality of included studies and the tool chosen depended on the design of the studies being assessed. The quality of quantitative studies was assessed by using a modified AXIS tool for assessing quality of cross-sectional surveys (Downes et al., 2016), while the quality of qualitative studies was assessed by the CASP Qualitative Checklist (CASP, 2018). The quality of Mixed Methods studies was evaluated by using the HCPRDU Evaluation tool for mixed methods studies (Long et al., 2002). The quality of systematic reviews was assessed by the CASP Systematic Review Checklist (CASP, 2018), whereas the quality of narrative reviews was assessed by the SANRA-a scale for the quality assessment of narrative review articles (Baethge et al., 2019). These tools were selected in particular because the questions contained within these tools capture the necessary quality issues that determine the validity and reliability of studies as described by Creswell (2003).

There are two aspects relating to the quality of studies, which are, validity and reliability. As noted by Creswell (2003), validity in quantitative research arises from the ability to accurately measure the outcome. Balnaves and Caputi (2001) contend that validity is of three types: internal, external and construct validity. Internal validity refers to the ability of the research design to allow for the drawing of a conclusion from the relationship between variables. External validity refers to the generalizability of the research findings. Construct validity measures the extent to which the investigator constructs and presents the phenomenon under study. According to Creswell (2003), reliability and validity do not refer to the same thing and neither do they have a similar connotation. The same constructs of validity, reliability and construct validity are used to assess qualitative and quantitative studies. The reliability and validity of qualitative and quantitative

methods in a study need to be assessed jointly rather than separately. Creswell (2003) contends that quantitative studies focus more on validity and this is done to ensure the numerical values used are credible and trustworthy. On the other hand, Creswell (2003) indicates that the reliability of a study is a measure of the stability or consistency of the findings. Reliability determines whether the same results could be obtained if the study was repeated elsewhere. Again, reliability can be split into internal and external reliability (Creswell, 2003).

The quality assessment of identified studies in this review therefore focused mainly on the validity of the findings. For the quality of quantitative studies, items relevant for assessing the quality of identified studies included the aim of the study, background setting and rationale, data sources, outcomes investigated and reported, relevance of the outcome measured, summary of main results and results, discussion and conclusions and strengths and limitations of the study. The modified AXIS checklists for cohort studies/ Cross-sectional surveys contained 10 questions addressing these necessary domains. Each item was therefore scored one point if sufficiently reported. Thus, each study was assigned a score ranging from 0 to 10 by the reviewer. On the other hand, for qualitative studies, items relevant for assessing the quality of identified studies included whether data was collected in a way that addressed the research issue, whether the recruitment strategy appropriate to the aims of the research, whether the relationship between researcher and participants had been adequately considered, whether data analysis was sufficiently rigorous, and how valuable is the research finding. The CASP checklist for qualitative studies contains 10 questions addressing these necessary domains. Each item was again scored one point if sufficiently reported. Therefore, each study had a total score, ranging from 0 to 10, by the reviewer. Regarding mixed methods studies, the HCPRDU Evaluation tool (Long et al., 2002) also contained 10 questions addressing these necessary domains and each item was also scored one point if sufficiently reported. Hence, each study was assigned a score ranging from 0 to 10 by the reviewer.

As for reviews, the CASP Systematic Review Checklist (CASP, 2018), contains 10 questions and the reviewer here adopted all of them. Each item was also scored one point if

sufficiently reported. Thus, each study was assigned a score ranging from 0 to 10 by the reviewer. Lastly, the modified SANRA-a scale for the quality assessment of narrative review articles (Baethge et al., 2019) contained 8 questions addressing these necessary domains. Each item was therefore scored one point if sufficiently reported. Therefore, each study was assigned a score ranging from 0 to 8 by the reviewer. In Appendices IV to VIII, a summary table showing how each of the included studies scored is provided. The appendices also show examples of scoring for each type of study designs included in this review in detail (e.g. one study representing quantitative, qualitative, mixed-methods, systematic and narrative review) to explain how quality assessment was done.

2.5.4 Methods for Data Analysis and Synthesis

All eligible studies had to meet the following inclusion criteria: a quantitative or qualitative study that examines the relationship between dimensions of infection control and adherence to components of IPC by HCWs in hospital settings. No language and publication date restrictions were applied. For quantitative studies, a narrative synthesis was used to summarise the outcomes of the identified studies using tables. In addition, a summary of select study characteristics was created and completed using a table. The results were grouped based on an analytic framework according to the important themes identified by the WHO (2011) report which defines a set of essential core components for IPC programmes. Findings from studies were summarised highlighting, for example, whether some socio-demographic factors such as age, gender, education, or nationality were identified as enabling or hindering adherence to IPC, or whether institutional factors such as availability of supplies, training, or organisational culture were critical.

The PRISMA guidelines (Liberati et al., 2009), which guided conducting this systematic review, suggest that to enhance quality of systematic reviews, two reviewers independently identify potential studies eligible for inclusion, extract data, and assess study quality. However, this study was conducted for the PhD degree, and therefore being an academic piece of work, it

was not possible for independent study selection, data extraction and study quality assessment to be conducted by a second reviewer. Therefore, all these tasks were conducted solely by the researcher. However, all work carried out by the researcher was checked for standard and quality by his two PhD supervisors. It is, therefore, hoped that this must have eliminated any issues that arise when academic work is not peer reviewed.

2.6 RESULTS OF THE LITERATURE REVIEW

A total of 8,192 studies were identified from electronic searches, of these, 8,072 studies were removed after screening the titles and abstracts because of their irrelevance to the aims of the review. One hundred and twenty full text articles were screened, and 30 studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in the review (5 were review articles and 25 were primary studies). Details of the key stages of the identification process and the search results are illustrated below in Figure 2.1:

Figure 2.1. The PRISMA Flow Diagram

The next subsection provides details on the studies included in the review.

2.6.1 Characteristics of the Included Studies

The 30 studies included in the review were conducted in different parts of the world. For example, as Table 2.3 below shows, eight studies were from the Middle East of which four were from KSA. Six studies were from Europe of which three were from the UK. Four studies were from America, whereas two studies were from Brazil (South America). As for the rest of the studies, four were from Asia (two from India and two from China), and four were from Nigeria. It is hoped that this diversity in the literature identified in this review may reflect a wider scope of factors affecting compliance with IPC in health care settings beyond the boundaries of KSA.

Regarding the aims of the studies, seven studies (including two systematic reviews and five primary studies) explored the role of multi-modal hand hygiene programmes such as World Health Organisation infection control programme or other related programmes. These studies were from across the globe of which one was from KSA, two from America, one from Switzerland, one from Germany and one from France. Eleven of the thirty studies reported the role of several organisational, individual and societal factors on influencing compliance with infection control. For example, a study by Smiddy et al., (2015) investigates the role of work environment characteristics which include access to resources, level of knowledge, provision of information, and organizational culture. In addition, Rabaan et al., (2017) look at the role of infrastructure and design, policy implementation, training program, surveillance and reporting standards. The rest of the studies reported the role of knowledge, attitudes, perceptions and organisational culture on affecting compliance with infection control. Table 2.3 below shows a summary of the main studies included in the review:

Table 2.3: Summary of studies included in review of factors influencing hospital infection control

Title	Author(s) and Country	Aim	Objective, Sample size and Method	Summary of Key Findings	Strengths	Limitations
1. Role of hand hygiene in healthcare-associated infection prevention.	Allegranzi and Pittet (2009) Switzerland	Examine multi-modal hand hygiene programme on compliance and the effectiveness of hand hygiene promotion strategies	Systematic review Unspecified number of publications	Implementation of a comprehensive, multi-modal hand hygiene programme with education on hand washing, hand hygiene observation, Hand hygiene electronic monitoring, performance feedback, alcohol-based hand rub, posters, were associated with increased compliance with hand hygiene practices. The authors conclude that to effectively improve hand hygiene in health care workers and reduce HCAI, the organizations should adopt multimodal strategy as an intervention.	Highlights the relative effectiveness of different hand hygiene promotion strategies such as alcohol-based hand rubs, chlorhexidine soap, education on hand washing, training, observation on hand hygiene, posters, feedback, Hand hygiene electronic monitoring, incentives, and focus group discussions	The variability of the types of Multi-modal hand hygiene programmes across the included studies means it's difficult to pinpoint which ones were associated with improved IPC
2. Relationship between patient safety climate and standard precaution adherence: a systematic review of the literature	Hessels and Larson (2016) America	Explore factors associated with adherence to IPC	Systematic review, 7 studies	Efforts to improve infection control programmes (such as 'bundled' or targeted interventions to prevent device-related or surgical site infections), or any other related or similar IPC models, may enhance adherence to Infection control and safety.	Clearly demonstrates the discordance between IPC guidelines and practices in different institutions, and tried to close that gap by suggesting what would probably work	Patient safety culture PSC and Standard precautions (SPs) were operationalized differently across studies
3. Systematic qualitative literature review of Health professionals' compliance with hand hygiene guidelines	Smiddy et al., (2015) America	Explore factors associated with adherence to IPC: access to resources, level of knowledge Organisational culture and subjective norms	Systematic review of the qualitative literature 22 publications	Work environment characteristics (i.e. access to resources, level of knowledge, provision of information, and organizational culture) influenced how health care workers complied with hand hygiene guidelines. Motivational factors (which largely depend on individual people's behaviour) and perceptions of the work environment (structural empowerment) were found to be factors that contribute to compliance with hand hygiene.	Highlights the importance of institutional, individual and social influences, or otherwise called subjective norms on HCWs behaviour in complying with infection control policies	The credibility, and transferability of qualitative evidence included in this review. Specifically, because they are qualitative in nature and also that none of the studies further explored why the participants felt the way they did regarding hand

Title	Author(s) and Country	Aim	Objective, Sample size and Method	Summary of Key Findings	Strengths	Limitations
						hygiene practices and compliance
4. Working practices and success of infection prevention and control teams: a scoping study	Hale et al., (2015) UK	Examine IPC models, explore the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of different models of IPC team-working; as monitors vs as educators vs as crisis managers	Qualitative Systematic review, 11 Qualitative studies	IPC models (i.e. IPC as intermediaries or as educators) are not effective in reducing infection in health care practices. IPC teams perform surveillance or education as their primary functions and they often face resistance to implementation of new IPC policies, especially when they conflicted with ingrained practices. Senior medical staff members being the major resisters and their influence creating a barrier to progress (Organisational culture).	Highlights how IPC teams balance everyday service delivery with management of outbreaks or other crisis situations demanding immediate attention Also highlighted the importance of Organisational culture (resistance to change) acts as an impediment to effective change in Infection control	Most of the included studies used qualitative methodologies to investigate the operation of IPC teams. This question could be better understood by using mixed methods studies
5. Organizational culture and its implications for infection prevention and control in healthcare institutions	De Bono et al., (2014) America	Investigate the role of organisational culture in IPC	Narrative review	The theory of OC within healthcare settings appear to impact on IPC-related behaviour. It highlights the paucity of well-designed studies but identifies sporadic literature suggesting that well-designed and customized OC change initiatives can have a positive impact on IPC practices such as hand hygiene.	Highlights the importance of organisational culture	Did not discuss what causes certain cultures to develop in certain institutions and the role of organisational support such as supplies and training and surveillance systems in de-reinforcing or re-enforcing certain cultures Narrative reviews may represent expert opinion not necessarily facts

Title	Author(s) and Country	Aim	Objective, Sample size and Method	Summary of Key Findings	Strengths	Limitations
6. Healthcare professionals' hand hygiene knowledge and beliefs in the United Arab Emirates	Ng, et al., (2017) UAE	Examine knowledge and beliefs and practice	Mixed methods design; a survey followed by focus groups with 96 nurses, 13 doctors	Most doctors remained sceptical about the importance of hand hygiene on prevention of hospital infections, and blamed HI on contaminated surfaces, until particular education techniques like the glow lotion and ultraviolet hand scanner were used to demonstrate inadequate handwashing, suggesting it would be important. There was no score difference on hand hygiene scores between doctors and nurses. Although doctors' hand hygiene knowledge was slightly higher than that of nurses (78.5% versus 73.5%).	This study offers insightful knowledge on how individual beliefs are likely to influence prevention and control practices.	Convenience sampling may create a selection bias towards HCP with an interest in hand hygiene
7. Improving hand hygiene compliance in health care workers: Strategies and impact on patient outcomes	Song et al., (2013) America	Explore multi-modal hand hygiene programme on compliance and the effectiveness of hand hygiene measurers	Observational study (Pre and Post Intervention) Unspecified number in a children's hospitals	Implementation of multimodal infection prevention interventions, for example, by providing training material and video tutorials for healthcare workers (HCWs) was associated with better compliance.	Offers insights on MRSA and how this can be controlled by properly instituted hand hygiene measurers or programmes	Some types of hand hygiene compliance measures as recommended by WHO i.e. Moments before clean/aseptic procedures and after body fluid exposure/risk, were not investigated
8. Implementation of the world health organization hand hygiene improvement strategy in critical care units	Mazi et al., (2013) KSA	Examine multi-modal hand hygiene programme on compliance, and the effectiveness of hand hygiene strategy	Observation study (Pre and Post Intervention) in 4 wards at King Abdul Aziz Specialist Hospital, Taif, KSA.	The World Health Organization strategy in combination with hygiene education as well as continuous evaluation and team approach increased compliance among the health care workers but in certain areas.	Highlights the effectiveness of the WHO Hand hygiene promotion strategy in improving compliance with hand hygiene, combined with health education, continuous evaluation and team approach	Cannot cover the sustainability of these efforts in the end. Probably changing behaviour, or investing in social capital would be the solution
9. Knowledge, attitudes, and practices of healthcare	Hosseinihashemi, et al., (2015)	Explore knowledge attitudes and practices	Quantitative Cross-sectional study of	Work experience and age were significant contributors to knowledge and attitudes and practice. Specifically, among people with the same experience levels, there was a positive linear	Highlights the importance of knowledge on practice	Self-reporting is likely to be associated with over-rating

Title	Author(s) and Country	Aim	Objective, Sample size and Method	Summary of Key Findings	Strengths	Limitations
personnel concerning hand hygiene in Shiraz University of Medical Sciences hospitals	Iran		377 nurses, doctors, therapists, technicians working in internal medicine; surgical, burn, oncology, and obstetrics wards; and intensive care units from 5 Shiraz University of Medical Sciences hospitals	correlation between total knowledge scores (correlation coefficient = 0.178, p=.001) and total attitude scores (correlation coefficient = 0.376, p < .001) with total practice scores.	Good sample size, i.e. a minimum sample of 322 was needed to obtain 95% confidence within an error of 5%. Recruited a variety of healthcare workers including doctors and nurses and allied health professionals and from different wards	The reporting of the findings is confusing and difficult to understand
10. Compliance with hand hygiene: reference data from the national hand hygiene campaign in Germany	Wetzker et al., (2016) Germany	Examine multi-modal hand hygiene programme on compliance, and the effectiveness of hand hygiene measurers	Observational study 109 participating hospitals collected from 576 wards between January 1st and December 31st, 2014 based on observational data submitted by the participating hospitals	<p>Implementation of multimodal infection prevention interventions, for example, by providing training material and video tutorials for healthcare workers (HCWs) was associated with better compliance</p> <p>Neonatal ICUs and paediatric non-ICUs maintaining higher compliance than adult care units.</p> <p>Compliance with hand hygiene was better among nurses than physicians. Overall compliance of nurses (78%) was significantly higher than for physicians (67%, P < 0.01)</p> <p>Overall, the rates of hand hygiene were higher after patient contact than before.</p> <p>The leaders in hand hygiene compliance were neonatal ICUs with a mean of 83% and a median of 90%: significantly better than surgical and medical ICU units (P < 0.01)</p>	Observation provides an opportunity to analyse the behaviour of HCWs and to recognize common mistakes on which to improve further hand hygiene interventions	Small sample size i.e. only 109/2000 Hospitals in German submitted compliance data. Secondly, the Hawthorne effect (compliance during observation periods is usually higher as HCWs who know that they are under observation tend to perform better) is a main bias for surveillance by Direct observation.

Title	Author(s) and Country	Aim	Objective, Sample size and Method	Summary of Key Findings	Strengths	Limitations
11. Evaluation of an ethical method aimed at improving hygiene rules compliance in dental practice	Offner et al., (2016) France	Exploring ethical training and how it created knowledge and motivation for student dentists to follow hygiene rules	Quantitative Prospective study, 130 clinician students	Thought experiment in ethics training improved motivation and compliance with hygiene rules	Emphasizes the effectiveness of a hand hygiene promotion strategy (the ethical training) on improvement of hand hygiene	Does not discuss other competing challenges other than instituting a programme, challenges such as people's attitudes and perceptions on importance of IPC and how this affects compliance
12. Assessing healthcare associated infections and hand hygiene perceptions amongst healthcare professionals.	Tan and Jeffrey (2015) KSA	Explore perceptions about the factors that facilitate IPC e.g. leadership, provision of guidelines, education and training	Quantitative survey self-administered questionnaire to 87 health professionals, healthcare professional i.e. medical doctors, nurses and others who have a direct contact to patients at least on a daily basis, from Ministry of Interior Security Hospitals, Jeddah	This study suggests that health professionals have high levels of awareness of associated infections; 27.6% of the respondents believed that there is about 0 – 10% chances that hospitalized patients will develop healthcare associated infections. On the other hand, there were 19.5% respondents who didn't believe there is such risk Organizational factors such as staff commitment and engagement, leadership of the department heads, provision of access to hand hygiene facilities, guidelines, education and training were significant factors affecting positive practices.	Provides a clear explanation on the role of organisational factors such as commitment, staff engagement and leadership are significant promoters of positive practices	Self-reporting is likely to be associated with over-rating Also, the small sample size i.e. only 87 participants were interviewed through questionnaire, Low response rate
13. Hospital hand hygiene compliance improves with increased monitoring and immediate feedback	Walker et al., (2014) America	Examine multi-modal infection control programme coupled with intensive monitoring programme and provision	Qualitative, Longitudinal study new hand hygiene monitoring programme over a 1-year period. Experimental departments with 2 hospital care	Installation of a real-time monitoring system with conspicuous and visible monitors, extensive education, immediate feedback and real-time data dissemination to leadership-improved compliance by health care workers.	Emphasizes the effectiveness of a hand hygiene promotion strategy (the ethical training) on improvement of hand hygiene	Does not cover the sustainability of these efforts in the end. Probably changing behaviour, or investing in social capital would be the solution

Title	Author(s) and Country	Aim	Objective, Sample size and Method	Summary of Key Findings	Strengths	Limitations
		of advanced technologies and training, effectiveness of a hand hygiene promotion strategy	units, different, but similar, departments served as controls			
14. Infection control practices in health care: Teaching and learning requirements of medical undergraduates	Ayub et al., (2013) India	Explore knowledge and practice	Quantitative Cross-sectional study (Structured Interview) 160 students, 100 faculty members	Only 31.25% of the STUDENTS indicated that they follow guidelines on infection prevention and control. The authors found that successful implementation of prevention and control practices requires a positive attitude and strict monitoring and vigilance by the management (teachers in the college). Authors think that medical students cannot self-assess their performance accurately as the assessment of a topic such as infection control knowledge and practice is potentially complex, therefore that, teamwork is a useful tool for promoting positive perception on reducing infection in health care.	Highlights the link between knowledge and practice	Self-reporting is likely to be associated with over-rating Does not explore the importance of other factors, other than knowledge in IPC
15. Attitudes towards infection prevention and control: an interview study with nursing students and nurse mentors.	Ward (2012) UK	Examine perceptions of both nursing students and their mentors; their attitudes towards IPC	Qualitative study 31 nursing students, 32 nurse mentors	The author found that most of the nurses have a negative perception of infection prevention and control practices. Qualified staff considered IC to be an additional workload burden as opposed to an integral aspect of patient safety and quality care.	Provides critical insight into nurses' perceptions as barriers to infection control	A qualitative study with a small sample size at one hospital in the UK. Therefore, it may not be transferable to nursing students and nurse mentors in other healthcare organisations
16. Questionnaire-based analysis of infection prevention and	Rabaan et al., (2017) KSA	Assess abidance, attitudes to, and awareness of IPC policies	Quantitative Survey, 607 healthcare workers in government,	The following factors were said to be major contributors of infection; hospital infrastructure and design contributing to (54.20%) of hospital acquired infections; lack and shortage of staff (53.71%); no infection control training	Unlike other studies, this research was comprehensive by trying to explore all possible factors to infection control from	As this was a quantitative survey, the responses might not represent reality of the ground; the 'yes'

Title	Author(s) and Country	Aim	Objective, Sample size and Method	Summary of Key Findings	Strengths	Limitations
control in healthcare facilities in KSA in regards to Middle East Respiratory Syndrome		and guidelines among HCP in different institution types in KSA (Identify areas of concern among HCWs on infection prevention in KSA HC facilities)	private hospitals and poly clinics	programme (51.73%), and no electronic surveillance system (81.22%). The authors found a high level of uncertainty among health professionals regarding institution-specific issues, policy implantation, surveillance and reporting standards, readiness, and competence to implement policies and respond to outbreaks. Carelessness of healthcare professionals was cited as the leading cause of infection with hospital facilities being the leading factor in the spread of diseases.	policy to preparedness, to facilities, to attitudes etc.	and no' responses may not be necessarily 'correct' of what is available at particular institutions
17. Perception and experiences of infection control practices among professional nurses in secondary health facilities in south-south Nigeria	Edet et al., (2017) Nigeria	Explore nurses experiences and perceptions about infection control practices	Qualitative study 54 nurses, in-depth interviews and focus group discussion	Compliance is hindered by negative attitude; where PIC is seen not to be part of the job for ward nurses. This could be due to non-familiarity with infection control practices or pressure of work. It is also hindered no availability/ provision of personal protective equipment.	Provides critical insight into nurses' perceptions as barriers to infection control	Qualitative therefore the results cannot be generalised Recruited only nurses, hence, it might not be representative of other professionals
18. Knowledge, awareness and compliance with standard precautions among health workers in north eastern Nigeria	Abdulrahem et al., (2012) Nigeria	Explore knowledge and practice in infection control	Qualitative, cross-sectional survey; self-administered questionnaire 276 HCWs	Generally, the respondents had less knowledge of IPC with only 13% being knowledgeable on the subject. Longer experience affected practice; for example, among those with experience of ten years and above, compliance with the use of sterile gloves, disposal of needles and other sharp objects was higher ($p < 0.05$). Those with ≥ 10 years working experience had a high level of awareness of universal precautions than those with ≤ 5 years ($p < 0.05$).	Highlights the low prevalence of IPC knowledge among HCWs in this part of Nigeria and adopted a very good study design to understand prevalence of knowledge	Does not consider the role of other factors such individual, and institutional factors

Title	Author(s) and Country	Aim	Objective, Sample size and Method	Summary of Key Findings	Strengths	Limitations
19. Infection control and practice of standard precautions among healthcare workers in northern Nigeria	Amoran et al., (2013) Nigeria	Examine factors contributing to non-compliance with IPC	Quantitative, cross-sectional Survey 421 HCWs	The lack of supplies such as PPEs and other supplies and utilities in the health facilities, was the main reason for not applying standard precautions. Most common non-compliances included; Not washing hands, Not using gloves, unsafe handling and disposal of sharp objects, and unsafe cleaning procedures.	Highlights the important factors associated with non-compliance e.g. demographic factors, training, past experiences with emergency infection issues	Qualitative, therefore, the results cannot be generalised
20. Knowledge and Practice of Health Care Workers on Infection Control Measures	Bai (2015) India	Explore knowledge and practice	Mixed methods study 106 nursing personnel. Knowledge was assessed by a structured questionnaire and practice was assessed by an observation checklist	Knowledge did not translate to high practice; i.e. although majority (67.2%) of the nursing staff and (71.1%) nursing students had adequate knowledge, during observation stage of the research it was seen that hand washing steps were not followed by 27.3% of nursing staff and 25.5% of the nursing students.	Somehow showed a link between knowledge and practice i.e. that although the knowledge score between participants was high, this did not translate into high compliance rates in the observation study	Convenient sampling technique was used and this might bias the results. Since authors used triangulation, it is difficult to understand the findings at individual level
21. Investigating Compliance with Standard Precautions During Residency Physicians in Gynaecology and Obstetrics.	Carvalho et al., (2016) Brazil	Explore compliance with standard precautions among resident physicians working in obstetrics and gynaecology	Quantitative, cross-sectional Survey, structured questionnaire, 58 resident physicians	Physician's compliance with standard precautions was intermediate. However, the results reflected that the participants were more cautious regarding compliance with other procedures other than others; for example, more compliant with the handling and disposal of sharp articles, and with the use of gloves.	Highlights how some of the IPC standard precaution measurers are regarded highly by practitioners, while others are not	Did not consider the role of other factors such individual, and institutional factors Small sample size.

Title	Author(s) and Country	Aim	Objective, Sample size and Method	Summary of Key Findings	Strengths	Limitations
22. Factors influencing nurses' compliance with Standard Precautions in order to avoid occupational exposure to microorganisms	Efstathiou et al., (2011) Cyprus	Examine factors that influence nurses' compliance with Standard Precaution	Qualitative 4 focused groups (N=30)	Factors that influenced compliance fell into the 4 domains of the HBM: - benefits (preventing infection, freedom from worrying about possibility of being infected), - barriers (e.g. emergency situation – no time to think of PPEs, Availability of equipment, difficulties associated with wearing some PPEs e.g. gloves, patient's discomfort, Too busy, lack of nursing personnel, the type of patient you are caring for e.g. children, concerns about the nurses appearance, if the procedure is not a norm in the hospital, experience, influence of other senior or role models), - severity (serious disease that can lead to death, fear of this disease, costs associated with being infected), susceptibility (risk of being infected, vulnerability to disease because of one's own immune system), cues to action (type of patient one is caring for e.g. if its elderly and frail or HIV positive, or foreigners, previous exposure, education and reminder system, personal characteristics, significant others), and -Self-efficacy (difficulty to change behaviour when one is used to it, like they have done so for many years and were trained that doing it is better. It becomes difficult to change it after, even though one letter knows it is not correct).	Highlights importance of knowledge and other factors in IPC. Used a theoretical framework the HBM to elicit the factors associated with non-compliance with infection control	Qualitative, therefore, the results cannot be generalised
23. Compliance with infection control standard precautions guidelines: a survey among dental healthcare workers in Hail Region, KSA	Haridi et al., (2016) KSA	Explore demographic, professional and institutional factors associated with good compliance with standard	Quantitative Cross-sectional survey 307 health professionals	Compliance with SP was high, with the majority (90.1%) of dentists complying to standard procedures. Predictors of compliance included; Institutional commitment to IPC requirements ((odds ratio [OR], 4.34; P <0.001), perceived adequacy of training (OR, 3.51; P = 0.003), and type of profession (dentist) OR, 2.99; P = 0.035. This could probably mean that institutions who are committed to better infection control allocate	Emphasises the role of type of profession and clinical practice plays in compliance with SIPs	Self-reporting is likely to be associated with over-rating

Title	Author(s) and Country	Aim	Objective, Sample size and Method	Summary of Key Findings	Strengths	Limitations
		IPC precautions guidelines among dentists and dental assistants		more resources and information, which might explain the better and positive outcomes.		
24. Knowledge of and adherence to hygiene guidelines among medical students in Austria	Herbert et al., (2013) Austria	Explore knowledge and practice	Quantitative Survey 192 medical students	While the knowledge on hygiene guidelines was good (70% judged themselves as having excellent knowledge), adherence was limited (43 and 49% for hand washing and general hygiene guidelines respectively) There were no statistically significant differences between the male and the female students. Nevertheless, female students demonstrated a higher self-assessment concerning the compliance and knowledge of infection control in the healthcare setting as compared to the males.	Demonstrates the discordance between knowledge and practice	Self-reporting is likely to be associated with over-rating Relatively small sample
25. Factors impacting compliance with standard precautions in nursing, China	Luo et al., (2010) China	Evaluate registered nurse compliance with standard precautions and analyse the factors that affect compliance	Quantitative Survey 1500 randomly selected nurses from 18 hospitals in Hunan Province, China	The factors affecting compliance included: training (odds ratio (OR: 2.17, CI 1.85–2.55), knowledge (OR: 1.94, CI 1.01–3.41), hospital grade (OR: 1.61, CI 1.79–1.86), presence of sharps disposal box in the department (OR 1.43, CI 1.10–3.41), general self-efficacy (OR 1.29, CI 1.04–1.59), exposure experience (OR 0.69, CI 0.56–0.85), and department in which the nurse worked (OR 1.24, CI 1.05–1.46).	Highlights the importance of individual and institutional factors associated with IPC Large sample size and randomly selected	Self-reporting is likely to be associated with over-rating Recruited only nurses and these views might not be the same with other professionals

Title	Author(s) and Country	Aim	Objective, Sample size and Method	Summary of Key Findings	Strengths	Limitations
26. Assessment of compliance to standard precautions among surgeons in Zagazig University Hospitals, Egypt, using the Health Belief Model	Mortada and Zalat (2014) Egypt	Evaluate Surgeons compliance with standard precautions and its associated factors using HBM	Quantitative cross-sectional study 307 surgeons	There was adequate compliance with standard precautions among surgeons. The factors associated with compliance included; Female gender (54.9% compliance rate), training, perceived awareness, perceived severity, and perceived barriers. Suggesting an association between knowledge and level of compliance.	Highlights importance of knowledge, female gender and other factors in IPC. Used a theoretical framework the HBM to elicit the factors associated with non-compliance with infection control Large sample size	Self-reporting is likely to be associated with over-rating
27. Gender differences in characteristics, occupational exposure, and infection control practices among dental professionals in Edo State, Nigeria	Osazuwa-Peters et al., (2012) Nigeria	Investigate the prevalence of infection control Practices and their associated factors	Quantitative survey, Self-administered questionnaire to 90 dental professionals	There were generally no gender differences in compliance with general infection control guidelines, except for: hand hygiene (favoured by women), eye protection (preferred by women), and protective clothing (favoured by men).	Highlights the role of female gender in compliance with infection control	Self-reporting is likely to be associated with over-rating Small sample size
28. Factors influencing adherence to standard precautions among nursing professionals in psychiatric hospitals	Piai-Morais et al., (2015) Brazil	Examine the factors associated with adherence to standard infection control precautions	Quantitative survey, Self-administered questionnaire to 35 nursing professionals	Nursing staff had high knowledge of occupational HIV transmission but adherence to SP was heavily influenced by individual, work-related and organizational factors. Institutional factors associated with adherence included availability of personal protective equipment ($r = 0.643$; $p < 0.0001$), and training ($p = 0.007$) Individual factors included discomfort; 82.90% of respondents indicated that they could not get used to wearing PPG while performing their duties.	Highlights the importance of institutional and individual factors affecting adherence with standard IPC	Recruited only nurses, therefore, the results might not be representative of other professions Self-reporting is likely to be associated with over-rating Small sample size

Title	Author(s) and Country	Aim	Objective, Sample size and Method	Summary of Key Findings	Strengths	Limitations
29. Influencing factors on use of standard precautions against occupational exposures to blood and body fluids among nurses in China.	Quan et al., (2015) China	Explore factors associated with adherence to standard infection control precautions	Quantitative survey, self-administered questionnaire to 1000 nurses	The factors affecting the use of standard precautions among nurses (in order of their importance) were availability of protective devices, knowledge, attitude, safety climate (availability of policy and IPC programme), and workload. For example, it was reported that knowledge had a 75% influence on attitudes and positive impacts towards compliance.	Highlights the importance of institutional and individual factors affecting adherence with standard IPC Large sample size	Recruited only nurses, therefore, the results might not be representative of other professions Self-reporting is likely to be associated with over-rating
30. Towards changing healthcare workers' behaviour: a qualitative study exploring non-compliance through appraisals of infection prevention and control practices.	Shah et al., (2015) UK	Explore how social and environmental circumstances shaped and influenced non-compliant behaviour	Qualitative survey Using a framework interview checklist	The main factors that influenced respondents' behaviour were: 1) ambiguity about responsibility for certain IPC practices, I am a doctor, so IPC is not my job; 2) prioritization attached to some IPC policies and practices with other competing needs for the hospital; and (3) traditional clinical roles (local normative practices) preached by influential peers (e.g. is a pharmacist really supposed to be telling us about infection control) challenged work relationships.	Highlights the role of organisational culture (institutional, social and organisational factors) affect compliance with SIPs	Qualitative, therefore, the results cannot be generalised

2.6.2 Appraisal of Included Studies

As previously mentioned in section 2.5.3 above, the quality of quantitative studies was assessed by a modified tool of the AXIS tool for assessing quality of cross-sectional surveys (Downes et al., 2016), whereas the quality of qualitative studies was assessed by the CASP Qualitative Checklist (CASP, 2018). The quality of Mixed Methods studies was evaluated by using the HCPRDU Evaluation tool for mixed methods studies (Long et al., 2002). The quality of systematic reviews was assessed by the CASP Systematic Review Checklist (CASP, 2018), whereas the quality of narrative reviews was assessed by the SANRA-a scale for the quality assessment of narrative review articles (Baethge et al., 2019). As this review included both quantitative and qualitative studies, quality issues among these studies varied. For quantitative cross-sectional surveys such as Ward (2012), Ayub et al., (2013), Quan et al., (2015), Haridi et al., (2016), and Rabaan et al., (2017), for example, content validity of these studies can be used to ascertain the validity of measuring tools (the structured questionnaires). However, their internal validity is doubtful. It is possible for subjects to influence the results positively to avoid painting themselves negatively. For this reason, the major problem with evidence from quantitative studies is that self-reporting is likely to be associated with over-rating. Therefore, this implicit bias should be considered when interpreting the results of this study.

Other problems that might arise from quantitative surveys, especially those that employed self-administered questionnaires include sampling method, small sample size or low response rate, whereas those that employed mixed methods approaches are mostly hit with the problem of convenient sampling. For example, in the study by Carvalho et al., (2016), only 58 resident physicians returned the structured questionnaire, whereas in Wetzker et al., (2016) only 109/2000 hospitals in German submitted compliance data. On the other hand, in Bai (2015), Ng et al., (2017), a convenient sample of 106 nursing personnel was used to assess their knowledge using a structured questionnaire, and a convenient sample of 96 nurses and 13 doctors was used to

administer a survey followed by focus groups discussion, respectively. These factors might affect the internal and external validity of their results.

Qualitative studies have problems of their own. A major problem of these is their external validity or reliability because the views expressed by respondents in an interview might be subjective only to that individual person and others might not think the same way. For this reason, evidence from qualitative reviews is not generalisable unless this has been repeated in many settings and covering across the known places. On the other hand, studies that employ direct observation such as Wetzker et al., (2016), main bias for surveillance by direct observation is the Hawthorne effect, where compliance during observation periods is usually higher as HCWs who know that they are under observation tend to perform better. Other quality issues include the inability to capture all the important variables or study population, or study designs. For example, Hale et al., (2015) in a systematic review including 15 qualitative studies and investigating the effectiveness of different IPC control models in compliance with IPC, indicated that since most of the evidence was qualitative, it could not be generalised. The authors proposed that perhaps the best methodological approach to study IPC practices was to adopt the mixed methods approach. On the other hand, the study by Offner et al., (2016) did not discuss competing challenges in depth other than instituting a programme, and people's attitudes and perceptions on importance of IPC and how they affect compliance. Similarly, a pre vs-post intervention observational study by Mazi et al., (2013) in 4 wards at King Abdul Aziz Specialist Hospital, Taif, KSA could not cover the sustainability of these efforts in the end.

It is worth noting that the models of infection control programmes differ from an institution to another and from a country to another. For example, in a systematic review including 7 studies that investigated the factors associated with adherence to IPC, patient safety culture (PSC) and Standard precautions (SPs), Hessels and Larson (2016) pinpointed the problem that IPC, PSC and SPs were operationalized differently across different studies, representing different institutions or hospitals. This may incorporate the risk of an additional bias in the evidence relating to the

effectiveness of IPC as different outcomes might not be of the same phenomenon. Lastly, some of the evidence included in this review was obtained from a narrative review. It is worth considering that narrative reviews may represent expert opinion, not necessarily facts.

2.7 MAIN THEMES AND SUBTHEMES

Using the thematic analysis approach to interpret data (Braun and Clarke, 2006), the included studies were read and organised several times to understand the literature, synthesise it and develop the main themes and subthemes which facilitate presenting the literature review and addressing the review questions. Guided by the recommendations set by Braun and Clarke (2006) and Nowell et al., (2017), the researcher familiarised himself with the studies, reading and re-reading them to identify the parts of the literature which are highly relevant to respond to the review questions. After searching for themes and reviewing them, the two key themes and subthemes defined in relation to the barriers and enablers to IPC in hospitals were as shown below:

Table 2.4 Main themes and subthemes

Themes	Subthemes	
Institutional factors associated with compliance with IPC procedures	Implementation of multi-modal infection control programmes	
	Organisational support	
	Organisational culture	
Individual factors associated with compliance with IPC procedures	Knowledge	
	Job title and length of service	
	Socio-demographic factors	Gender, age, nationality and race
		Self-efficacy

The first theme and its associated subthemes address the first review question ‘What is the role of institutional factors, including availability of guidelines, training, surveillance, supplies, and

organisational culture in facilitating or hindering adherence with IPC procedures in health care institutions?’ The second theme and its associated subthemes respond to the second question ‘What is the role of individual factors, including socio-demographic factors such as age, education, gender, nationality, individual attitudes and perceptions and self-esteem in facilitating or impeding infection control practices in health care institutions worldwide?’ The next sections discuss the identified themes and subthemes based on the included studies.

2.7.1 Theme One: Institutional Factors Associated with Compliance with IPC

2.7.1.1 Implementation of Multi-Modal Infection Control Programmes

The WHO advocates for the implementation of infection control regulations ensuring that health care facilities implement the recommended guidelines to reduce the occurrence and spread of diseases and put up measures for early detection of illness and isolation precautions (WHO, 2008). The WHO first Global Patient Safety Challenge (Allegranzi et al., 2007) introduced a concept known as “My five moments for hand hygiene”. The initiative adopts different measures to reduce instances of HAIs. Healthcare staffs are, thus, encouraged to embrace preventative disease strategies such as hygiene through hand washing, while being required to monitor an outbreak in health care settings and report it for proper treatment (Allegranzi et al., 2007). Furthermore, WHO (2011) defined a set of essential core components for such IPC programmes including:

- putting up an IPC programme with some staff appointed as IPC officers;
- drafting policy guidelines;
- staff training;
- staffing on IPC;
- putting up an infection control surveillance to check compliance with IPC practices;
- installing a microbiology laboratory to support IPC;

- adopting an environmental cleaning and waste disposal programme to ensuring a clean and safe environment, and
- monitoring and evaluation of IPC programmes.

This review aimed at gathering evidence on the effectiveness of the WHO infection surveillance and control framework or other similar models.

A review by Allegranzi and Pittet (2009) describes the effectiveness of the WHO infection control model, and other models which among other things incorporate interventions such as training and education on hand washing and hand hygiene observation, alcohol-based hand rub, chlorhexidine soap, hand hygiene electronic monitoring, performance feedback, posters. The authors concluded that the implementation of a comprehensive, multi-modal hand hygiene programme with education on hand washing, hand hygiene observation, hand hygiene electronic monitoring, performance feedback, alcohol-based hand rub, posters, were associated with increased compliance with hand hygiene practices (see Table 2.3 in section 2.6.1).

In KSA, Mazi et al., (2013) evaluate HCWs compliance with IPC, pre and post implementation of WHO initiative. The authors concluded that the WHO strategy in combination with hygiene education as well as continuous evaluation and team approach increased compliance. Along similar lines, Song et al., (2013) in the USA and Wetzker et al. (2016) in Germany report similar results (see Table 2.3). In addition, a study by Walker et al., (2014) show that installation of a real-time monitoring system with conspicuous and visible monitors, extensive education, immediate feedback and real-time data dissemination to leadership improved compliance by healthcare workers. In their review of the literature, Hessels and Larson (2016) indicate that targeted infection control programmes such as ‘bundled’ interventions to prevent device-related or surgical site infections, for example, may enhance adherence to infection control and safety. Finally, Offner et al., (2016) report that ethical training and the way it created knowledge and motivation for student dentists to follow hygiene rules resulted in good compliance with IPC.

2.7.1.2 Organisational Support (Policy, Leadership, Provision of Facilities and Supplies, Staff Training, Education, Engagement and Performance Feedback)

Several reviewed articles show the role of organisational support in facilitating infection control efforts. For example, a quantitative survey by Tan and Jeffrey (2015), recruiting 87 health professionals from MOH hospitals in Jeddah, found that organisational factors such as commitment to staff training and engagement, leadership, provision of hand hygiene facilities, significantly promote positive practices (Table 2.3).

Policy and guidelines: Implementation of and compliance with infection and control guidelines are one of the most efficient ways to reduce HAIs. In a short study, Ayub et al., (2013) sought to find out the role of education in compliance and implementation of these guidelines. The study used a total of 160 finalists in a medical school and 100 subjects from one of the medical schools in India. They were randomly selected. Surprisingly, only 31.25 percent of the subjects indicated that they follow guidelines on infection prevention and control. Therefore, the authors concluded that empowering college students with skills and knowledge in infection control would lead to more compliance when they officially join the sector. Although this study was conducted in India, it offers insightful knowledge on how the education system in KSA can borrow from India and promote infection control practices among health professionals. While this study offers an excellent explanation of how education can promote positive perceptions, it is focused on India which has a different system from KSA. The paper also does not directly link successful infection prevention and control among health professionals to having an excellent education system.

Leadership: Walker et al., (2014) carried out a similar study and found out that inadequate organisation support and absence of an embedded compliance culture among health professionals had a negative impact on infection reduction. In their research, Walker and colleagues recommend the establishment of real-time electronic monitoring programs such as hand hygiene monitoring programme in all healthcare facilities to promote a prevention and control culture among health

professionals. Hessels and Larson (2016) agree with Walker et al., (2014) and Hosseinialhashemi, et al., (2015) and add that all healthcare organizations should prioritize infection prevention and control. They argue that prioritising infection prevention and control could promote a compliance culture and positive perception from everyone, as well as reduce the number of infections significantly. Along a similar line, Hale et al., (2015) indicate that it is vital for hospital management to come up with strict infection prevention and control practices. Ayub et al., (2013) provide the same suggestion as Hale et al., (2015) and add that successful implementation of prevention and control practices requires a positive attitude and strict monitoring and vigilance by the management.

Supplies and other resources: The importance of providing adequate supplies cannot be emphasised enough. A qualitative survey by Efstathiou et al., (2011), involving 30 nurses grouped into four focus groups to investigate factors influencing nurses' compliance with standard infection control procedures, highlighted the availability of equipment as one of the factors impeding compliance with recommended IPC practices. Lack of resources has also been echoed by Tan and Jeffrey (2015) in KSA, Smiddy et al., (2015) in the USA, Piai-Morais et al., (2015) in Brazil, Amoran et al., (2013) in Nigeria, and Quan et al., (2015) in China, indicating that the lack of supplies such as PPEs and other supplies and utilities in the health facilities were the main reason for not applying standard precautions. In their survey, Efstathiou et al., (2011) and Rabaan et al. (2017) identified the lack of staff as one of the obstacles to compliance with recommended IPC practices. Specifically, in Rabaan et al.,'s (2017) study, 53.71 of the respondents indicated that the shortage of staff was a significant contributor to non-compliance with IPC practices.

Education: This has been highlighted as another critical determinant of compliance with IPC practice. Jradi et al., (2013) indicate that education is an effective aspect in helping healthcare workers to adapt to their working conditions. The authors argue that the level of education determines the level of knowledge on standard practices and its significance, with inadequate knowledge on the infection control practices reducing compliance with the standard practices

(Sodhi et al., 2013). Furthermore, according to Quan et al., (2015), a pathway analysis indicated that knowledge had a 75% influence on influencing the attitude and positive impacts towards compliance. Similarly, Sodhi, et al., (2013) compared knowledge among different nurses such as nursing supervisors, nurses in charge and junior nurses. The authors concluded that experienced nurses had good knowledge of various infection control practices, whereas nurses with less experience had average knowledge, and that >80% of nurses with good knowledge complied to infection control procedures. Therefore, this review explored the effectiveness of education programmes in enhancing compliance with IPC.

According to Bai (2015), continuous education programmes on infection control are one of the interventions which can create an organizational environment that complies with the recommended practices on infection control. Therefore, Bai (2015) recommended that postgraduate education of IPC should be emphasised as postgraduate education was associated with high compliance to the standards. Furthermore, Bai (2015) indicated that continuous education courses, regarding infectious control, demonstrated a desirable impact on compliance to standard practices of infection control. Similarly, as indicated above, the review by Allegranzi and Pittet (2009) found that infection control programmes that incorporated continuous education, especially on hand washing and hand hygiene observation, were associated with an increased compliance with hand hygiene practices.

In a mixed-methods study conducted in the UAE, Ng et al., (2017) similarly emphasise the role of education in the prevention and control of infections. The authors found the majority of doctors remained sceptical about the importance of hand hygiene on prevention of hospital infections, and blamed HI on contaminated surfaces. However, education techniques, like the glow lotion and ultraviolet hand scanner to demonstrate inadequate handwashing, were effective in changing the doctors' perceptions, highlighting the importance of education.

In China, Luo et al., (2010) indicated that training was found to influence compliance (odds ratio (OR: 2.17, CI 1.85–2.55). Moreover, a quantitative survey by Rabaan et al., (2017) in KSA

suggests that 51.73% of the respondents thought that lack of education on infection control is a contributor to compliance with infection control. Similar results have been also reported by Mazi et al., (2013) and Haridi et al., (2016) in KSA, Song et al., (2013) in USA, Wetzker et al., (2016) in Germany, and Offner et al., (2016) in France.

Performance feedback: Evidence from this review indicates that the presence of immediate feedback about the negative or positive behaviours regarding compliance with infection prevention and control practices has a positive influence on infection reduction. According to the study by Walker et al., (2014) on the benefits of feedback in a healthcare setting, immediate feedback instils a sense of responsibility among individuals. Therefore, it is vital for auditors to continue providing feedback to all the health professionals. The auditors need to be transparent in their evaluation, and this should be a reminder for all practitioners to continue adhering to good practices when dealing with patients.

Hale et al., (2015) concur with Walter et al., (2014) and add that continuous feedback is key to sustainable practices. Smiddy et al., (2015) express the same opinion by applauding the provision of timely feedback. However, Walker et al., (2014) argue that providing immediate feedback on noncompliance with these practices should never be taken as a punishment, but a teaching opportunity for all the healthcare workers. The provision of feedback should be done in a manner that allows them to discover the benefits of compliance and this will help develop a positive attitude or perception. On their part, Hagel et al., (2014), as used in Wetzker et al., (2016), observed that health professionals tend to develop the Hawthorne Effect in infection prevention and control, especially when they realise that they are under observation. Therefore, the best way to observe their compliance and provide feedback is to carry it out without their knowledge. In that way, it is possible to come up with non-biased and honest feedback regarding their performance and help them become more compliant (Allegranzi and Pittet, 2009).

2.7.1.3 Organisational Culture

In their study on infection prevention and control, Smiddy et al., (2015) recognise that the lack of compliance is a collective challenge that should be handled by everyone in the sector. As noted by Ward (2012), using nursing students as subjects, it was observed that most of the people had a negative perception toward infection prevention and control practices during clinical placement. They identified it as an extra workload that takes much of their time. Although subjects viewed it as an integral part of care, they observed that most clinical staff view it as a necessary inconvenience. The subjects indicated that infection prevention could not happen when there are other tasks to do and this was more common among doctors. While the organisation may provide necessary support, when not all health professionals are not supportive and work as a team, it is difficult to achieve the desired results. Similarly, Edet et al., (2017) studied the experiences and impressions of professional nurses on infection control practices. The authors employed a descriptive qualitative research design using focused groups and in-depth interviews of 54 subjects in total. They observed the perception of professionals towards these practices suggesting that compliance was hindered by negative attitude where infection control practices were not seen as part of the job for ward nurses.

In their study on the factors associated with adherence to standard infection control precautions such as how social and environmental circumstances shape their behaviour, Shah et al., (2015) found that one of the main factors that influenced respondents' behaviour was ambiguity about responsibility for certain IPC practices. Notably one of the negative attitudes was like: "I am a doctor, so IPC is not my job". On the other hand, Hale et al., (2015) tried to understand the implication, traditional roles IPC officers are assigned within the chains of their organisational culture, and influences on the effectiveness of such institutions. The traditional roles assigned to IPC officers by their organisations are a hindrance to effectiveness of their office. IPC officers are seen either as intermediaries or as educators. IPC teams perform surveillance or education as their primary functions and they often face resistance to implementation of new IPC policies, especially

when they conflicted with ingrained practices, senior medical staff members being the major resisters and their influence creating a barrier to progress.

Rabaan et al., (2017) argue that effective implementation of infection control and prevention practices in the health facilities depends on training, awareness and compliance. The authors note that poor prevention practices have led to increased infections in KSA. Therefore, the authors conducted a study to measure the awareness and attitude of health professionals towards infection prevention and control policies and guidelines. A total of 607 respondents across all levels were used in this study. The findings reveal a high level of uncertainty among health professionals regarding policy implantation. Carelessness of healthcare professionals was cited as the leading cause of infections with hospital facilities being the leading factor in the spread of infections.

In their quantitative cross-sectional study, Ayub et al., (2013) contend that there are multiple strategies that can promote positive perception in the reduction of infection and teamwork is the best of them. Offner et al., (2016) agree with Ayub et al., (2013) and note that the most effective strategy to deal with infections is the commitment of all the stakeholders in the healthcare sectors. Implicitly, individuals need to work collaboratively. The most sustainable and successful prevention of infection is when everyone works together to ensure a high level of compliance. Based on these studies, there is no doubt teamwork has a substantial role in lowering the high rates of infections.

Smiddy et al., (2015) recommend the establishment of multidisciplinary teams that could work to ensure sustainable infection prevention and control practices. It is imperative for the multidisciplinary teams in healthcare settings to remain committed and work towards the promotion of positive practices. Mazi et al., (2013) add that this multidisciplinary approach can enhance behavioural management and improve the perception of health professionals. This confirms that infection prevention and control is not an individual effort but a team effort.

2.7.2 Theme Two: Individual Factors Associated with Compliance with IPC

2.7.2.1 Knowledge

Good hygiene practices during patient care are arguably one of the vital infection prevention and control measures that lower infections in healthcare facilities. However, the role of knowledge in facilitating compliance with IPC practices is not well understood. Ng et al., (2017) conducted a study to examine infection prevention and control beliefs and knowledge of health professionals with the focus being on the United Arab Emirates, which has a similar setting to KSA. In this study, 109 subjects participated in the study. Among them were 13 doctors and 96 nurses. The authors found that there was no difference on hygiene scores between doctors and nurses and that the majority of doctors remained sceptical about the importance of hand hygiene on prevention of hospital infections, and blamed contaminated surfaces. The findings of this study suggest that education is needed for infection prevention and control practices. The study also suggests that dealing with the beliefs of doctors is key given the huge leadership role they play in healthcare organizations. The cultural and religious belief system in UAE is similar to KSA; thus, this study may offer insightful knowledge on how individual beliefs are likely to influence prevention and control practices.

In India, a mixed methods study recruiting 106 nursing personnel and assessing their knowledge using a structured questionnaire and practice by direct observation, Bai et al., (2015) indicate that knowledge did not translate to high practice. Specifically, although the majority (67.2%) of the nursing staff and (71.1%) nursing students had adequate knowledge, during observation stage of the research it was seen that hand washing steps were not followed by 27.3% of nursing staff and 25.5% of the nursing students. Along a similar line, in Australia, Herbert et al., (2013) in a quantitative study recruiting 192 medical students to investigate their IPC knowledge and practice, found that while the knowledge on hygiene guidelines was good (70% judged themselves as having excellent knowledge), adherence was limited (43 and 49% for hand washing and general hygiene guidelines respectively). In India, in a short study, Ayub et al., (2013)

sought to find out the role of education in compliance and implementation of these guidelines. The study used 160 randomly selected finalists in a medical school and 100 subjects from one of the medical schools in India. Only 31.25 percent of the subjects indicated that they followed guidelines on infection prevention and control. The authors concluded that empowering college students with skills and knowledge in infection control would lead to more compliance.

2.7.2.2 Job Title (Description) and Length of Service

According to the literature reviewed here, there are suggestions that compliance with standard practices of infection control vary between physicians and nurses, depending on the level of training and experience as Carvalho et al., (2016) indicate. Based on this study, physicians generally have higher education and training than the nurses. However, the freshly graduated physicians have demonstrated poor compliance with the standard practices, while highly experienced nurses prove high compliance than the freshly graduated physicians (Carvalho et al., 2016). In addition, in Egypt, Mortada and Zalat (2014) reported that the majoring of nurses demonstrated higher compliance than the male physicians. This finding suggests that the level of standard procedure training, thus, determines the level of compliance, as physicians and nurses typically demonstrate higher compliance with the use of gloves, masks, and goggles (Luo et al., 2010). Nurses, however, show an increased compliance to aprons, indicating that the level of experience and standard practices training determine the extent of compliance (Luo et al., 2010).

In exploring additional factors leading to these discrepancies, the authors argue that the quality and level of knowledge between the nurses and the physicians vary significantly. In most curricula, the physician education is detailed and comprehensive as compared to that of the nurses due to the career requirements (Carvalho et al., 2016). Therefore, in medical school, compliance with the standard practices of infection control are emphasized since physicians come into close contact with the infectious agents, and thus have an active role in preventing the spread (Luo et al., 2010). However, it has been noted that a significant level of non-compliance among the nurses

is attributable to non-compliance by the physician (Carvalho et al., 2016). Thus, in the clinical setting, the physicians act as role models to the nurses, and the level of compliance by the nurses entirely depends on that of the physicians. It could also be because of the gender differences, as there are generally more female nurses than male, and given that women tend to show a higher compliance to standard practices as compared to the men, this might explain some of these differences, in addition to the levels of experience and training of the physicians and nurses (Mortada and Zalat, 2014).

In KSA, Haridi et al., (2016) investigated professional and institutional factors associated with good compliance with standard IPC precautions guidelines among dentists and dental assistants. Compliance with SP was high, with the majority (90.1%) of dentists complying to standard procedures and type of profession i.e. being a dentist was one of the significant predictors of compliance (OR, 2.99; $p=0.035$). In Nigeria, Abdulraheem et al., (2012) conducted a quantitative, cross-sectional survey using a self-administered questionnaire recruiting 207 HCWs to investigate knowledge and practice in infection control. They reported that generally, the respondents had less knowledge of IPC with only 13% being knowledgeable on the subject. Longer experience affected practice. For example, among those with experience of ten years and above, compliance with the use of sterile gloves, disposal of needles and other sharp objects was higher ($p < 0.05$). Those with ≥ 10 years working experience had a high level of awareness of universal precautions than those with ≤ 5 years ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, Hosseinialhashemi, et al., (2015), in Iran, found that work experience and age were significant contributors to knowledge and attitudes and practice. Specifically, among people with the same experience levels, there was a positive linear correlation between total knowledge scores (correlation coefficient = 0.178, $p=.001$) and total attitude scores (correlation coefficient = 0.376, $p < .001$) with total practice scores.

2.7.2.3 Socio-demographic Factors

Socio-demographic factors may influence compliance and standard practices for infection control among healthcare workers, leading to different healthcare workers having different perceptions to these different levels of compliance. In KSA, being an Islamic country, culture-related barriers may be severe in there and may have a huge impact on infection prevention and control practises, hence the need to review this subject in-depth. The major cultural barriers identified in the study include gender, education, age, job title (description), nationality and the lack of a common language and culture of communication. The following sections will summarise findings from the included studies on these factors.

2.7.2.3.1 Gender, Age, Nationality and Race

In terms of compliance and standard practice of infection control, there are contradicting findings about gender variations. For example, men have been reported to show reduced compliance and practice than women (Osazuwa-Peters et al., 2012). Hand hygiene and the use of goggles have been shown to be highly preferable among the women (Mortada and Zalat, 2014). Men, on the other hand, find protective clothing favourable more than women, indicating that overall men and women, to a particular extent, tend to adhere differently to the standard practices of infection control. The level of compliance to handwashing based on gender has further been explored by Osazuwa-Peters et al., (2012), revealing that women demonstrated a higher adherence to handwashing as compared to the men even among the staff working in the critical care unit (Osazuwa-Peters et al., 2012). Furthermore, based on the use of goggles, a significant gender variability has been identified by Osazuwa-Peters et al., (2012) as more women than men were noted wearing the protective goggles.

According to a study carried out by Herbert et al., (2013), among male and female students in Austria there were no statistically significant differences between the male and the female students. Nevertheless, female students demonstrated a higher self-assessment concerning

knowledge of infection control in the healthcare setting as compared to the male (Herbert et al., 2013). They also had a higher self-assessment of compliance and practices of infection control than their male counterparts, while male students demonstrated a reduced compliance to hand hygiene during the observational study (Herbert et al., 2013). Thus, women may demonstrate a higher compliance to standard practices of infection control than men in a normal clinical setting based on Herbert et al., (2013).

In Nigeria, Osazuwa-Peters et al., (2012) evaluated surgeons' compliance with standard precautions and its associated factors using HBM. Female gender was associated with a higher compliance rate (54.9%), with perceived awareness, perceived severity, and perceived barriers to infection control. The presence of contradictory findings indicates that the perceptions of healthcare professional could remain the same in case they were of the opposite gender. The most essential aspect that determines their level of compliance is access to information regarding infection control.

Age is a significant determinant of the level of knowledge and experience on compliance and standard practices of infection control (Efstathiou et al., 2011). Physicians aged between 20 and 35 years have been identified as demonstrating a lower level of compliance with the personal protective wear, hand washing, and waste disposal of potentially infectious materials, with this age group showing negligence to standard practices (Amoran and Onwube, 2013). Moreover, the group has little experience in infection control and compliance with procedures while professionals aged above 35 years had more experience and knowledge in compliance with the standard practices. Their level of education is relatively higher, leading to increased compliance with protective wear, hand washing, and waste disposal (Efstathiou et al., 2011).

Elsewhere, HCWs between the age of 20 and 35 years have also been shown to demonstrate inadequate knowledge because of insufficient training, thus, showing a limited understanding of compliance to standard practices of infection control (Abdulraheem et al., 2012). Particularly, HCWs aged above 35 years old showed exceptional compliance to the standard

practices, probably due to their long years of experience in the clinical setting (Abdulraheem et al., 2012). Conversely, young members of staff have lacked knowledge, probably due to inadequate experience with issues of infections in the healthcare setting (Shah et al., 2015). The authors recommended training to improve knowledge of infection control in the healthcare setting. The rates of compliance improved with participation in regular training through conferences and seminars, which encouraged compliance with the standard practices of infection control while improving concordance with procedures and policies.

According to Efstathiou et al., (2011), Caucasians in the US have excellent compliance infection control practice, while the Hispanics and the African Americans display poor compliance and practice of standards for infection control. Such variations are attributable to the differences in socio-economic status and language barriers (Piai-Morais, et al., 2015). It is important to note that the quality of medical education varies as in the US, the quality of medical education is higher as compared to other countries (Piai-Morais et al., 2015). Health beliefs also differ among the nationalities, thereby affecting the compliance behaviour of the HCWs as Efstathiou et al., (2011) explain. For instance, a physician or nurse may show compliance with the standard practices depending on their perceived level of risk for acquiring a given infection. Moreover, the severity of the condition, in case it is transmitted will impact the adherence rate of the HCWs from different nationalities (Efstathiou et al., 2011). Thus, based on the Health Belief Model, HCWs will have different levels of risk perception, leading to different levels of adherence to standard practices in infection control as Efstathiou et al., (2011) suggest. However, this finding is not demonstrated elsewhere as in Haridi et al., (2016). In a self-administered questionnaire administered to 307 healthcare workers in a tertiary hospital in KSA, Haridi et al., (2016) reported that it is higher institutional commitment as regard IC requirements and type of profession (e.g. dentist) which were independent predictors of compliance to infection control ((odds ratio [OR], 4.34; $P < 0.001$), and OR, 2.99; $P = 0.035$ respectively), and not the nationality of the healthcare workers. This is probably because institutions who are committed to better infection control allocate more

resources and information, which might explain the better and positive outcomes. However, due to the paucity of evidence on this outcome, there is a need for more research to determine the exact role of nationality and ethnicity on infection control behaviour.

2.7.2.3.2 Self-efficacy: Individual Commitment to Compliance

The literature suggests that positive perception is a result of individual commitment towards infection prevention and control. In their study on hand hygiene as part of infection prevention in Iran, Hosseinialhashemi et al., (2015) observe that the lack of commitment is the largest contributor of infections in hospital settings. This clearly implies that in order to have a positive perception and promote effective infection prevention and control practices, there should be a collaborative commitment. Along a similar line, a study by Offner et al., (2016) conducted in France identified leadership commitment as the major factor determining the success or failure of infection prevention and control. The interviews conducted by Efstathiou et al., (2011) with nurses in Cyprus may clarify the reasons behind this perspective. The authors report that one of the reasons nurses indicated for non-compliance was self-efficacy, that is, difficulty to change behaviour when one is used to it. The nurses indicated that if they had done something for many years and were trained in doing it because it was thought to be better, it becomes difficult to change it after, even if, later they come to know it is not correct.

Song et al., (2013) in a retrospective cohort study concur that commitment is critical in infection prevention and control. In their study to improve hand hygiene as part of infection control, the authors observed that commitment improves tremendously efforts towards a reduced number of infections per hospital, and further lower the morbidity and mortality rates. The authors further mention that one of the most effective strategies for reduction of hospital infections is having an embedded culture of infection prevention and control such as hand hygiene. Therefore, Song and colleagues recommend that the World Health Organization should advocate for five moments of infection prevention for healthcare professionals, which include: before touching

patients, after touching patients, before a sterile procedure, after coming into contact with body fluid, and post-touching patients' environment. These five moments are key to infection prevention, but they cannot be actualised when the health professionals lack commitment or a positive perception. It is commitment that breeds positive perception.

2.8 CONTRIBUTION OF THE LITERATURE AND GAPS

Although this literature review presents several findings and conclusions, it can be narrowed down to two or three main findings and conclusions. First, the literature has provided insights into the many factors that are likely to affect HCWs compliance with infection prevention and control practices. These factors can be divided into organisational and societal factors, and individual and societal factors. The literature identifies insufficient organisational support, lack of supplies and equipment, policy and training, good surveillance system, individual efforts and lack of teamwork as factors that are likely to make health professionals fail to comply with infection control procedures.

The literature has identified the infection control models that have been shown to improve compliance with IPC such as automatic monitoring of hand hygiene. Regarding individual factors, although there is an agreement on the role of professional and length of service (Luo et al., 2010; Mortada and Zalat, 2014), the role of knowledge is still unclear (Ayub et al., 2013; Herbert et al., 2013; Ng et al., 2017). As for socio-cultural factors, similarly, whereas there is some evidence to consider age as a contributing factor in infection control (Efstathiou et al., 2011, Abdulraheem et al., 2012), there are contradictions in showing the role of gender and type of profession, with some studies suggesting that there is more compliance among physicians or dentists (Luo et al., 2010; Mortada and Zalat, 2014), whereas others found contradictory results (Carvalho et al., 2016).

Among others, the evidence from this review suggests that promotion of a positive perception towards infection prevention and control practices may result in individual commitment towards infection prevention and control (Ayub et al., 2013; Walker et al., 2014; Bai,

2015; Smiddy et al., 2015, Hosseinialhashemi, et al., 2015; Tan and Jeffery, 2015; Offner et al., 2016). The evidence from this review has also highlighted the need for a multidimensional approach that considers both individual and organizational factors such as establishing good policy, provision of enough supplies, setting up of automatic monitoring system, among others (Allegranzi and Pittet, 2009; Ward, 2012; Mazi et al., 2013; Smiddy et al., 2015; Wetzker et al., 2016; Rabaan et al., 2017).

The discussions and emergent themes raised in this chapter provide important points on the main influencing factor of infection prevention and control practices. These themes will be used to explore factors that might be influencing HCWs' compliance with infection prevention and control in KSA. It is important, however, to point out that there are a few issues that the literature does not address. First, most of the studies on perception of healthcare professionals, and how this influences compliance, are outside of KSA, the local context of this study. Due to the cultural differences between KSA and other countries internationally, having a conclusive remark based on these studies is substantially problematic. Second, most of the studies are on handwashing as one of the infection prevention and control practice while little has been done on other practices such as use of personal protective equipment that could also lower the number of infections. Third, the literature lacks evidence on the level of infection control policy and training in KSA, and how this influences HCWs' perceptions and compliance with IPC. These are significant research gaps that can be addressed in the current study. These gaps are used to design the conceptual model and methodology for this study. Therefore, the main research aim is to provide a comprehensive understanding of HCWs' perceptions of infection control practice in KSA, with a particular focus on the role of perceptions in influencing compliance with infection prevention and control practices in KSA. As previously mentioned in Chapter One, the three key research questions are:

1. What are healthcare workers' perceptions of infection prevention and control practices within the two research hospitals in KSA?

2. What institutional factors influence healthcare workers' compliance with infection prevention and control practices within the two hospitals in KSA?
3. How do the individual factors influence healthcare workers' compliance with infection prevention and control practices within the two hospitals in KSA?

The next section presents a summary of the chapter.

2.9 SUMMARY OF THE CHAPTER

The purpose of this review is to identify the factors associated with non-compliance with infection control procedures with the aim of finding a research gap to inform direction and research design for this study. Evidence to this effect was searched from MEDLINE (Ovid), CINAHL (EBSCOhost), Web of Science and other sources of grey literature. Thirty articles, out of the 8,192 studies from across the globe, were found relevant (of which 5 were review articles and 25 were primary studies) and included in the review. The themes covered included the effectiveness of multi-modal infection control programmes such as the WHO infection control programme, and effectiveness of organisational, individual and societal factors, such as knowledge and education, supplies, and training in influencing compliance.

The review included both quantitative and qualitative studies. Quantitative studies are likely to be marred by self-reporting bias, and therefore, are likely to be associated with over-rating. On the other hand, the external validity or reliability of qualitative evidence is doubtful as views expressed by respondents in an interview might be subjective only to that individual person and might not be generalised. In spite of these challenges, a number of factors were identified as being associated with non-compliance with infection control procedures including type of infection control programme model (i.e. multi-modal, or selective), organisational factors such as establishing good policy, provision of enough supplies, and setting up of automatic monitoring system, and finally, socio-demographic factors such as age and length of clinical experience. The gaps by the review identified included, firstly, having conflicting evidence on the role of

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knowledge training and socio-demographic factors, secondly, very few or no KSA based studies on the role of perceptions and training on infection control, thirdly, most studies being focused on handwashing, while, finally, there is few evidence on compliance with other important codes of conduct in infection control such as use of PPEs. These gaps helped lay the foundation for the design of this study.

CHAPTER THREE: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this chapter is to outline the conceptual framework which guides the study. To inform this research, several health behavior models and theories have been considered. Therefore, in this chapter, the main three models which may explain and predict health-related behaviors as well as inform health intervention designs will be examined: the Health Belief Model (HBM), (Hochbaum 1956; Becker, 1974; Champion and Skinner, 2008; Rosenstock, 1974), the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen, 1985), and the Systems Engineering Initiative for Patient Safety (SEIPS) Framework (Carayon et al., 2006/2015).

The chapter begins first with showing the gaps in the literature this study aims to address. Second, the main three models considered to guide the study will be explored. The strengths and limitations of each model will be detailed. A review of the WHO framework for the design of infection control programmes will be provided along with a rationale which justifies the use of the widely used healthcare human factors systems model, the SEIPS Framework (Carayon et al., 2006/2015) in particular when developing the conceptual model for this study.

3.2 FOCUS OF THE STUDY

Several factors are attributed to the spread of HAIs including non-adherence to code of practice such as hand washing or use of PPEs, proper disposal of waste, non-judicious prescription of antibiotics, dangerous use of injections and other medication devices, preparation and serving of unhygienic food and careless cohort of patients. The reasons behind such practices vary significantly by region or place and might include institutional factors such as unavailability or ineffective infection control policies (Ayub et al., 2013), inadequate infrastructure, facilities or supplies (Smiddy et al., 2015; Tan and Jeffrey, 2015), or inadequate personnel or funding

(Damani, 2007; Raka, 2009). In addition, the lack of proper training (Luo et al., 2010; Bai, 2015; Rabaan et al., 2017), performance feedback (Walter et al., 2014; Hale et al., 2015), and organisational culture (Ward, 2012; De Bono et al., 2014; Edet et al., 2017) are identified as other contributing factors which lead to the spread of HAIs.

Based on the literature, there are also some individual factors such as knowledge (Paudyal et al., 2008; Vaz et al., 2010; Chang et al., 2014), job description and length of service (Luo et al., 2010; Mortada and Zalat, 2014; Hosseinalhashemi et al., 2015) and gender, ethnicity, age and nationality (Osazuwa-Peters et al., 2012; Herbert et al., 2013; Mortada and Zalat, 2014). The contribution of these factors to hospital infection control has been sufficiently covered in previous works reviewed in the previous chapters in this study (Ward, 2012; De Bono et al., 2014; Hale et al. 2015; Hosseinalhashemi, et al., 2015; Edet et al., 2017; Ng et al., 2017).

However, most of the studies on the role of perceptions of health professionals regarding compliance with IPC are conducted in different contexts outside KSA. Primarily due to the cultural differences between KSA and other countries around the world, making a conclusive remark about the role of HCWs' perceptions of IPC in KSA and how these perceptions affect compliance with IPC based on these international studies is substantially problematic. Furthermore, most of the studies focus on handwashing as one example of IPC practices while other practices have not been sufficiently explored such as the use of PPEs which can reduce the risk of infections. Finally, the literature lacks evidence on the level of infection control policy and training in KSA and how these factors influence HCWs' perceptions and compliance with IPC. Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the perceptions of HCWs of IPC and how these perceptions among other factors influence compliance with recommended IPC practices within healthcare facilities in KSA.

To guide this research, three models which have been applied in various health domains were considered. The following sections investigate the HBM model, the TPB model, and the SEIPS model in detail. The reasons for using the SEIPS Framework as the conceptual framework for this study are also provided.

3.3 THE HEALTH BELIEF MODEL (HBM)

As indicated in Chapter One, the HBM was first developed in the 1950s by social psychologists Hochbaum, Rosenstock and Kegels working in the U.S. Public Health Services (Hochbaum 1956; Becker, 1974; Rosenstock, 1974; Champion and Skinner, 2008). According to Rosenstock (1974) and Orji et al., (2012), the HBM was developed as a systematic method to explore and explain the reasons for not undertaking preventive health measures as well as address problem behaviours that cause health concerns. Therefore, based on Rosenstock (1974), the main aim of the HBM is to improve public health through understanding why individuals do not take preventive measures to increase control over their own health.

The model suggests that individuals engage in a health behaviour, as for example, wearing gloves whilst drawing blood based on the satisfaction of several factors. Firstly, they must be knowledgeable about the disease or health issue in question and this knowledge affects their individual perceptions about their susceptibility to the disease such as HIV/AIDS. Secondly, several factors act as modifying factors to their likelihood of adopting a healthy behaviour. For example, they must perceive the health threat or disease to be severe enough to harm or kill them if they are negligent and end up having it. Some demographic and socio-cultural factors such as age, gender, ethnicity, personality, socio-economic status, and cues to action such as knowing somebody who caught the disease and died from it also act as modifying factors. Thirdly, the perceived benefits which will be gained by complying with the health behaviour contribute to the likelihood of them adopting the health behaviour.

An example of how the above-mentioned factors play out in HIV/AIDS education of HCWs is provided below in Table 3.1:

Table 3.1: Example of Health Belief Model in HIV/AIDS Control among HCWs (Adapted from University of Twente. Communication Studies Theories. Health Belief Model. Available at: https://www.utwente.nl/en/bms/communication-theories/sorted-by-cluster/Health%20Communication/Health_Belief_Model/).

Concept	Gloves Use Education Example
1. Perceived Susceptibility	HCWs believe they can get STIs or HIV.
2. Perceived Severity	HCWs believe that the consequences of getting STIs or HIV are significant enough to try to avoid.
3. Perceived Benefits	HCWs believe that the recommended action of using gloves would protect them from getting STIs.
4. Perceived Barriers	HCWs identify their personal barriers to using gloves (e.g. gloves limit their ability to handle needles) and explore ways to eliminate or reduce these barriers.
5. Cues to Action	HCWs receive reminder cues for action in the form of incentives (such as pencils with the printed message "no glove, no love") or reminder messages (such as messages in emails or posters in the hospital, or prizes to those complying with the health behaviour).
6. Self-Efficacy	HCWs confident in using gloves correctly in all circumstances.

Another example of the HBM model is shown below in Figure 3.1 which is adapted from Hochbaum (1956), Becker (1974) and Rosenstock (1974):

Figure 3.1: The Health Belief Model

Based on all of the above, the HBM is based on the understanding that a person will take a health-related action if that person:

- feels that a negative health condition such as HIV can be avoided,
- has a positive expectation that by taking a recommended action, he/she will avoid a negative health condition, as for example, wearing gloves will be effective at preventing HIV, and
- believes that he/she can successfully take a recommended health action, as for example, he/she can use gloves comfortably and with confidence.

According to Rosenstock (1974), culture is one of the major influences of individuals' attitudes and beliefs. Therefore, healthcare workers' perceived susceptibility to infections in a

hospital setting, and their subsequent actions on infection control may also be shaped by their religious and cultural inheritance.

The HBM can be used to understand observed behaviour and predict expected behaviours among people based on their classification of their perceived susceptibility, beliefs and cues to action. The Health Belief Model has been applied to a broad range of health behaviours and subject populations. For example, the HBM has been used in health promotion and encouraging preventive health behaviours including adherence to good diet, exercise, vaccination and contraceptive practices (Conner and Norman, 1996). In addition, the model has been used in avoiding health-risk behaviours such as smoking, understanding sick-role behaviours such as clinic use, physician visits, and compliance with recommended medical regimens following professional diagnosis of an illness (Conner and Norman, 1996).

The use of simplified health-related constructs is one of the strengths of the HBM which makes the model easy to implement and test (Orji et al., 2012). Although it is one of the most widely used theories in the design and evaluation of health behaviour interventions as Kretzer and Larson (1998) and Orji et al., (2012) point out, the HBM has several limitations which may affect its use to inform and predict a range of behaviours with health outcomes. Examples of these limitations include the low predictive capacity of existing HBM's variables, the small effect size of individual variables, and the lack of obvious rules of combination and relationship between the individual variables (Kretzer and Larson, 1998; Taylor et al., 2007; Orji et al., 2012). Based on Taylor et al., (2007), evidence suggests that in most areas of health-related behaviour, the HBM has only a weak predictive power. It is estimated that the HBM variables predict approximately 20% of the variance in healthy behaviour on average (Orji et al., 2012).

Not considering environmental and economic factors which may affect certain health behaviours and promote or prohibit the recommended actions are other examples of the limitations of the HBM. All of these limitations indicate that the model is incomplete and there are other significant variables which determine healthy behaviour that the HBM has not taken into account

as Kretzer and Larson (1998), Taylor et al., (2007) and Orji et al., (2012) indicate. To achieve the aims of this research and understand the facilitators and barriers to IPC in two healthcare facilities in KSA, it was vital to consider other models which can better explain the factors which affect compliance with IPC practices.

3.4 THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOUR (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Ajzen, 1985) is used to predict individuals' intentions to engage in a behaviour at a particular time and place. The TPB is used to understand motivational influences on behaviour (Ajzen, 1985; Conner and Armitage, 1998; O'Boyle et al., 2001; White et al., 2015). It focuses on the intention as a locus of control. The TPB argues that people's behaviour is shaped by three types of beliefs:

- Behavioural beliefs which refer to attitudes towards the behavior, as for example, whether a person is willing to perform the behavior, thinks it's a good thing to do and prefers to do it, if circumstances allow;
- Normative beliefs which refer to subjective norms such as an individual's perceptions about the particular behaviour, which is influenced by the judgment of significant others. For instance, normative beliefs include what we think others think is the right thing to do and the social pressure involved in engaging in a behaviour;
- Self-efficacy or perceived behaviour control which refer to whether we believe the behavior is simple or complex enough for us to be able to do it (Conner and Armitage, 1998, p. 1429).

Consequently, the manifestation of those factors may enhance or impede the enactment of the behaviour. In simpler terms, behaviour beliefs, normative belief and perceived behaviour

control, if all positive, may make the individual perform the behaviour as shown in Figure 3.2 below:

Figure 3.2: Theory of Planned Behavior. Adapted from Conner and Armitage (1998).

As shown in the figure above, the behaviour is the result of intention, while the intention is believed to be determined by three beliefs. First, behavioural beliefs which mean attitude towards the behaviour. The beliefs may be either positive or negative. Second, subjective norms or normative beliefs which refer to what we think others want to see us behave, the peer pressure, the organisational culture, how things are done here, what significant others like respected peers, or doctors, or senior people or any significant others think. Third, the intention is believed to be determined by the perceived behavioural control or self-efficacy.

The TPB suggests that these factors shape individuals' attitudes towards a specific behavior, the evaluation of the intended behaviour, and subsequent behavioural outcome (Ajzen and Madden, 1986, p. 460). The theory argues that the more favourable attitude towards a certain behaviour, it is accepted socially, and the individual has more control over that specific behaviour, the more likely they are to perform that behaviour (Conner and Armitage 1998, p.1431). For example, a nurse can think that wearing gloves before cleaning up a soiled patient and changing their beddings is a good thing and will prevent infection. However, it might be that in this hospital

and ward, and in this society, touching a patient with bare hands is perceived as a sign of compassion and love. In addition, the patient is seen as a fellow human, not to be segregated, but rather is shown compassion, love and acceptance. This social pressure may lend the nurse to not use gloves because of the need to comply with the social norm or expected behaviour.

Social norms are very influential shapers of behaviour as those who do not follow them are labelled as deviant, different, naïve, not good people, arrogant, or not belonging to the group. Thus, subjective norms are the normative beliefs which are considered normal or average in an organisation. As for perceived behavioural control, this refers to the amount of control which an individual perceives to have over the environment, situation, or resources, for example, and that they can act even if this is not considered normal by their environment and get away with it (Conner and Armitage, 1998, p.1431).

The theory of planned behaviour is used by several organisations to predict how people will react to changes in their environment, and to explain what their attitudes, intentions and behavioural relations would be (O'Boyle et al., 2001). The theory has also been effective in predicting health-related behaviour like quitting smoking and performing exercises. It has been used to develop an explanatory model to understand compliance with hand hygiene procedures such as in O'Boyle et al., (2001) and White et al., (2015). Through this model, researchers have been able to predict how people will react to these issues or change their lifestyles, which may also help in finding ways to improve health. This knowledge can subsequently be used for educating the individuals to achieve the desired behaviour (Conner and Armitage, 1998, p.1431).

Nevertheless, there are some limitations of the TPB which affect the usefulness of this theory to explain human behaviour and develop helpful interventions (Taylor et al., 2007; Sniehotta et al., 2014). For example, Sniehotta et al., (2014) indicate that the theory has been criticised for its limited focus on rational reasoning, while unconscious influences on behaviour are excluded. In addition, the role of emotions beyond anticipated affective outcomes and the static explanatory nature of the theory which does not facilitate understanding the evidenced effects of

behaviour on cognitions and future behaviour are among the limitations of the TPB (Sniehotta et al., 2014). In O'Boyle et al.,'s (2001) study, the authors indicate that the variables, which include intention to practice hand hygiene, did not predict actual adherence to hand hygiene. Furthermore, White et al., (2015) suggest that the use of topics which were predetermined by the TPB framework may have resulted in limiting the scope of their study.

The two major concerns which Sniehotta et al., (2014) highlight are about the validity and utility of the TPB because some of the theory's propositions are patently false. Moreover, the TPB is not suitable as a theory of behaviour change because it does not theorise how cognitions change (Sniehotta et al., 2014). Even though the TPB has contributed to the development of knowledge, Sniehotta et al., (2014) argue that the theory does not provide explanatory hypotheses which meaningfully differ from other theories and does not accurately communicate accumulated empirical evidence. Taylor et al., (2007) indicate having no evidence in relation to improving or reducing health outcomes in the UK through using TPB informed interventions as the primary concern of TPB based studies has been predicting and understanding intentions and behaviours.

Because of the limitations of the HBM and TPB, there was a need to consider another model to develop the conceptual framework of this study while considering the behavioural and systematic components of infection control practices. It was important that the model used should involve most of the core components of the WHO (2011) framework for IPC which has been developed to prevent healthcare-associated infections and prepare for and respond to communicable diseases crises in line with the recommendations of local studies conducted in KSA such as Mazi et al., (2013) and international ones including primarily Allegranzi and Pittet (2009). In the following sections, the WHO (2011) framework for IPC which helps plan, organise and implement an IPC programme and the SEIPS framework are examined in detail. A rationale for using the SEIPS framework which is one of the most widely used healthcare human factors systems models (Holden, et al., 2013) is provided.

3.5 THE WORLD HEALTH ORGANISATION FRAMEWORK FOR IPC

The WHO (2011) recommends a multi-modal model for IPC. As WHO (2011) suggests, the IPC programme should have eight core components shown below in Figure 3.3:

Figure 3.3: WHO Essential Components of IPC Programmes

The WHO infection control strategy emphasises that every healthcare facility should have a person or team to ensure that infection control procedures are implemented when handling patients. Furthermore, in every country, there should be appointed trained professionals in charge of infection control at the local and national levels, comprising healthcare professionals, qualified nurses and other personnel responsible for implementing IPC activities at any level within a healthcare system. These professionals should display an increased level of knowledge and skills

in connection with the general IPC principles, surveillance of diseases and outbreak management and monitoring of clinical practices (WHO, 2008).

Other workers who should be included in the infection control structure include dentists, medical assistants, laboratory workers and housekeeping employees who provide patient care at any level, and managerial members of staff should not be excluded either. These teams and professionals should further collaborate with public health departments and create links between local and provincial public health which provide help with any information that is useful in controlling infectious diseases (WHO, 2008). Furthermore, WHO emphasises that healthcare facilities formulate and implement infection control guidelines and put up measures for early detection of infections and isolation precautions. However, the scope of practice might be different in healthcare facilities depending on the type of care offered. It advocates that priority should be given to the most frequent or risky practices such as surgical processes and use of indwelling catheters based on regulations that ensure a uniform implementation of welfare strategies to prevent HAIs.

The performance of comprehensive IPC practices has been reviewed previously in Chapter Two. It was indicated, for example, among the findings, a review by Allegranzi and Pittet (2009) describes the effectiveness of the WHO infection control model and other models which incorporate interventions such as training and education on hand washing and hand hygiene observation, alcohol-based hand rub, chlorhexidine soap, hand hygiene electronic monitoring, performance feedback and posters. The authors concluded that the implementation of a comprehensive, multi-modal hand hygiene programme with education on hand washing, hand hygiene observation, hand hygiene electronic monitoring, performance feedback, alcohol-based hand rub and posters were associated with increased compliance with hand hygiene practices.

As another example, in their study, Mazi et al., (2013) suggest that the WHO strategy in combination with hygiene education as well as continuous evaluation and team approach can increase compliance in healthcare facilities in KSA. Therefore, the choice of the SEIPS

Framework (Carayon et al., 2006) as a conceptual model for this study was considered more appropriate particularly that this model involves most of the core components of IPC identified by the WHO and would, therefore, help develop an optimal research design for this study.

3.6 THE SEIPS FRAMEWORK

The SEIPS model is one of the leading conceptual frameworks in human factors engineering research (Holden et al., 2013; Carayon et al., 2015). As Carayon et al., (2006) argue, the SEIPS model can be used to help address the systemic problems of patient safety. The model examines issues through the lens of complex interactions between people and systems. The model includes organisations, technology and tools, the environment, tasks and people. According to Carayon et al., (2015), the SEIPS model is an improvement of earlier patient safety frameworks. It incorporates both the causes and control of medical errors.

The proposed health safety model by Carayon et al., (2015) has two components, “the Work System” and “the Process”. In the work system model, a person, as for example, a HCW who could be a nurse, doctor, dentist or other employee of a healthcare institution such as a laboratory scientist, biomedical engineer or the patient, performs a range of tasks using various tools and technologies. The performance of these tasks occurs within a certain physical environment and under specific organisational conditions. The five components of the work system are, therefore, the person, tasks, tools and technologies, physical environment and organisational conditions which interact with each other and influence each other. Examples of the elements of the various SEIPS model components are shown below in Table 3.2:

Table 3.2: Components of the SEIPS Model. Adapted from Carayon et al., (2015).

	Component	Elements (Examples)
Work system or structure	Person	Education, skills, knowledge, motivation and needs, physical characteristics, psychological characteristics
	Organisation support	Organisational culture or potential safety culture; teamwork, coordination, collaboration and communication, work schedules, social relationships, supervisory and management styles, performance evaluation, rewards and incentives; Supplies and materials e.g. gloves, face masks, aprons, alcohol-based hand rub, disposable aprons, gowns or coats
	Technologies and tools	Electronic hand wash monitoring system, automatic soap dispensers, hand wash sinks, alcohol-based hand rub, electronic health records, computerised order entry and bar coding, human factor of technologies
	Tasks	Work schedule and length of working hours, job demands (e.g. workload, time pressure, cognitive load, need for attention, number of tasks assigned, job content, challenge and utilisation of skills, autonomy, job control and participation)
	Environment	Layout, noise, lighting, temperature, humidity and air quality, work situation design, proximity of bins and hand wash material, proximity of storage place for gloves, aprons, masks etc., proximity of sinks and other hand washing facilities, layout of wards and mixture of types of patients in wards
Process	Core processes and other processes	Surveillance, performance feedback, audits, reward and punishment, purchasing and stock piling system
Outcomes	Process outcomes	Compliance with hand hygiene, wearing gloves, wearing masks, wearing aprons, proper waste disposal, good nursing practices (e.g. not recapping needles).

As shown above, *personal factors* include workload, education, knowledge, skills, motivational needs and psychological characteristics which might be influenced by the country of

origin. **Organisational needs** include institutional support, as for example, IPC policy, leadership, training, motivation in terms of incentives and punishments, performance feedback, teamwork, coordination, communication, organisational culture, work schedule and social relationships. Examples of **technological tools** include electronic hand wash monitoring systems, automatic soap dispensers, medical devices and personal ability to use these technologies. As for **tasks**, they include various job tasks for different professions such as nursing duties or physician duties. **The environment** includes the layout of physical infection control facilities such as hand wash dispensers, garbage bins, wards etc. The interactions between the various components “produce” different outcomes, including patient-oriented outcomes such as getting a nosocomial infection or not and organisational outcomes such as increase or decrease in HAIs.

The SEIPS model can be used to understand the behavioural and systematic components of infection control practices. Although providing no specific guidance as to the critical elements is one of the limitations of the SEIPS model (Carayon et al., 2006), it has been utilised as the guiding framework for patient safety analyses in over 50 studies, ranging from primary care clinics to ICUs (Holden et al., 2013). For instance, the SEIPS model has previously been used to identify barriers and facilitators for infection prevention practices for clostridium difficile infection (Yanke et al., 2015), ventilator-associated pneumonia (Safdar et al., 2016), and HAIs in the ICU (Caya et al., 2015).

Reviewing the literature indicates that organisational support in providing supplies and equipment, training, performance feedback, and technology is crucial for IPC compliance (Efstathiou et al., 2011; Amoran et al., 2013; Tan and Jeffrey, 2015; Smiddy et al., 2015; Piai-Morais et al., 2015; Quan et al., 2015). Therefore, the systems which organisations will adopt and the tasks assigned to different individuals as suggested by the SEIPS Framework (Carayon et al., 2006) will be also dictated by the environment, knowledge and attitudes of the HCWs, their perceptions regarding their susceptibility to infections, the severity of the possible infection, demographic and other sociocultural factors such as age, gender, type of profession (nurse, or

physician, or allied health professional) and work experience as perceived barriers to action. For all of the above mentioned reasons, the SEIPS model was chosen as the basis for designing the conceptual model of this study particularly that the WHO (2011) framework for infection control programmes is considered an example of good infection control programmes and the SEIPS model involves most, if not all, the aspects of the core components of the WHO framework.

As shown below in Figure 3.4, in this study, the SEIPS model was used to identify organisational factors such as the availability of infection control policy and team, organisation commitment to infection control by provision of supplies and training, setting up of monitoring and evaluation programmes. In addition, the model is used to show technological factors such as provision of automatic hand washing monitoring systems, and provision of utilities as automatic soap dispensers. The SEIPS model will also help identify tasks such as workload, and finally, environment such as the availability of and distance to soap dispensers, garbage bins, and patient cohort in wards:

Figure 3.4: Conceptual model for this study. Notes: The SEIPS model is adopted from (Barker et al., 2017).

3.7 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER THREE

In this chapter, three health models were examined to guide the study outlining the strengths and limitations of each model. Although the HBM and the TPB are widely used models, the SEIPS model which is considered an improvement of earlier patient safety frameworks and incorporates both the causes and control of medical errors was chosen as a conceptual framework guiding this study. The primary reasons for this choice are because the SEIPS model involves the eight core components of the WHO framework for the design of infection control programmes which has been developed to prevent healthcare-associated infections and prepare for and respond to communicable diseases crises. In addition, the SEIPS model can be used to understand the behavioural and systematic components of infection control practices unlike the HBM and the TPB models which provide limited explanations of human behaviour.

CHAPTER FOUR: METHODOLOGY

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter discusses the research philosophy and methods adopted in the research. A pragmatic approach employing both the positivist and realist approaches was implemented. Following this, the study adopted the mixed methods approach to understand the perceptions of healthcare workers' (HCWs) of infection prevention and control and how HCWs' perceptions and other individual and institutional factors influence compliance with infection control practices at two hospitals in the Qassim region in KSA. In addition, the chapter discusses the data collection methods used to investigate the role of perceptions and other factors in infection control. The chapter provides rationales for using a quantitative survey, a semi-structured interview and a non-participant observation. The main aim is to understand individual and institutional factors associated with compliance with recommended infection control practices based on participants' points of view. The incorporation of the aforementioned methods aims also at understanding the reasons for carrying out the observed IPC practices and participants' perceptions of IPC practices. A detailed explanation of the data analysis procedures will follow. Finally, the research reliability, validity, and ethical considerations will be explained.

4.2 RESEARCH PARADIGM

Based on Punch (2016), there are implicit philosophical assumptions/paradigms which underpin and affect the choice of research methods. Therefore, understanding the philosophical underpinnings is the first and most crucial step in any researcher's journey because it would help in identifying the research methodology, design and methods. Guba and Lincoln (1994, p. 105) define a paradigm as "the basic belief system or worldview that guides the investigator, not only in the choices of methods but in ontologically and epistemologically fundamental ways." Before identifying the research philosophical worldviews and how they influence this research, it would

be worthwhile to reflect on ontology and epistemology which are considered important to discuss before considering the philosophical worldviews that inform any research (Punch, 2016). According to Crotty (1998), ontology is the study of being and it refers to the assumptions we make about what constitutes reality. On the other hand, epistemology is concerned with the nature and forms of knowledge acquired only through the investigation of a phenomenon. It refers to the assumptions of how knowledge can be created, acquired and communicated (Cohen et al., 2007, p. 7). Guba and Lincoln (1994, p. 108) explain that epistemology asks the following question: what is the nature of the relationship between the would-be knower and what can be known? As all assumptions are conjecture, the philosophical underpinnings of each paradigm can never be empirically proven or disproven. Methodology refers to the strategy or plan of action which lies behind the choice and use of particular methods (Crotty, 1998, p. 3). Therefore, methodology is concerned with why, what, from where, when and how data is collected and analysed. Guba and Lincoln (1994, p. 108) explain that methodology asks the following question: how can the inquirer go about finding out whatever they believe can be known? As for methods, they are the specific techniques and procedures used to collect and analyse data (Crotty, 1998, p. 3).

There are many general paradigms such as positivism, interpretivism and pragmatism. The scientific paradigm, positivism, rose to prominence during the Enlightenment era (Crotty, 1998, p. 19). For positivists, the social world is independent from the researcher's own involvement, and therefore, unaffected by the researcher. The positivist point of view fits the use of quantitative methods of deduction to measure relationships of cause and effect. Therefore, positivism is mostly associated with quantitative methods (Niglas, 2010). Some elements of positivism underpin this research through the implementation of quantitative methods.

The positivist epistemology is one of objectivism; that is, meaning solely resides in objects and not in the conscience of the researcher (Crotty 1998; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). The ontological position of positivism is one of realism. Realism is the view that objects have an existence independent of the knower (Cohen et al., 2007, p. 7). Denzin and Lincoln (2018) indicate

that positivists rely on surveys, and experimental, and quasi-experimental methodologies. In positivism, one version of reality exists (Rubin and Rubin, 2005). Positivists go forth into the world impartially, discovering absolute knowledge about an objective reality and use quantitative methods to collect analyse and interpret data. The researcher and the researched are independent entities. The researcher aims to obtain this meaning. Therefore, a discoverable reality exists independently of the researcher (Pring, 2000, p. 59). Most positivists assume that reality is not mediated by our senses. Language fulfils a representational role as it is connected to the world by some designative function; consequently, words owe their meaning to the objects which they name or designate (Frowe, 2001, p. 176).

Surveying the literature shows that the term 'positivism' suggests some negative connotations (Biesta, 2010). There have been also several criticisms of positivism such as criticising its reductionist and mechanistic view of nature which rejects the ideas of individuality, choice and freedom (Hammersley, 2012; Cohen et al., 2015). Other criticisms of positivism which Hammersley (2012) and Cohen et al., (2015) point out include ignoring the role of researchers, failing to provide reliable knowledge, encouraging control and passivity of human behaviour as well as dehumanising people through presenting them using numbers.

On the other hand, the interpretivist paradigm holds that truth is subjective and it rejects the natural science approach to social research (Bryman, 2012). In other words, interpretive epistemology is one of subjectivism or relativism, that is, reality is subjective and differs from person to person (Guba and Lincoln, 1994, p. 110). In interpretivism, qualitative methods are mostly used to conduct research to understand the subjective nature of reality which is based on people's personal viewpoints and behaviour (Punch, 2009). Moreover, rather than narrowing knowledge into a few ideas, interpretivists explore varied complex views (Creswell, 2014). However, like positivism, interpretivism has received some criticisms because of its several limitations. According to Hammersley (2012), interpretivism does not provide generalisable conclusions as it relies on researching a small number of people or cases. In addition, proving that

certain factors produce certain outcomes is not possible in interpretivism. It is possible that the findings of interpretive research are inconstant, biased or inaccurate. Therefore, doubts may be raised regarding the validity of its interpretations (Hammersley, 2012; Cohen et al., 2015). Emphasising cultural factors to understand reality in interpretivist research has been also criticised (Hammersley, 2012).

The third paradigm is the pragmatic which uses both the positivist and interpretivist approaches in parallel or sequentially (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017). Pragmatists argue that knowledge is acquired through both action and reflection (Biesta, 2010). For pragmatists, knowledge is about relationships between actions and consequences. Greene and Hall (2010) provide a summary of some characteristics of pragmatism drawn from the writings of pragmatist thinkers as Charles Sanders Peirce, William James and John Dewey and mixed methods literature. For instance, the characteristics of pragmatism include rejecting dualism, focusing on action, problem-solving, supporting the values of democracy, freedom, equality, and progress. Table 4.1 below summarises the three main research paradigms considered in this study and discussed above:

Table 4.1: The Epistemological and Ontological Views Guiding this Research

Paradigm	Pragmatic	Positivist	Interpretivist
Methods	Quantitative and Qualitative	Quantitative	Qualitative
Logic	Deductive and Inductive	Deductive	Inductive
Epistemology	Modified dualism; Findings probably objectively “True”	Objectivism, i.e. that meaning solely resides in objects, not in the conscience of the researcher	Subjectivism i.e. reality is subjective and explores the extent to which it is affected by the culture, place and environment of the researcher
Ontology	Accepts external reality and chooses explanations that closely resemble reality	Naïve realism	Relativism

Different paradigms inherently contain different ontological and epistemological views. Therefore, they have different assumptions of reality and knowledge which underpin their particular research approach, which is reflected in their methodology and methods. Every research is based upon its own ontological and epistemological assumptions. Researchers need to assume a position regarding their perceptions of how things really are and how things really work. The choice of the best method employed in collecting and analysing or interpreting depends on the research question to be answered (Halcomb and Hickman, 2015). Based on the selected approach, data collection is accomplished; data analysis follows with the aim of drawing conclusions from one set of data or providing comparisons between the sets of data. Nonetheless, the process used is informed by the research method selected.

To achieve the aim of this research which intended to understand HCWs' perceptions of IPC practices and the role which these perceptions and other factors play in affecting compliance with IPC practices in KSA, the philosophical stances of pragmatism were used. To best address the research questions, this study started with an initial quantitative survey which is grounded in a positivist epistemology to explore the level of implementation of recommended IPC practices and the factors which might influence compliance with IPC procedures in two tertiary hospitals in the Qassim region of KSA.

The study then incorporated some elements of the interpretive paradigm through using qualitative interviews and observations to understand the context of the data obtained from the quantitative survey and to extract further data on the nature of reality. The choice of the qualitative methods was considered appropriate to understand the perceptions of HCWs of IPC and how these perceptions among other socio-demographic and institutional factors influence compliance with IPC standard procedures in KSA. The findings from quantitative and qualitative data collected in this mixed methods research design were integrated to provide a better understanding of the research problem. This way of combining both paradigms was described by Creswell and Plano Clark (2017) and Tashakkori and Creswell (2007) as a useful paradigm which draws on the benefits of both positivist and interpretivist approaches.

The next section discusses the characteristics of mixed methods approach and provides reasons for employing this approach to conduct this study.

4.3 METHODOLOGY

Methodology refers to the strategy or plan of action which lies behind the choice and use of particular methods (Crotty, 1998. p. 3). Therefore, methodology is concerned with why, what, from where, when and how data is collected and analysed. Guba and Lincoln (1994, p. 108) explain that methodology asks the following question: how can the inquirer go about finding out whatever they believe can be known? This research employed the mixed methods approach

(pragmatism) in which the combined ideologies of quantitative as well as qualitative research methods were incorporated (Feilzer, 2010).

Mixed method research is one of the three primary paradigms of research which include qualitative and quantitative paradigms. For carrying out an effective research on a problem, researchers ought to apply these research methods to build persuasive arguments and support to the findings. If neither qualitative nor quantitative approaches can provide answers, a better understanding of the research problem or evidence about a hypothesis, mixed research techniques are used (Riazi and Candlin, 2014, p. 142). In such a situation, the two research methods are used together where one method relies on the other in various ways to better understand the research problem or get the final research facts (Fusch and Ness, 2015, p. 1410).

Since the aim of this research was to provide a better understanding of infection control practices in KSA, with a particular focus on the factors which influence the level of implementation of infection control, the mixed methods approach was the most suitable choice to facilitate investigating the factors associated with compliance with recommended IPC practices. Tashakkori and Creswell (2007) and Creswell and Plano Clark (2017) describe the mixed methods approach, which draws on the benefits of both positivistic and interpretivist approaches as the most beneficial when there are complex research questions, where the truth lies not only in empirical evidence and embedded in numbers, but also from a deep understanding of the participants feelings, motivations, enabling factors, and challenges.

4.3.1 Mixed Methods Research

4.3.1.1 The Philosophy of Mixed Methods

Pragmatism is the underlying philosophical framework for mixed methods research. Pragmatism employs positivist and interpretive approaches either together in parallel or in a sequence (Venkatesh et al., 2013). The pragmatist paradigm, unlike other philosophical viewpoints, is not committed to one reality. There is a belief in the potential to have multiple

perspectives regarding a research problem, and qualitative and quantitative methods can be combined in a single study (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003; Somekh and Lewin, 2005; Creswell, 2009).

4.3.1.2 History of Mixed Methods

A prevalent view is that the history of mixed methods research began with the work of Campbell and Fiske (1959) on triangulation with a complete development of actual mixed method studies in the 1980s (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011). This period saw the initial interest in using more than one method in a study. Many researchers from different disciplines began writing their research beyond simply using qualitative and quantitative methods as distinct, separate strands in a study (Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2003). However, some researchers argue that the use of mixed methods predates the emergence of “mixed methods research” as a distinct and self-conscious strategy in the 1950s (Maxwell, 2016). The author argues that terms such as survey had a very different meaning in the early part of the 20th century from what they later acquired; ‘participant observation’ was done in the 1920s but was not then called that nor was it considered clearly distinct from modes of data collection now regarded as quite different (Platt, 1996, p. 44).

As will be detailed below, quantitative and qualitative approaches are employed for different purposes. Each approach has its own strengths and limitations. The reason researchers started combining both quantitative and qualitative research designs stems from the realisation of the limitations of the positivist paradigm, that is, there is no single truth to reality. It was, therefore, realised that relying on quantitative surveys to understand the complexity of human behaviour would be wrong because behaviour also involves subjective opinions. In addition, although positivism attempts to reduce the complex to the simple by simplifying and controlling variables, it is extremely difficult to study some variables which might be hidden from the researcher and only become known when participants are interviewed and the reasons, for example, for their behaviour or choices, values, and attitudes are known.

Based on Creswell and Plano Clark (2011) and Cohen et al., (2015), advocates of mixed methods approach argue that combining quantitative and qualitative approaches in one research can help overcome the weaknesses of each approach, offer the best way to understand the research problem and address the research questions. Despite its complexity, the various promising advantages of mixed methods approach encouraged the choice of this methodology to conduct this research which aims to collect subject and objective data to provide a comprehensive understanding of HCWs' perceptions of infection control and the role of HCWs' perceptions and other individual and institutional factors in influencing compliance with recommended infection control procedures in KSA.

4.3.1.3 Quantitative Research: Strengths and Limitations

Quantitative research is a study technique that scientifically and quantitatively examines theories by using measurements, stating the causes and making inferences (Guba and Lincoln, 1982; Greene and Hall, 2010; Creswell, 2014). Theoretically, quantitative research provides the researcher with the opportunity to test the causal effect relationships. Researchers use quantitative methods to investigate research findings by testing scientific theories and hypotheses. For instance, quantitative methods can be applied in the field of social sciences with the intention of collecting data that measures the frequency of behaviours (e.g. compliance with hand washing) and their relationship with outcomes (e.g. number of hospital infections). Researchers who opt to use the quantitative paradigm retain impartiality. Therefore, they can easily manage and prevent bias because this paradigm relies on the collection and analysis of existing knowledge (Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

This research paradigm supports empirical thinking by operating from an extensive theory all the way down to conclusive results that either affirm or contradict the hypothesis or estimated value. In its design, the quantitative paradigm employs the use of an organised format starting with a theory which helps deduce a hypothesis or predict the outcome. The procedure of testing the

hypothesis involves the identification of the parameter to be tested, the tools and instruments used to collect data and the means of conducting the research. Researchers can subsequently conduct the study through experimentation or a research survey using an experimental design to test the result of a 'treatment' on the population under research. Under the experimental method, a series of trials are conducted in a random and controlled manner, and the result of the test is measured on two distinct groups where one is allocated as the control group and the other as the study group. The best practice is where the methodology is 'blinded', which means, the participants are placed randomly into each group. The study's implementation can also be double-blinded such that the researchers cannot distinguish the control group from the study group. The hypotheses may be proved by the test and therefore corroborated, or they may be refined or rejected (Punch and Oancea, 2014).

In conducting a survey, a questionnaire can be used to collect information or data that pertains to a group of people or a study population. A questionnaire comprises a set of close-ended questions which are meant to test the hypothesis or research question against a given estimate (Creswell, 2014). Structured interviews and structured observations as well as content analysis are other examples of data collection methods which are usually associated with quantitative approach (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Bryman, 2012).

This research is concerned with investigating the role of HCWs' perceptions and other individual and institutional factors in affecting compliance with infection control procedures in KSA. The quantitative paradigm was employed in this research to measure differences in perceptions according to some factors identified from reviewing the literature. Based on the literature review presented in Chapter Two, institutional factors such as organisational support in provision of supplies and equipment, formulation and implementation of policy and training, good surveillance system, performance feedback, organisational culture such as existence of supportive or blame culture, teamwork and other organisational social behaviours have been identified as

factors that are likely to make healthcare professionals fail or be successful in achieving compliance with recommended infection control procedures.

The literature also identifies certain individual and socio-demographic factors such as knowledge, age and length of service or work experience, gender and type of profession that influence compliance with IPC practices. Organisational culture (OC) is defined as the assumptions, values, and norms shared among colleagues (Borg, 2013). These beliefs can influence an individual's thinking and behaviour either positively or negatively and are crucial for the success of an organisation. According to the HBM model (Hochbaum, 1956; Becker, 1974; 2008; Rosenstock, 1974), people's beliefs are a function of their culture.

The KSA culture is defined by Islamic heritage. The traditions of the country are deeply rooted in the Islamic teachings and the customs of the Arabs learned at an early age from families and in schools. The religious and cultural heritage of Islam in KSA is expressed in social interactions between men and women, the Arabic language and in the customs and practices of the Arabic people. The Islamic culture and the Arabic ethnicity attribute different meanings for men and women. It was therefore presumed that gender might be one of the primary social factors influencing infection control practices in KSA.

As a summary, in this research, the survey administered aimed to test the role of HCWs' perceptions regarding the standards of infection control practices in KSA. The data collected was used to identify differences in HCWs' perceptions based on their profession, gender, age, academic qualifications, country of origin, and hospital setting. The eight research hypotheses tested in the quantitative phase are summarised below in Figure 4.1:

Figure 4.1: Research Hypotheses

One of the advantages of quantitative research is its consistent approach in a methodical process developing from theory to setting of hypotheses to data collection and analysis and to a conclusion, which either upholds or refutes the hypothesis. The process is designed in such a manner that it can be replicated and eventually generalised to a population that reflects the sample. This type of study can support research involving large populations by employing the use of statistical analysis. Theoretically, it provides the researcher some room for independence, despite being limited by the supposition that context-specific qualities cannot be accommodated in the research findings. The significance of this is that overviews of larger populations do not always relate to all situations (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004).

In this research, although the quantitative evidence gathered intended to be generalised to the population reflecting the sample in KSA, there are some limitations of quantitative research

which the researcher needs to acknowledge. For example, according to Bryman (2012), quantitative research disregards the differences between the social and the natural world, ignores participants' context and personal voice, and excludes discovery. Quantitative researchers rely on theories which may not reflect participants' understandings. Moreover, the abstract findings of quantitative research may not be applicable to specific contexts. Finally, Bryman (2012) indicates that the validity of the findings of quantitative research may be dubious because they do not show how the findings relate to everyday contexts. Therefore, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches in this research in a mixed methods design may be considered a real strength to address the limitations of each type of research.

4.3.1.4 Qualitative Research: Strengths and Limitations

Providing a simple definition of qualitative research is a challenge because of the underpinning philosophical, disciplinary, and historical influences (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). Therefore, because of its complexity, Denzin and Lincoln (2018, p. 10) indicate that qualitative research “means different things in each of these moments.” Denzin and Lincoln (2018) define qualitative research in general as follows:

Qualitative research is a situated activity that locates the observer in the world. Qualitative research consists of a set of interpretive, material practices that make the world visible. These practices transform the world. They turn the world into a series of representations, including fieldnotes, interviews, conversations, photographs, recordings, and memos to the self. At this level, qualitative research involves an interpretive, naturalistic approach to the world. This means that qualitative researchers study things in their natural settings, attempting to make sense of, or interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018, p. 10).

Qualitative research makes interpretations by conclusively exploring the participants' experiences and how they understand their social world (Bryman, 2012). This research paradigm, which is based on context-specific impacts, is thoughtful and receptive to the participants' opinion of reality (Gelling, 2015). It is applied where a smaller number of cases are explored. Contrary to

quantitative research, qualitative research is free of the limitations such as of limiting variables or testing theory. Consequently, it generates theory depending on the type of the research method used. Facilitating an in-depth exploration of a topic is one of the primary strengths of qualitative research (Cleary et al., 2014). In this approach, researchers gather data through their interactions with the participants in the form of open-ended questions exploring concepts. Conclusions are derived from an iterative process which can be driven by either data or participants, and finally by drawing implications from the data (Gelling, 2015).

Qualitative data may be collected through interviews, but it can involve fieldwork and direct observations, requiring the researcher to showcase rigor and the ability to establish trustworthiness. The benchmark used to test for rigor involves ascertaining credibility, reliability, transferability and confirmability (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). Data collection tools such as interviews are renowned tools used in the gathering of data in both the research methodologies discussed above. Focus groups which are a category of the interview are also frequently employed to unravel and comprehend the existing differences, sways, conduct or inspiration of a cluster of people relating to certain attributes under focus (Krueger and Casey, 2015). Nevertheless, qualitative data may come in different forms other than words. Neuman (2014) and Punch and Oancea (2014) indicate that images from documents, transcripts, artefact, sound recordings, and observation records and notes provide examples of forms of qualitative data.

A successful and useful qualitative method of study is that which can describe the issue under research in detail and within the context. Such research considers narrow and specified situations through the lenses of the participants while acknowledging their opinions and understanding all changes if carried out over a prolonged duration. Jonson and Onwuegbuzie (2004) argue that as the data describes results from fieldwork or a narrow situation, it is impossible to make generalisations, which is one of the limitations of qualitative research. Additionally, the processes of data collection and data analysis are time-consuming. Researcher's biases and subjectivity are other limitations of qualitative research (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). Finally,

qualitative research may be influenced by the personal relationship between the researcher and participants (Bryman, 2012).

Apart from the sharp differences between the two research methodologies, it is evident that they provide researchers with flexibility. This flexibility, in turn, allows them to easily answer diversified research questions in an orderly and systematic manner. However, the past three decades have witnessed an affirming stance for the pragmatic paradigm, thus removing the gap between different thoughts of the scholarly spectrum. In this study, quantitative and qualitative research were combined to facilitate gaining a comprehensive understanding of infection control strategies, influences and challenges in healthcare facilities in KSA. As previously mentioned, the factors contributing to the lack of adherence to infection control protocols among HCWs in KSA are under-researched. To explore and explain HCWs' perceptions of IPC practices and how their perceptions among other individual and institutional factors play a role in affecting HCWs' compliance with recommended IPC practices, a structured questionnaire survey was developed to measure the factors that are likely to affect healthcare professionals' compliance with IPC practices.

However, realising the limitations of the positivist paradigm of there being no single truth to reality, it was concluded that relying only on quantitative surveys to understand the complexity of human behaviour would be insufficient because behaviours also involve subjective opinions. These opinions are shaped by many factors including, for example, the culture in which one lives or grew up in, personality traits, and education levels. To this end, a pragmatic paradigm was employed in this research using a mixed methods approach to identify the factors associated with compliance with infection control measures in KSA. The positivist approach was used in the quantitative survey to understand the level of implementation of recommended IPC practices and role of perceptions, individual and other institutional factors in influencing compliance with IPC practices. On the other hand, the interpretive approach was used to help understand why HCWs' chose to follow/not follow infection control procedures to explore alternative truths such as the

subjective and cultural or environmental reasons. Semi-structured qualitative interviews and non-participant observations were employed to understand HCWs' perceptions of IPC practices and explore the factors which influence compliance with IPC policies and guidelines from different viewpoints in depth in their natural settings.

Using quantitative or qualitative research would provide a partial understanding of the research problem. The choice of the mixed methods approach then was the most suitable to conduct this research and benefit from the complementary nature of quantitative and qualitative approaches (Lieber and Weisner, 2010). The next section examines the advantages of triangulation which this mixed methods research benefited from.

4.3.2 Triangulation in Mixed Method Research

Mixed method triangulation is defined as the process of combining several research methods to carry out the study of one problem (Hussein, 2015, P. 13). Triangulation is used by researchers to study a particular aspect to understand reality through incorporating techniques on multiple modes of analysis (Bryman, 2017 p. 65) as shown in Figure 4.2 below:

Figure 4.2: Triangulation Diagram.

4.3.2.1 Advantages of Using Triangulation in Research

The application of triangulation in research methods has a positive impact on the entire research process (Mayoh and Onwuegbuzie, 2015, p. 96). The triangulation process or studying a problem from different perspectives and using mixed research methods facilitate easy understanding of complex, misunderstood phenomenon (Riazi and Candlin, 2014, p. 140). Additionally, triangulating research methods solves the limitations that a single approach of research could have had in researching a complex reality. Generally, triangulating research methods provides one or more conclusions and enables the researcher to determine the suitable conclusion (Gibson, 2017, p. 199).

Triangulation reduces the instances of bias and prevents possible assumptions that the researcher might develop during research (Shannon-Baker, 2016, p. 328). The conclusions about the phenomenon under study are based on the results from every angle of generating reality or the truth (Bryman, 2017, p. 60). Personal biases or assumptions are not accommodated or are reduced to a minimal in this case as findings obtained from different methods are compared before concluding, thereby ensuring accuracy in the final findings (Archibald, 2016, p. 250). Despite having many advantages of using triangulation, it is important to acknowledge that there are some limitations which researchers need to consider.

4.3.2.2 Limitations of Using Triangulation

The first limitation of using triangulation is that the lack of a common method of research and uniformity of the methodology used brings confusions in the process of study (Venkatesh et al., 2013, p. 37). As the final results in triangulation depend on comparison between the results of various research methods, the variance of the methods used makes it difficult for the researchers to compare findings. Second, researchers who use triangulation often fail to explain their research criteria since they rely on the combined analysis to interpret a phenomenon (Guest, 2013, p. 149). For instance, the resultant reluctance of the researchers in verifying findings has initiated a lot of inaccurate information in the field of research and study (Denscombe, 2014, p. 101). Third, most of the researchers know only one criterion of study (Taylor et al., 2015, p. 40), that is, most researchers major in only one method of research in their studies. Triangulation design, in this case, may be inconvenient for some researchers as they have to try to familiarise themselves or look for other researchers who are experts in the other field (Guest, 2013, p. 144).

To address the challenges of using triangulation in this mixed methods research, the design of this study was developed thoughtfully, and the research process was conducted after spending a long time reading about carrying out mixed methods research. The next section presents the mixed methods design used to carry out this research.

4.3.3 Mixed Methods Research Design

There are various ways of combining quantitative and qualitative research in mixed methods research. According to Creswell (2014), the three most common designs are the convergent parallel, explanatory sequential and exploratory sequential, which are shown below in Figure 4.3:

Figure 4.3: Basic Mixed Methods Designs (Source: Creswell, 2014, p. 220).

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information.

The three basic designs shown above are differentiated by the order of data collection, analysis and interpretation. For example, when implementing the convergent parallel design which is also referred to as the concurrent design (Fetters et al., 2013), the researcher collects both quantitative and qualitative data, analyses them separately and then compares the results to determine any inconsistency or decide whether the data confirms or disconfirms each other. On

the other hand, based on Creswell (2014), the exploratory sequential approach starts with the collection of qualitative data which helps determine the quantitative data collection process to be used. Finally, the explanatory sequential design is the opposite of exploratory sequential in that quantitative data is collected first and it highlights primary areas that require qualitative investigation.

To collect and analyse data in this mixed methods research, the convergent or as known as concurrent design was chosen because this design would facilitate collecting richer data which meets the aim of this study. Concurrent triangulation is primarily characterised by having two or more than two methods put in place to cross-validate and confirm the findings of a particular study (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017, p. 59). After information is gathered regarding a phenomenon, various methods are put in place to test and determine its validity and relevance (Brannen, 2017, p. 76). If the outcome of both methods concurs then the collected data is valid and reliable when finding out the reality (Archibald, 2016, p. 255). Furthermore, in concurrent triangulation, quantitative and qualitative data is collected at one stage. The data is then analysed separately and subsequently compared to obtain the final analysis (Hussein, 2015, p. 15). In concurrent design, both strands, quantitative and qualitative, have equal priority (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011).

Because information collected from quantitative and qualitative sources in this research is equally important and both sources of data were needed to provide a comprehensive understanding of infection control measures in KSA, the concurrent design was used. Therefore, both types of data were collected during a similar timeframe, analysed separately and then the results were merged to allow for comparison of data and obtaining complementary data which provides a comprehensive understanding of HCWs' perceptions and the role of perceptions and practices of HCWs towards infection control in KSA. The model for the concurrent triangulation design followed to conduct this research is illustrated below in Figure 4.4:

Figure 4.4: Concurrent Triangulation Research Design.

Concurrent triangulation has various benefits for conducting research and validating the findings, which encouraged adopting this research design. The findings that the researchers draw after carrying out a study do not always have to be real with clear interpretations (Heale and Forbes, 2013, p. 106). The description of data requires the application of various methods so that a comparison can be made between the results of multiple methods (Wilson, 2014, p. 74). Consequently, the results are always accurate as they are derived from the similarities of the used methods for verifying data. Concurrent triangulation helps the researchers ascertain findings before concluding (Hussein, 2015, p. 14).

Analysing data through triangulation design helps minimise threats to internal validity by ensuring that they are realised and addressed (Hussein, 2015, p. 16). As research by triangulation involves both the analyses of qualitative and quantitative methods, the two strive to minimise the inadequacies of a single method (Heale and Forbes, 2013, p. 107). Quantitative design works towards controlling bias so that facts about a phenomenon are understood well (Wilson, 2014, p. 76). On the other hand, the qualitative method attempts to highlight the perspectives of all the

participants by considering the first-hand experience to collect a reasonable data (Hussein, 2015, p. 13).

Despite having many advantages for using the concurrent mixed methods design, there are some challenges which may arise when quantitative and qualitative approaches are integrated. As Bryman (1992) indicates, each approach has different aims and concerns which makes it difficult for researchers to compare data when triangulating quantitative and qualitative findings. It is possible that quantitative results may not confirm qualitative findings which poses a challenge for mixed methods researchers. According to Creswell and Plano Clark (2011), the data generated by one approach rarely confirms completely the findings generated by the second approach. To respond to this challenge in this research, both the similarities and differences in quantitative and qualitative data are discussed in detail in Chapters Five and Six.

The next section provides a detailed description of the quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis processes.

4.4 METHODS

This section provides some background information to understand the research settings and processes. The section describes plans or strategies used to conduct this research such as participant sampling procedures and how both types of quantitative and qualitative data were collected, analysed and interpreted.

4.4.1 Research Settings

This study was conducted in two tertiary care hospitals (Buraidah Central Hospital and King Fahad Specialised Hospital) located in the Qassim region of KSA in the centre of KSA, approximately 300 km northwest of the capital city, Riyadh. In total, there are 542 hospitals in KSA of which 415 are governmental and 127 are private hospitals. The Buraidah Central Hospital is the first hospital to be opened in the Qassim region in 1375. It is a specialist hospital and serves

the entire population of the Qassim region, which stood at 1.4 million inhabitants in the 2017 population census (The Statistics Portal, 2017). It has a capacity of approximately 300 beds and employs over 500 HCWs (about 100 doctors and 400 nurses and other cadres) – Table 4.2. below illustrates staffing within KSA hospitals:

Table 4.2: Staffing within KSA Hospitals

Hospital	Bed Numbers	Number of Medics	Number of Nursing Staff*	Types of Wards/ Activity
Buraidah Central Hospital (HOSPITAL 2)	Approx 300	Approx 100	Approx 400*	General medical/surgical
King Fahad Specialised Hospital (HOSPITAL 1)	Approx 500	Approx 300	Approx 900*	Specialist medical/surgical. Maternity/Paediatrics
Total	800	400	1300	

*Includes all ‘biomedical’ staff, including domestics/administrative and (registered and non-registered) nursing staff – more specific nursing numbers will be attained during the finalisation of access arrangements.

On the other hand, King Fahad Specialised Hospital is also a referral hospital for the Qassim region and has a capacity of around 500 beds and employs 1,200 HCWs (doctors, nurses and others). These hospitals were selected arbitrarily and out of convenience, as the researcher was working at one of the selected hospitals and is well known in the other. Therefore, it was believed that doing the research there would facilitate access to participants to understand the perceptions of HCWs of infection control practices in their respective hospitals and the factors which affect compliance with recommended infection control practices.

4.4.2 Quantitative Data Collection and Analysis

4.4.2.1 Facility-based Cross-Sectional Survey Sampling

The most significant components of quantitative research are the population, the sample, instrument and tool to be used, data analysis method and data interpretation method. The participants are selected from a sample which represents the entire population under research. The sampling framework offers direction for selection of participants that will enable one to draw conclusions about the given population (De Vaus, 2002). Probability sampling is the optimal sampling technique for making deductions about a population, and it depends on the ability to define the population as well access the sampling frame. A sampling frame is simply a list of the population and the capability to choose the sample arbitrarily, which offers the benefit of minimising selection bias during the selection of participants (Moule and Goodman, 2014). On the other hand, non-probability sampling is used where there are difficulties of contacting participants and where participants are not readily available as it does not rely on the random selection of participants. The best examples of non-probability sampling are purposive, convenience and quota sampling (De Vaus, 2002).

In this research, probability sampling was used for the facility-based quantitative cross-sectional survey to ensure minimising selection bias while recruiting participants who were directly relevant to achieve the purposes of this research. The self-administered questionnaire was targeted to nurses and doctors from the two hospitals to better understand the factors associated with HCWs' perceptions of and compliance with IPC practices. The focus was on nurses and physicians working in acute hospital settings who also had direct patient contact. All the staff who did not have direct contact with patients (such as biomedical staff as well as non-medical staff and non-nursing staff) were excluded from the study. The target population across the healthcare sector in these areas in (Hospital 1 and Hospital 2) was 1052 participants. In this survey, a total of 498 participants were recruited. All the 498 nurses and physicians were invited to participate by email

and were asked to complete either an electronic questionnaire (using SurveyMonkey) or a printed hardcopy of the questionnaires distributed and delivered by hand at each of the hospitals.

Distributing the questionnaire using both forms electronic and paper was intended to increase survey response rate. Although an advantage of online questionnaire is lowering the data collection costs, completing a paper questionnaire may be a practical and easy method for some participants as they only need a pen and time to participate (Ebert et al., 2018). However, the disadvantages of a paper questionnaire according to Ebert et al., (2018) include, for example, participants may leave some questions unanswered, they may write more answers for one question than allowed, and they may check a box outside the intended boundaries. The risk as a result is compromising the data particularly when completed questionnaires are read by a machine because these errors often result in missing values (Ebert et al., 2018).

In this research, the online survey collected 200 responses and the printed hardcopy survey collected 298 responses over a 12-week period between July 2016 and September 2016. A tool developed by CheckMarket (2018) indicated that a sample size of 282 would have an 80% power to identify any factors associated with infection control. This study's sample was, therefore, above the minimum required number of 282 participants. The measures followed to deal with missing data will be explained later in this chapter.

4.4.2.2 Questionnaire Design

According to Babbie and Mouton (2001) and Fowler (2002), a questionnaire is an imperative quantitative survey tool which can elaborate on the characteristics of many participants over a large geographical location. Dörnyei (2003, p. 6) defines the questionnaire as an efficient tool in terms of saving the researcher some efforts, saving research time during data collection and analysis, which can be important factors at the planning stage, and is a low-cost tool. The main reason for employing the questionnaire as a main data collection tool in this research is due to its effectiveness in collecting information in a structured form in a short time frame (Cohen et al.,

2015). Another reason is that participants can answer the questions at their own convenience without being influenced by the presence of the researcher, which can reduce bias when providing answers (Bryman, 2012). Furthermore, compared to qualitative data, analysing numerical data is straightforward and it does not require much time (Dörnyei, 2003).

Nevertheless, researchers need to be aware of the limitations of questionnaires. Dörnyei (2003) points out that there is a possibility that the questionnaire is poorly designed which influences the quality of the responses. Designing the questionnaire may be difficult and it requires lots of time to prepare (Cohen et al., 2015). In addition, participants' responses may be limited which affects the scope of the data generated (Bryman, 2012). Another limitation which Bryman (2012) indicates is that there might be some missing data because participants may skip questions which influences measuring the variables created in the questionnaire.

To benefit from the many advantages offered by using the questionnaire while aiming at reducing its limitations, the research questionnaire was planned well, and the questions were clearly presented. The research questionnaire was thoroughly planned in accordance with the guidelines for survey design 'Survey Administration Steps for Mixed-Mode Surveys' outlined by Sorra et al., (2016) when developing Hospital Survey on Patient Safety Culture (HSOPSC). The research questionnaire was designed to incorporate the core aspects of the conceptual model presented earlier in Chapter Three (i.e., the SEIPS Framework) which guided the overall research process.

Guided by the design of the questionnaire items in the user's guide developed by Sorra et al., (2016) to measure the level of patient safety culture, the design of the research questionnaire was developed to measure infection control practices at two hospitals in KSA. For example, as in Sorra et al., (2016), the research questionnaire was designed to capture a range of responses on a 5-point Likert scale containing positive, neutral or negative responses (strongly agree, agree, neither agree nor disagree, disagree, strongly disagree). However, it is important to point out that the questionnaire developed in this study differs from Sorra et al.,'s (2016) questionnaire whether

in its context or aim as this study mainly measures HCWs' perceptions of and influences on infection control practices among nurses and physicians who have direct contacts with patients in two hospitals in KSA from their different points of view, whereas Sorra et al.,'s (2016) questionnaire primarily assessed patient safety culture among staff in general including non-nursing staff.

The main reason for using the rating scale questions is because they produce numbers while at the same time, they develop a flexible response with the ability to determine frequencies and correlations as Cohen et al., (2015) point out. Nonetheless, there are some limitations which researchers using rating scales need to be aware of such as the lack of checks on whether the participants are telling the truth, participants may need to elaborate on the issue researched, and participants may avoid the two extreme poles at each end of the continuum of the rating scale so that they are not called extremist. To address the limitations of rating scales, the participants were invited to a semi-structured interview to elaborate further on the issues raised.

To provide answers to the research questions and test the hypotheses defined, the research questionnaire items were organised in two sections. In Section 1: Demographics (Questions 1-6), the data collected was used to identify differences in HCWs' perceptions based on their profession, gender, age, academic qualifications, country of origin, and hospital setting. In Section 2: Your Perceptions of Infection Control (Questions 7-31), there were 25 questions covering eight themes: the overall quality of infection control (4 questions), outbreak preparedness (2 questions), leadership (2 questions), policies and guidelines (2 questions), training and support (4 questions), surveillance, monitoring and evaluation of infection control (4 questions), resources and supplies (2 questions) and supportive or blame culture (5 questions). The questionnaire is provided in Appendix IX in detail.

The questionnaire was originally created in English and was later translated into Arabic and delivered bilingually to facilitate getting responses from non-Arabic speaking participants. The questionnaire was accompanied by an information sheet explaining the aim and objectives of

the study. The information sheet also gave clear instructions on how to complete the survey. For the hard copy questionnaire, survey collection boxes were sited in secure areas of the hospital under guidance of the medical directors of these hospitals. Over three months, several reminders were sent to the participants to accumulate more responses and invite them to participate in a semi-structured interview. Data from the completed electronic and paper questionnaires was coded into an Excel file for analysis.

4.4.2.3 Data Analysis and Synthesis

Quantitative data was checked, edited, coded and entered into Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 17.0 for analysis. Participants' responses to a set of 25 questions which explored their perceptions of the quality of infection control at their hospitals were grouped by themes to allow for comparison and later for triangulation with qualitative data. The eight themes investigated HCWs' perceptions of:

- quality of infection control in their ward/department/hospitals (4 questions);
- preparedness against outbreaks (2 questions);
- quality of infection control leadership (2 questions);
- guideline and policies (2 questions),
- training and support (4 questions);
- surveillance, monitoring and evaluation and practice (4 questions);
- resources and supplies (2 questions); and
- existence of either supportive or blame culture on infection control (5 questions).

Composite scores, of HCWs' responses, on the 5-point Likert scale (i.e. 1=Strongly Agree, 2=Agree, 3=Neither Agree or Disagree, 4=Disagree and 5=Strongly disagreed), to each question were computed by summation of the responses within the composite scales and dividing by the number of participants. Negatively worded items were reversed when computing positive response

percentages. Descriptive statistics (i.e. total number and proportions of participants falling under each score) were used to describe the distribution of respondent's scores on the 5-point Likert scale, for each question, and grouped by relevant themes. Data on these scores were presented using bar graphs. Proportions of 60% and above were considered as good majority of respondents having that particular perception on the patient safety criteria.

The study also aimed at investigating factors associated with HCWs' perceptions of the status of infection control in their respective ward/department or hospital. For this analysis, first, respondents' answers to the dependent variables on the five Likert scale were binned to a 3 point nominal score where 1=Agree or Strongly Agree, 2=Neither Agree or Disagree (Neutral) and 3=Disagree or Strongly Disagree. Then composite level scores were computed by summation of the composite scores for each question relating to that theme and dividing by the number of questions under each theme. Negatively worded items were reversed when computing positive response percentages. Association between the outcome or dependent variable (perceptions) and the predictor or independent variables (age, sex, education, profession, nationality and hospital) were assessed at two levels. Firstly, in a univariate analysis, the Chi-square test was employed to measure any difference between observed and predicted values at a p value of <0.05 . Secondly, variables that were significant in the univariate analysis, were further explored using Multinomial Logistic regression, in a multivariate analysis. Association was measured using relative risk ratios (RRR) at significance cut-off value of $p<0.05$. For the outcome value, the ordinal scores for the level Disagree (3) was used as the baseline.

4.4.2.4 Missing Data

Different methods can be used to deal with missing data. The answer differs based on the size of the unanswered item or the kind of the item within a large scale. The first instance looks at whether the participants failed to respond to the single item such as 'academic qualifications' or 'gender' or any question from the demographics section then they were of necessity excluded from

any analyses that examine the influence of that variable on other variables. Likewise, if a participant left a whole scale or set of related questions unanswered, for example if they answered none of the questions on infection prevention and control or none of the items on a Likert scale, then that case was excluded from the analyses.

4.4.3 Qualitative Data Collection and Analysis

In the qualitative phase, two data collection tools were used: interviews and observations. Like questionnaires, employing the qualitative tools offers many advantages while they have some limitations. The following subsections present the qualitative data collection and analysis processes outlining the challenges faced with participant sampling at this stage.

4.4.3.1 Semi-structured Interviews

To examine the factors which promote and constrain infection control practice in KSA in detail, physicians, nurses and infection control staff were invited to participate in one-to-one, semi-structured qualitative interviews. Cohen et al., (2015) define the interview as a purposeful and question-based conversation which is governed by some rules. The interviewer asks a set of questions and may show ignorance and the responses can be as detailed as possible. The main reasons for choosing the interview are its popularity in qualitative research and giving the researcher control over questioning (Brinkmann, 2018). In comparison with other data collection techniques, the flexibility and adaptability of the interview as well as exploring in greater depth the participants' personal experiences related to the research question make this technique appealing to researchers (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006; McConnell-Henry et al., 2010; Bryman, 2012). While the researcher and interview participants interact during conversation, meaning is constructed (Cohen et al., 2011). Moreover, observing participants' non-verbal behaviour and involving several senses are some of the strengths of the interview (Bell, 2010).

However, the interview can be time and effort consuming as researchers need much time to plan for the interview, travelling time to the interview site, the actual interview time, transcribing and analysing interviews (Bryman, 2012). Analysing interviews may be biased because of their subjectivity which is another limitation of interviews (Bell, 2010). Furthermore, not all participants feel comfortable while being interviewed which makes using this tool inconvenient for some participants (Cohen et al., 2015). It is possible that the researcher is tired during the interview process which influences the progress of the interview (Cohen et al., 2015). The final limitation Creswell (2014) points out is that some participants may not be articulate and perceptive which influences the quality of the data gathered.

To respond to the limitations of interviews in this research, the design of the interviews was carefully planned based on a semi-structured guide. Cohen et al., (2015) indicate the various types of interview which differ in many ways including the openness of their purpose, their degree of structure, whether they aim for description or interpretation, or the degree they are exploratory or hypothesis-testing. Researchers choose the interview type based on the purposes of their research. For example, Punch and Oancea (2014) indicate that in structured interviews the researcher plans the questions, response categories and asks the questions in order. In semi-structured interviews, the researcher prepares some questions and prompts to facilitate discussion without restricting the discussion to the questions set. As for the unstructured type of qualitative interviews, the researcher prepares the general themes which participants may or may not be asked about depending on the topics they raise during the discussion.

The semi-structured type was selected in this research as it gives the researcher flexibility while guiding the discussion (Brinkmann, 2018). This flexibility is important as the researcher can change the order of questions and ask other questions depending on the answers the interviewees provide (Bryman, 2012). Another choice the researcher had to consider when designing the interview was whether to interview participants individually in one-to-one interviews or in a group discussion setting which is referred to as focus groups. In focus groups method, around six to

twelve people are gathered in a room with a trained moderator to discuss an issue the researcher is interested to know more about (Neuman, 2014). Focus groups usually emphasise a certain theme or topic that is explored in depth (Bryman, 2012). Generally, the discussion lasts for about 90 minutes and the study uses four to six separate groups (Neuman, 2014).

In focus groups, Bryman (2012) indicates that the researcher is interested in how individuals discuss a specific issue as members of a group, rather than simply as individuals. For example, the researcher is concerned about the ways the individuals respond to each other's views and develop a view out of the interaction that occurs within the group. This contrasts with individual interviews where the researcher focuses on exploring the individual point of view of each participant in depth and meaning is constructed based on the interaction between the researcher and the individual participant (Cohen et al., 2015). Therefore, in focus groups, the interaction within the group and the collective construction of meaning are important rather than the individual views of each participant (Bryman, 2012; Cohen et al., 2015). Furthermore, in focus groups, the predominate agenda is the participants' rather than the researcher's. The two forms of qualitative interviews have many strengths and limitations which researchers need to consider when planning the interview. Examples of the strengths and limitations which affected the choice of interview form in this research are summarised below in Table 4.3:

Table 4.3: Strengths and Limitations of individual interviews and focus groups (Sources: Bryman, 2012, p. 501; Neuman, 2014, p. 472; Cohen et al., 2015, p. 436; Guest et al., 2017).

Interview forms	Strengths	Limitations
Individual interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The individual point of view of participants and the way they interpret the world where they live are highlighted. • Meaning is constructed based on the interaction between the researcher and the individual participant. • The researcher’s agenda can predominate. • There is a higher potential for gaining more insight into a participant’s personal thoughts, feelings, and world view. • There is a higher potential for having a greater range and depth of themes discussed in individual interviews. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The interviews may be more cost-effective than focus groups for reaching data saturation. • Individual interviews require more planning compared to focus groups. • Some participants may not feel comfortable to disclose personal information and discuss very sensitive topics. • Researcher’s biases may affect the interview process.
Focus groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The natural setting encourages participants to express their ideas freely. • Members of social groups who are marginalised are encouraged to express their opinions openly. • Participants may feel empowered, especially in action-oriented research projects. • Participants may ask each other to explain their answers. • Interaction within the group and the joint construction of meaning are highlighted. • The researcher gains a better understanding of why participants feel the way they do, and how they collectively make sense of a phenomenon and construct meanings around it. • Focus groups may facilitate the elicitation of a wide variety of different views in relation to a specific issue. • Participants will often argue with each other and challenge each other’s views. This may help the researcher to develop more realistic accounts of what people think as they are challenged to think about and possibly revise their views. • It is possible to generate a large amount of data in a short time at low cost. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group dynamics may affect participation. A dominant member may control discussion while inarticulate members may have limited chances to express their views. • A “polarization effect” exists, that is, attitudes become more extreme after group discussion. • The discussion may be limited to only one or a few topics. • Focus groups can generate fewer ideas than individual interviews when comparing on a per-person basis, which may result in gaining ‘surface’ data compared to individual interviews. • A moderator may unintentionally limit open, free expression of group members. • Researchers cannot reconcile the differences that appear between individual-only and focus group–context responses. • There is a possible loss of control over proceedings. • There is the potential for unwanted group effects. Disagreement and conflict may arise.

In this research, despite their many strengths, conducting individual interviews was preferred rather than focus groups which involve several participants because this research is concerned with building up an understanding of the research problem based on the individual views of different participants rather than the collective views of the group and how participants respond to each other's views and challenge them (Bryman, 2012). To explore HCWs' perceptions of infection control practices in two healthcare facilities in KSA and identify other factors affecting infection control practices which required probing each participant's personal thoughts, feelings, and views about the research problem guided the choice of carrying out in-depth one-to-one interviews with participants.

The interview questions were guided by the frameworks directing this research such as the SEIPS Framework (Carayon et al., 2006) which captures most of the core components of WHO (2011) IPC programmes discussed in Chapter Three. Barker et al., (2017), which studies facilitators and barriers to infection control at a large private hospital in Gurgaon, India, was another influential study which the interview schedule benefited from due to having many participants from India working at both research hospitals. However, it is important to point out that the interview schedule developed was designed to suit the local context of this study and address the aim of this research, that is, understanding the perceptions of HCWs and the level of compliance with recommended infection control practices in KSA. The semi-structured guide developed during the interview process is provided in Appendix X. Examples of the main topics the participants were asked about include:

- participants' perceptions of current infection prevention and control measures;
- infection prevention and control policy development;
- staff education and training;
- surveillance of diseases and compliance with IPC;
- participants' perceptions of their organisational culture, in terms of infection prevention and control, and

- suggestions for improvements.

Approximately 15 participants were intended to be recruited based on the research objectives. Purposive sampling was used to invite nurses and physicians from the two hospitals who were working in acute hospital settings and had a direct contact with patients to participate in the semi-structured interview. Invitations were sent to HCWs' work email in addition to providing the invitation at the end of the questionnaire. Despite sending several reminders over a period of three months, seven participants volunteered to participate in the follow-up interview from the two hospitals (King Fahad Specialist Hospital four participants comprising of three physicians and one nurse; and Buraidah Central Hospital three participants comprising of two nurses and one physician).

In line with Cohen et al., (2015), some participants may not feel comfortable with the interview. In this research, for cultural reasons some participants were worried about participating in research. Some participants particularly non-Saudi nationals may have feared losing their job which discouraged them from participating despite showing interest in the study. Therefore, the relatively small sample could be one of the limitations of the qualitative phase in this research. As Cleary et al., (2014) warn, having too few participants may risk getting adequate depth and breadth of information. However, in this research, an interpretivist approach was adopted to maintain rigour and evaluate the sufficiency of the sample size through reaching saturation point. The concept of saturation which originates in grounded theory refers to the criterion for judging when to stop collecting further information because the researcher reaches a point where no new information or themes are observed in the data (Guest et al., 2006; Bryman, 2012).

In qualitative research, saturation is the most widely used principle for determining sample size in qualitative research (Vasileiou et al., 2018). As Guest et al., (2006, p. 60) suggest, saturation has become 'the gold standard by which purposive sample sizes are determined in health science research.' Therefore, reaching saturation point was used in this research to determine whether

adequate data was collected to generate rich data which allowed exploring HCWs' perceptions of infection control practices in KSA and identifying other factors affecting infection control practices.

Because qualitative data collection and analysis went hand in hand in the field during the research process, by the sixth interview saturation of themes was reached and further data collection was considered unnecessary because new data would not bring additional insights to the research questions. To determine and confirm saturation in this research the seventh interview was conducted, the researcher compared the frequency of new codes and themes generated in each interview with the ones already analysed. When the analysis indicated a significant repetition of information due to similarities in participants' comments, reaching saturation point was confirmed. In the next chapter, the research codes and themes identified, and their frequencies in interviews will be presented in detail. Because significant information was replicated among participants and no new themes emerged, the qualitative sample recruited was considered convenient to provide relevant information to address the aim of the research particularly that questionnaires and observations were also used as complementary data collection tools to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research problem.

Participants were invited to contact the researcher to arrange date and time for the interview. HCWs had two months as a cooling-off period prior to data collection. They could withdraw from the study during this two-month interval. In addition, HCWs were also free to withdraw their data after collection and prior to the commencement of data analysis. All participants were requested to provide consent prior to commencing the interview. Details of the consent form are provided in Appendix XI. Interviews were conducted over a one-month period (1 Sep 2016 to 30 Sep 2016). All participants who read and understood the information sheet had the opportunity to ask questions and were free to voluntarily withdraw at any time without providing any reasons. Interviews were audio recorded and typically lasted ten to twenty minutes. No identifiable information was collected.

4.4.3.2 Thematic Data Analysis

To facilitate the analysis of interview data, tape recorded interviews were written down in Arabic and then translated into English. Correct understanding relies on proper transcription and translation; thus, the researcher must listen to the audio recordings and compare with the transcript content to achieve accuracy in understanding the original content during interpretation (DiCicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006). Therefore, in this research the written content was read several times to grasp the internal meaning of the content. An important decision which the researcher had to take to analyse qualitative data was considering the application of either framework or thematic analysis. Both approaches are popular particularly in healthcare research and they share some similarities as they systematically and clearly apply the principles of conducting qualitative analysis to a series of interconnected stages that direct the process (Smith and Firth, 2011).

In framework analysis, as Smith and Firth (2011) explain, the researcher systematically follows structured topic guides to explore data in depth and identify patterns within the data. The researcher moves back and forth across the data to refine themes until a coherent account is developed. The process of refining themes may result in the development of a conceptual framework. The systematic approach adopted in framework analysis facilitates both examining data in depth and increasing the rigour of the analytical processes through retaining an effective and transparent audit trail (Smith and Firth, 2011). However, this approach completely differs from inductive approaches, as for example, grounded theory, where the research design is developed in response to the data gathered rather than is strictly predefined (Smith and Firth, 2011).

As for thematic analysis which resembles framework analysis in its initial stages, Smith and Firth (2011) point out that the data is systematically examined to identify patterns and significant themes within data which would facilitate understanding the phenomenon researched. Nevertheless, thematic analysis is characterised by flexibility in interpreting data (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Clarke and Braun, 2013). For example, according to Braun and Clarke (2006), the

flexibility of thematic analysis allows the researcher to determine themes in different ways. Therefore, using thematic analysis offers a wide range of analytic options. Generating unexpected insights is another advantage which characterises the use of thematic analysis. Furthermore, the theoretically flexible approach can be applied across a range of epistemologies and research questions.

To understand the perceptions of healthcare professionals of infection prevention and control practices and influences on IPC compliance in KSA, following a flexible approach would facilitate generating unanticipated insights and gaining a broader understanding of the research problem while strictly following a structured guide would potentially limit the themes developed during data analysis. Both the framework approach and thematic analysis show a greater emphasis on making the data analysis process transparent and illustrating the linkage between the stages of the analysis (Smith and Firth, 2011). However, thematic analysis has been criticised for being subjective, lacking transparency in relation to the development of themes which affects assessing the rigour of the findings, and lacking depth (Smith and Firth, 2011).

Because of its flexibility in interpreting data, thematic analysis was performed to identify, analyse and report patterns in qualitative data (Clarke and Braun, 2013). Directed by the conceptual framework of this research, thematic analysis was conducted using an inductive approach where during the analytical process of coding data is labelled into key concepts or themes developed from existing concepts or ideas (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The identified themes carry meanings which are relevant to the research question (Willing, 2014).

Allowing for an inductive approach while having some identified themes is one of the key strengths of thematic analysis which encouraged its choice to organise and analyse this research data. Another advantage of performing thematic analysis is that it helps understanding participants' views while illuminating similarities and differences in their views as well as offering unexpected insights (Nowell et al., 2017). Furthermore, the highly theoretically flexible approach does not need any commitment to a certain theory nor detailed theoretical and technological

knowledge of other qualitative approaches to explore patterns in the data (Clarke and Braun, 2013; Nowell et al., 2017). Although it is a quick method which researchers can learn, it results in generating rich data (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Nevertheless, like any other approaches, there are some limitations of thematic analysis which researchers need to acknowledge. For example, Nowell et al., (2017) indicate that when generating themes, there is a possibility that flexibility results in a lack of coherence. Moreover, conducting a rigorous thematic analysis may be problematic for novice researchers due to the lack of extensive literature on thematic analysis. Therefore, the analysis of the data in this research was guided by the steps outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) and Nowell et al., (2017) as shown below in Figure 4.5:

Figure 4.5: Phases of Thematic Data Analysis

Although the phases of thematic analysis shown above are presented as a linear process in Braun and Clarke's (2006) guidelines, the process is iterative and it requires moving back and forward between phases as Nowell et al., (2017) point out. In this research, data collection and analysis went hand in hand. With the aim of providing a detailed analysis of some aspects of the

data the research is concerned about exploring, some pre-determined themes were developed from the concepts outlined in the conceptual model guiding the research, the SEIPS model (Carayon et al., 2006) and the WHO's set of essential core components for IPC programmes (WHO, 2011). While gathering the data and noting patterns, initial codes which fit into the pre-existing coding framework were developed. Nevertheless, using the semi-structured interview schedule allowed for flexibility in developing new codes which later developed into themes. Detailed notes about development and hierarchies of codes and themes were taken. At the end of the process, six key themes were identified as shown below:

Figure 4.6. Key Research Themes

The next section examines the final data collection tool and analysis used in this study.

4.4.3.3 Non-participant Observations

Non-participant structured observations were conducted to understand HCWs' compliance with infection control policies at the two research hospitals. According to Patton (2015), observations describe activities, actions, behaviour, conversations, interactions, and organisational processes or any other aspects of human behaviour. The use of observations in qualitative research

is important to collect live data (Cohen et al., 2015). Therefore, observations facilitate understanding the research context (Savin-Baden and Tombs, 2017). Moreover, collecting data as they happen naturally in their social situations helps producing more valid data (Cohen et al., 2015).

Based on Bell (2010), there may be sometimes a gap between what people say they do and what they do. For this reason, in this research, observations aimed at establishing whether HCWs were indeed complying with infection control practices which were identified based on the SEIPS Framework (Carayon et al., 2006), including hand hygiene practices, respiratory and cough hygiene practices and other IPC practices such as wearing gloves, facemasks, aprons and other PPEs.

However, the limitations of observations include, the data gathered, and its interpretation may be influenced by the researcher's perceptions, prejudices and biases (Bell, 2010; Cohen et al., 2015). Because observations may be less reliable than other methods, Cohen et al., (2015) advise using observations in combination with other methods to provide data triangulation, which this research employed. To avoid bias and false compliance, HCWs at the two hospitals were blinded to the observation. The time and date of observations were negotiated with the heads of departments, but HCWs did not know when exactly their practices were under observation. This was done to ensure that HCWs behaved naturally in a way reflecting their normal pattern of behaviour rather than perform better because of the influence of the observer.

Permission to observe HCWs' compliance with infection control practices was obtained from the administration of the two hospitals. Eight observations were conducted over a period of one month from 1 August 2016 to 30 August 2016 (5 hours per day/ 5 days per week, for 4 weeks). This amounted to approximately 100 hours of observation to enable capturing enough information regarding participants' attendance, shifts and schedules. This approach was chosen to ensure that it covered an adequate number of HCWs from those clinics. Observations 2, 5, 7 and 8 were carried out at King Fahad Specialist Hospital (hereafter referred to as Hospital 1), whereas observations

1, 3, 4 and 6 took place at Buraidah Central Hospital (Hospital 2). Details of the ward and the number of physicians or nurses observed are provided in Table 4.4 below:

Table 4.4: Observation Record

Observation (No)	Physicians observed (No)	Nurses observed (No)	Department	Hospital
1	4	5	Orthopedics	Hospital 2
2	2	8	Emergency department (ER)	Hospital 1
3	6	6	Medical & Surgical ward (male)	Hospital 2
4	4	7	Medical & Surgical ward (female)	Hospital 2
5	5	8	Ear, Nose and Throat Department	Hospital 1
6	3	6	Ophthalmology	Hospital 2
7	3	0	Dermatology	Hospital 1
8	1	1	General Gastroenterology Clinic	Hospital 1
Total	28	41	69 HCWs	

Observations can be structured, semi-structured or unstructured. They can be participant or non-participant. Each type offers possibilities and has some limitations (Bell, 2010). As Cohen et al., (2015) explain, in structured observations, the researcher plans in advance what they want to observe. In the semi-structured type, although the researcher prepares an agenda of issues, the data is gathered in a far less pre-planned way. As for the unstructured observations, the researcher observes what is happening without planning in advance. In participant observations, the researcher participates in the researched events, unlike non-participant observations where the researcher has a passive role (Cohen et al., 2015).

In this research, to guide the structured observations, ensure consistency, and facilitate a systematic analysis of the discourse, requirements of the NHS Scotland Standard Infection Control Precautions (SICPs) (NHS Scotland; NHS NSS, 2016) were used. The NHS tool was chosen because hospitals in KSA follow the model used in advanced countries like the UK and use their tools as a reference. Hence, using the NHS tool is considered appropriate in the research context. The form captures all the aspects of infection control areas such as hand hygiene, respiratory cough

hygiene and use of PPEs such as gloves, aprons, full body gowns and eye protection when attending to patients admitted with infectious diseases. It also captures information on proximity and the manner of storage of PPEs in these facilities (see Appendix XII).

Like interviews, thematic analysis was used to organise and interpret observation data. Observation data was analysed using inductive analysis, where the researcher coded the observations into where he thought they might fall among the themes developed from the requirements of the SICPs (NHS Scotland, 2016) which were used to guide the observations. Participants' behaviours were grouped as compliant or not compliant with the expected behaviours regarding respiratory and hand hygiene, or proper use of PPEs.

Macnee and McCabe (2007) advise considering the researcher's knowledge and experience and using it to interpret the results. In this study, the researcher has previously worked for years as a medical microbiologist, and then as an infection control practitioner in the same place where the study was carried out, under the same working conditions. These experiences made it easier for the researcher to understand all the data provided by the participants and possibly get an accurate interpretation of the data.

4.5 RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY

Obtaining valid and reliable data are the main concerns which all researchers care about (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). According to Bryman (2012), validity refers to the integrity of the findings and confirming whether the items measure what they are intended to measure. As for reliability, it refers to the degree of the consistency of the findings. However, it is important to point out that the meanings of validity and reliability are different in quantitative and qualitative research (Cohen et al., 2015).

The thoroughness of any quantitative research is demonstrated by testing the reliability and validity of the methodologies used. During the creation of a questionnaire for implementation of the survey design, it is tested to determine the consistency in measuring the expected outcome

or its reliability. This is done using a test-retest method and by subsequently evaluating the results to assess whether the responses are consistent. Validity confirms that the instrument meets its intended use, which is simply known as content validity. Timmins (2015) indicates that content validity comprises of question design, the sequence of questions, the duration of time needed to complete the task and the correct measurement scale. Additionally, under quantitative research, data is processed statistically where experimental designs use comprehensive statistics to make conclusions about the population from the studied sample. Descriptive analysis, on the contrary, is mostly used in the case of a survey design to provide an informative summary of outcomes. Besides the written description, it also encompasses tabulations and graphical representations of data (De Vaus, 2002).

In this study, the Cronbach's alpha was calculated to check internal consistency/reliability for each of the composite items to ensure that items within each composite were consistent. The Cronbach's alpha is a measure of internal validity that analyses and examines the internal consistency of the items included in the research. It is a measure of reliability (Nguyen, 2010) and internal consistency that assesses the way an arrangement of things is closely linked as a collection of factors. It is also used as a means of assessing scale dependability. A Cronbach's alpha value of 0.60 or greater is deemed acceptable (Sorra and Nieva, 2004). In this study, the Cronbach's alpha for the composites was 0.854 and ranged from 0.83 to 0.88 (See below Table 4.5). The Cronbach's alpha values suggest a preferable level of internal consistency reliability for this study as according to Pallant (2007), values above 0.8 are considered desirable. Thus, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.854 indicates the satisfactory performance of the questionnaire in assessing the variables of interest, besides showing good internal consistency. Removal of individual items did not affect the internal consistency of the scale. The internal consistency in the questionnaire's case ranged from 0.836 to 0.860, indicating that all items have an equal measure of reliability. This highlights the strength of the items and the overall scale in the assessment of attitudes and

behaviours concerning infection control policies. Thus, it can be assumed that this scale is a reliable measure of the outcome of interest in this sample.

Table 4.5: Scale: Summary and Reliability Statistics

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	433	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	433	100.0
a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.			
Reliability Statistics			
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardised Items	N of Items	
.850	.854	25	

Apart from the estimation of internal consistency, researchers aim to prove that the scale being referred to is one-dimensional, and exploratory factor investigation is one technique for checking dimensionality (Litwin, 1995). Furthermore, there are several alpha value ratios that are acceptable, with the range being between 0.70 and 0.95 (Nunnally and Beristen, 1994). A value below this range may be the result of a small sample in the number of questions or a small interrelation between heterogeneous factors (Cohen and Swerdlick, 2010). For instance, if a low value is obtained and determined to be a result of poor correlation between the elements, some of the sample statistics should either be reviewed or omitted from the workings (Cortina, 1993). One simple way to identify poor correlation is by calculating individual sample correlation with the overall score test. However, if the alpha value is beyond the permissible maximum, it implies that some elements may be unnecessary and could be evaluating the same hypothesis, although appearing to be different. The maximum recommended alpha value is 0.90 (Eberhard et al., 2011). Therefore, Cronbach's alpha is not a factual test, rather it is a coefficient of unwavering quality or

consistency. This measure is less prone to error or zero random measure. This, for example, is reflected in any element that introduces a haphazard or arbitrary distortion in the process of measurement resulting in inconsistent measurements, and therefore the measure is used to ascertain that the approach is free of systematic error. Finally, it is utilised as a chronic distortion or consistency measure that highlights the underlying concept of interest in order to assess the reliability of the measure.

In qualitative research, there are different terms used to refer to validity as, for example, trustworthiness, authenticity and credibility (Creswell, 2014). Qualitative reliability is focused on the research process itself and ensuring consistency between the data obtained and the findings (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). Researchers can use several strategies to assess the trustworthiness of their research which are different from the ones used in quantitative research (Cohen et al., 2015). For example, Creswell (2014) advises researchers to spend prolonged time in the research field to understand the researched phenomenon better. This advice was followed in this study particularly as just mentioned in the above section the researcher has worked in the research setting for a long time. Another strategy which was adopted in this research is providing rich description of the research context, data analysis and findings using relevant quotes from the participants (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). The analysis of the data was guided by the conceptual framework of the study which was used to monitor data interpretation and reduce bias. More importantly, triangulation was used to increase confidence in research statements, reduce the instances of bias and better understand the research problem (Creswell, 2014).

4.6 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Ethics, according to Saunders et al. (2009, p. 600), can be defined as “the appropriateness of the researcher’s behaviour in relation to the rights of those who become the subject of a research project, or who are affected by it.” Several ethical issues are likely to arise throughout all phases of research—from choosing and formulating the research topic to writing up and reporting the

findings of the research, while designing the research and collecting, processing, storing, and analysing the data. These ethical issues require special consideration. In addition to being methodologically sound, research has to be morally defensible (Creswell, 2003; Gomm, 2004; Saunders et al., 2009). The following ethical issues were considered, in this study.

Ethical approvals to conduct this study were obtained at the beginning of the research, from the University of the West of Scotland, the Qassim region MOH and the instructional ethics committees of the two hospitals (Appendices XIII to XVI). Participation in this study was voluntary. The staff had two months as a cooling-off period prior to data collection, and during these two months they were free at any time to withdraw from participation in the study. In addition, participants were given an option to withdraw their data after the collection period and prior to the commencement of data analysis. Finally, all participants read and understood the information sheet for the study. They had the opportunity to ask questions to ensure that they understood that participation was voluntary and that they had freedom to withdraw at any time without attributing any reasons. Participants who did not wish to participate in this part of study were excluded from any data collection and/or analysis.

For the observation phase, HCWs were made aware of the ongoing study (that a researcher would be observing the HCW while treating them during the study), via information sheets and posters (Appendix XVII). Stickers were used to identify the bed spaces of patients where observation was taking place. The researcher was removed from the clinic room if the patient did not wish to be observed. Questionnaires from the self-administered cross-sectional survey and the observational arm of the study were anonymised and treated with strict confidentiality. No names of participants or patients were written on the self-administered questionnaire or the observational tool (anonymous observational data). Participants also understood that the information gathered during this observation and the interviews were recorded and would be analysed and used to report/publish on the issue of IPC. It was planned that the information and reports obtained from the analysis of data gathered in this study would be shared through conference presentations,

publication in peer reviewed journals and reports to the two participating hospitals. No personal data or names were included in these reports; the participants' names were substituted by codes as a form of identification, whereas the information provided by the research participants was handled in a confidential manner (Britten et al., 1995; Gomm, 2004; Saunders et al., 2009).

4.7 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER FOUR

This chapter analyses the research methodology and methods used to collect and analyse the research data. A rationale is provided for employing a pragmatic paradigm using the mixed methods approach rather than solely relying on the quantitative or qualitative approach alone. Depending on quantitative surveys to understand the complexity of human behaviour would be insufficient because behaviours also involve subjective opinions. Therefore, a mixed methods approach utilising both quantitative and qualitative designs was adopted.

To better understand the factors associated with HCWs' perceptions and compliance with IPC, three data collection tools were used. The first tool is a quantitative survey that employed a semi-structured questionnaire followed by data analysis using descriptive statistics, wherein the chi-squared test was applied to measure any differences in categorical variables. Second, semi-structured interviews were conducted to gather richer and more detailed information from participants. The third data collection tool is non-participant observation which helped observe HCWs' compliance with infection control practices at the two research hospitals. The qualitative results were thematically analysed. The results from the three sources of data were triangulated. The objective of triangulation is to provide a clear picture and uncover some variables that might be hidden from the researcher and might only become known when participants are interviewed so that the reasons for their behaviour or choices, values, and attitudes are known. Finally, the research reliability, validity and all ethical precautions undertaken in this study have been detailed.

CHAPTER FIVE: RESULTS AND ANALYSIS OF INDIVIDUAL DATASETS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the results drawn from both quantitative and qualitative studies through a mixed-methods approach. First, the chapter presents the perceptions of healthcare workers (HCWs) regarding the standards of infection control practices in their respective hospitals and explores the demographic, occupational and country specific factors associated with their perception. These perceptions were further explored in the structured interview. The results of the quantitative and qualitative interviews were then triangulated with the results of the observed adherence to recommended infection prevention and control (IPC) practices using the data obtained from non-participant observations.

5.2 RESULTS OF THE QUANTITATIVE SURVEY

5.2.1 *Participation Rate*

The questionnaire was administered to nurses and doctors from the two hospitals in Qassim region located in the centre of KSA, approximately 300 km northwest of Riyadh, the capital city of KSA. The survey was conducted over a 3-month period (1 July 2016 to 30 Sep 2016). The survey involved nurses and physicians within acute hospital settings who had direct contact with patients. The recruited sample included 498 nurses and physicians with 433 respondents completing the full questionnaire (participation rate = 86.9%). Data from 65 HCWs was not included in this analysis for several reasons. For example, 42 HCWs did not answer all the questions. Five HCWs did not provide demographic data nor complete some questions regarding their perceptions in the questionnaire.

5.2.2 Demographic and Other Characteristics of Healthcare Workers

Of the 433 HCWs included in the questionnaire, the majority (312; 72.1%) were females, compared to only 121 (27.9%) males, and this difference was statistically significant (Chi-square 168.5, $p < .0001$, Table 5.1). Regarding their age, the majority of HCWs (287; 66.3 %) were young adults aged between 20–34 years, compared to 112 (25%) who were middle-aged, between 35–49 years and only 34 (7.9%) were aged 50 years or over (Chi-square statistic is 348.91, p value < 0.00001). In terms of education, most of HCWs had a Bachelor degree (278; 64.2%), about 70 HCWs (16.2%) had a diploma degree, 30 HCWs (6.9%) had a Masters degree, 43 HCWs (9.9%) had a Board degree and 12 HCWs (2.8%) had a PhD degree (Chi-square = 686.77, p value is < 0.00001).

In terms of nationality, most of HCWs were foreigners (74.1%), with only 112 HCWs (25.9%) were from KSA. The nationalities of foreign HCWs were as follows: India 4 (0.9%), Yemen 33 (7.6%), Pakistan 99 (22.9%), Philippines 5 (1.2%), Syria 22 (5.1%), Egypt 24 (5.5%), Sudan 1 (0.2%), Indonesia 1 (0.2%), Palestine 1 (0.2%) and Jordan 1 (0.2%), and these differences were statistically significant (Chi-square 88.0, $p=0.025$).

Regarding HCWs' professions, the majority were registered nurses (283; 65.4%), while 15 (3.5%) were unregistered nurses and 135 (31.2%) were physicians (Chi-square 374.58, $p < 0.00001$). The majority (269; 62.1%) of HCWs were from King Fahad Specialist Hospital (Hospital 1), whereas 164 (37.6%) worked in Buraidah Central Hospital (Hospital 2) (Chi-square 50.92, $p < 0.00001$).

Table 5.1 below summarises the above-mentioned demographic results:

Table 5.1 Descriptive statistics of six demographic questions. Data are in numbers and percentages.

Variable	Number (Percentage) <i>n</i> (0%)	Chi-Square (Pearson)	<i>p</i> value		
Gender					
Male	121 (27.9)	$\chi^2=168.5$	<.0001		
Female	312 (72.1)				
Age					
20-34	287 (66.3)	$\chi^2=348.91$	< 0.00001		
35-49	112 (25.9)				
50 or over	34 (7.9)				
Education					
Diploma	70 (16.2)	$\chi^2= 686.76$	< 0.00001		
Bachelor	278 (64.2)				
Master	30 (6.9)				
Board	43 (9.9)				
PhD	12 (2.8)				
Nationality					
KSA	112 (25.9)	$\chi^2=88.0$	0.025		
India	131 (30.3)				
Yemen	4 (0.9)				
Pakistan	33 (7.6)				
Philippines	99 (22.9)				
Syria	5 (1.2)				
Egypt	22 (5.1)				
Sudan	24 (5.5)				
Indonesia	1 (0.2)				
Palestine	1 (0.2)				
Jordan	1 (0.2)				
Profession					
Nurse-unlicensed	15 (3.5)			$\chi^2= 374.58$	< 0.00001
Nurse-licensed	283 (65.4)				
Physician	135 (31.2)				
Workplace					
HOSPITAL 1	269 (62.1)	$\chi^2= 50.92$	<.00001		
HOSPITAL 2	164 (37.9)				

5.2.3 Perceptions on Characteristics of Infection Control in the Hospitals

The qualitative survey was comprised of twenty-five questions which explored HCWs' perceptions on issues related to infection control in their ward or hospital. The questions were grouped into eight themes because the questionnaire was designed in such a way that HCWs were asked the same question twice with a slight change in the wording. For example, in trying

to understand HCWs' perceptions of the quality of infection control, one question was whether they thought the quality of infection control in the ward or department was good, and another was whether they thought the quality of infection control in the hospital as a whole was good. As both questions belonged to the same theme (quality of infection control), when synthesising data, all data which were related by theme such as quality of infection control were grouped together as they were addressing the same theme.

Similar reasoning was used to group the other responses, such as training, supplies or blame culture. Presenting the responses to questions which discussed the same theme individually would result in repetition and would make understanding the data difficult. Therefore, the questions were grouped into the eight themes as follows:

- overall quality of infection control in the hospital and ward: Questions 7-10.
- preparedness against outbreaks: Questions 11 and 12.
- quality of infection control leadership: Questions 13 and 14.
- guideline and policies: Questions 15 and 20.
- training and support: Questions 16-19.
- surveillance, monitoring and evaluation of infection control: Questions 21, and 23-25.
- resources and supplies: Questions 22 and 26.
- supportive or blame culture on infection control at the hospitals Questions 27-31.

HCWs' responses to all questions relating to their perceptions of each of the eight themes described above are presented in Appendix XVIII. The next sections examine HCWs' responses to the questionnaire in detail.

5.2.3.1 Perceptions on Quality of Infection Control Services in the Hospital/Ward

The survey questionnaire contained four questions two of which asked HCWs whether infection control in their ward or hospital is good. The other two questions explored whether

HCWs thought that infection control in their ward and hospital respectively could be better. HCWs' responses to these 4 questions on a 5-point Likert scale are summarised in supplementary table (Appendix XVIII) and in Figure 5.1A and Figure 5.1B below.

Regarding the two questions on whether they thought that infection control in the ward and hospital was good, the majority of HCWs either agreed or strongly agreed with 265 and 272 of the 433 (around 63%) agreeing and 84 and 93 of 433 (some 21.5%) strongly agreeing with the statement that infection control in their ward or hospital was good. On the other hand, 46 and 54 (around 12.4%) HCWs neither agreed nor disagreed, whereas 21 and 27 disagreed and only 1 and 2 HCWs respectively strongly disagreed with the two statements as Figure 5.1A shows:

Figure 5.1A: Perceptions of quality of infection control services in the ward and hospital (Questions 7-8).

It should be noted that even though most respondents thought that infection control in their ward or hospital was good, a large majority (around 60.3%; 251/261 of the 433) agreed and

110/117 of 433 (approximately 20.0%) strongly agreed with the assertion that infection control in their ward or hospital could be better. These results may indicate HCWs' awareness of gaps in implementing recommended IPC practices at the hospitals. Almost an equal number (53 and 55) neither agreed nor disagreed, and very small numbers; 8 and 1 and 2 respectively, disagreed and strongly disagreed that there is a need for improvement as shown below:

Figure 5.1B: Perceptions on whether infection control could be better (Questions 9 -10).

5.2.3.2 Perceptions on Outbreak Preparedness

The questionnaire contained two questions on outbreak preparedness; one asking whether HCWs thought that the ward or department was prepared and, another asking whether they thought the hospital as a whole was prepared for any outbreak of healthcare-associated infections. The results on a 5 Likert score are provided in Figure 5.2 below and summarised in Appendix XVIII. Again, the majority of HCWs 258/433 (60.0%) agreed with the two statements that the

ward/department and the hospital were prepared for any outbreaks, whereas around 14% (62 two and 64 out of the 433) strongly agreed. Similarly, around 14% (69 and 70 of the 433) were neutral (neither agreed or disagreed), whereas a small proportion 8.5% (37 and 35/433) disagreed with 5 and 8 disagreeing strongly that the institutions are prepared for outbreaks as shown below:

Figure 5.2: Perceptions on outbreak preparedness (Questions 11-12).

5.2.3.3 Perceptions on Hospital Leadership and Guidelines on Infection Control

Two questions investigated whether the institutions had in place good infection control leadership. There were also two questions exploring whether there were clear guidelines and policies on infection control. Again, the majority (253 and 257/433; around 59.4%) of HCWs indicated that there was good infection control leadership in their ward/department and hospital, with 75/433 (16.9%) strongly agreeing. Less than 16.2% (70 and 67 out of the 433 participants) were neutral whereas very few HCWs (30) disagreed and even fewer (3 and 5 respectively) strongly disagreed that there is good leadership as shown below in Figure 5.3A:

Leadership in the hospital/ward

Figure 5.3A: Perceptions on good infection control leadership (Questions 13-14).

Regarding infection control guidelines, most of HCWs (268, 270/433; around 62.4%) indicated that their ward/department had a set of guidelines that they were able to access to support IPC practices as shown below in Figure 5.3B and Appendix XV. Nearly a fourth of HCWs (23.6%, 102, 92/433) strongly held this view. A small proportion (41 and 51, around 11.8%) neither agreed nor disagreed, whereas 18 and 41, and 1 and 4 disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively:

Infection control guidelines

Figure 5.3B: Availability of infection control guidelines (Questions 15 and 20).

5.2.3.4 Perceptions on Training and Support

The questionnaire included four questions that investigated whether the hospitals offered sufficient levels of training to support good IPC practice, and explored HCWs' self-confidence or their perception of their competence in carrying out infection control activities. HCWs' competence was explored using Questions 16 and 19 which asked whether the respondents felt that they had received enough training and they were able to provide infection control without further training. On the other hand, the lack of competence was explored through Questions 17 and 18 which asked the respondents whether they felt that they would need further education and training in order to carry out good infection control practices.

The analysis of the results of Questions 16 and 19 indicates that most HCWs (273/433;
174

63.0%) felt that they were offered enough training, but the number was lower for those who agreed that they could provide infection control without further training (178/433; 41.1%). A similar pattern was seen with the number of HCWs who strongly agreed with the two questions (69 and 25) respectively as Figure 5.4A below shows:

I had enough training and feel competent

Figure 5.4A: Perceptions on adequacy of infection control training (Questions 16 and 19).

The lower numbers of HCWs who felt that they could provide infection control without further training in in agreement with the results of the analysis of Questions 17 and 18, where the majority of HCWs (271,278/433; 64.2%) felt that they needed more training in order to provide good infection control practice; with 71 and 76 strongly agreeing with such statements, 60 and 61 were neutral. Moreover, very few HCWs, 21/24 and 1/2 disagreeing and strongly disagreeing with the same, indicating that they believe they do not need further training as shown below in Figure 5.4B:

Need for education

Figure 5.4B: Perceptions on the need for more infection control training (Questions 17 and 18).

5.2.3.5 Perceptions on Surveillance, Monitoring and Evaluation of Infection Control

The survey aimed to understand whether HCWs perceived that there was enough infection control surveillance in the researched hospitals. Surveillance was explored by asking HCWs three questions related to their knowledge as to whether there IPC practice was checked and about their awareness of any IPC surveillance going on in their ward/department or hospital (see Appendix XVIII). Furthermore, good infection control practice was explored by asking the HCWs whether they know of other staff who do not practice good infection control as Figure 5.5A and 5.5B below show.

Regarding surveillance, the results indicate that there is some kind of surveillance going on both the wards and departments of the two hospitals studied here. This is exemplified by having a large number of HCWs (200 and 37) who disagreed or strongly disagreed with the statement that no one checks their infection control practices. This is further supported by having

a large number of HCWs (274, 278) who agreed that they are aware of infection control surveillance in the ward/department and hospital respectively, compared to a small number of HCWs (72 and 23) who agreed or strongly agreed with the statement that nobody checks their infection control practice as shown below in Figure 5.5A:

Figure 5.5A: Perceptions on surveillance of infection control practices (Questions 21, 23 and 24).

On the other hand, the results shows a divided opinion regarding practice, with a third of HCWs (138 and 51) agreeing and strongly agreeing that there are HCWs who do not implement safe infection control practices, and another third (130, 17) disagreeing and strongly disagreeing with this statement, and 97 being neutral as Figure 5.5B shows below:

Practice

Figure 5.5B: Perceptions on good infection control practices in the ward/hospital (Question 25).

5.2.3.6 Perceptions on Supplies and Infection Control Resources

Two questions investigated whether HCWs thought that their hospital or ward/department supplies, and resources were sufficient to enable them to prevent and control infection during care delivery. The adequacy of the supply of gloves was highlighted in one of the questions. Because of their basic and vital nature in infection control, they are the most frequently used and they play a major role in preventing infection.

The majority of HCWs 197/207 out of 433 (around 47.8%) and 34/84 out of 433 disagreed and strongly disagreed with the assertion that the hospital or the ward does not provide enough supplies. However, a few HCWs (63/105) and (16/31) agreed and strongly agreed that the ward or hospital does not provide enough supplies, whereas 66 and 81 were neutral. This suggests that whereas there are supplies, a substantial number of HCWs 121 and 94, (between 21.7% and 30.0%) thought that sometimes these supplies are not adequate:

Supplies and materials

Figure 5.6: Perceptions on supplies and materials (Questions 22 and 26).

5.2.3.7 Perceptions on the Existence of Supportive or Blame Culture on Infection Control

The survey investigated the existence of either supportive or blame culture at the two hospitals, using a set of 4 questions which asked whether nurses or physicians are blamed when there is an infection outbreak or incident in the hospitals, and one question asking whether generally, in these hospitals, staff are supported to improve their IPC practice. The results indicated having a divided opinion regarding blame culture, with 81 to 122 agreeing, and 18 to 38 strongly agreeing that nurses or doctors are blamed when there is an outbreak in the ward/department or hospital. On the other hand, between 124 and 157 disagreed with the statement and 29 and 38 strongly disagreed and between 111 and 148 HCWs were neutral as Figure 5.7A shows below:

Blame culture

Figure 5.7A: Perceptions on the existence of blame culture (Questions 27 to 30).

As for supportive culture, most participants agreed that staff are supported to improve their infection prevention and control practice with 245 agreeing, and 97 strongly agreeing that nurses or doctors are supported to improve their infection prevention and control practice. However, 33 disagreed with the statement and 6 strongly disagreed and 52 HCWs were neutral as Figure 5.7B below shows:

Figure 5.7B: Perceptions on the existence of supportive culture (Question 31).

5.2.4 Factors Associated with Perceptions on Infection Control: The Association Between Demographic Variables and Participants' Perception Scores

The aim of the questionnaire is to understand the factors associated with participants' perceptions of the quality of infection control, leadership, supplies, surveillance and culture at their respective hospitals. The following sections explain the association between demographic variables and HCWs' perception scores.

5.2.4.1 Data and Coding

The outcome variable was HCWs' perceptions on the identified aspects of infection control on a five-point Likert scale; 1=Strongly Agree, 2=Agree, 3=Neither Agree or Disagree, 4=Disagree and 5=Strongly disagreed. As this is ordinal data, due to the nature of the question,

the important ranks of the ordered data were whether they agreed, disagreed or were neutral. For this reason, HCWs' answers on the five Likert scale could be binned to a nominal scale where 1=Agree or Strongly Agree, 2=Neither Agree or Disagree (Neutral) and 3=Disagree or Strongly Disagree. As some of the questions were negative, this ranking was reversed for these questions. Details of the coding and its binning codes are presented in Table 5.2 below.

The predictor variables (independent variables) included age, sex, education, profession, nationality and hospital of the survey. A full description of these variables is presented in Table 5.1 (see section 5.2.2). The coding that was used for binary variables such as gender is provided in Table 5.2. As some of the predictor categorical variables were not binary, they could be binned to either binary or what was thought to be the most sensible way to present this data. For example, due to distinct cultural differences between KSA and other countries, responses were expected to differ only if a participant is a Saudi or not. Therefore, the nationality variable was binned to 1=Saudi and 2=Non-Saudi.

Several research studies have shown that education only matters if one contrasts secondary vs. university and undergraduate vs. postgraduate. For this reason, the education variable was binned to 1=undergraduate and 2=postgraduate. There were not any HCWs with no university education. Therefore, coding was restricted to these two choices. Details of the coding for all the categorical predictor variables are provided in Table 5.2 below:

Table 5.2 Codes for the dependent and independent variables

Variable	SurveyMonkey response options	SPSS response option 1	SPSS response option 2
1-Profession	X3 1-Nurse-unlic 2-Nurse-lic 3-Physician	X2 1-Nurse (1, 2) 2-Physician (3)	
2-Gender	X2 1-Male 2-Female	X2 Male Female	
3-Age	X3 1-(20-34) 2-(35-49) 3-(50+)	X2 1-(20-34) 2-(35+)	
4-Academic	X5 1-Diploma 2-Bachelor 3-Master 4-Borad 5-PhD	X2 1-Graduate (1,2,3) 2-Post-graduate (3,4,5)	
5-Nationality	X11 Open text (generatedx11 nationalities)	X2 1-Saudi 2-Non-Saudi	
6-Place of work	X2 1-KFSH 2-BCH	X2 Hospital 1=KFSH Hospital 2=BCH	Traditional hospital
7-(direction)	Mixed	1=positive 1=strongly agree Change of direction	*Identify those questions where the positive is (Q7, 8, 11-16, 19, 23-31) *Turn around (Reversing negatively) (Q 9, 10, 17, 18, 21)
8-(scale)	X5Likert scale 1-Strongly agree 2-Agree 3-Neither 4-Disagree 5-Strongly disagree	X3 1-Agree 2-Neither 3-Disagree	

5.2.4.2 Statistical Analysis

The association between the outcome or dependent variable (perception score on the 3 nominal scores; 1=Agree, 2=Neither and 3=Disagree) and the predictor or independent variables such as age, sex, education, profession, nationality and hospital were assessed at two levels. Firstly, the Chi-square test was employed for a univariate analysis and significance at $p < 0.05$. The chi-square

test was chosen as it measures any difference between observed and predicted values. As this study is one of the few surveys in KSA, there are no reliable posterior distributions on these opinions. Therefore, the use of expected values would more likely yield unbiased estimates about where the true values lie. Secondly, variables that were significant in the univariate analysis were further explored using Multinomial Logistic regression, in a multivariate analysis. The association was measured using relative risk ratios (RRR) at significance cut-off value of $p < 0.05$. For the outcome value, Disagree (3) was used as the baseline.

5.2.4.3. Factors associated with perceptions of quality of infection control

The association between an aggregated HCW's perception score for the two questions as to whether the quality of infection control is good, and the six independent demographic variables was undertaken. The results of the univariate analysis indicate that profession, education, gender and nationality were independent predictors of HCWs' perceptions about the quality of infection control at their respective hospitals (Table 5.3A-1). Specifically, 83.56% (249/298) nurses thought that infection control in their department or hospital was good compared to 63.7% (86/135) of doctors (Chi-square 27.0133, $p < 0.0001$). On the other hand, 80.75% (281/348) of undergraduates thought it was good compared to 63.53% (54/85) postgraduates (Chi-square 16.2954, $p < 0.0001$). Similar results were observed for gender and nationality as Table 5.3A-1 below shows. There was no significant difference in perception by age group or HCWs' workplace/hospital.

In a multivariate analysis, only profession and nationality remain significant factors; Specifically, nurses were more likely to agree (than to disagree) that the quality of infection control in their ward or hospital was good than doctors relative risk ratio (RRR): 0.3115, $p = 0.049$ (Table 5.3A-1). Similarly, Saudis were more likely to perceive that the quality of infection control in their ward or hospital was better than non-Saudis (RRR: 3.44, $p = 0.006$). For both variables, the relative risk of nurses vs. doctors to remain neutral than to disagree and the relative risk of Saudis vs. non-Saudis to remain neutral than to disagree were not statistically significant

(RRR: 0.615, p=0.447, and RRR: 1.0403, p=0.935):

Table 5.3A-1: Demographic factors associated with perception of overall quality of infection control services in the hospital or ward

Perceptions about Quality of Infection Control (Good)							
		1	2	3		Univariate	Multivariate
	Profession	Agree	Neither	Disagree	Total	Chi-Square (p value)	RRR (p value)
1	Nurse	249	41	8	298	27.0133	Neither 0.615
	%	83.56	13.76	2.68	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.447)
2	Doctor	86	31	18	135		Agree 0.3115
	%	63.7	22.96	13.33	100		(0.049*)
	Total	335	72	26	433		
	%	77.37	16.63	6.00	100		
	Age						
1	20-34	218	51	18	287	0.987	NA
2	%	75.96	17.77	6.27	100	(0.61)	
	35+	117	21	8	146		
	%	80.14	14.38	5.48	100		
	Total	335	72	26	433		
	%	77.37	16.63	6	100		
	Gender						
1	Male	82	23	16	121	17.1442	Neither 2.330
	%	67.77	19.01	13.22	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.158)
2	Female	253	49	10	312		Agree 1.256
	%	81.09	15.71	3.21	100		(0.677)
	Total	335	72	26	433		
	%	77.37	16.63	6.00	100		
	Education						
1,2	Graduate	281	53	14	348	16.2954	Neither 0.8002
	%	80.75	15.23	4.02	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.700)
3,4,5	Post-graduate	54	19	12	85		Agree 0.5322
	%	63.53	22.35	14.12	100		(0.227)
	Total	335	72	26	433		
	%	77.37	16.63	6.00	100		
	Nationality						
1	Saudi	66	32	14	112	30.214	Neither 1.0403
	%	58.93	28.57	12.5	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.935)
2	Non-Saudi	269	40	12	321		Agree 3.44
	%	83.8	12.46	3.74	100		(0.006*)
	Total	335	72	26	433		

	%	77.37	16.63	6.00	100		
	Hospital						
	HOSPITAL 1	206	48	15	269	0.9052	NA
	%	76.58	17.84	5.58	100	(0.636)	
	HOSPITAL 2	129	24	11	164		
	%	78.66	14.63	6.71	100		
	Total	335	72	26	433		
	%	77.37	16.63	6.00	100		

Note: Results of the analysis of responses to Question 7. Infection control in this ward/department is good, and Question 8. Infection prevention and control in this hospital is good.

Two of the questions on IPC quality respectively asked whether HCWs thought that IPC in their ward/department could be better and whether IPC in their hospital could be better. The results of the analysis of the responses to these two questions is provided in Table 5.2A-2 below. The majority of HCWs (i.e., between 87.36% and 92.47%) agreed with the statement that infection control in their ward or department could be better, but this finding did not differ by any of the six demographic variables, i.e., by profession, education, age, gender, nationality or hospital, therefore no multivariate analysis was conducted:

Table 5.3A-2: Demographic factors associated with perception of overall quality of infection control services in the hospital or ward

Perceptions about Quality of Infection Control (Could be better)							
		1	2	3		Univariate	Multivariate
	Profession	Agree	Neither	Disagree	Total	Chi-Square (p value)	RRR (p value)
1	Nurse	267	26	5	298	0.763	NA
	%	89.6	8.72	1.68	100	(0.683)	
2	Doctor	119	12	4	135		
	%	88.15	8.89	2.96	100		
	Total	386	38	9	433		
	%	89.15	8.78	2.08	100		
	Age						
1	20-34	251	30	6	287	3.0006	NA
2	%	87.46	10.45	2.09	100	(0.223)	
	35+	135	8	3	146		

	%	92.47	5.48	2.05	100		
	Total	386	38	9	433		
	%	89.15	8.78	2.08	100		
	Gender						
1	Male	109	8	4	121	2.1298	NA
	%	90.08	6.61	3.31	100	(0.345)	
2	Female	277	30	5	312		
	%	88.78	9.62	1.6	100		
	Total	386	38	9	433		
	%	89.15	8.78	2.08	100		
	Education						
1,2	Graduate	311	32	5	348	3.8776	NA
	%	89.37	9.2	1.44	100	(0.144)	
3,4,5	Post-graduate	75	6	4	85		
	%	88.24	7.06	4.71	100		
	Total	386	38	9	433		
	%	89.15	8.78	2.08	100		
	Nationality						
1	Saudi	101	9	2	112	0.1747	NA
	%	90.18	8.04	1.79	100	(0.916)	
2	Non-Saudi	285	29	7	321		
	%	88.79	9.03	2.18	100		
	Total	386	38	9	433		
	%	89.15	8.78	2.08	100		
	Hospital						
	HOSPITAL 1	235	27	7	269	2.4782	NA
	%	87.36	10.04	2.6	100	(0.29)	
	HOSPITAL 2	151	11	2	164		
	%	92.07	6.71	1.22	100		
	Total	386	38	9	433		
	%	89.15	8.78	2.08	100		

Note: Results of the analysis of responses to Question 9. Infection prevention and control in this ward/department could be better, and Question 10. Infection prevention and control in this hospital could be better. NA = Not applicable.

5.2.4.4 Factors Associated with Perceptions About Preparedness for Outbreak

Regarding the factors affecting whether HCWs think that their hospital and ward/department are prepared enough for any incidences of outbreaks of healthcare-associated infections, in a univariate analysis, profession, education, gender and nationality were significant

factors, whereas age and hospital were not. Nurses were more likely to have a positive perception, with 249/298 (83.56%) of them agreeing with this statement compared to 85/135 (62.96%) of the doctors (Chi-square, 22.3524, $p < 0.0001$) – as shown below in Table 5.3B. Similarly, more females thought that they were prepared than males (80.77% vs. 67.77%; Chi-square 8.3781, $p = 0.015$); also, more undergraduates (81.9%) and non-Saudis (82.24%) agreed with this statement compared to postgraduates (57.65%) and Saudis (62.5%) (Chi-square 23.8149, $p < 0.0001$ and Chi-square 19.5123, $p < 0.0001$, respectively). However, there were no differences by age or hospital.

In a multinomial multivariate logistic regression model, only education and nationality remained significant. Healthcare workers with undergraduate education were more likely agree (than to disagree) with the statement that they were prepared for any outbreak than those with postgraduate education (RRR: 0.2681, $p = 0.003$). On the other hand, non-Saudis were more likely to agree that they were prepared for an outbreak than Saudis (RR: 3.489, $p < 0.000$). For these variables, there was no statistically significant difference between disagreeing and being neutral:

Table 5.3B: Demographic factors associated with perception of hospital or ward preparedness for outbreaks

Perceptions about Preparedness for Outbreak							
		1	2	3		Univariate	Multivariate
	Profession	Agree	Neither	Disagree	Total	Chi-Square (p value)	RRR (p value)
1	Nurse	249	27	22	298	22.3524	Neither 1.4336
	%	83.56	9.06	7.38	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.521)
2	Doctor	85	28	22	135		Agree 0.6129
	%	62.96	20.74	16.3	100		(0.294)
	Total	334	55	44	433		
	%	77.14	12.7	10.16	100		
	Age						
1	20-34	224	33	30	287	1.1341	NA
2	%	78.05	11.5	10.45	100	(0.567)	
	35+	110	22	14	146		
	%	75.34	15.07	9.59	100		
	Total	334	55	44	433		
	%	77.14	12.7	10.16	100		

	Gender						
1	Male	82	22	17	121	8.3781	Neither 0.7329
	%	67.77	18.18	14.05	100	(0.015*)	(0.566)
2	Female	252	33	27	312		Agree 0.5287
	%	80.77	10.58	8.65	100		(0.162)
	Total	334	55	44	433		
	%	77.14	12.7	10.16	100		
	Education						
1,2	Graduate	285	37	26	348	23.8149	Neither 0.5007
	%	81.9	10.63	7.47	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.195)
3,4,5	Post-graduate	49	18	18	85		Agree 0.2681
	%	57.65	21.18	21.18	100		(0.003*)
	Total	334	55	44	433		
	%	77.14	12.7	10.16	100		
	Nationality						
1	Saudi	70	21	21	112	19.5123	Neither 1.6961
	%	62.5	18.75	18.75	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.225)
2	Non-Saudi	264	34	23	321		Agree 3.489
	%	82.24	10.59	7.17	100		(<0.000*)
	Total	334	55	44	433		
	%	77.14	12.7	10.16	100		
	Hospital						
	HOSPITAL 1	203	36	30	269	1.2025	NA
	%	75.46	13.38	11.15	100	(0.548)	
	HOSPITAL 2	131	19	14	164		
	%	79.88	11.59	8.54	100		
	Total	334	55	44	433		
	%	77.14	12.7	10.16	100		

Note: Results of the analysis of responses to Question 11. This ward/department is prepared in the event of an infection control outbreak/ incident, and Question 12. This hospital is prepared in the event of an infection control outbreak/ incident. NA = Not applicable.

5.2.4.5 Perceptions About the Quality or Existence of Infection Control Leadership,

Guidelines and Policy

The results of the analysis conducted to investigate the demographic factors influencing HCWs' perceptions of the quality of infection leadership and guidelines in their hospital or ward

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are presented below in Table 5.3C-1 and Table 5.3C-2. The results of a univariate analysis indicated that profession, gender, education and nationality significantly influenced participants' perceptions on leadership and effectiveness of guidelines, whereas age and hospital did not. Specifically, more nurses agreed that the leadership in their ward or hospital was good (262/298;87.92%) compared to 89/135 (65.93%) of doctors, while the corresponding percentages were 93.96% vs. 75.56% for guidelines and this was statistically significant (Chi-square 34.288, $p<0.0001$; and Chi-square 40.0964, $p<0.0001$, respectively). More females 263 (84.29%) than males 88 (72.73%) agreed that there was good leadership and 285 (91.35%) of females and 97 (80.17%) of males agreed that there were good guidelines (Chi-square 10.9472, $p=0.004$, and Chi-square 10.5585, $p=0.005$) respectively.

Similarly, a majority (294/348: 84.48%) of those with an undergraduate degree agreed, compared to 57/85 (67.06%) of those with a post-graduate degree for perceptions on leadership, with the percentages being 91.38% vs. 75.29% for guidelines (Chi-square 21.3574, $p<0.0001$; and Chi-square 17.3149, $p<0.0001$, respectively). Furthermore, a larger proportion (277/321; 86.29%) of non-Saudis than Saudis (74/112; 66.07%) thought leadership was good, and the corresponding percentages were 93.15% vs. 74.11% for guidelines (Chi-square 27.0459, $p<0.0001$; Chi-square 30.1015, $p<0.0001$, respectively) as shown below in Table 5.2C-1 and Table 5.3C-2.

In the multivariate model profession, education and nationality were significant factors for a positive perception on leadership (RRR: 0.2362, $p=0.003$, RRR: 0.404, $p=0.045$ and RRR: 4.367, $p<0.0001$). On the other hand, profession, gender and nationality were factors for agreeing on availability of guidelines (RRR: 0.0375, $p<0.0001$, RRR: 0.2975, $p=0.029$ and RRR: 4.4368, $p=0.005$) as shown below in Table 5.3C-2.

Table 5.3C-1: Demographic factors associated with perception about the quality of infection control leadership

Perceptions about quality of infection control leadership							
		1	2	3		Univariate	Multivariate
	Profession	Agree	Neither	Disagree	Total	Chi-Square (p value)	RRR (p value)
1	Nurse	262	24	12	298	34.288	Neither 0.7327
	%	87.92	8.05	4.03	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.603)
2	Doctor	89	20	26	135		Agree 0.2362
	%	65.93	14.81	19.26	100		(0.003*)
	Total	351	44	38	433		
	%	81.06	10.16	8.78	100		
	Age						
1	20-34	227	33	27	287	2.2902	NA
	%	79.09	11.5	9.41	100	(0.318)	
2	35+	124	11	11	146		
	%	84.93	7.53	7.53	100		
	Total	351	44	38	433		
	%	81.06	10.16	8.78	100		
	Gender						
1	Male	88	14	19	121	10.9472	Neither 0.9959
	%	72.73	11.57	15.7	100	(0.004*)	(0.994)
2	Female	263	30	19	312		Agree 0.5445
	%	84.29	9.62	6.09	100		(0.187)
	Total	351	44	38	433		
	%	81.06	10.16	8.78	100		
	Education						
1,2	Graduate	294	34	20	348	21.3574	Neither 0.3879
	%	84.48	9.77	5.75	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.105)
3,4,5	Post-graduate	57	10	18	85		Agree 0.4044
	%	67.06	11.76	21.18	100		(0.045*)
	Total	351	44	38	433		
	%	81.06	10.16	8.78	100		
	Nationality						
1	Saudi	74	16	22	112	27.0459	Neither 2.2125
	%	66.07	14.29	19.64	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.101)
2	Non-Saudi	277	28	16	321		Agree 4.3666
	%	86.29	8.72	4.98	100		(<0.0001*)
	Total	351	44	38	433		
	%	81.06	10.16	8.78	100		
	Hospital						
	HOSPITAL 1	221	27	21	269	0.876	NA
	%	82.16	10.04	7.81	100	(0.645)	
	HOSPITAL 2	130	17	17	164		

	%	79.27	10.37	10.37	100		
	Total	351	44	38	433		
	%	81.06	10.16	8.78	100		

Note: Results of the analysis of responses to Question 13. There is good infection prevention and control leadership within the ward/ department, and Question 14. There is good infection prevention and control leadership within the hospital. NA = Not applicable

Table 5.3C-2: Demographic factors associated with perception about the existence or quality of infection control guidelines and policy

Perceptions about quality of infection control Guidelines							
	Total	1	2	3		Univariate	Multivariate
	Profession	Agree	Neither	Disagree	Total	Chi-Square (p value)	RRR (p value)
1	Nurse	280	16	2	298	40.0964	Neither 0.0431
	%	93.96	5.37	0.67	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.001*)
2	Doctor	102	15	18	135		Agree 0.0375
	%	75.56	11.11	13.33	100		(<0.0001*)
		382	31	20	433		
	%	88.22	7.16	4.62	100		
	Age						
1	20-34	251	21	15	287	0.7663	NA
	%	87.46	7.32	5.23	100	(0.682)	
2	35+	131	10	5	146		
	%	89.73	6.85	3.42	100		
	Total	382	31	20	433		
	%	88.22	7.16	4.62	100		
	Gender						
1	Male	97	15	9	121	10.5585	Neither 0.2632
	%	80.17	12.4	7.44	100	(0.005*)	(0.061)
2	Female	285	16	11	312		Agree 0.2975
	%	91.35	5.13	3.53	100		(0.029*)
	Total	382	31	20	433		
	%	88.22	7.16	4.62	100		
	Education						
1,2	Graduate	318	19	11	348	17.3149	Neither 1.5215
	%	91.38	5.46	3.16	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.554)
3,4,5	Post-graduate	64	12	9	85		Agree 0.6158
	%	75.29	14.12	10.59	100		(0.390)
	Total	382	31	20	433		
	%	88.22	7.16	4.62	100		
	Nationality						
1	Saudi	83	16	13	112	30.1015	Neither 1.3073

	%	74.11	14.29	11.61	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.674)
2	Non-Saudi	299	15	7	321		Agree 4.4368
	%	93.15	4.67	2.18	100		(0.005*)
	Total	382	31	20	433		
	%	88.22	7.16	4.62	100		
	Hospital						
	HOSPITAL 1	239	17	13	269	0.8012	NA
	%	88.85	6.32	4.83	100	(0.67)	
	HOSPITAL 2	143	14	7	164		
	%	87.2	8.54	4.27	100		
	Total	382	31	20	433		
	%	88.22	7.16	4.62	100		

Note: Results of the analysis of responses to Question 15. The ward/ department has a set of guidelines that I can access to support my infection prevention and control practices, and Question 20. The hospital has a set of guidelines that I can access to support my infection prevention and control practices. NA = Not applicable

5.2.4.6 Factors Associated with Perceived Competence and Training Needs

The results of the analysis of participants' responses regarding the factors associated with the two positive perceptions on adequacy of training are provided below in Table 5.3D-1, whereas those for the two negative perceptions of competency and need for more training are provided below in Table 5.3D-2. In the univariate analysis, nationality and hospital were significant predictors of HCWs' perceptions of whether the training they received was adequate, with between 16% and 27% perceiving that the training was adequate (Chi-square 6.75, $p=0.034$ and Chi-square 7.7044, $p=0.021$) as Table 5.3D-1 shows.

On the other hand, the overwhelming need for more training was felt equally across the six demographic factors, with between 83% and 89% indicating that they needed more training, i.e. there were no significant differences by gender or education, for example, on agreeing for the need of further training (Table 5.3D-2). In a multivariate multinomial logistic analysis, non-Saudi nationals were more likely to perceive that they were being offered adequate training on infection control than Saudis (RRR: 2.7941, $p=0.013$). Healthcare workers at Hospital 1 were more likely to agree that they were having adequate training than those of Hospital 2 (RRR: 0.3967, 0.017) as Table 5.3D-2 below shows:

Table 5.3D-1: Demographic factors associated with perception of adequacy of training and support needs

Perceptions about adequacy of training and support needs							
		1	2	3		Univariate	Multivariate
	Profession	Agree	Neither	Disagree	Total	Chi-Square (p value)	RRR (p value)
1	Nurse	72	199	27	298	0.2246	NA
	%	24.16	66.78	9.06	100	(0.894)	
2	Doctor	31	90	14	135		
	%	22.96	66.67	10.37	100		
	Total	103	289	41	433		
	%	23.79	66.74	9.47	100		
	Age						
1	20-34	68	191	28	287	0.0821	NA
	%	23.69	66.55	9.76	100	(0.96)	
2	35+	35	98	13	146		
	%	23.97	67.12	8.9	100		
	Total	103	289	41	433		
	%	23.79	66.74	9.47	100		
	Gender						
1	Male	25	81	15	121	2.2113	NA
	%	20.66	66.94	12.4	100	(0.331)	
2	Female	78	208	26	312		
	%	25.00	66.67	8.33	100		
	Total	103	289	41	433		
	%	23.79	66.74	9.47	100		
	Education						
1,2	Graduate	83	233	32	348	0.1547	NA
	%	23.85	66.95	9.2	100	(0.926)	
3,4,5	Post-graduate	20	56	9	85		
	%	23.53	65.88	10.59	100		
	Total	103	289	41	433		
	%	23.79	66.74	9.47	100		
	Nationality						
1	Saudi	19	77	16	112	6.75	Neither 1.7533
	%	16.96	68.75	14.29		(0.034*)	(0.106)
2	Non-Saudi	84	212	25	321		Agree 2.7941
	%	26.17	66.04	7.79			(0.013*)
	Total	103	289	41			
	%	23.79	66.74	9.47			
	Hospital						

	HOSPITAL 1	75	173	21	269	7.7044	Neither 0.7091
	%	27.88	64.31	7.81	100	(0.021*)	(0.306)
	HOSPITAL 2	28	116	20	164		Agree 0.3967
	%	17.07	70.73	12.2	100		(0.017*)
	Total	103	289	41	433		
	%	23.79	66.74	9.47	100		

Note: Results of the analysis of responses to Question 16: I am offered sufficient levels of training to support good IPC practice; and Question 19: I can provide good IPC without the need for further education. NA = Not applicable.

Table 5.3D-2: Demographic factors associated with perception of inadequacy of training and support needs

Perceptions about inadequacy of training and support needs							
		1	2	3		Univariate	Multivariate
	Profession	Agree	Neither	Disagree	Total	Chi-Square (p value)	RRR (p value)
1	Nurse	256	26	16	298	0.4649	NA
	%	85.91	8.72	5.37	100	(0.793)	
2	Doctor	116	10	9	135		
	%	85.93	7.41	6.67	100		
	Total	372	36	25	433		
	%	85.91	8.31	5.77	100		
	Age						
1	20-34	248	25	14	287	1.3683	NA
	%	86.41	8.71	4.88	100	(0.505)	
2	35+	124	11	11	146		
	%	84.93	7.53	7.53	100		
	Total	372	36	25	433		
	%	85.91	8.31	5.77	100		
	Gender						
1	Male	108	8	5	121	1.5877	NA
	%	89.26	6.61	4.13	100	(0.452)	
2	Female	264	28	20	312		
	%	84.62	8.97	6.41	100		
	Total	372	36	25	433		
	%	85.91	8.31	5.77	100		
	Education						
1,2	Graduate	299	27	22	348	1.5805	NA
	%	85.92	7.76	6.32	100	(0.454)	
3,4,5	Post-graduate	73	9	3	85		
	%	85.88	10.59	3.53	100		

	Total	372	36	25	433		
	%	85.91	8.31	5.77	100		
	Nationality						
1	Saudi	97	10	5	112	0.5257	NA
	%	86.61	8.93	4.46	100	(0.769)	
2	Non-Saudi	275	26	20	321		
	%	85.67	8.1	6.23	100		
	Total	372	36	25	433		
	%	85.91	8.31	5.77	100		
	Hospital						
	HOSPITAL 1	235	18	16	269	2.46	NA
	%	87.36	6.69	5.95	100	(0.292)	
	HOSPITAL 2	137	18	9	164		
	%	83.54	10.98	5.49	100		
	Total	372	36	25	433		
	%	85.91	8.31	5.77	100		

Note: Results of the analysis of responses to Question 17: I need more education and training to support good IPC practice; and Question 18: I feel the need to attend the education and training sessions provided to me. NA = Not applicable.

5.2.4.7 Factors Associated with Perceptions on Adequacy of Infection Control Surveillance

We explored the factors associated with HCWs' scores to the three questions which asked whether they knew of any ongoing surveillance or whether anybody checks their compliance. In univariate analysis, the five factors profession, gender, education, nationality and hospital were significant predictors of HCWs' perceptions on the adequacy of surveillance in their hospital or ward. Nurses were more likely to be aware of ongoing surveillance in the ward or hospital (61.74%; 184/298), compared to doctors (31.85%; 43/135) (Chi-square 45.4814, $p < 0.0001$). Similar results were indicated for female gender, having an undergraduate degree and being a foreigner and hospital type as shown below in Table 5.3E.

In a multivariate multinomial logistic regression, only three factors remained significant and these were profession, nationality and hospital. Nurses were more likely to agree that either somebody checks their infection control practice, or they are always aware of surveillance going on in their ward department or hospital than doctors (RRR: 0.3370, 0.005). However, it is also

important to note that they were also more likely to be neutral than disagree (RRR: 0.4231, $p=0.033$). Regarding nationality, a higher proportion of non-Saudis (61.37%; 197/321) agreed with the above-mentioned statement than Saudis (26.79%; 30/112) and this was statistically significant (RRR: 3.9073, 0.0001). Furthermore, HCWs from both hospitals were more likely to agree or were neutral with the above statements than disagree (RRR: 2.274, $p=0.007$ and RRR: 1.7800, $p=0.044$), respectively.

As for practice, profession and nationality were significant factors for either being neutral or agreeing with the statement that there are staff who do not practice good infection prevention and control. Specifically, for professionals the relative risks of for neutral and agreeing were RRR: 0.1768, $p<0.0001$ and RRR 0.1841, $p=0.001$, whereas for nationality, they were RRR: 2.5956, $p=0.012$ and RRR: 7.886, $p<0.0001$.

Table 5.3E: Demographic factors associated with perception of existence of surveillance and monitoring

Perceptions about surveillance and monitoring							
Code	Profession	1 Agree	2 Neither	3 Disagree	Total	Univariate Chi-Square (p value)	Multivariate RRR (p value)
1	Nurse	184	73	41	298	45.4814	Neither 0.4231
	%	61.74	24.5	13.76	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.033*)
2	Doctor	43	38	54	135		Agree 0.3370
	%	31.85	28.15	40.0	100		(0.005*)
	Total	227	111	95	433		
	%	52.42	25.64	21.94	100		
	Age						
1	20-34	160	70	57	287	3.986	NA
	%	55.75	24.39	19.86	100	(0.136)	
2	35+	67	41	38	146		
	%	45.89	28.08	26.03	100		
	Total	227	111	95	433		
	%	52.42	25.64	21.94	100		
	Gender						
1	Male	38	39	44	121	32.9265	Neither 0.7494
	%	31.4	32.23	36.36	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.459)
2	Female	189	72	51	312		Agree 1.0712
	%	60.58	23.08	16.35	100		(0.857)

	Total	227	111	95	433		
	%	52.42	25.64	21.94	100		
	Education						
1,2	Graduate	201	87	60	348	27.7366	Neither 0.7101
	%	57.76	25	17.24	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.386)
3,4,5	Post-graduate	26	24	35	85		Agree 0.4809
	%	30.59	28.24	41.18	100		(0.060)
	Total	227	111	95	433		
	%	52.42	25.64	21.94	100		
	Nationality						
1	Saudi	30	40	42	112	41.6031	Neither 1.2620
	%	26.79	35.71	37.5	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.459)
2	Non-Saudi	197	71	53	321		Agree 3.9073
	%	61.37	22.12	16.51	100		(<0.0001*)
	Total	227	111	95	433		
	%	52.42	25.64	21.94	100		
	Hospital						
1	HOSPITAL 1	141	59	69	269	8.2541	Neither 2.274
	%	52.42	21.93	25.65	100	(0.016*)	(0.007*)
2	HOSPITAL 2	86	52	26	164		Agree 1.7800
	%	52.44	31.71	15.85	100		(0.044*)
	Total	227	111	95	433		
	%	52.42	25.64	21.94	100		

Note: Results of the analysis of responses to Question 21: No one checks on my infection prevention and control practice, Question 23: I am always aware of the IPC surveillance going on in the ward/ department; and Question 24: I am always aware of the IPC surveillance going on in the hospital. NA = Not applicable.

5.2.4.8 Factors Associated with Perceptions on Adequacy of Infection Control Supplies

Regarding the factors associated with HCWs' perceptions on the adequacy of supplies, the univariate model showed that age, nationality and hospital were significant factors. Specifically, 68.4% (184/269) of HCWs from Hospital 1 felt that their ward/ department does not provide sufficient resources to enable them to prevent and control infection during care delivery compared to only 52.44% (86/164) for Hospital 2 (Chi-square 20.996, $p < 0.0001$) (Table 5.3F). On the other hand, the majority of non-Saudis (69.16%; 222/321) felt that there were not enough supplies, compared to Saudis (42.86%; 48/112), and these differences were statistically

significant (Chi-square 32.786, $p < 0.0001$). A larger proportion of older individuals (≥ 35 years old—72.6%; 106/146) felt that supplies were inadequate, compared to 57.14% (164/287) of younger healthcare workers (Chi-square 9.9269, $p = 0.007$).

The three factors age, nationality and hospital remained significant in a multinomial logistic regression as Table 5.3F below show. Younger HCWs were more likely to agree that supplies were adequate than older ones (RRR: 0.4782, $p = 0.048$). Non-Saudis were more likely to agree or were neutral, that supplies were inadequate than Saudis (RRR: 10.2107, $p < 0.0001$, and RRR: 2.1784, $p = 0.023$), and participants working at Hospital 1 were more likely to agree or were neutral with the statement that supplies were inadequate than those working at Hospital 2 (RRR: 2.0442, $p = 0.078$, and RRR: 3.005, $p = 0.004$):

Table 5.3F: Demographic factors associated with perception of adequacy of supplies and resources

		Supplies					
		1	2	3	Total	Univariate	Multivariate
	Profession	Agree	Neither	Disagree		Chi-Square (p value)	RRR (p value)
1	Nurse	182	43	73	298	2.5386	NA
	%	61.07	14.43	24.5	100	(0.281)	
2	Doctor	88	23	24	135		
	%	65.19	17.04	17.78	100		
	Total	270	66	97	433		
	%	62.36	15.24	22.4	100		
	Age						
1	20-34	164	49	74	287	9.9269	Neither 0.7654
	%	57.14	17.07	25.78	100	(0.007*)	(0.451)
2	35+	106	17	23	146		Agree 0.4782
	%	72.6	11.64	15.75	100		(0.048*)
	Total	270	66	97	433		
	%	62.36	15.24	22.4	100		
	Gender						
1	Male	72	17	32	121	1.6019	NA
	%	59.5	14.05	26.45	100	(0.449)	
2	Female	198	49	65	312		
	%	63.46	15.71	20.83	100		
	Total	270	66	97	433		

	%	62.36	15.24	22.4	100		
	Education						
1,2	Graduate	218	48	82	348	3.5342	NA
	%	62.64	13.79	23.56	100	(0.171)	
3,4,5	Post-graduate	52	18	15	85		
	%	61.18	21.18	17.65	100		
	Total	270	66	97	433		
	%	62.36	15.24	22.4	100		
	Nationality						
1	Saudi	48	18	46	112	32.786	Neither 2.1784
	%	42.86	16.07	41.07	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.023*)
2	Non-Saudi	222	48	51	321		Agree 10.2107
	%	69.16	14.95	15.89	100		(< 0.0001*)
	Total	270	66	97	433		
	%	62.36	15.24	22.4	100		
	Hospital						
	HOSPITAL 1	184	44	41	269	20.996	Neither 3.005
	%	68.4	16.36	15.24	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.004*)
	HOSPITAL 2	86	22	56	164		Agree 2.0442
	%	52.44	13.41	34.15	100		(0.078*)
	Total	270	66	97	433		
	%	62.36	15.24	22.4	100		

Note: Results of the analysis of responses to Question 22: The ward/ department does not provide sufficient resources to enable me to prevent and control infection during care delivery; and Question 26: There are never any gloves when you need them. NA = Not applicable.

5.2.4.9 Factors Associated with Perceptions about Existence of Supportive or Blame Culture on Infection Control at the Ward or Hospitals

The survey included four questions that enquired whether HCWs felt that there was a blame culture in their hospitals when something regarding infection control goes wrong. A univariate analysis investigating the factors associated with a negative perception (i.e. that there was a blame culture) included age and nationality. Foreign workers were more likely to perceive that there was a blame culture in their hospital or ward (49.22%; 158/321) than Saudis (29.46; 33/112) (Chi-square 23.2702, $p < 0.0001$) as shown below in Table 5.3G.

Similarly, young HCWs were more likely to agree with this statement (Chi-square

6.0469, p=0.049) as Table 5.3G below presents. However, in a multinomial logistic regression, only nationality remained significant, suggesting that HCWs of foreign origin felt they were more likely to be blamed if something goes wrong (RRR: 2.9323, p<0.0001). The data also indicates that a significant number of them chose to be neutral than to disagree with the statement that there was a blame culture (RRR: 2.2970, p=0.008).

Table 5.3G: Demographic factors associated with perception of existence of blame culture

Perceptions about existence of blame culture							
	Profession	1 Agree	2 Neither	3 Disagree	Total	Univariate Chi-Square (p value)	Multivariate RRR (p value)
1	Nurse	136	57	105	298	1.0322	NA
	%	45.64	19.13	35.23	100	(0.597)	
2	Doctor	55	30	50	135		
	%	40.74	22.22	37.04	100		
	Total	191	87	155	433		
	%	44.11	20.09	35.8	100		
	Age						
1	20-34	121	52	114	287	6.0469	Neither 1.6815
	%	42.16	18.12	39.72	100	(0.049*)	(0.074)
2	35+	70	35	41	146		Agree 1.4441
	%	47.95	23.97	28.08	100		(0.132)
	Total	191	87	155	433		
	%	44.11	20.09	35.8	100		
	Gender						
1	Male	46	26	49	121	2.6125	NA
	%	38.02	21.49	40.5	100	(0.271)	
2	Female	145	61	106	312		
	%	46.47	19.55	33.97	100		
	Total	191	87	155	433		
	%	44.11	20.09	35.8	100		
	Education						
1,2	Graduate	154	69	125	348	0.0774	NA
	%	44.25	19.83	35.92	100	(0.962)	
3,4,5	Post-graduate	37	18	30	85		
	%	43.53	21.18	35.29	100		
	Total	191	87	155	433		
	%	44.11	20.09	35.8	100		
	Nationality						
1	Saudi	33	18	61	112	23.2702	Neither 2.2970
	%	29.46	16.07	54.46	100	(<0.0001*)	(0.008*)
2	Non-Saudi	158	69	94	321		Agree 2.9323
	%	49.22	21.5	29.28	100		(<0.0001*)
	Total	191	87	155	433		
	%	44.11	20.09	35.8	100		
	Hospital						
	HOSPITAL 1	128	52	89	269	3.6053	NA

	%	47.58	19.33	33.09	100	(0.165)	
	HOSPITAL 2	63	35	66	164		
	%	38.41	21.34	40.24	100		
	Total	191	87	155	433		
	%	44.11	20.09	35.8	100		

Note: Results of the analysis of responses to the four questions: 27. Nursing staff are blamed if there is an outbreak in the ward/ department. 28. Nursing staff are blamed if there is an outbreak in the hospital. 29. Physicians are blamed if there is an outbreak in the ward/ department. 30. Physicians are blamed if there is an outbreak in the hospital. NA = Not applicable.

5.2.5 Summary of the Findings of the Quantitative Survey

The results of the survey show HCWs' positive perceptions where the majority 61.2% (265/433) to 63.0% (272/433) indicated that infection control in their ward/department or hospital was good, preparedness for outbreaks was good (60.0%; 258/433), and that there was good leadership and infection control guidelines (∞ 59.4%; 253 and 257 / 433 and ∞ 62.4%; 268 and 270 / 433). Moreover, the results indicated that there was adequate training and support (\leq 63.0%; 273 and 178 / 433), some ongoing surveillance (\leq 64.2% (200, 274, 278 / 433), and some supplies (\leq 47.8%; 197 and 207 / 433).

Nevertheless, the results suggest that there are gaps in the implementation of safe infection control and prevention practices in the two hospitals which need to be addressed to improve compliance with recommended IPC practices. For example, 58.0% to 60.3% (251 and 261/ 433) of HCWs indicated that infection and control in their respective ward/department or hospital could be better, and most of them ∞ 64.2% (271 and 278 / 433) agreed that there was need for more training. Furthermore, a good number of HCWs 43.6% (189/433) agreed or strongly agreed that some staff do not practice safe infection control procedures. In addition, almost a third of the respondents (21.7% to 27.9%; 94 and 121 / 433) agreed or strongly agreed that there are not enough infection control supplies. Furthermore, it is worth noting the existence of blame culture when things go wrong.

Several factors were associated with HCWs' perceptions on the status of infection control in their respective ward/department or hospital. Results of the multinomial logistic regression indicated that profession and nationality were the most important predicting factors for HCWs'

attitudes on the quality of infection control, quality of leadership and guidance and surveillance and monitoring. However, the results show that perceptions on outbreak preparedness were influenced by HCWs' level of education and nationality. Education also played a role in affecting HCWs' perceptions on leadership and guidance. The results suggest that there were differing opinion on adequacy of training and supplies by hospital and nationality. It is worth noting that younger HCWs were more likely to agree with the statement that there were adequate resources for infection control. Nationality remained the predominant factors in HCWs' perceptions about the existence of a blame culture with more non-Saudis agreeing with the statement that nurses or doctors are blamed when there is an outbreak of healthcare associated infections.

Table 5.5 below summarises the quantitative findings presented in this chapter:

Table 5.5: Summary of the findings of the Quantitative Survey on perceptions on the state of infection control

Theme	Perception	Associated Factors	
		Univariate	Multivariate
1. Overall quality of infection control			
<i>Good (2 questions)</i>	Majority; 63% (265 and 272 / 433) agreed	Profession, Gender, Education, Nationality	Profession, Nationality
<i>Needs improvement (2 questions)</i>	Majority; ∞ 60.3% (251 and 261/ 433) agreed	None	N/A
2. Outbreak preparedness			
<i>Prepared (2 questions)</i>	Majority; 60.0% (258/433) agreed	Profession, Gender, Education, Nationality	Education, Nationality
3. Infection control leadership and guidelines			
<i>Good leadership (2 questions)</i>	Majority ∞ 59.4% (253 and 257 / 433) agreed	Profession, Gender, Education, Nationality	Profession, Education, Nationality
<i>Good guidelines (2 questions)</i>	Majority; ∞ 62.4% (268 and 270 / 433) agreed	Profession, Gender, Education, Nationality	Profession, Gender, Nationality
4. Training and support			
<i>Enough training (2 questions)</i>	Majority; ≤63.0% (273 and 178 / 433) agreed	Nationality, Hospital	Nationality, Hospital
<i>I need more training (2 questions)</i>	Majority; ∞ 64.2% (271 and 278 / 433) agreed	None	N/A
5. Surveillance and monitoring			
<i>There is surveillance (3 questions)</i>	Majority; ≤64.2% (200, 274, 278 / 433) agreed	Profession, Gender, Education, Nationality, Hospital	Profession, Nationality, Hospital
<i>Practice - bad (1 question)</i>	Opinion divided; 138 and 51 agreed and strongly agreed	Profession, Nationality	Profession, Nationality
6. Supplies and resources			
<i>Supplies inadequate(2 questions)</i>	Almost half; ≤ 47.8% (197 and 207 / 433) disagreed	Age, Nationality, Hospital	Age, Nationality, Hospital
7. Blame culture			
<i>Exists (4 questions)</i>	Opinion divided; 99 to 160 agreeing or strongly agreeing and 153 to 195 disagreeing or strongly disagreeing	Age, Nationality	Nationality
<i>Doesn't exist (1 question)</i>	Majority; 56.6% (245/433) agreed	Age, Nationality	Nationality

Notes: NA = Not applicable

5.3 RESULTS OF THE SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

Qualitative semi-structured interviews with physicians, nurses and infection control staff, were carried out to examine the HCWs' perceptions of the status of infection control in the two hospitals participating in this study. The semi-structured interviews were conducted over a one-month period (1 Sep 2016 to 30 Sep 2016). They involved a convenient sample of seven HCWs recruited from both hospitals. From King Fahad Specialist Hospital (Hospital 1), three physicians and one nurse were interviewed. From Buraidah Central Hospital (Hospital 2) two nurses and one physician were interviewed. Three HCWs were females. Two HCWs were Saudi nationals. The HCWs' age ranged from 28 to 58. HCWs' roles included formulating infection control policies, coordinating infection control and hand hygiene orientation programmes and training new staff.

The one-to-one in-depth interview, using a semi-structured guide, focused on identifying HCWs' perceptions along the six main themes covered in the quantitative survey:

- the overall quality of infection control in their hospital and ward/department;
- the status of infection control leadership, guidelines and policy;
- training and support needs in infection control;
- surveillance, monitoring and evaluation of infection control practices;
- availability and adequacy of supplies and infection control resources; and
- the IPC culture—including whether there exists a supportive or blame culture in their respective hospital and ward/department.

Table 5.6 below presents a summary of the question(s) asked in interviews triangulated with the themes covered by the quantitative survey:

Table 5.6: Triangulating the quantitative survey and the qualitative interview

Theme	Question to cover this theme
1. Overall quality of infection prevention and control in the hospital and wards	1. Tell me how do you feel about IPC generally in the ward/ department? 2. How might IPC be better, if that is possible? ○ What makes you feel like that? ○ Why do you say that? ○ Can you explain that a bit more? ○ Other questions based on participants' responses.
2. Infection prevention control leadership, guidelines and policy	3. What do you know about the...or have you ever been involved in any IPC policy development?
3. Perceived competence, and training and support needs in infection control	4. Can you tell me a bit about the education and training (staff development) that takes place here to support IPC?
4. Surveillance, monitoring and evaluation of infection control practices	5. Can you tell me how you feel about the monitoring of IPC?
5. Supplies and infection control resources	6. How might you describe the resources available to you to support good IPC practice?
6. Supportive or blame culture on infection control at the hospitals	7. How would you describe the organisational culture in terms of IPC?

The research codes and themes identified from HCWs' responses as well as their frequencies in interviews are presented in detail in Table 5.7 below. Themes were grouped following Attride-Stirling (2001) thematic networks, which is a technique for conducting thematic analysis where statements are fitted to the global, organising and basic themes. The main reasons for using thematic networks are because this technique offers practical and effective procedures for performing an analysis, allows a methodical systematisation of textual data, shows each step in the analytic process, helps organising and presenting analysis and facilitates a rich exploration of a text's overt structures and underlying patterns (Attride-Stirling, 2001).

Table 5.7: Codes and global, organising and basic themes in interview data

Codes	Themes (Basic)	Themes (Organising)	Themes (Global)
Good (20 times) Better (10 times) Compliance (10 times) Behaviour (5 times) Abiding (2 times) Aware (5 times) Active (2 times) Difficulties (2 times) Weak (2 times) Acceptance (4 times) Perfect (2 times) Follow (12 times) Feedback (2 times) Improvement (6 times) Increase (8 times) Availability (19 times)	Gloves, face masks, hand hygiene, handwashing, hand rub, disposable aprons, availability of medical supplies, number of infection control coordinators, number of staff involved in management of infection control, outbreaks, quick and fast response to outbreaks, size of infection control department, whom the infection control department reports to, precautions, awareness of the code of conduct, improvement in infection control practice, setting-up of infection control departments, importance attached to infection control in this hospital, skills, specialists' involvement, availability of infection control consultants, number of healthcare workers vaccinated, knowledge, behaviour change, number of people who have enough experience in infection control, infection control exams, budget allocation towards infection control, well-equipped laboratory, blood culture bottles	Infection control Management Prevention Surveillance Supplies Leadership Guidelines Code of conduct Training and support Monitoring Evaluation Personal protective equipment Department	<p>Overall quality of infection prevention and control in the hospital and wards (all interviews).</p>
Policy (19 times) Meetings (10 times) Nurses (28 times) Specialists (6 times) Taking front seats (2 times)	Multi-drug resistant infections, policies, meetings, orientation programme, lectures and daily departmental infection control rounds	Infection control policy and procedures Code of conduct Infection control manual Guidelines Infection control director Infection control and hygiene team Infection control nurse	<p>Infection control leadership, guidelines and policy (all interviews).</p>

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<p>MRSA control sessions (5 times) Awareness of the infection control procedures (10 times) Hand hygiene (17 times) Waste management (2 times) Housekeeping (4 times) Preparedness (7 times)</p>	<p>Training on spillage management, weekly training programme and monthly orientation program, management of outbreak of certain infectious diseases, infection control precautions, daily infection control rounds, weekly lectures for the whole hospital, yearly regional infection control meeting</p>	<p>Education regarding infection prevention Orientation and special training schedules Follow-up trainings Conferences Workshops Diploma course Job-specific training</p>	<p>Perceived competence, and training and support needs in infection control (all interviews).</p>
<p>Achieving 100% compliance (4 times) Monitor hand hygiene, waste management, terminal cleaning, general cleaning, Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections (CAUTI), Central Line Associated Blood Stream Infections (CLABSI), Surgical Site Infections (SSI), Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia (VAP) and PPE (22 times)</p>	<p>Surveillance activities, details of any infections they have identified, reports, daily microbiology reports, microbiology reports</p>	<p>Monitoring Collecting information Infection control committee Nurse Infection control coordinator</p>	<p>Surveillance, practice, monitoring and evaluation of infection control (all interviews).</p>
<p>Availability (19 times) Preparedness (8 times) Stocks (2 times) Satisfactory (2 times) Lacking (8 times) Shortage (5 times) Gaps (10 times)</p>	<p>PPEs, Facemasks, N95 face masks, gloves, aprons, gowns, shields, brochures, signs including alert signs usually hanging on the doors and corridors, housekeeping materials</p>	<p>Stocks Replenishment of supplies Replenishment or Restocking plan Checklist of supplies Supply chain Volume of resources</p>	<p>Supplies and infection control resources (all interviews).</p>
<p>No finger pointing (7 times) Discuss any difficulties (5 times) Blame culture (9 times) Comment (7 times).</p>	<p>infection control and management, notification of diseases, coordination, difficulties, conflict</p>	<p>Communication</p>	<p>Supportive or blame culture on infection control at the hospitals (all interviews).</p>

5.3.1 Perceptions of Healthcare Workers on the Status of Infection Control

In Table 5.6 above, a summary of the results of triangulating the responses to the seven themes (from the 25 questions) covered in the quantitative survey and the questions asked to HCWs in the semi-structured interview are provided. Detailed analysis of HCWs' views is provided in the following sections supported by quotes from the seven HCWs who participated in interviews.

5.3.1.1 Overall Quality of Infection Prevention and Control in the Hospital and Wards

To understand HCWs' perceptions of the overall quality of infection prevention and control in their institution, two main questions were asked. First, HCWs were asked about their beliefs about the quality of IPC generally in the ward/ department and how might IPC be better, if that is possible. Second, HCWs were encouraged to discuss the reasons behind their arguments in details. The results show that most of HCWs believed that infection control in their hospital/ward is good. Moreover, the results indicate that there have been improvements in awareness and importance attached to infection control in KSA since the arrival of the Middle East Severe Coronavirus (MERS-CoV) infection between 2007 to 2014 (participants 3, 4 and 7).

However, all HCWs argued that infection control could be better. This suggests that HCWs were aware of gaps in implementing recommended infection control and prevention practices. This was further evidenced when some HCWs specified particular areas that need further enhancement or improvement such as education and training (participants 2, 3, 4 and 6), supplies (participants 3 and 4), staffing (participant 3) and specialists' involvement (participant 1). Some HCWs indicated that their hospitals apply sanctions if one does not follow infection guidelines (participant 1) or fails to attend training or fails the exam (participants 1, 4 and 6).

The findings from interviews which suggest that infection control in HCWs' hospital or ward/department is good confirm the findings of the quantitative survey which show that the majority of HCWs believe that the overall quality of infection control is good in their hospital or

ward/department. Another agreement between the findings of interview and quantitative survey which triangulation highlights is HCWs' awareness of gaps in implementing recommended IPC practices which need to be addressed to make infection control better.

According to participants 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 the quality of IPC practices is good now and there has been a notable improvement particularly after the outbreak of the corona virus (MERS-COV) in the Middle East in 2007 as HCWs explained. For example, Participant 1 said, "I cannot say that we are achieving 100% compliance from either nurses, or doctors, or health workers in general, but we are trying to optimize infection control in all departments." Participant 3 emphasised the importance of infection control and precaution in every department in the hospital saying:

"We anticipate that every health worker, nurse and physician, a technician even everybody should be fully aware of the code of conduct relating to infection control, such as hand hygiene and other infection control precautions. I would say, in our department we are abiding by the infection control precautions at every step."

Similarly, Participant 5 said, "as a head nurse, I can say that infection control in my department/ward is going well and is good. We have not had had an outbreak of any infections or anything." Participant 6 highlighted the differences in infection control practices followed in different countries. The participant argued that before 2007 coronavirus outbreak, infection control in their department was weak. However, after the outbreak of corona, the attention given to infection control in the hospital has been increasing so that infection control is now the biggest and the strongest department in the hospital. Participant 6 believed that there has been about 60% or 70% improvement in infection control in the hospital. The participant argued that in the hospital they want to improve infection control and prevention more. However, making progress may take a long time to change people's attitude and behavior.

HCWs argued that there are some measures followed in the two hospitals which have resulted in having a good quality of IPC from their perspective. For instance, Participant 2 indicated that they are focusing on the individual training programme, bedside teaching

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programme and they are analysing the practices of the staff and offering them training to ensure good quality of IPC. In addition, Participant 3 said that they are using in (RESUS) area or other monitoring procedures particularly when staff are attending to patients admitted with certain infectious diseases. At Hospital 1, Participant 4 indicated that an annual orientation on infection control is provided for all staff to increase their knowledge. Attending the orientation session is compulsory for all employees. Another training opportunity is provided by the Gulf Council Centre for Training. They are offering diplomas in infection control, which the participant argued is an improvement of infection control in KSA.

Along a similar line, Participant 6 said that they are improving infection control through giving lectures and workshops on a weekly basis. There are daily departmental infection control rounds to teach staff about what to do and how to prevent the infection not only in theory, but in actual practice. Moreover, they are administering written exams and offering certificates to those who pass the exams. If one fails, they need to retake the exam after one week. If they do not pass it, further actions are taken by the hospital director such as denying the staff member from going on their annual leave.

Regarding Participant 1, he indicated that departmental directors of infection control are now reporting directly to the hospital director and medical directors in order to facilitate quick and fast response as the participant illustrated. Such measures provide an example of how the hospital is ensuring a quick response to any outbreaks or ensuring that any kind of misbehavior regarding infection control is dealt with instantly. As for Participant 5, the aseptic techniques used have prevented infection outbreaks in the hospital. Nevertheless, all HCWs showed awareness of some gaps which need to be addressed to further improve compliance with infection prevention and control policies and guidelines in their hospitals. For instance, upon asking Participant 4 about the quality of IPC in his department, he said the following:

“At the moment, I think that there has been a great improvement in infection control practice than when I first started. I have seen the setting-up of infection control departments in the region, but at first, it was so difficult, we were not aware, even the hospital director was not. I can say that, in our hospital, we are not finding

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difficulties regarding infection control now; however, we still need to educate people, both patients and staff, in certain areas of infection control so as to make further improvements.”

The participant said that hand hygiene provides an example of an important area which he believed patients and staff need to receive further education and training to improve infection control. Furthermore, Participant 4 argued that improving the availability of medical supplies for cleaning and hand washing is needed. Despite having some improvement in the budget allocations towards infection control since the SARS outbreak, the participant pointed out that they have problems with their supplies for the basic things needed for infection control.

According to Participant 1, infection prevention and control can be better when medical specialists are involved in infection control. Although the participant emphasised having faith in the expertise that is available in infection control now and feeling lucky to have an infection control consultant in the hospital, the participant indicated the need for a wide range of medical specialists, taking roles and becoming leaders in infection control to improve IPC. Participant 1 pointed out that they are trying to improve nurses and doctors' compliance with infection control pushed by their beliefs in the critical importance of preventing healthcare-associated infections. To increase nurses and doctors' compliance with infection control, the participant said that some schools are proposing strategies or sanctions to be imposed following non-compliance such as cutting salaries and suspending practice if nurses and doctors are not vaccinated.

Similarly, Participants 2, 3 and 7 proposed providing staff with continuous training to improve their knowledge about infection control practices. Participant 2 illustrated the important need for providing ongoing training based on her experience:

“This one transmission of infection we had one of these days was because some HCWs in the hospital were not strictly following infection prevention precautions, like hand hygiene practices. According to me this could be prevented through training. I see this, because sometimes we have outbreaks such as the MERS (Middle East Respiratory Syndrome) where Hospital 2 became the main corona Centre in the Qassim area, and due to this, infection control here was revamped, and there was a lot of education on infection control going around. Following this, I observed

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tremendous behavior change among HCWs here. That's why I think that education, and especially ongoing education, is the key to successful infection control."

Participant 3 called for increasing awareness of the importance of infection control and prevention among healthcare providers and workers. The participant said that supplying training for interns and new staff is vital. Furthermore, the participant suggested that new staff undertake some exams, where one must pass first before being allowed to work in their respective department.

Other gaps which Participant 3 identified include having a shortage of infection control staff who coordinate with hospital staff and provide them with feedback on their infection control practice, the lack of infection control education within the hospital, and the lack of supplies:

"Even our infection control department, which coordinates all infection control activities in this hospital, I feel that they are thin on the ground. They are trying, but the department is not enough, they are doing their best, but their numbers are not enough to cover the whole hospital."

Therefore, Participant 3 suggested increasing the number of infection control coordinators in each department to provide staff with feedback and help them identify certain infectious diseases, give them protocol procedure and to remind them with how to deal with infectious disease. As for supplies, Participant 3 pointed out that they are facing a big problem such as the lack of blood culture bottles not only in his department, but also in the main stock, in Mudriah (branch of MOH). The shortage of supplies is leading them to treat patients with any infectious disease, especially patients presenting with septicaemia, septic shock, UTI, chest infection, meningitis with antibiotics without knowing what the culture result is.

The lack of supplies was similarly identified by Participant 7 as an influential factor which needs to be addressed to improve the quality of IPC and achieve compliance with recommended IPC practices:

"the last time we had MERS-CoV here, we didn't have some of the PPEs such as N95 masks. Also, our laboratory didn't have enough culture disks, for growing and typing the viruses (which is important for confirming diagnosis), and I think that having such

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a problem for such an important item is serious and not good for our hospital. In addition, blood culture bottles have not been available in the last six months, in this hospital. In this case, if you have a patient presenting with septicemia, we as practitioners are hesitant to try and confirm the diagnosis and identify the causative agent through blood test, because we don't know if the relevant culture bottles are in supply or not. In addition, sometimes if one requests for these from the medical store, if I request them to give me 5 bottles, they will give 2.”

This may indicate the serious impact the shortage of supplies is having on improving the quality of infection control in the two hospitals particularly as the outbreak of infections can threaten patients' lives and requires urgent actions from HCWs. The final gap which Participant 5 pointed out to improve the quality of IPC is following the aseptic technique which recommends observing hand hygiene, as for example, when changing dressings on a patient. The participant explained that HCWs should wash their hands properly, put on multiple layers of gloves, then with sterile gloves on, remove the dressing, remove the dirty gloves, and use the next layer of sterile gloves to apply new dressing on the patient. If HCWs followed this aseptic technique, many infections can be prevented. However, Participant 5 argued that HCWs sometimes do not follow the technique as needed particularly doctors because of their busy schedule during the day which can lead to the spread of infections.

5.3.1.2 Infection Control Leadership, Guidelines and Policy

To evaluate the existence of an infection control policy, leadership and guidance in the studied hospitals, HCWs were asked about what they know about IPC policy development in their hospital and whether they have ever been involved in any IPC policy development. All HCWs indicated that their respective hospitals now have infection control policies. For example, Participant 4 said, “Yes, definitely we have one now... we implemented the Gulf countries infection control manual and another one for surveillance.” As another example, Participant 6 said, “we now know what infection control is, how to prevent infections inside this building. We now are aware of the importance of hospital infection control in this country.”

All HCWs agreed that the policies are good. In addition, HCWs said that infection control policies are mainly based on the Centers for Disease Control (CDC), the World Health Organization (WHO), the Gulf Cooperation Countries (GCC) and the National Health Safety Network (NHSN) infection control policies. This finding is in agreement with the findings from the quantitative survey where the majority of HCWs (351/433; 81.06%) thought that there was good infection control leadership in their ward/department and hospital (Table 5.3C-1). Also, most of them (382/433; 88.22%) thought that their ward/department had a clear set of guidelines so that they are able to access support to comply with safe IPC practices (Table 5.3C-2).

To understand in depth the existence of infection control policy and guidance in the two hospitals from HCWs' perceptions in interviews and their participation in policy development, the HCWs were asked to provide some information on infection prevention and control policy development in their respective hospitals. Participants 1, 2 and 3 indicated their direct involvement in infection control policy development. For example, as an assistant of the hospital director for medical services, Participant 1 illustrated that he has been formulating policies for multi-drug resistant infections. Apart from being involved in the multi-drug policy, at the time coronavirus outbreak Participant 1 was involved in conducting daily meetings for corona prevention. Moreover, Participant 3 explained his role in coordinating infection control and hygiene in the last six months saying:

“Yeah, I have been involved in last six months as an infection control and hygiene coordinator for the department of internal medicine. My role, among others, mainly involves teaching the internal resident and specialist or consultant about infection control. I am also a member of the entire hospital infection control and hygiene team”.

Adopting the CDC, WHO and GCC (Gulf Cooperation Countries) infection control policies, Participants 2 and 6 pointed out that infection control policy and procedures are formulated in Hospital 2. Participant 2 said that the policy is updated every two years “as to take care of any new developments or new infections, such as MERS-CoV which necessitated adding

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of new guidelines due to the natural history of the new challenge”. In this way, Participant 2 argued, they ensure keeping the staff informed and updated on infection control.

Along a similar line, Participant 4 explained how infection control policy in Hospital 1 has been developed based on the CDC EPIC publication, and to some extent the WHO publication earlier, but currently the Gulf countries infection control manual and another one for surveillance are implemented. Other important publications used when preparing infection control policies as Participant 4 added include a Ministry of Health publication “infection control”, the guidance from the CDC, and the Canadian National Health Safety Network. Participant 7 pointed out that the National Health Safety Network (NHSN) and the CDC are approved by the MOH. Therefore, Participant 4 argued that they “go for best practice in different areas actually but don’t commission international publications.”

5.3.1.3 Perceived Competence, and Training and Support Needs in Infection Control

To explore participants’ perceived competence, and training and support needs in infection prevention and control, HCWs were asked about the education and training (staff development) that take place in the two hospitals to support good IPC practice. However, the analysis of interviews shows a divergence in responses, with some HCWs arguing that the hospitals are offering enough training (Participants 1, 2, 6 and 5), while others suggested that infection training was either weak, inadequate or becoming less and less over time (Participants 3, 4, 6 and 7). In particular, for Participants 4 and 6, although good training has been provided, they criticised the reduction in training opportunities in recent years (especially in the past 2 years) both at hospital level and at national level as provided by the MOH.

The interview results agree with the results obtained from the quantitative survey, where most of the HCWs who participated in the survey claimed receiving inadequate training and expressed their need for more training to support good IPC practice. Specifically, in the survey, although while responding to question 11 and 14, most HCWs (273/433; 63.0%) indicated that

they are offered enough training, the number was lower for those who agreed that they can provide good infection control practice without further training (178/433; 41.1%). To provide good infection control practice, the majority of HCWs (271,278/433; 64.2%) argued that they needed more training (Figures 5.4A and 5.4B).

To examine responses of HCWs in interviews in details, their views on infection control training are analysed here. According to Participants 1, 2, 5 and 6, adequate training is provided. The participants illustrated with examples the training offered in the two hospitals. For instance, Participant 1 who works at Hospital 1 said, “yes, education regarding infection prevention behaviour and attitude has been enhanced since the coronavirus break. We have trainings for prevention of MERS-CoV MRSA and other infections.” The participant emphasised that all new employees or HCWs have to participate in their infection control teaching and learning programmes.

In Hospital 2, Participant 2 said that there are orientation and special training schedules which the staff have developed and are usually updated every year:

“For example, we have training on spillage management if there are any spill management changes, or something like, we will then. We have a weekly training programme and monthly orientation program. These trainings are compulsory for all staff and for the new staff that just joined us, we offer the orientation programme. We choose different topics for each session, e.g., procedures for control of MRSA.”

After each training, Participant 2 said, an evaluation form is used to check staff’s understanding, knowledge and competence. Similarly, Participant 5 argued that adequate training is provided. Training is offered on a weekly and monthly basis. There is a training session for all staff every Tuesday. If one fails some exams, they are asked to retake them. The goal, as Participant 5 argued, “is to ensure that all staff are well aware of the infection control procedures. There is no complacency; this year infection role is good”. As for Participant 6, he argued that the staff are now better informed about infection control and how to prevent infections inside the hospital because there are lectures and daily departmental infection control rounds to teach staff

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about the practicalities and not only the theory. The participant explained his role in infection control training saying:

“For the staff of the department infection control I make a round every day with the staff about the new policy and about how to deal with the person and how to prevent infection and make a round every day and make lectures for the whole hospital weekly and monthly and yearly. There is also a regional infection control meeting yearly.”

Despite saying that at a national level, the MOH is now paying more attention to infection control, Participant 6 was critical of the decrease in the number of meetings on infection control for the directors of infection control in Riyadh (the capital city) and other places that the MOH used to host particularly in the last two years. Along a similar line, Participant 4 suggested that there has been a reduction in training opportunities recently:

“Yes, actually, a couple of years ago there was more activity as we used to have so many conferences, workshops, training and the MOH and orientation course. However, for the last two years I have seen a reduction in activity, there are now less and less training opportunities, or workshops. I do not know why this is happening, but for sure it is becoming less and less. Still, the MOH send experts from time to time, to come and conduct one or two-day training. Still I think we need more of that.”

Rather than just offering short-term training opportunities and workshops, Participant 4 suggested offering a diploma course in infection control for some of the Saudis. The participant said that he knows that a very few individuals obtained their diplomas from the region, but they are very few up to now. He argued that as far as he knows, there are only two people who have a diploma in infection control.

Participant 7 similarly stressed the need for offering more training opportunities suggesting focusing on both simple and broad issues in infection prevention and control in different sessions:

“We have too small, small parts and different, different sessions; I would love if they had put all of them together. I think that way it would be more effective. I mean if I am taking ICU guideline, which includes hand hygiene, waste management and all the minor things. My approach is you first teach hand hygiene, and then let the HCWs implement and then monitor and ensure that they have graduated from that, and then move to the next issue.”

Another suggestion which Participant 7 made is providing follow-up trainings after the orientation training because offering orientation training only is not effective. Furthermore, the participant advised offering job-specific training because it is more effective:

“job-specific training means we have to train according to their level, because if I am teaching you in English as a doctor you will understand, but as a housekeeping staff you cannot. So, we can't hear because we have a lot of housekeeping staff with different languages (we have Bangladeshi, Indian, Pakistani) so what we are doing here is we made a different training policy for people like housekeeping staff, we teach them in their language, as a part of training.”

Along a similar line, Participant 3 criticised the deficit in training in infection control at Hospital 1 arguing that infection control is emphasised when there is an infection outbreak:

“Actually, we have a deficit in this area here; the infection control department usually emphasises on the infection control and hand hygiene only when there is an outbreak of certain infectious disease, for maybe like 4 to 5 months, then after that they relax and you see no infection control trainings or precautions.”

Participant 3 indicated that he has been sending emails to the infection control department, emphasising the need to apply and implement infection control precautions at least every month to teach the newcomers, the employees, the new interns and sometimes to remind the doctors as it is possible to forget the importance of following infection control procedures such as hand hygiene.

5.3.1.4 Supplies and Infection Control Resources

HCWs' perception of their ward/department and hospitals' standing on supplies to enable them to prevent and control infection during care delivery was explored while asking the participants to describe the resources available to support good infection prevention and control practice. The analysis shows that there was a consensus among most HCWs who argued that supplies were average or even poor. Most HCWs alluded to the fact that there are some limitations

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and sometimes there are shortages in stocks. However, Participants 2 and 5 argued that supplies were good, and everything needed for infection control is available.

Five out of the seven HCWs (Participants 1, 2, 3, 4 and 7) indicated that sometimes there are supply problems, with the N95 face masks particularly being singled out. Participant 3 pointed out that there is always a shortage of N95 facemasks. The participant argued that because of this shortage some departments even put up some regulations as to when these masks may be used, although the policy has been a total failure.

The findings show some reasons for having problems with supplies which include bureaucracy and a centralised requisition system, i.e., where all purchases are made at the MOH headquarters in Riyadh, and the long distance makes things problematic. It is important to point out that the results of the interview are not in agreement with those obtained from the quantitative survey, where the majority of HCWs 197/207 out of 433 (around 47.8%) and 34/84 out of 433 disagreed and strongly disagreed with the assertion that the hospital or the ward does not provide enough supplies (Figure 5.6). However, a few HCWs (63/105) and (16/31) agreed and strongly agreed that the ward or hospital does not provide enough supplies, whereas 66 and 81 were neutral. This suggests that while there are supplies, a substantial number of HCWs 121 and 94, (between 21.7% and 30.0%) thought that sometimes these supplies are not adequate.

In interviews, analysing HCWs views of infection control supplies and resources at their respective hospitals highlights some problems with the availability of infection control supplies. For example, Participant 1 explained that as a governmental hospital, they are dependent on the MOH for financing their entire budget. This means the availability of resources depends on the MOH provision. Similarly, Participant 6 said that infection control supplies are provided by the GCC and the MOH. However, Participant 7 pointed out that the staff at the hospital have to approach the MOH for everything they need which can be problematic because of the distance between the MOH headquarters in Riyadh and the hospital location in the Qassim region:

“we have lots of problems with resources and supplies. You know this is a government hospital, and because we have to approach the ministry for everything, and because

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of the distance between us and the ministry, this always creates delays and some problems. You know already that the directorate is in Riyadh.”

Participant 7 explained that she studied supply chain, including the supply chain guideline or policy last year while taking part in a course organised by the MOH. The course covered estimating the volume of resources the staff would need over a certain period of time, and a replenishment or restocking plan. Therefore, the participant said that she makes a checklist, in which if an item is used up to 80%, she has to inform the line managers to act accordingly and apply for new stocks. If there a good restocking plan was not developed, they would run into problems such as what happened during the last MRS outbreak as Participant 7 clarified. Therefore, Participant 7 emphasised having a huge gap with their supplies due to the supply chain policy, but they are trying to close that gap.

Participant 1 also indicated having some problems with infection control supplies. The participant stressed working to support the infection control department saying, “we have been developing their numbers, together with other HCWs and we are trying to have no problems with finance, we are trying to limit the problems that we have.” Along a similar line, Participants 3 and 4 indicated that some materials are always available while others are unavailable. For example, hand hygiene material and housekeeping are “satisfactory” as Participant 4 described while some personal protective equipment are lacking. Participant 3 said that brochures, and signs including alert signs usually hanging on the doors and corridors are always available. However, sanitizers and antiseptic gels are not available sometimes. Moreover, Participant 3 pointed out that facemasks’ shortage is always a problem at Hospital 1:

“In addition, usually we run out of facemasks, they are always in short stock, sometimes the N95 are in short stock, sometimes the shields are. During the last outbreak, I was told that we had run out of stock of N95 facemasks. I am not sure whether the shortage is a problem of the hospital or the MOH; I cannot be sure about that. Usually, we send letters to the hospital directors that we need supply all the time. Now we have at least the supply for the upcoming season like N95 masks, eyes precaution and gowns especially for the infectious disease generally.”

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Participant 3 highlighted the problems with the shortage of N95 facemasks indicating that some departments at the hospital are implementing some policies like when to use the N95, i.e., the fittest policy. However, some doctors find N95 facemask more comfortable and fit better. Therefore, they do not follow the procedure and protocol of the fittest as Participant 3 explained. According to Participant 3, the reason why the hospital always runs out of N95 masks and there are restrictions on when to use them could be either because they are expensive, or because there is always a shortage in stocks.

However, the views of Participants 1, 3, 4, and 7 detailed above contrast with the views of Participants 2 and 5 who argued that all infection control supplies are available. For example, upon asking Participant 2 to describe the resources available to support good infection prevention and control practice, she said the following:

“Yeah, we have resources and we have records for this one; we have daily assessment records and weekly assessment records. Different sections have a checklist of the types of resources they need. We are fixing time limits for replenishment of supplies and have a checklist that we use.”

Similarly, Participant 5 confirmed having all what is needed for infection control particularly N95 masks in all sizes:

“all things regarding infection control we have, if there is any shortage, we write a letter to our nursing director and they will talk to our stock director and immediately they will provide it. I do not know whether we are lacking anything, if any for now, we have everything in stock. All stocks are available; all PPEs and especially N95 we have it, and all sizes.”

The differences in responses maybe because Participants 2 and 5 work at Hospital 2 unlike Participants 1, 3, 4, and 7 who work at Hospital 1. Therefore, HCWs’ perceptions may have been affected by the problems with supplies in Hospital 1.

5.3.1.5 Surveillance, Practice, Monitoring and Evaluation of Infection Control

In addition to exploring the quality of infection control, its leadership, guidelines and policy, participants' perceived competence, and training and support needs as well as its supplies, the monitoring and evaluation of infection control were investigated. Most HCWs indicated that the monitoring of infection control in their respective hospitals is good. However, two participants indicated the absence of an organised infection control structure (Participants 3 and 4). These results agree with the results obtained from the quantitative survey, where a large number of HCWs (274, 278) agreed that they are aware of infection control surveillance in the ward/department and hospital respectively, compared to a small number of HCWs (72 and 23) who agreed or strongly agreed with the statement that nobody checks their infection control practice (Figure 5.5A).

Upon exploring with HCWs their perceptions about the monitoring of infection prevention and control at their hospitals, most of them said that it is good particularly when it is compared to how the monitoring of infection control was a few years ago. For example, Participants 1 and 6 stressed noticing the big change in staff's behaviour and following infection control code of practice or instructions which are set by the MOH or other institutions at both hospitals. Because of the noticeable change Participant 1 argued that Hospital 1 is the best among government hospitals:

“we are not achieving 100% either compliance or prevention, but we are trying to approach it. In the last few months, I can say we have made so much progress and are the best among government hospitals.”

Participant 1 illustrated that six months ago and last year they had some outbreaks of hospital infections which alerted the staff and the MOH officials to the problems with infection control in the hospital. The participant also expressed his worries about infection outbreaks in this season in particular. Therefore, he said that he was going to send reminders to the staff to follow infection prevention and control procedures.

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Participant 7 indicated that there are more than 25 different types of monitoring at Hospital 1 which six nurses do. For example, the nurses monitor hand hygiene, waste management, terminal cleaning, general cleaning, CAUTI, Central Line Associated Blood Stream Infections (CLABSI), Surgical Site Infections (SSI), Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia (VAP) and PPEs. Therefore, the participant said there is so much to monitor. However, it is important to point out that Participants 3 and 4 criticised monitoring infection control in Hospital 1. For example, Participant 3 indicated that there is no organised infection control structure or a coordinator for infection control like a nurse or technician to remind all physicians to follow infection control guidelines before every procedure. Similarly, Participant 4 said that few staff are involved in infection control and are interested in it besides the lack of regional training resources:

“The setup in KSA is not like UK. Here the setup is difficult because there are no regional training resources. The head of the infection department is the one who conducts the trainings. Also, not many staff want to be involved in infection control because not many people are interested. However, the number of infection control practitioners, I think is still satisfactory.”

In Hospital 2, Participants 2, 5 and 6 argued that infection control is monitored. Participant 2 explained how the staff are monitoring infection control. For instance, the participant said, there is a surveillance system, patients' files are checked and information on any incidence of staff being infected are collected. Furthermore, Participant 2 pointed out that there is an efficient microbiology department system which sends reports providing results of cultures they have done and details of any infections they have identified on a daily basis. These reports are sent to the higher authority and the infection control committee at the hospital. Participant 2 added that she presents details of the surveillance activities to the infection control committee. The committee give some suggestions and recommendations for the staff to follow.

Participant 5 illustrated that they sometimes get MRSA positive patients or MRSA wound swab patients which is usually reported at once. If MRSA positive with bacterium powder, dressing or bath this is reported to the MOH weekly. The participant said that most of the time it

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is abscess while nosocomial infections are very rare. Participant 5 pointed out that she seldom experiences any nosocomial infection at Hospital 2. Most of the infections are from outpatient's department as the participant clarified.

5.3.1.6 Supportive or Blame Culture on Infection Control at the Hospitals

To understand whether there was generally a supportive or blame culture in the two hospitals included in this study, HCWs were asked to describe the organisational culture in terms of infection prevention and control. The results indicate that there is a good infection control culture in the hospitals, although two HCWs criticised infection control culture indicating that sometimes conflict arises particularly due to having some people who do not like to be monitored or told to comply with infection control procedures. Again, the results here agree with the quantitative survey results, where the majority responded that staff are supported in infection controls, indicating that there was a good infection control culture in their hospitals (Figure 5.7B). Details of responses from the interviewees are provided below.

According to Participant 1, there is generally a good organisational culture in Hospital 1. There are good communication channels between departments and infection control as well as between infection control and management and higher authorities in the hospital as the participant said. Upon receiving reports from all departments, Participant 1 indicated that proper action is taken at once. In agreement with Participant 1, Participants 3, 4 and 7 argued that there is good coordination between infection control department and other departments in Hospital 1. For example, Participant 7 said that the organisation chart begins with the hospital director, the infection control director, and six practitioners who together are the executive branch of infection control and they ensure that there is a good infection culture.

Participant 3 explained the steps taken when there is an outbreak and how the departments plan and coordinate infection control practices:

“Yes, usually we receive cases with certain infectious diseases, or with suspected infectious diseases. We notify the public health and infection control department of

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any such cases. For example, the corona virus, influenza A, H1N1, meningitis and encephalitis, all these are notifiable diseases. We have to isolate the patient in a positive or negative pressure room or normal isolation rooms in the ward. If we have a patient admitted with an infectious disease, then we take some precautions to prevent hospital spread. For example, we put up signs on the doors or corridors to alert everybody that they need to be cautious when getting in contact with the patient, before taking blood samples.”

Participant 4 also pointed out that infection control coordinators in Hospital 1 discuss the difficulties they face every morning. However, this sometimes results in conflict particularly if the infection control coordinator is a foreigner as the participant said because some professionals personalise things and think that they are monitored rather than the occurrence of infections. Participant 4 clarified that for cultural reasons, it can be difficult for patients in the hospital to stop a doctor or a nurse from attending to them just because they have not washed their hands. This may be different from the situation in the UK where a patient can ask the nurse or doctor to wash their hands prior to treatment. In a community which is not very familiar with patient safety, senior staff are always complaining from being monitored as Participant 4 argued:

“Here, senior staff are always complaining why you are monitoring. I tell them it is the law, so I have to monitor you even if you are senior. However, this is quite strange to them, you know in a community which is not very familiar with patient safety. I mean we should be.”

Therefore, Participant 4 advised educating people more about what physicians and nurses should be doing in relation to infection prevention and control. In Hospital 2, Participant 5 argued that most of the doctors are not doing hand hygiene before dressing because of laziness. In addition, there is an acute shortage of dressings such as wound dressings for diabetes foot. Therefore, the participant indicated that doctors sometimes just cover the wounds with sterile gauze or use antiseptics.

Nevertheless, Participants 2 and 6 argued that there is good coordination and cooperation rather than a blame culture in the hospital. As Participant 2 explained, there is a separate infection

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control department which is headed by the director of infection control. Each department and section have a coordinator who makes daily sections rounds and reports to the director of infection control, who in turns reports to the hospital director. Participant 6 said that there has been a remarkable improvement in infection control recently. He described what the infection control staff are doing saying:

“every day we make rounds in the department, check patient files, take samples and send to the microbiology department to ensure that any possible cases of infections are identified and dealt with on time. We have this type of plan. All the staff now know this policy, and there has been tremendous improvement in our ability to identify and treat healthcare associated infections.”

Therefore, Participant 6 indicated having a good organisational culture in terms of infection prevention and control. Finally, in the next section, participants’ comments on different aspects related to infection prevention and control and recommendations are examined.

5.3.1.7 Participants’ Comments on Infection Control and Recommendations

At the end of each interview, HCWs were asked to make comments on any aspects they thought were relevant to the discussion but not covered in the questions. Participant 5 stressed that most if not all doctors and healthcare professionals are complying with hand hygiene to prevent HAIs. Participants 2, 4, 6 and 7 suggested some improvements in infection control activities. The main recommendations the participants suggested include: improving supplies, increasing the number of infection control consultants and holding more infection control meetings between the MOH and hospitals.

According to Participant 2, there is a shortage of some medical supplies such as PPEs and supplies for hand hygiene despite requesting them a long time ago. Therefore, the participant recommended providing more supplies. Similarly, Participant 7 suggested improving the supplies provided, for example, getting disinfectants which should be based on the needs they have in the hospital.

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Participant 4 highlighted that the policy and management of infection control are good. However, having one infection control consultant in the geriatrics department and a consultant working in the maternity department is not enough. More consultants are needed particularly in the coming years. Finally, Participant 6 recommended increasing the number of meetings between the infection control department and MOH in KSA to discuss staff's needs and improve infection control. The participant emphasised the importance of the visits that MOH officials used to make to the hospital which are recently decreasing in number.

Table 5.8: Perceptions on hospital or ward/departments’ infection control – Semi-structured Interview

Study domain	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3	Participant 4	Participant 5	Participant 6	Participant 7
1. Overall quality of infection prevention and control in the hospital/wards	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good	Average
	Appreciated that the infection control and prevention measures were improving in their department.	They were focusing on critical areas in their department as well as training and analysing the practices of the staff.	Infection control and prevention is highly important in their department, as they apply infection control precautions in all steps while dealing with patients in their RESUS department.	Confirmed that there was a tremendous improvement in this regard as their director actively implemented infection control.	Positive progress in their department, as they practiced the aseptic technique.	The staff embraced and practiced IPC after around six years.	It requires more effort as perfection is required to attain and promote infection control.
2. Infection control leadership, guidelines and policy	Good	Good	Good	Good	Poor	Good	Good
	They hold meetings on a daily basis to help prevent the outbreaks.	They mainly take policies from CDC, WHO and GCC. They then update these bi-annually or as required in case of any changes, for example in the MERS..	Mentioned serving as a coordinator for infection control and hand hygiene in the past six months in their department.	Have been involved in deliberating on various policies before settling on the best, as opposed to commissioning international policies without due investigation of the same.	Has not actively participated in policy deployment.	actively involved in sensitisation measures as they educate staff around the hospital on the same.	They evaluate the policies based on NHSN (National Health Safety Network).
3. Outbreak preparedness	Average	Average	Good	Average	Good	Good	Average

	Efficiency attained is not at its optimum but the concerned medics were working on improvement.	Improvements were thus being made through training and correcting any wrongdoings.	Applying infection control precaution, at every step they are using in (RESUS) area or any observation during the procedure and before contact with the patient sometimes.	More training and education were required to sensitise the staff on improvement.	Positive progress in their department.	Overall improvement observed.	Need more focus on each point and lots of effort for infection control.
4. Perceived competence, and training and support needs in infection control:	Good	Good	Poor	Average	Good	Good	Good
	Gave an example of a scheduled MERS-CO prevention as well as MRSA. Furthermore, he insisted that any other staff coming to their institute have to go through the appropriate training for the same.	Have annual training outlined in their training schedules whereby employees are oriented on the same.	Observed laxity in his department as action is only taken after a catastrophe.	Complained that training sessions had reduced, when compared to the past two years when they had many modules of training, workshops, and conferences.	Have an orientation programmer taking them through the training every month, and special sessions every week on Tuesdays for those wishing to retake the lessons.	They hold small sessions on a daily basis to update the staff on new policies. Besides, they also hold infection control meetings for the whole region annually.	Training tailored to fit their staff since there may exist language barriers if a single language was used for all staff. They thus have job-specific training in their department.
5. Supplies and infection control resources:	Average	Good	Poor	Average	Good	Average	Average
	Some challenges with finances since they are fully dependent on the MOH.	They have resources as well as records and checklists to help assess staff development.	Have insufficient resources; for example, the antiseptic gels are usually insufficient. For the upcoming season, the respondent was concerned that	Observed shortages in their department, although when compared to other facilities he thought that theirs was better placed.	Happy with the resources allocated since they had everything as required.	Sixth displayed some of the material and resources sent over from the MOH through the GCC.	Complained of the long procedures and steps involved in reaching out to the MOH as they requested for supplies.

			there are shortages in various supplies including N95 masks and gowns.				
6. Surveillance, practice, monitoring and evaluation of infection control	Good	Good	Poor	Average	Good	Good	Good
	Optimism as they were gradually improving. He was however concerned on the outbreaks and hence explained that plans were underway to remind workers to be on the lookout.	Constant surveillance as well as daily checks to check patients' files and staff details.	Department did not have sufficient monitoring mechanisms put in place to support IPC.	Setup mechanisms were not as efficient as those set up in other countries such as the UK where he was based. He complained that they lacked a regional training head. Nonetheless, he felt that the number of infection control practitioners was satisfactory.	Satisfied with the progress in their department as they were getting MRSA positive in patients or MRSA wound swab. Treatments were always conducted immediately.	Observed tremendous improvement in their department as the staff had changed their attitudes towards infection control and prevention.	Rigorous monitoring in their department since they have several aspects they have to supervise, such as hand hygiene and waste management.
7. Supportive or blame culture on infection control at the hospitals	Supportive	Supportive	Supportive.	Supportive	Blame culture	Supportive	Supportive
	Good communication channels within their department. The response time on any issues is thus swift as a result of the proper channels established.	Daily visits are made to the subsections as reports are handed over to the respective heads following the hierarchy to the topmost.	Whereby they notify the public health department and infection control after which they may take the appropriate procedures.	They rotate the infection control and prevention profession from one area to another, since training is not done equally in their department.	Complained that doctors in their department were lazy and simply failed in observing the control and preventive measures put in place.	Do follow-up on patients and report any changes to the appropriate staff, thus ensuring infection control in their department.	Hierarchical in nature with the hospital director at the top, followed by the infection control director, and finally six practitioners at the bottom.

5.4 RESULTS OF THE OBSERVATION STUDY

The researcher carried out non-participant observation as a final data collection method. This non-participant observation was aimed at understanding HCWs' compliance with infection control policy practices at the two research hospitals. Observations were carried out to enable capturing enough information on HCWs' IPC practices, attendance, shifts and schedules. In total, eight observations involving sixty-nine HCWs were conducted over a one-month period from 1 August 2016 to 30 August 2016. Seven observations were conducted during daytime from 7:00 AM to 15:00 PM. However, Observation 2 was carried out over 24 hours in the emergency department (ER) ward in Hospital 1.

Observations 2, 5, 7 and 8 were carried out at King Fahad Specialist Hospital (Hospital 1), while Observations 1, 3, 4 and 6 were conducted at Buraidah Central Hospital (Hospital 2). Details of the ward and the number of physicians or nurses observed are provided in Table 5.9 below:

Table 5.9 Number of physicians and nurses observed and institution/ward:

Observation (No)	Physicians observed (No)	Nurses observed (No)	Department	Hospital
1	4	5	Orthopaedics	HOSPITAL 2
2	2	8	Emergency department (ER)	HOSPITAL 1
3	6	6	Medical & Surgical ward (male)	HOSPITAL 2
4	4	7	Medical & Surgical ward (female)	HOSPITAL 2
5	5	8	Ear, Nose and Throat Department	HOSPITAL 1
6	3	6	Ophthalmology	HOSPITAL 2
7	3	0	Dermatology	HOSPITAL 1
8	1	1	General Gastroenterology Clinic	HOSPITAL 1
Total	28	41	69 HCWs	

A form designed by the SICP (NHS Scotland; NHS NSS, 2016) was used to guide the observations (Appendix XII). The form captures information on several infection control areas, including hand hygiene, respiratory cough hygiene and use of PPEs such as gloves, aprons, full body gowns and eye protection when attending to patients admitted with infectious diseases. It

also captures information on proximity and the manner of storage of PPEs in these facilities.

Observation data was analysed using the Attride-Stirling (2001) framework, where HCWs' behaviours were fitted to the global, organising and basic themes as shown below in Table 5.10:

Table 5.10 Codes and global, organising and basic themes in thematic analysis:

Codes	Themes (Basic)	Themes (Organising)	Themes (Global)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Did not wash hands, hands visibly soiled or dirty • Did not expose forearms • Did not remove all hand/wrist jewellery • Fingernails not cut short • Had artificial nails • Did not cover all cuts or abrasions with a waterproof dressing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forearms exposure • Removal of all hand/wrist jewellery • Fingernails short • No artificial nails • Covering of all cuts or abrasions with a waterproof dressing • Washing hands with non-antimicrobial liquid soap and water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before washing hands • Before touching a patient who has infectious disease • Before clean/aseptic procedures. If Alcohol-Based Hand Rubs (ABHR) cannot be used then antimicrobial soap should be used • After body fluid exposure risk • After touching a patient • After touching a patient's immediate surroundings 	Hand hygiene
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Covered nose and mouth with disposable tissue • Disposed waste in proper waste bins • Did not perform cough etiquette and hygiene • Used hand wipes despite there being running water • Did not wash hands before performing ABHR • Did not keep contaminated hands away from their face • Provided respiratory and cough hygiene assistance to patients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Covering of nose and mouth with a disposable tissue when sneezing • Proper disposal of all used tissues promptly into a waste bin. • Washing hands with non-antimicrobial liquid soap and warm water after coughing, sneezing, • Using tissues, or after contact with respiratory secretions or objects contaminated by these secretions • Use of hand wipes. • Keep contaminated hands away from the eyes, nose and mouth • Staff promote respiratory and cough hygiene, helping those (e.g., elderly, children) who need assistance with this, e.g., providing patients with tissues, plastic bags for used tissues and hand hygiene facilities as necessary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When sneezing, coughing, wiping and blowing the nose • Disposal of soiled tissues • After sneezing or blowing nose • After contact with respiratory secretions or objects contaminated by these secretions • Use of wipes • Management of contaminated hands • Promotion of hand hygiene to patients 	Respiratory cough hygiene
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Did not use PPEs • Did not store PPEs in right place or near place of use • Did not properly dispose of PPEs after use • Did not wear right size of gloves, or enough layers when performing multiple tasks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of PPEs • Storage of PPEs • Location of PPEs storage • Disposal of PPEs after use, Proper use of gloves 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before touching a patient who has infectious disease • Before drawing blood or taking any body samples • Before clean/aseptic procedures. If ABHR cannot be used then antimicrobial soap should be used 	Personal protective equipment (PPEs)

The results of observation showed poor infection control practices in the observed hospitals. Although there was some level of compliance with some infection control procedures, the hospitals or staff fell short of compliance in other areas suggesting a need for greater effort to improve infection control practices. These results will be analysed thematically in depth in the following subsections.

5.4.1. Hand Hygiene

A key finding which appeared from the analysis of observations is showing poor hand hygiene practices generally among the HCWs observed in the two hospitals. This finding is based on many examples which show poor hand hygiene practices. For example, although none of the HCWs had cuts, abrasions or long fingernails, exposure of arms was partly observed in two out of eight observation shifts. The observed HCWs exposed their arms in Observation 4 which involved four female physicians and seven female nurses in Medical and Surgical Wards in Hospital 2 from 7:00 to 9:00 am and from 10:00 to 12:00 pm. In Observation 5 also, which involved five nurses and eight physicians of the Ear, Nose, and Throat Department (ENT) in Hospital 1, most of the HCWs exposed their arms from 7:00 to 9:00 am and from 13:00 to 15:00 pm. However, in the other six observation shifts, the HCWs did not expose forearms before performing hand hygiene. Such a practice shows following poor hygiene practices.

In the eight observation shifts, none of the HCWs removed their jewellery such as watches during hand wash (if they washed their hands) during any observation. Furthermore, most HCWs did not wash their hands to perform hand hygiene in the following six situations:

- before touching a patient;
- after touching a patient;
- after touching a patient's immediate surrounding;
- before performing clean or antiseptic procedures;
- after body fluid exposure risk, and

- when hands were visibly soiled or dirty.

In most observations, precisely in six out of eight observations, HCWs did not wash their hands before touching a patient. Performing hand hygiene before touching a patient was noted in Observation 5 which involved five nurses and eight physicians at the Ear, Nose, and Throat Department (ENT) in Hospital 1 and Observation 6 which involved three physicians and six nurses at the Department of Ophthalmology in Hospital 2. All HCWs observed in these two shifts from 7:00 am to 15:00 pm washed their hands before touching a patient showing that they were practicing hand hygiene.

After touching a patient, HCWs did not wash their hands in half of the observation shifts (four out of eight observations). Performing hand hygiene after touching a patient was seen in Observations 4, 5, 6 and 7 which in total involved eighteen physicians and eighteen nurses from both hospitals. However, in almost all observations (seven out of eight), HCWs did not wash their hands after touching a patients' immediate surroundings. Only in Observation 6, the HCWs observed from 7:00 to 9:00 am in the Department of Ophthalmology in Hospital 2 (three physicians and six nurses) performed hand hygiene after touching a patients' immediate surroundings.

In a bit more than half of the observation shifts (five out of eight), HCWs did not wash their hands before performing clean or antiseptic procedures. Practicing hand hygiene was seen, firstly, in Observation 1 which involved four physicians and five nursing staff in orthopaedic ward in HOSPITAL 2 from 7:00 am to 15:00 pm. Secondly, in Observation 2 which involved two physicians and eight nurses in the emergency department (ER) ward in Hospital 1, HCWs practiced hand hygiene before performing clean or antiseptic procedures from 1:00 to 9:00 am and from 13:00 to 15:00 pm. Thirdly, in Observation 8 which involved one physician and one nurse at the General Gastroenterology Clinic in Hospital 1, the HCWs observed practiced hand hygiene before performing clean or antiseptic procedures from 7:00 am to 15:00 pm.

In half of the observation shifts (four out of eight observations), HCWs did not wash their hands after body fluid exposure risk. In Observations 1, 3, and 4 which all took place in Hospital 2 involving fourteen physicians and eighteen nurses in total, performing hand hygiene after body fluid exposure risk was seen. In Observation 7 which took place in the Dermatology Clinic in Hospital 1, three physicians were seen washing their hands after body fluid exposure risk. Finally, in a bit more than half of the observations (five out of eight), HCWs did not wash their hands with soap or antiseptic when hands were visibly soiled. Performing hand hygiene when hands were visibly soiled was noted in Observations 1, 4 and 6 which took place in Hospital 2. In Observation 1 which involved four physicians and five nursing HCWs at the orthopaedic ward, the HCWs practiced hand hygiene when hands were visibly soiled from 13:00 to 15:00 pm. Hand hygiene practices were also followed in Observation 4 from 7:00 am to 15:00 pm in which four female physicians and seven nurses in Medical and Surgical Wards were involved. Performing hand hygiene when hands were visibly soiled was noted in Observation 6 which involved three physicians and six nurses in the Department of Ophthalmology from 7:00 to 9:00 am.

All of the above-mentioned practices demonstrate poor hand hygiene practices in both hospitals. However, it is important to indicate that this finding which is based on observation data is in sharp contrast with the finding of qualitative interviews which suggests that the quality of infection control is good in both hospitals as HCWs argued. Triangulating the results of observations and interviews shows that the observation finding agrees with the interview finding which highlights HCWs' awareness of gaps in implementing IPC practices. As previously explained in section 5.3.1.1, HCWs pointed out the need for improvement of infection control practices such as the need for further education and training (participants 2, 3, 4 and 6), improvement in provision of supplies (participants 3 and 4), and staffing (participant 3) and specialists' involvement (participant 1) to improve infection control practices.

Comparing the findings obtained from the three sources of data shows that the key observation finding does not confirm the finding of the quantitative survey where most HCWs

(around 63%) indicated that the overall quality of infection control is good. However, the key observation finding agrees with the quantitative finding which shows a large majority of HCWs (around 60.3%) were aware of gaps which need to be addressed to make infection control better.

Table 5.11 below summarises the observed hand hygiene practices in the eight observation shifts:

Table 5.11 Summary of observed hand hygiene infection prevention and control practices

Observation	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Comments
Hospital / ward	H2 Orth	H1 ER	H2 Surg	H2 Surg	H1 ENT	H2 Eye	H1 Derm	H1 Geri	
Before performing hand hygiene: - Expose of forearms; - Remove all hand /wrist jewellery (a single, plain metal finger ring is permitted but should be removed, or moved up, during hand hygiene); - Ensure fingernails are clean, short and that artificial nails or nail products are not worn; - Cover all cuts or abrasions with a waterproof dressing.	X	X	X	√	√	X	X	X	Poor practices
	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	
	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	
To perform hand hygiene: - ABHRs must be available for staff as near to point of care as possible. Where this is not practical, personal ABHR dispensers should be used. Perform hand hygiene: 1. before touching a patient; 2. before clean/aseptic procedures. If ABHR cannot be used, then antimicrobial soap should be used; 3. after body fluid exposure risk; 4. after touching a patient; and 5. after touching a patient's immediate surroundings	X	X	X	X	√	√	X	X	Poor practices
	√	√	X	X	X	X	X	√	
	√	X	√	√	X	X	√	X	
	X	X	X	√	√	√	√	X	
	X	X	X	X	X	√	X	X	
	√	n/a	n/a	√	n/a	√	n/a	n/a	

*Notes: n/a not applicable or that observation didn't happen.

In the next section, the analysis of observation data in relation to respiratory cough hygiene practices is provided.

5.4.2 Respiratory cough hygiene

Analysing the findings from observations shows that the observed HCWs were implementing extremely poor cough hygiene practices. This finding is supported by noticing the following practices in the eight observation shifts:

- HCWs did not cover the nose and mouth with a disposable tissue when sneezing, coughing, wiping and blowing the nose;
- HCWs did not dispose of all used tissues promptly into a waste bin;
- HCWs did not wash their hands with non-antimicrobial liquid soap and warm water after coughing, sneezing, using tissues or after contact with respiratory secretions or objects contaminated by these secretions;
- HCWs did not use hand wipes when running water was available;
- HCWs did not apply ABHR at the first available opportunity following the use of hand wipes; and
- HCWs did not promote respiratory and cough hygiene by helping those who need assistance with this such as providing the elderly and children with tissues, plastic bags for used tissues and hand hygiene facilities as necessary.

In six out of eight observations, the observed HCWs did not cover their nose and mouth with disposable tissues when sneezing or coughing. In addition, they did not dispose used tissues promptly in a waste bin. Following respiratory cough hygiene practices was partly observed in Observations 1 and 7. In Observation 1 which involved four physicians and five nursing HCWs in the orthopaedic ward in Hospital 2, the observed HCWs covered their nose and mouth with disposable tissues when sneezing or coughing between 7:00 to 9:00 am only. Similarly, in

observation 7 which involved three physicians at the Dermatology Clinic in Hospital 1, the observed HCWs covered their nose and mouth with disposable tissues when sneezing or coughing between 7:00 to 9:00 am and 13:00 to 15:00 pm.

In all observations, HCWs did not wash their hands with non-antimicrobial liquid soap and warm water after coughing, sneezing, using tissues or after contact with respiratory secretions or objects contaminated by these secretions. Furthermore, there was a high tendency to use hand wipes even when there was running water in all observation shifts. In most cases, the observed HCWs did not apply ABHR at the first available opportunity following use of hand wipes. Not applying ABHR was observed in six out of eight observations (Observations 1, 3, 5, 6, 7 and 8).

However, some of the observed HCWs in Observations 2 and 4 performed ABHR after using hand wipes. Following respiratory hand hygiene was seen in Observation 2 from 1:00 to 3:00 am, 7:00 to 9:00 am, 16:00 to 18:00 pm and 22:00 pm to 24:00 am. The observation took place in the emergency department (ER) ward in Hospital 1 involving two physicians and eight nurses. Similarly, in Observation 4, which involved 4 female physicians and 7 female nurses in Medical and Surgical Wards in Hospital 2, the HCWs were keen on washing their hands and performing ABHR from 7:00 am to 15:00 pm.

Finally, in all observation shifts, none of the observed HCWs promoted respiratory hygiene by helping those who need assistance with this such as providing the elderly and children with tissues, plastic bags for used tissues and hand hygiene facilities as necessary.

Table 5.12 below provides a summary of the observed respiratory and cough hygiene practices in both hospitals:

Table 5.12 Summary of observed respiratory and cough hygiene practices:

Observation	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Comments
Hospital / ward	H2 Orth	H1 ER	H2 Surg	H2 Surg	H1 ENT	H2 Eye	H1 Derm	H1 Geri	
Cover the nose and mouth with a disposable tissue when sneezing, coughing, wiping and blowing the nose.	√	X	X	X	X	X	√	X	Extremely poor practices
Dispose of all used tissues promptly into a waste bin.	X	√	X	X	X	X	√	X	
Wash hands with non-antimicrobial liquid soap and warm water after coughing, sneezing, using tissues or after contact with respiratory secretions or objects contaminated by these secretions.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Hand wipes should not be used by staff in the hospital or care home setting for hand hygiene unless there is no running water available.	X	√	X	√	X	X	X	X	
Staff may use hand wipes followed by ABHR and should wash their hands at the first available opportunity.	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Keep contaminated hands away from the eyes, nose and mouth.	X	X	√	X	X	X	√	X	
Staff should promote respiratory and cough hygiene, helping those (e.g., elderly, children) who need assistance with this, e.g., providing patients with tissues, plastic bags for used tissues and hand hygiene facilities as necessary.	X	X	√	X	X	X	X	X	

5.4.3 Use of personal protective equipment (PPEs)

The analysis of observation data shows poor PPE practices in both hospitals. In half observation shifts (four out of eight), the storage of PPEs in both hospitals was found close to the point of use. For example, in Hospital 1, storing PPEs close to the point of used was noted in Observations 2, 5, and 8. Similarly, in Hospital 2, Observation 3 shows the storage of PPEs close to the point of use. However, in Observations 3 and 8, PPEs were not seen stored well in a clear or dry area to prevent contamination until they are needed for use. Storing PPEs under poor conditions was seen from 7:00 am to 15:00 pm.

Based on observation data, most of the observed HCWs used single-use items in almost all observation shifts except in Observation 2 which took place in Hospital 1. Nevertheless, the results indicate that in almost all observations PPEs were not properly disposed of after use into the correct

waste stream. This may suggest having poor PPE practices in both hospitals. Proper disposal of PPEs after use was seen only in Observation 1 from 7:00 am to 15:00 pm. As mentioned previously, Observation 1 took place in the orthopaedic ward in Hospital 2 involving four physicians and five nursing HCWs.

In most observations (six out of eight), the observed HCWs wore gloves when exposure to blood and/or other body fluids was expected. Using gloves as a precaution was seen in Observations 2, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8. However, in Observations 1 and 3, both in Hospital 2, HCWs were not seen using gloves even when contact with body fluids was likely. HCWs' observed behaviour may be associated with poor PPE practices. This conclusion is based on observing four physicians and five nursing HCWs in the orthopaedic ward from 7:00 am to 15:00 pm in Observation 1 and observing six male physicians and six male nurses in the medical and surgical ward from 7:00 to 9:00 am and 13:00 to 15:00 pm in Observation 3.

Although most of the observed HCWs wore gloves when contact with body fluids was likely, the majority did not change their gloves immediately after completing a task or a procedure. In six out of eight observation shifts, HCWs were not seen changing their gloves following a task completion. To be precise, in Observations 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 which in total involved fifty-seven HCWs out of sixty-nine observed HCWs did not change their gloves after completing a task. Such a practice is associated with poor PPE practices. However, in Observations 2 and 8 which both happened in Hospital 1, the twelve observed HCWs were seen changing their gloves immediately after use.

Another observed example of poor PPE practice is seeing HCWs not changing their gloves immediately after performing a puncture. After performing a puncture in three observation shifts, Observations 2, 3, and 7, the observed HCWs did not change their gloves immediately after use in Observation 3. In this observation which happened in the medical and surgical ward in Hospital 2, six male physicians and six male nurses were involved.

Not using the right type of gloves which are proper for use and fit well to avoid excessive sweating and interference with dexterity is another observed example of poor PPE practice in the two healthcare facilities involved in this research. In five out of six observation shifts, the observed HCWs were seen wearing gloves which were either large, loose or ill-fitted. Not using proper gloves was noticed in Observations 2 and 5 which happened in Hospital 1 and in Observations 1, 3 and 6 which happened in Hospital 2. However, in Observation 8, the physician and nurse observed in the General Gastroenterology Clinic in Hospital 1 used well-fitted gloves from 7:00 am to 15:00 pm.

As for aprons, in all observation shifts, a good culture of using aprons was apparent when HCWs anticipated contamination of their uniform. Nevertheless, in five observation shifts, the soiled aprons were not changed after attending to a patient and before attending another one. For example, in Observations 3, 5, 6, 7 and 8, the observed HCWs did not change aprons between patients and/or following completion of a procedure or task. Changing aprons between patients and/or following completion of a procedure as recommended was seen in Observation 2 from 1:00 to 3:00 am and Observation 4 from 7:00 to 9:00 am.

Similarly, although most of the HCWs in six observation shifts were seen wearing full body gowns when there was a risk of extreme splashing in the operation theatre, these were not changed at once following the completion of a task in a bit more than half of the observation shifts. Precisely, in Observations 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 the forty-eight observed HCWs were not seen changing their full body gowns after completing a task or a procedure. Changing full body gowns was noticed in Observation 2 from 1:00 to 9:00 am and from 16:00 to 21:00 pm.

Finally, in almost all observation shifts HCWs did not wear eye/face protection at the time blood and/or body fluid contamination to the eyes/face was anticipated particularly during aerosol generation procedures. Wearing eye/face protection was seen in very few instances in Observations 4, 5 and 6 mainly from 7:00 to 9:00 am. This indicates observing poor PPE practices. In Table 5.13 below, a summary of the observed PPEs practices is presented:

Table 5.13 Summary of the observed use of PPEs:

Observation	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Comments
Hospital / ward	H2 Orth	H1 ER	H2 Surg	H2 Surg	H1 ENT	H2 Eye	H1 Derm	H1 Geri	
<p>PPEs must be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - located close to the point of use; - stored to prevent contamination in a clean/dry area until required for use (expiry dates must be adhered to); - single-use only items unless specified by the manufacturer; and - disposed of after use into the correct waste stream, i.e., healthcare waste or domestic waste. <p>Reusable PPE items, e.g., non-disposable goggles/face shields/visors must have a decontamination schedule with responsibility assigned.</p>	X	√	√	X	√	X	X	√	Good and poor practices
	√	√	X	√	√	√	√	X	
	√	X	√	√	√	√	√	√	
	√	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
<p>Gloves must be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - worn when exposure to blood and/or other body fluids is anticipated/likely;² - changed immediately after each patient and/or following completion of a procedure or task; - changed if a perforation or puncture is suspected; and - appropriate for use, fit for purpose and well-fitting to avoid excessive sweating and interference with dexterity. <p>Double gloving is recommended during some Exposure-Prone Procedures (EPPs), e.g., orthopaedic and gynaecological operations or when attending major trauma incidents.</p>	X	√	X	√	√	√	√	√	Poor practices
	X	√	X	X	X	X	X	√	
	n/a	√	X	n/a	n/a	n/a	√	n/a	
	X	X	X	n/a	X	X	n/a	√	
<p>Aprons must be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - worn to protect uniform or clothes when contamination is anticipated/likely, e.g., when in direct care contact with a patient; and - changed between patients and/or following completion of a procedure or task <p>Full body gowns/Fluid repellent coveralls must be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - worn when there is a risk of extensive splashing of blood and/or other body fluids, e.g., in the operating theatre; and - changed between patients and immediately after completion of a procedure or task. 	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	Poor practices
	n/a	√	X	X	X	X	X	X	
	n/a	√	√	√	√	√	√	n/a	
	n/a	√	X	√	X	X	X	n/a	
<p>Eye/face protection (including full face visors) must be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - worn if blood and/or body fluid contamination to the eyes/face is anticipated/likely, e.g., by members of the surgical theatre team and always during Aerosol Generating Procedures. Regular corrective spectacles are not considered eye protection. 	X	X	X	√	√	X	X	X	Very poor practices

The findings from observation which suggest improper use of PPEs may be related to the shortage in supplies which some interview participants highlighted previously in section 5.3.1.1. Participants 3 and 7 argued that most of the time the hospital runs out of PPEs and supplies, particularly N95 masks, and sometimes it takes long before these are replenished. The shortage of supplies can impact on improving the quality of infection control in the two hospitals particularly as the outbreak of infections can threaten patients' lives and requires urgent actions from HCWs.

However, it is important to point out that the findings from observations are in sharp contrast with the findings of the quantitative survey, where most HCWs indicated that their hospitals and wards/departments were providing enough resources and supplies for infection control, whereas a few HCWs (63/105) and (16/11) agreed and strongly agreed that the ward or hospital does not provide enough supplies. This suggests that while there are supplies, in the survey a substantial number of HCWs 121 and 94, (between 21.7% and 30.0%) thought that sometimes these supplies are not adequate.

5.5 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER FIVE

This research aims to provide a better understanding of infection control practices in KSA, with a particular focus on the factors which influence compliance with recommended IPC. However, the findings from the three sources of data show disagreements regarding the ways HCWs perceived the status of infection control practices at their respective hospitals as they expressed their perceptions in the semi-structured interviews and the quantitative survey and the ways HCWs were observed implementing infection control practices in both healthcare facilities.

In contrast with the findings of qualitative interviews and quantitative survey which suggest that the quality of infection control is good in both hospitals as the participants indicated, the results of observation showed poor infection control practices as demonstrated by implementing poor hand hygiene and cough hygiene practices as well as improper use of PPEs. HCWs were seen not washing their hands or putting on gloves, before and after touching patients.

They also were not seen changing their disposable aprons after conducting a procedure. Sometimes, PPEs were not disposed properly and were not stored in easily accessible places. Therefore, the findings of observations suggest that compliance with IPC procedures was suboptimal in both hospitals included in this study.

Nevertheless, triangulating the results from the three data sources shows that HCWs are aware of gaps in implementing IPC practices in the two hospitals which need to be addressed to improve compliance with recommended IPC practices. A number of factors were identified as contributing to HCWs' non-compliance with the IPC including the lack of sufficient supplies, the need for further education and proper training, the lack of well-trained IPC specialists and poor surveillance which are vital to improve infection control practices. It is important to indicate that a number of demographic and sociocultural factors such as education, gender, profession and nationality, were associated with influencing HCWs' perceptions infection control quality. The next chapter discusses the results in relation to the literature.

CHAPTER SIX: DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

6.1 INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this chapter is to present and discuss the key findings of the study in relation to the existing literature to better understand the perceptions of HCWs of infection prevention and control and identify the factors associated with compliance with recommended IPC practices in two tertiary hospitals in the Qassim region of KSA. This discussion of findings facilitates gaining a comprehensive understanding of infection control strategies, influences, gaps and barriers in implementing IPC practices in KSA. The identification of influences affecting compliance with IPC practices and gaps in IPC practices can facilitate the development of strategies which can support long-term compliance with IPC practices in KSA.

The research was guided by the conceptual framework of the study, the SEIPS Framework (Carayon et al., 2006/2015) which involves the eight core components of the WHO framework for the design of infection control programmes which has been developed to prevent healthcare associated infections and prepare for and respond to communicable diseases crises (WHO, 2011). The main six themes developed to address the research questions are: overall IPC quality, IPC leadership, guidelines and policy, perceived IPC competence and training, IPC surveillance and evaluation, IPC supplies and resources, and IPC culture.

The chapter begins with presenting a summary of key findings followed by a critical detailed discussion. To integrate the findings with the current evidence and organise the presentation of discussion, the three main research questions are used as main headings. The chapter concludes with presenting the strengths, challenges and limitations of the study.

6.2 SUMMARY OF KEY FINDINGS

According to Watkins et al., (2006), infection control practice is the foundation of modern healthcare. Nevertheless, the authors indicate that researching the perceptions of HCWs of infection control and how these perceptions affect adherence to the recommended IPC guidelines is minimal. While this has changed over the past few years in Europe as extensive research has been conducted, there has been little research carried out in KSA healthcare facilities, the local context of this study.

The perceptions and attitudes of HCWs towards infection control have a huge impact on the clinical environment which, in turn, influences patient exposure to infection-related illnesses. Patients are at a higher risk of healthcare-associated infections when HCWs have poor perceptions and attitudes towards complying with recommended IPC practices. Therefore, this study investigates HCWs' perceptions of infection control practices and how these perceptions among other factors influence compliance with the recommended IPC practices in two KSA healthcare facilities.

Guided by the conceptual framework developed for this study, some factors which can potentially influence compliance with IPC practices were identified based on the literature review. For example, firstly, institutional factors including formulation and implementation of IPC policies and training, organisational support in the provision of supplies and equipment, good surveillance systems and organisational culture, whether it is supportive or blame-centric. Secondly, individual factors such as demographic and sociocultural factors which include age, gender, education, ethnicity and self-efficiency were identified.

In line with many national and international studies, for example, Watkins et al., (2006), Allegranzi and Pittet (2009), Efstathiou et al., (2011), Ward (2012), Ayub et al., (2013), Mazi et al., (2013), Tan and Jeffrey (2015), Hosseinialhashemi et al., (2015), Shah et al., (2015), Smiddy et al., (2015), Offner et al., (2016), Edet et al., (2017) and Rabaan et al., (2017), the findings of

this study confirm that both institutional and individual factors can positively and/or negatively affect HCWs' adherence to recommended IPC practices.

In addition to exploring HCWs' perceptions based on their perspectives, the study investigated HCWs' compliance with infection control procedures including hand hygiene, respiratory cough hygiene, the use and storage of personal protective equipment (PPEs) through direct non-participant observation to verify whether the existence of positive perceptions translate into compliance. However, similar to the findings of many studies universally including Jain et al., (2012), Ayub et al., (2013), Bai (2015) and Hosseinialhashemi et al., (2015) in India, Tan and Jeffrey (2015) in KSA, Hessels and Larson (2016) in America and Edet et al., (2017) in Nigeria, triangulating the findings shows large differences between the knowledge, perceptions and attitudes of HCWs towards infection control and their compliance with IPC procedures in practice at the two research hospitals because of several institutional and individual influences.

In agreement with Tan and Jeffrey (2015), the findings indicate that achieving and sustaining compliance is still a challenge in KSA healthcare facilities despite publishing numerous guidelines. The discrepancy between HCWs' perceived IPC practices and their observed compliance with IPC guidelines may reflect people's tendency to exaggerate their socially desirable behaviours when self-reporting their practices as Haridi et al., (2016) suggest. Despite indicating some improvements in infection control in KSA, especially since the MERS coronavirus outbreak, there are still challenges that need to be addressed and areas of improvement identified particularly in relation to supplies, education and training, surveillance and the staffing of the infection control department.

The key findings which emerged then based on the three sources of data are summarised below in Figure 6.1:

Figure 6.1 Key Research Findings

The main research findings summarised above are discussed in detail in relation to the literature in the following sections.

6.3 WHAT ARE HEALTHCARE WORKERS' PERCEPTIONS OF INFECTION PREVENTION AND CONTROL PRACTICES WITHIN THE TWO RESEARCH HOSPITALS IN KSA?

6.3.1 HCWs' Positive Perceptions of IPC

Based on HCWs' perspectives, the findings show positive perceptions of IPC measures because of several positive influences. For example, positive perceptions are indicated by HCWs' self-beliefs about having good knowledge about IPC, showing good level of confidence in the hospitals' preparedness for infection outbreaks, offering or receiving IPC training, having appropriate IPC policies to guide HCWs, showing awareness of the importance of applying infection control precautions, showing leadership commitment to satisfy IPC requirements and demonstrating the tremendous improvement in practising IPC in all departments at the two research hospitals in the last few years. What is implied in the findings then, in agreement with Haridi et al., (2016), it is important to emphasise, sustain and improve the structural support for IPC within the institutions to ensure adherence with recommended IPC practices.

The findings of the survey and interview suggest that HCWs perceived the quality of IPC practices to be good. Most HCWs believed that the hospitals are prepared for infection outbreaks. The findings suggest that there is good infection control leadership, training, and guidelines as HCWs argued. HCWs believe that the IPC policies which are primarily based on the Centre for Diseases Control (CDC), the World Health Organisation (WHO), the Gulf Cooperation Countries (GCC), and the National Health Safety Network's (NHSN) infection control policies are good. Moreover, the findings indicate having mandatory IPC training and education as well as monitoring and evaluation strategies in place to assess HCWs' compliance with IPC guidelines as positive influencers.

Based on HCWs' perspectives, the WHO set of guidelines on core components IPC programmes (WHO, 2011, 2016) appears to be applied in hospitals. Unlike nursing students in Ward's (2013) study and professional nurses in Edet et al., (2017) who showed negative perceptions about IPC, in the survey and interview in this study HCWs showed awareness of the

importance of adhering to IPC guidelines and HCWs believed that they followed IPC guidance. The findings of the studies conducted by Walker et al., (2014), Hosseinialhashemi, et al., (2015) and Hessels and Larson (2016) suggest that prioritising infection prevention and control can facilitate having a positive attitude to IPC and the development of a compliance culture which can reduce the number of infections significantly. Moreover, based on Quan et al., (2015), knowledge can positively influence the use of standard precautions through attitude mediation. However, the findings of the survey and interview contrast with the key finding of observations in this study which shows a gap between HCWs' perceptions and the actual application of IPC practices. This key finding is in accordance with the literature such as Jain et al., (2012), Ayub et al., (2013), Bai (2015), Tan and Jeffrey, (2015), and Edet et al., (2017).

In their quantitative cross-sectional study in India, for example, Ayub et al., (2013) caution that having a positive attitude towards IPC measures is not in itself sufficient to influence HCWs' compliance with recommended IPC guidelines and policies. Along a similar line, in their quantitative survey in KSA, Tan and Jeffrey (2015) explore HCWs' perceptions about the factors that facilitate IPC in KSA. One of the main findings of the study indicates that HCWs showed a high level of awareness about healthcare-associated infections and the importance of hand hygiene. Tan and Jeffrey (2015) attribute this awareness to the formal training HCWs attended previously. However, their findings suggest that being knowledgeable does not necessarily lead to high level of compliance with IPC practices.

Edet et al., (2017) report similar findings. For example, Edet et al., (2017) indicate that based on the responses they received in their qualitative study, nurses seemed to be knowledgeable about the meaning of IPC in the hospital setting and they showed good understanding of the benefits of adhering to standard precautions. However, practising standard precautions was hindered by the lack of supplies as the nurses pointed out (Edet et al., 2017). Therefore, Tan and Jeffrey (2015) and Haridi et al., (2016) recommend conducting observational studies to determine

the level of compliance with recommended hand hygiene practices, which is one of the strengths of using the mixed methods approach in this study.

6.3.2 HCWs' Suboptimal Compliance with IPC Precautions

Despite HCWs' emphasis on the importance of IPC and adherence to recommended guidelines, the findings indicate that HCWs' observed compliance with IPC practices was poor, that is, suboptimal. This confirms what Ayub et al., (2013) indicate by saying that having a positive attitude towards IPC measures alone does not necessarily affect HCWs' compliance with recommended IPC practices in reality. The finding is also consistent with the finding of Tan and Jeffrey (2015) mentioned above as showing awareness does not necessarily translate to compliance. The observed suboptimal compliance is also in accordance with the findings of the survey and interview which highlight HCWs' awareness of barriers and gaps in IPC practices which need to be addressed to improve compliance with IPC guidelines in the two healthcare facilities included in this study.

The finding of this study which shows suboptimal compliance with IPC procedures is consistent with the findings of many studies in developed and developing countries, which Ayub et al., (2013), Mazi et al., (2013), Song et al., (2013), De Bono et al., (2014), Bai (2015) and Hessels and Larson (2016) indicate, continue to demonstrate suboptimal IPC practice because of several factors discussed in detail in this chapter. However, the findings are contrary to the findings of Haridi et al., (2016) who conducted a quantitative cross-sectional survey to explore demographic, professional and institutional factors associated with good compliance with standard IPC precautions among dentists and dental assistants in KSA. Haridi et al., (2016) indicate that self-reported compliance with standard precautions was good, with the majority (90.1%) of dentists suggesting that they are complying with standard procedures. However, as Haridi et al., (2016) point out, the figures which indicate HCWs' perceived high adherence to recommended IPC practices may represent an overestimate as they were derived from self-reporting of

compliance with IPC practices. Haridi et al., (2016) indicate that people tend to exaggerate their socially desired behavior when self-reporting. Therefore, the authors suggested using observations to verify and complement their survey.

In their questionnaire-based analysis of IPC in healthcare facilities in KSA, Rabaan et al., (2017) indicate that effective IPC in healthcare facilities relies on both awareness and compliance of HCWs at all levels of the organisation. Poor compliance with IPC guidelines, which is indicated by the findings of the current study, adversely affects the quality of healthcare delivery and poses health threats to patients and HCWs. The WHO (2011) framework recommends that healthcare facilities implement infection control guidelines to reduce the occurrence and spread of disease as well as ensure the early detection and isolation of infection.

According to Assiri et al., (2013), the spread of infection is prevented by the implementation of transmission-based precautions which involve standard infection control precautions including regular hand hygiene, the use of personal protective equipment such as gloves, gowns and eye protection, and vaccinations to reduce the risk associated with the transmission of blood-borne microorganisms and pathogens. As Rim and Lim (2014) indicate, HCWs are expected to implement IPC procedures when dealing with recognised and unrecognised sources of infection such as blood and other body fluids.

In their review of the literature, Allegranzi and Pittet (2009) indicate that handwashing is the most essential element of IPC. Similarly, Tan and Jeffrey (2015, p. 108) describe hand hygiene as the “cornerstone” of IPC measures in reducing healthcare associated infections. The WHO’s initiative “My five moments for hand hygiene” (Allegranzi et al., 2007) is considered a standardised approach to guide the training, monitoring and reporting compliance with hand hygiene. In this approach, the five moments identified are: before patient contact, before an aseptic task, after body fluid exposure risk, after patient contact and after contact with patient surroundings. Nevertheless, the findings of this study highlight observing poor infection control

practices as demonstrated by implementing poor hand hygiene and cough hygiene practices as well as improper use and storage of PPEs.

As the findings of this study show, the majority of observed HCWs were not seen washing their hands nor putting on appropriate gloves, before and after touching the patient, after touching the patient's immediate surroundings, before applying clean/antiseptic procedures, and after body fluid exposure. In addition, the majority of observed HCWs did not cover their noses and mouths with a disposable tissue when sneezing or coughing and did not dispose of the used tissue promptly in a waste bin. These practices suggest a poor baseline hand and cough hygiene compliance. Furthermore, the findings of the study show that observed HCWs did not wear the right type of gloves, change their gloves immediately after use, or when performing a puncture nor change their disposable aprons as recommended after conducting a procedure. Sometimes, PPEs were not disposed properly and were not stored in easily accessible places. Such practices are associated with poor PPE practices which negatively affect compliance with IPC precautions as Efstathiou et al., (2011) highlight in their qualitative study which examines the factors that influence nurses' compliance with standard precaution in Cyprus. To improve adherence to IPC. Efstathiou et al., (2011) recommend having protective equipment at HCWs' disposal whenever they need them.

The findings of this study are consistent with the results of similar studies in KSA such as those conducted by Mazi et al., (2013), Tan and Jeffrey (2015), and Rabaan et al., (2017) who reported poor implementation of recommended IPC practices. For instance, Mazi et al., (2013) evaluated HCWs' compliance with IPC practices, pre and post implementation of WHO initiative. The findings of Mazi et al.,'s (2013) study indicate poor compliance prior to the use of the intervention strategy. Although the findings of their study indicate observing significant improvement in the immediate post intervention period, Mazi et al., (2013) suggest that high level of improved compliance was not sustained in certain phases of the extended follow up period. Therefore, based on the observed inability to achieve sustained hand hygiene compliance Mazi et al., (2013) concluded that changing behavior is complex and using intervention campaigns can

temporarily result in behavior modification. As Quan et al., (2015) indicate, behavior change is a long process which is influenced by many internal and external factors including knowledge, attitudes, intention, self-efficacy, stress, social support and environment.

For sustained hand hygiene compliance, Mazi et al., (2013) recommend considering other factors which affect adherence to recommended IPC practices, which this study aimed to identify to facilitate the development of strategies which can support sustained compliance with recommended IPC practices in KSA. In line with many studies including, for example, Watkins et al., (2006), Allegranzi and Pittet (2009), Jain et al., (2012), Ayub et al., (2013), Song et al., (2013), De Bono et al., (2014), Hosseinalhashemi et al., (2015), Smiddy et al., (2015) Hale et al., (2015), Quan et al., (2015), Haridi et al., (2016) and Edet et al., (2017), the findings of this study show several factors that influence HCWs' ability to comply with recommended IPC guidelines. The factors which acted as barriers and/or facilitators to IPC compliance are discussed in the next sections along with a discussion of the identified gaps in IPC practices in the two research hospitals.

6.4 WHAT INSTITUTIONAL FACTORS INFLUENCE HEALTHCARE WORKERS' COMPLIANCE WITH INFECTION PREVENTION AND CONTROL PRACTICES WITHIN THE TWO HOSPITALS IN KSA?

Based on the literature, organisational support, which includes for example, the provision of adequate equipment, supplies, policies, guidelines, leadership, staffing, education and training, surveillance and feedback are important for compliance with infection control practices (Luo et al., 2010; Efstathiou et al., 2011; Ayub et al., 2013; Mazi et al., 2013; Sodhi et al., 2013; Song et al., 2013; Mortada and Zalat, 2014, Walker et al., 2014; Bai, 2015; Piai-Morais et al., 2015; Hale et al., 2015; Hosseinalhashemi et al., 2015; Smiddy et al., 2015; Tan and Jeffrey, 2015; Quan et al., 2015; Hessels and Larson, 2016; Haridi et al., 2016; Offner et al., 2016; Wetzker et al., 2016; Ng et al., 2017; Rabaan et al., 2017). Many authors argue that the lack of organisational support is more likely to lead to a lack of individual efforts and teamwork as these practices are likely to

make HCWs develop a negative attitude or perception towards infection control which consequently lead to non-compliance (Efstathiou et al., 2011; Ward, 2012; Amoran et al., 2013; Ayub et al., 2013; Walker et al., 2014; Tan and Jeffrey, 2015; Smiddy et al., 2015; Piai-Morais et al., 2015; Quan et al., 2015; Haridi et al., 2016; Rabaan et al., 2017). In accordance with the literature, the triangulated findings show the influential role of institutional factors in implementing recommended IPC practices based on HCWs' perspectives and their observed IPC practices.

6.4.1 Institutional Factors as Facilitators to IPC Compliance

Based on HCWs' perspectives, the findings suggest that there are mainly three institutional factors which positively influence adherence to IPC guidelines. The findings show that the majority of HCWs attributed their perceived good quality of IPC implementation to the effective infection control leadership in their ward or hospital, having a set of guidelines that HCWs are able to access to support IPC practices and focusing on offering appropriate IPC training and bedside teaching programme. These findings are consistent with the findings of similar studies such as Luo et al., (2010), De Bono et al., (2014), Walker et al., (2014), Tan and Jeffrey (2015), Smiddy et al., (2015), Haridi et al., (2016), Edet et al., (2017) and Rabaan et al., (2017) which indicate the importance of organisational factors such as policy, guidelines, leadership and staff training in positively influencing HCWs' compliance with recommended IPC practices.

6.4.1.1 Positive Organisational Culture

According to Tan and Jeffrey (2015), organisational factors primarily including staff engagement, commitment of the department heads and leadership, and the provision of education, training, and guidelines significantly promote positive hand hygiene practices. Prioritising IPC implementation, having supportive leadership, providing HCWs with opportunities to learn and establishing monitoring programmes can help create a positive organisational culture which is

important to influence compliance with recommended IPC practices among HCWs such as hand hygiene (De Bono et al., 2014; Walker et al., 2014; Hosseinialhashemi, et al., 2015; Smiddy et al., 2015; Hessels and Larson, 2016).

Organisational culture as De Bono et al., (2014) indicate encompasses both the perceptions and practices which the members of the organization share. Having shared beliefs and values does not only give members of the organisation meaning, but also provides them with the rules for behaviour in their organisation (De Bono et al., 2014). Therefore, De Bono et al., (2014) argue that effective IPC depends on creating a supportive organisational culture in the organisation where there is strong leadership and an adequate number of well-trained staff. Poor leadership, on the other hand, can hinder the implementation of IPC practices. (Ayub et al., 2013; Hale et al., 2015; Hessels and Larson 2016).

In this study, the findings of the survey show an optimal supportive culture as most HCWs agreed that staff are supported to improve their infection prevention and control practice. The findings also show that most HCWs indicate having good infection control leadership and a set of guidelines that they are able to access to support IPC practices. In interviews, one of the healthcare workers pointed out that sanctions are applied when they do not follow IPC guidelines in the hospital or miss an IPC training opportunity. According to Edet et al., (2017), having effective IPC policies and guidelines can enhance the professional experiences and understanding of infection control practices among HCWs. Therefore, the presence of a positive organisational culture in the researched hospitals is perceived to have a positive influence on compliance with recommended IPC practices. Nonetheless, observing suboptimal compliance indicates the existence of some negative influences or barriers which hinder compliance with IPC precautions in the two healthcare facilities involved in this study.

6.4.1.2 Infection Control Education and Training

The findings of the survey and interview suggest that most HCWs have received training. The findings indicate that to increase HCWs' knowledge of IPC and ensure implementing IPC guidelines, there are compulsory annual orientation sessions, individual training programmes, bedside teaching programmes, programmes based on analysing the current practices of HCWs, weekly lectures and workshops. Based on interviews, there are written exams and Hospital 1 is offering diplomas in infection control, which HCWs perceive as examples of improvement of infection control practice in KSA.

Although the literature indicates having conflicting evidence regarding the role of education and training in improving adherence with recommended IPC practices as some studies suggest that more knowledge can translate to better outcomes (Mazi et al., 2013; Sodhi et al., 2013; Song et al., 2013; Haridi et al., 2016; Wetzker et al., 2016; Offner et al., 2016; Ng et al., 2017; Rabaan et al., 2017), while others indicate that having knowledge may not in itself lead to high level of compliance with IPC practices (Jain, et al., 2012; Ayub et al., 2013; Bai, 2015; Tan and Jeffrey, 2015; Quan et al., 2015; Edet et al., 2017), in this study HCWs expressed their wish to receive additional education and training. Despite indicating that HCWs have received IPC training and they perceived it as a positive influence, to improve the quality of IPC practices at the research hospitals particularly in relation to hand hygiene, most HCWs highlighted their need for further training in both the survey and interview. This may suggest as Rabaan et al., (2017) note, HCWs may consider the level of staff training offered not appropriate enough to equip them with skills needed for implementing recommended IPC policy and guidelines. The findings of interviews suggest that training sessions in the last two years may have been reduced compared to previous years. Therefore, based on HCWs' perspectives, the findings show the importance of offering sustained and adequate training to increase HCWs' knowledge and enhance compliance with IPC practices similar to many studies including Allegranzi and Pittet (2009), Luo et al.,

(2010), Song et al., (2013), Mortada and Zalat (2014), Smiddy et al., (2015), Haridi et al., (2016), Offner et al., (2016), Wetzker et al., (2016) and Rabaan et al., (2017).

As Luo et al., (2010) recommend in their quantitative study of the factors influencing compliance with standard precautions in nursing in china, strengthening standard precautions training can help reduce hospital infections and protect the health of patients and HCWs. The authors indicate that changing individual practice and improving compliance with standard precautions rely on familiarising individuals with the content and meanings of the standard precautions and strengthening their health concepts as health activity habits can be developed through learning, attaining knowledge and skills, and forming health beliefs and attitudes. Therefore, in line with the recommendations of many studies, primarily Allegranzi and Pittet (2009) and Luo et al., (2010), this study suggests that HCWs in KSA would benefit from providing sustained training and education particularly on hand washing, cough hygiene practices and the storage and use of PPEs to extend their knowledge about IPC practices and increase their compliance with IPC guidelines.

Although the findings of the survey and interview suggest that there is a positive organisational culture and most HCWs show positive perceptions of IPC, the findings of the observation indicate that having knowledge, positive attitudes towards IPC and receiving training are not sufficient to ensure adherence with IPC precautions. The triangulated findings show that there are some institutional factors which negatively influence compliance with IPC precautions. These factors are discussed in the next section based on HCWs' perceptions and their observed IPC practices with support from the literature.

6.4.2 Institutional Factors as Barriers to IPC Compliance

Consistent with the findings of Rabaan et al., (2017) in KSA, the findings of this study indicate that HCWs are aware of limitations in the implementation of IPC precautions because of some institutional barriers. The findings show that several institutional factors are perceived as

contributing to non-compliance with the recommended IPC guidelines primarily including the lack of proper supplies, shortage of infection control personnel and inefficient infection surveillance mechanisms. The findings are in line with many studies such as Allegranzi and Pittet (2009), Luo et al., (2010), Efstathiou et al., (2011), Amoran et al., (2013), Ayub et al., (2013), Rosenthal et al., (2013), Bai (2015), Odell (2015), Piai-Morais et al., (2015), Tan and Jeffrey (2015), Quan et al., (2015), Smiddy et al., (2015), Haridi et al., (2016), Edet et al., (2017) and Rabaan et al., (2017) which show how the inadequacy of supplies, lack of well-trained infection control staff and inefficient infection surveillance systems can influence HCWs' ability to comply with IPC precautions in practice. The barriers to IPC implementation the findings show may explain the disparity between HCWs' positive perceptions of IPC and the observed suboptimal compliance with recommended IPC practices. The barriers identified in the study may also justify the contradictory findings collected from the three data sources: the survey, interview and observation. Identifying barriers, as Song et al., (2013) suggest, is important to determine focused areas for improvement and consequently improve compliance with IPC precautions.

6.4.2.1 Shortages in Supplies

Despite showing a supportive infection control culture in the survey and the interview, the findings indicate that most of HCWs identified shortages in supplies as the main influential factor affecting their IPC practices. Therefore, most HCWs indicated that the lack of adequate supplies requires attention to improve the quality of IPC practices in their healthcare facilities. In particular, in interviews HCWs pointed out the lack of N95 face masks and PPEs such as gloves, culture bottles, petri dishes, sanitisers, and antiseptic gels which are vital to reduce healthcare-associated infections. Despite having some improvement in the budget allocations towards infection control since the SARS outbreak, in interviews HCWs indicated that there are problems with their supplies for cleaning and hand washing which are essentially needed for infection control. Based on

observations, the findings also suggest that PPEs were not properly used, and they were not sometimes properly stored to prevent contamination until required for use.

As HCWs explained, most of the time the hospital runs out of PPEs particularly N95 masks, and sometimes it takes long before these are replenished. HCWs indicated that the inadequacy of supplies negatively affects compliance with standard precautions. This is similar to the findings of Efstathiou et al., (2011) qualitative study which involved 30 nurses in four focus groups to investigate factors influencing nurses' compliance with standard infection control procedures. According to Efstathiou et al., (2011), the non-availability of protective equipment such as masks and gloves is one of the main factors impeding compliance with IPC. As the findings of the study carried out by Quan et al., (2015) show, when proper PPEs are lacking, having improvements in HCWs' knowledge and attitudes are not enough to ensure adherence to recommended practices. The literature abounds with examples of studies which suggest that the lack of adequate supplies in healthcare facilities is the main reason for non-compliance with standard precautions such as Amoran et al., (2013) in Nigeria, Tan and Jeffrey (2015) in KSA, Piai-Morais et al., (2015) in Brazil, Quan et al., (2015) in China and Smiddy et al., (2015) in the USA. Therefore, as for example, Luo et al., (2010) recommend, providing adequate PPEs is proposed in this study to protect HCWs and patients as well as reduce hospital infections. Storing PPEs at HCWs' disposal may positively contribute to enhancing the implementation of recommended IPC practices as Efstathiou et al., (2011) advise.

In this study, it became apparent in interviews that some departments put up regulations to limit when N95 face masks can be used because of the shortage of supplies. Some HCWs alluded to bureaucracy as one of the main reasons for the lack of supplies. Because the studied hospitals are government hospitals and orders for supplies such as PPEs need to be approved by the Ministry of Health headquarters, delays happen as a result of the remoteness of the two healthcare facilities. However, it is important to point out that some HCWs suggested that the lack of supplies was merely a management issue among infection control leaders. For example, it was indicated that

having insufficient supplies was due to infection control leaders' non-familiarity with creating a good supply chain or estimating volume of resources that would be required over a certain period of time and creating a replenishment or restocking plan.

What is implicit in HCWs' comments is that a blame culture around making mistakes may exist at the hospitals although most HCWs said that staff are supported to improve their IPC practice. Based on the findings of the survey, opinions were divided regarding HCWs' perceptions of the existence of a blame culture, with a bit less than half of HCWs indicating that there is a blame culture in their respective hospitals. Consistent with the findings of Ayub et al., (2013) and Rabaan et al., (2017), nearly about half of HCWs believed that some staff do not follow IPC policies and guidelines. Having a busy schedule during the day and carelessness of HCWs were cited as the reasons for non-compliance and the leading causes of infections in interviews which were similarly suggested in Rabaan et al.,'s (2017) study in KSA.

A good number of HCWs suggested in the survey that nurses tended to be more blamed than physicians when there is an infection outbreak or incident in the ward or hospitals. Therefore, the study recommends addressing the reasons that can lead to the development of a blame culture around making mistakes which can result in negative perceptions that can hinder compliance with IPC precautions. The study recommends addressing the divide between knowledge and practice through developing intervention strategies that can reinforce a supportive environment where the essential needs which ensure HCWs' implementation of recommended IPC practices are provided. Having well-trained infection control leaders who can develop appropriate restocking plans that meet HCWs' needs is critical to respond to the identified barriers to IPC compliance and ensure that the knowledge and skills are translated into practice.

6.4.2.2 Lack of Well-trained Infection Control Staff

The WHO (2011) defines a set of essential core components for IPC programmes, which recommends appointing trained healthcare professionals in every healthcare facility as IPC

officers who are in charge of implementing infection control practices and drafting policy guidelines. According to WHO (2008), infection control professionals need to be highly skilled. In addition, they should have a high level of knowledge in relation to the general principles of IPC, surveillance of disease and outbreak management, and monitoring of clinical practice. Availability of personnel has been highlighted as an important factor for compliance in the literature as in Efstathiou et al., (2011), Mazi et al., (2013), Piai-Morais et al., (2015) and Rabaan et al., (2017).

The findings of this study; however, show a lack of trained infection control staff who can coordinate infection control activities in the healthcare facilities and provide HCWs with immediate feedback on their infection control practice. Although HCWs perceived the policy and management of infection control to be good in the survey and interview, some indicated that having one infection control consultant in the department or hospital is not enough. The impact of understaffing as Allegranzi and Pittet (2009) and Mazi et al., (2013) identify is poor hand hygiene compliance, which was observed in this study. Along a similar line, in their survey, Efstathiou et al., (2011) and Rabaan et al. (2017) indicate that the shortage of staff is a significant contributor to non-compliance with recommended IPC practices. Therefore, to improve infection prevention and control in the two healthcare facilities involved in this study, HCWs suggested increasing the number of medical specialists in each department who are trained to be IPC leaders and coordinators to provide staff with feedback, help them identify certain infectious diseases, give them protocol procedure and to remind them with how to deal with infectious disease.

It is important to point out that the results obtained in this study agree with the evidence reviewed in this study, which suggests that IPC models only incorporating the appointment of IPC officers and putting up policies are not effective. Specifically, a review by Hale et al., (2015) from the UK indicates that IPC models, where the IPC officers take the role of intermediaries or educators, are not effective in reducing infection in healthcare practices. This is because IPC teams performing surveillance or education as their primary functions often face resistance in the implementation of new IPC policies especially when they are conflicted by ingrained practices.

For instance, senior medical staff members are major resisters and their influence creates a barrier to progress. As previously indicated in Chapter Two (section 2.7.2.3), in KSA, HCWs' resistance to implement new IPC policies is may be a challenge due to some cultural reasons.

Allegranzi and Pittet (2009) indicate that the implementation of comprehensive multi-modal IPC programmes, as for example WHO infection control model, which incorporate interventions such as training and education on hand washing and hand hygiene observation, alcohol-based hand rub, chlorhexidine soap, electronic hand hygiene monitoring, and performance feedback were associated with increased compliance with IPC practices. Similar results were reported by Mazi et al., (2013), Haridi et al., (2016) and Rabaan et al., (2017) in KSA, Walker et al., (2014), Smiddy et al., (2015), Hessels and Larson (2016) in the USA, and Quan et al. (2015) in China. In line with these studies, the findings suggest that HCWs in KSA context would benefit from implementing a comprehensive multi-modal IPC programme and incorporating the interventions Allegranzi and Pittet (2009) recommend in their review to increase their compliance with recommended IPC guidelines.

6.4.2.3 Inefficient Infection Surveillance Mechanisms

Based on Rosenthal et al., (2013) and WHO (2016), infection surveillance, particularly when complemented with immediate feedback, is a significant component of HAIs prevention which can facilitate identifying outbreaks, establishing endemic baseline rates of disease and evaluating infection control measures. Edet et al., (2017) argue that together with workplace policy, surveillance can enhance HCWs' perception of IPC practices because they focus on organisational factors to develop a positive orientation towards compliance and long-term strategies for infection control practices. Hence, hospitals with efficient surveillance mechanisms in place are more likely to have lower rates of HAIs.

The findings of this study suggest that the two healthcare facilities surveyed have surveillance mechanisms in place to check on adherence to IPC practices with just over half of

HCWs showing awareness of an ongoing infection control surveillance in their wards, departments or hospitals. Similarly, in interviews, most HCWs indicated having surveillance mechanisms in both hospitals. However, the findings of the survey and the interview show that HCWs perceive the current surveillance mechanisms to be inefficient to support IPC practices despite indicating improvements in the last few years. This is in line with the findings of Rabaan et al., (2017) who reported ineffective surveillance in KSA healthcare facilities.

In their qualitative longitudinal study of the effectiveness of a new hand hygiene monitoring programme (HHMP) over a one-year period, Walker et al., (2014) indicate that direct monitoring when combined with immediate feedback can efficiently increase hand hygiene compliance. The authors suggest that noncompliant incidents may be used as teaching opportunities to give HCWs responsibility and ownership of the process instead of punishments. In this way, it is hoped that the provision of feedback about the negative or positive behaviours would allow HCWs to see the benefits of compliance, which will also help them develop a positive attitude or perception. Similarly, Ayub et al., (2013) and Hale et al., (2015) suggest that it is vital for hospital management to come up with strict infection prevention and control practices. As Ayub et al., (2013) argue, successful implementation of prevention and control practices requires a positive attitude and strict monitoring and vigilance by the management.

Consistent with the findings of Ayub et al., (2013), Walker et al., (2014) and Hale et al., (2015), the study suggests that HCWs in KSA would benefit from conducting overt and covert surveillance and providing immediate feedback on both positive and negative behaviors to increase compliance with IPC guidelines and reduce infections. It is vital for auditors to be transparent in their evaluation and continue providing feedback to all the health professionals to use this opportunity as a reminder for all practitioners to continue adhering to good practices when dealing with patients.

The next section discusses the role of individual factors in affecting HCWs' adherence to recommended practices.

6.5 HOW DO THE INDIVIDUAL FACTORS INFLUENCE HEALTHCARE WORKERS' COMPLIANCE WITH INFECTION PREVENTION AND CONTROL PRACTICES WITHIN THE TWO HOSPITALS IN KSA?

The literature indicates that individual factors such as gender, age, education, type of profession, race, nationality and self-efficacy may influence HCWs' perceptions and compliance with infection control guidelines and policies (Watkins et al., 2006; Allegranzi and Pittet, 2009; Luo et al., 2010; Efstathiou et al., 2011; Osazuwa-Peters et al., 2012; Mazi et al., 2013; Sodhi et al., 2013; Hosseinalhashemi et al., 2015; Tan and Jeffrey, 2015; Carvalho et al., 2016; Rabaan et al., 2017). As Allegranzi and Pittet (2009) indicate, individual factors may offer additional insight into hand hygiene actions for example. In the quantitative and qualitative phases of this study, the influences of individual or demographic and sociocultural factors were explored. In particular, the roles of age, gender, education, type of profession, nationality, place of work and self-efficacy on affecting the perceptions of HCWs and their compliance with IPC practices were examined. However, given the relatively small samples recruited in the qualitative phases, the discussions on the influences of individual factors are mainly based on the quantitative findings. In line with the literature, the findings show the importance of individual factors in influencing the perceptions of HCWs of IPC practices in their healthcare facilities.

The quantitative findings indicate that nationality is the most significant factor associated with influencing HCWs' perceptions of infection control practices. In addition to nationality, the findings identify three other main influential factors which are: gender, profession, and education. In agreement with Watkins et al., (2006), identifying the factors which impact the compliance of HCWs can facilitate developing strategies which can support long-term compliance with IPC practices. The next subsections discuss these findings in detail.

6.5.1 Gender

Unlike the findings of Rabaan et al., (2017) which suggest that variation in nurses' responses in their survey in healthcare facilities in KSA was not influenced by their gender, in this study the findings of the survey indicate that responses to survey questions were impacted by HCWs' gender. These findings are in line with the findings of Osazuwa-Peters et al., (2012) who evaluated gender differences among dental professionals in Nigeria. However, it is important to indicate that in a multivariate analysis, sometimes gender was not a significant factor in this study. Furthermore, the findings of observations show that gender may affect compliance. However, the findings of interviews indicate having no significant differences in perceptions by gender. Hence, consistent with the literature, triangulation indicates the presence of contradictory findings regarding the significant role of gender in impacting perceptions and compliance (Osazuwa-Peters et al., 2012; Herbert et al., 2013; Mortada and Zalat, 2014).

As the quantitative findings show, female HCWs showed more positive perceptions of the overall quality of IPC practices at their workplace compared to their male counterparts with 81.09% females perceiving infection control in their ward/hospital to be good compared to 67.77% males. However, the findings of the interview show no differences in perceptions by gender as all HCWs agreed that the overall quality of IPC practices is good in their hospitals.

The quantitative findings suggest that gender significantly affected HCWs' views of the preparedness of their hospital for any incidences of infection outbreaks as more females than males thought that they were prepared for any incidences of infection outbreaks. In addition, the findings show that gender significantly influenced HCWs' responses regarding infection control leadership and guidelines. Based on the findings, more females than males indicated having a positive perception of IPC leadership and guidelines. The findings also show that more females positively perceived hospital's surveillance and monitoring mechanisms. However, gender did not affect HCWs' views of training and support offered at their respective hospitals. Furthermore, this

demographic factor did not impact their perceptions of supplies and resources as well as their views of IPC culture.

Based on the findings of observations, female HCWs were sometimes keen to show adherence to recommended IPC practices more than their male counterparts. Still, the findings conclude that observed compliance is poor. Therefore, although gender may influence HCWs' perceptions of IPC, the triangulated findings suggest that its influence may not be much significant on HCWs' perceptions of and their compliance with IPC practices. Further research may help assessing the impact of gender on HCWs' perceptions and compliance with IPC.

6.5.2 Profession

According to Allegranzi and Pittet (2009), the most influential factors observed in determining poor hand hygiene compliance include belonging to a particular professional category such as doctor, nursing assistant, physiotherapist, or technician. The findings of the survey show that HCWs' perceptions of the overall quality of infection control practices at their hospitals were significantly influenced by their profession. In addition, this factor affected HCWs' attitudes regarding the hospital's preparedness for infection outbreaks, IPC leadership and guidelines as well as IPC surveillance and monitoring.

The quantitative findings indicate that profession is a significant factor which positively influenced nurses' views of the quality of infection control in their ward or hospital as nurses were more likely to agree than doctors that the quality of infection control in their ward or hospital was good. Moreover, the findings show that nurses had more positive perceptions of the level of the preparedness for any incidences of outbreaks of infections in their hospital than doctors.

Based on quantitative findings, HCWs' profession significantly influenced their views of IPC leadership and guidelines. The findings suggest that more nurses agreed that IPC leadership in their ward or hospital was good than doctors. Moreover, compared to doctors, more nurses positively perceived the existence of a set of guidelines which they are able to access to support

IPC practices. The findings also indicate that more nurses were aware of ongoing surveillance in their ward department or hospital than doctors. In their study in KSA, Mazi et al., (2013) report finding high levels of compliance among nursing staff. Similarly, in this study the findings of observations show that nurses tended to show more compliance with IPC practices compared to doctors, but it is important to point out that the overall level of compliance observed was suboptimal in the two healthcare facilities.

6.5.3 Education

Surveying the literature indicates that the level of education can influence HCWs' attitudes and compliance with IPC practice (Jradi et al., 2013; Ayub et al., 2013; Sodhi et al., 2013; Bai, 2015; Quan et al., 2015; Ng et al., 2017; Rabaan et al., 2017). However, the findings of Moralejo et al., (2018) suggest that education may have little or no difference in knowledge and may slightly improve compliance with IPC practices. In line with the literature, in this study, the quantitative findings indicate that education is an important factor which influenced HCWs' perceptions of the quality of IPC in their workplace. However, unlike the findings of Bai (2015) which emphasise the importance of providing postgraduate education of IPC because it is associated with high compliance with IPC standards, the findings of this study suggest that HCWs with undergraduate education were more likely to show positive perceptions of the quality of IPC compared to those with postgraduate education. As another example, the findings of this study show that education positively influenced HCWs views of the level of hospital preparedness for any incidences of outbreaks of infections. The findings suggest that more undergraduates showed positive perceptions of hospital preparedness than postgraduates.

The quantitative findings indicate that education was a significant factor for a positive perception on leadership. A majority of HCWs with an undergraduate degree indicated having good perceptions of the quality of leadership compared to HCWs with a postgraduate degree. Moreover, HCWs with undergraduate degrees were more likely to show positive perceptions of

IPC guidelines than those with postgraduate degrees. This may indicate that although education influences HCWs' perceptions of IPC, having postgraduate education may not necessarily lead to having positive perceptions. The presence of positive perceptions may be related to other institutional or individual factors.

6.5.4 Nationality

According to Efstathiou et al., (2011) and Piai-Morais, et al., (2015), the quality of medical education varies in different countries which can result in having different health beliefs among HCWs from different nationalities. These differences influence the compliance of HCWs with recommended IPC practices. In line with these studies, the findings of the survey in this research indicate that nationality is the most significant factor which impacted HCWs' perceptions of IPC practices. However, this contradicts the findings of Haridi et al., (2016) in KSA which suggest that HCWs' nationality does not influence compliance with IPC practices.

In this study, for example, nationality significantly affected HCWs' perceptions of the overall quality of infection control at the two healthcare facilities. The findings indicate that Saudis were more likely to perceive that the quality of infection control in their ward or hospital to be good than non-Saudis. In addition, nationality influenced HCWs' perceptions of their hospital preparedness for any incidences of infection outbreaks with more non-Saudis showing agreement with the statement that the hospital was prepared for an outbreak than Saudis.

The quantitative findings show that nationality significantly influenced HCWs' perceptions of IPC leadership and guidelines. Based on the findings, more Saudis perceived leadership and guidelines to be good than non-Saudis. The findings also suggest that nationality impacted HCWs' perceptions of IPC training with more non-Saudis indicating that they received adequate training on infection control than their Saudi counterparts. Furthermore, nationality significantly influenced HCWs' perceptions of IPC surveillance and supplies. The findings

indicate that more non-Saudis showed awareness of ongoing surveillance than Saudis. Compared to Saudis, more non-Saudis believed that there were not enough supplies in their hospital.

Finally, nationality significantly influenced HCWs' negative perceptions of culture in their ward or hospital. The findings show that non-Saudi HCWs were more likely to perceive that there was a blame culture in their hospital or ward than their Saudi counterparts. The findings suggest that HCWs of foreign origin felt they were more likely to be blamed if something goes wrong in their ward or hospital.

6.5.5 Place of Work

The findings of Nofal et al., (2017) show that the perceptions of HCWs may be influenced by differences in institutional policies in healthcare facilities. In agreement with the findings of Nofal et al., (2017), in this study, the quantitative findings indicate that HCWs' place of work can be sometimes a significant factor which influences HCWs' perceptions of IPC practices due to having different institutional policies. For example, the findings show that more HCWs at Hospital 1 perceived the training they received to be adequate than their counterparts at Hospital 2. Based on the results of univariate analysis, the place of work is a significant predictor of HCWs' perceptions of the appropriateness of IPC training. As another example, the findings suggest that the place of work is a significant factor which influenced HCWs' perceptions of the adequacy of infection control surveillance with more HCWs from both hospitals agreeing that they are aware of IPC surveillance in their workplace than disagreeing. Nevertheless, it is important to mention that the observed level of compliance with IPC recommended practices was poor in both hospitals suggesting the existence of barriers which affected translating knowledge and positive perceptions to practice.

The findings show that the place of work significantly affected the views of HCWs regarding the adequacy of IPC supplies. Based on quantitative findings, more HCWs at Hospital 1 indicated that supplies are inadequate to enable them to prevent and control infections compared

to HCWs at Hospital 2. Along a similar line, the findings of the interview show that more HCWs at Hospital 1 identified the lack of adequate supplies as one of the gaps in current IPC practices which needs to be addressed to improve IPC compliance. However, the quantitative findings show the place of work was not a significant factor which influenced HCWs' perceptions of hospital preparedness for incidences of infection outbreaks. All in all, these findings indicate the importance of considering the influence of HCWs' place of work on their perceptions of and compliance with recommended IPC practices.

6.5.6 Age

Some studies such as Yassi et al., (2007), Nofal et al., (2017) and Russell et al., (2018) suggest that the age of HCWs plays an important role in affecting their perceptions of IPC. Based on Efstathiou et al., (2011), age significantly influences the level of HCWs' knowledge, experience and compliance with IPC practices. In this study, the quantitative findings show that age may have an influence on HCWs' perceptions of IPC, but its influence may not be significant. For example, the quantitative findings indicate that age affected HCWs' perceptions of the adequacy of supplies and the existence of a blame culture. The findings suggest that younger HCWs who were less than 35 years old were more likely to agree that supplies were adequate than their older counterparts. In addition, the findings show that age negatively influenced HCWs' views of IPC culture. For example, younger HCWs were more likely to perceive that there was a blame culture in their hospital or ward. However, the findings show that, unlike nationality, age was not a significant factor. It is important to mention that the quantitative findings show that age did not play a significant role in influencing the views of HCWs regarding whether they think that their hospital and ward/department are prepared enough for any incidences of outbreaks of healthcare associated infections. Therefore, the findings suggest that although age influences HCWs' perceptions of IPC, the influence of this factor may not be significant.

6.5.7 Self-Efficacy

Luo et al., (2010) define self-efficacy as a general confidence in one's own ability to deal with changeable environments and cope with new experiences. According to Lou et al., (2010) and Efstathiou et al., (2011), having high self-efficacy positively affects compliance with IPC practices. In this study, the relationship between IPC compliance and self-efficacy among HCWs in the two hospitals in KSA was explored in the questionnaire and interview through the level of confidence they showed in their ward or hospital's ability to deal with cases of new healthcare-associated infection outbreaks. More importantly, HCWs' views of their own competence, leadership commitment, self-confidence to implement IPC practices and the need for further IPC training were used to provide deeper insights into the level of self-efficacy among HCWs.

Similar to the findings of Efstathiou et al., (2011) which reported difficulties in changing behavior because of the influence of previous training, the findings in this study suggest that there is a lack of self-efficacy among HCWs which was reflected in statements in the interview indicating that for some cultural reasons senior HCWs' may show resistance to being monitored particularly by non-Saudi HCWs. The lack of self-efficacy may also be indicated by the quantitative and qualitative findings which show an agreement among the majority of HCWs regarding the need for providing sustained high-quality training which would facilitate compliance with recommended IPC practices.

Although the quantitative findings suggest that HCWs in both hospitals showed confidence in the hospitals' ability to cope with infection outbreaks, it was apparent in the questionnaire, interview, and observation that the shortages in supplies HCWs identify and senior HCWs' resistance to being monitored which are influenced by some cultural reasons can be barriers to compliance with safe IPC practices in the research hospitals. Therefore, the study recommends providing continuous high-quality training to promote a positive culture of IPC compliance.

6.6 STRENGTHS OF THE STUDY

The strengths of this study lie in its aims, originality, contribution to body of knowledge and mixed methods research design. This study offers a comprehensive understanding of HCWs' perceptions of IPC in two hospitals in the Qassim region in the centre of KSA and how HCWs' perceptions among other factors influence compliance with the recommended infection control practices. To achieve the intended aims of the study, HCWs' attitudes towards IPC in their workplace, the quality of IPC practices, perceived competence and training, perceived influences on compliance with IPC guidelines, and HCWs' actual practices of IPC are critically examined.

In KSA, little research has been conducted to examine the association between the perceptions of HCWs of IPC and their compliance with recommended IPC guidelines in practice. The factors contributing to the lack of adherence to infection control protocols among HCWs are under-researched in the local context of the study. Therefore, this study provides a valuable insight into the association between HCWs' perceptions of IPC and their compliance with IPC procedure in KSA. Furthermore, the findings of this study contribute some new knowledge to the existing field of infection prevention and control nationally and internationally. For example, in line with the literature, the findings of this research show big differences between the knowledge, perceptions and attitudes of HCWs towards infection control and their compliance with IPC procedures in practice (Jain et al., 2012; Ayub et al., 2013; Bai, 2015; Hosseinalhashemi et al., 2015; Tan and Jeffrey, 2015; Hessels and Larson, 2016; Edet et al., 2017). The findings indicate that the presence of positive perceptions may not translate into compliance because of several barriers the study identifies primarily including the lack of supplies, need for sustained high-quality training, shortage of well-trained IPC staff and inefficient surveillance mechanisms. In addition, the discrepancy between HCWs' perceived IPC practices and their compliance with IPC guidelines in practice may be due to people's tendency to exaggerate their socially desirable behaviours when self-reporting their practices (Haridi et al., 2016). The findings of this study will

help inform changing the policy on infection control in KSA to protect the health of HCWs and patients as well as reduce medical and economic burdens.

Despite the challenges, using mixed methods design and triangulating the findings of the survey, interview and observation add to the strengths of the study. This study employed quantitative and qualitative methods in a concurrent design. Quantitative data was gathered using online and paper questionnaire. As for qualitative data, it was collected using semi-structured face to face interviews and non-participant structured observations. Results of both quantitative and qualitative data were triangulated to provide an in depth understanding of HCWs' perceptions and their role among other institutional and individual factors in influencing compliance with recommended IPC practices in two hospitals in KSA. Moreover, triangulating results facilitates understanding the reasons for non-complacency and highlights opportunities to enhance IPC compliance.

The validity of the research findings arises from the ability to accurately measure the outcome (Creswell, 2003). The internal validity of qualitative data is doubtful as self-reporting is likely to be associated with over-rating, that is, participants are more likely to present themselves positively as mentioned previously. For example, the findings of interviews indicate good self-reported perceptions of IPC quality and compliance with recommended guidelines among HCWs. However, verifying these findings with the findings of the survey and observation showed a gap between HCWs' perceptions and actual application of IPC practices. Therefore, triangulating results from quantitative surveys with qualitative methods such as semi-structured interviews and direct non-participant observations can minimise the instances of bias developed when using qualitative studies only to understand the factors that influence compliance with IPC practices.

Many similar studies conducted in various contexts locally and internationally have used either quantitative methods only (Luo et al., 2010; Abdulraheem et al., 2012; Osazuwa-Peters et al., 2012; Amoran et al., 2013; Mortada and Zalat, 2014; Piai-Morais et al., 2015; Quan et al., 2015; Tan and Jeffrey, 2015; Carvalho et al., 2016; Haridi, et al., 2016; Rabaan et al., 2017), or

only qualitative methods (Ward, 2012; Shah et al., 2015; Hale et al., 2015; Edet et al., 2017). Since this study was conducted using a concurrent mixed methods design, it can be much stronger and more vigorous in its methodological approaches (Bai, 2015; Ng et al., 2017).

6.7 CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

It is important to point out that using the mixed methods design posed some challenges during the research process. For example, triangulating the results collected from the three data sources revealed some differences in the findings which at the beginning of the data analysis process were difficult to resolve. Triangulation showed discrepancies between HCWs self-reported knowledge about IPC, their positive attitude to IPC, their perceptions about what they do to comply with the recommended IPC practices in their workplace and what HCWs really do in practice to implement IPC guidelines. Therefore, the limitations inherent in using triangulation methods should be kept in mind when interpreting the results of this study. To respond to the challenges and limitations of triangulation, the researcher spent a long time reading and re-reading the data and the professional literature to facilitate conducting the analysis and presentation of mixed methods research findings.

Conducting a pilot study, which was not possible in this research, may have helped reduce the challenges encountered in this study. Therefore, it is recommended for future research. Despite the challenges, the findings of this study offer a valuable insight on the links between how HCWs in KSA perceive IPC practices in their workplace and their actual compliance with IPC. The gaps between the knowledge and perceptions of HCWs towards infection control and their adherence to IPC procedures exist because of several influences and barriers which affect IPC implementation in the two healthcare facilities.

The limitations of this study may be related to the small sample sizes as this study involved two hospitals in KSA and interviewed seven HCWs from both hospitals. Specifically, in this study, 498 nurses and physicians were recruited from two tertiary care hospitals (Buraidah Central

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Hospital and King Fahad Specialised Hospital), located in the Qassim region in the centre of KSA, approximately 300 km northwest of the capital city of Riyadh. However, KSA is a huge country with a total of 542 hospitals, of which 415 are governmental and 127 are private. The Buraidah Central Hospital and the and King Fahad Specialised Hospital serve the Qassim region which has a population of 1.4 million inhabitants, out of a population of 32 million people in KSA (The Statistics Portal, 2017).

In the qualitative phase of research, the relatively small sample is another possible limitation. For cultural reasons, some HCWs were worried about participating in this study. Non-Saudi nationals in particular showed some interest in sharing their views in this study, but maybe they worried about losing their job. This, however, did not affect the depth or breadth of information gathered as rich data was collected and triangulated with data collected using the questionnaire and observation.

Despite every effort taken to involve more HCWs in this research, it is important to clarify that the size of the study was limited by the fact that it is a PhD project. Therefore, time and financial constrains meant that the study had to be trimmed to a feasible or manageable size. Due to the small number of hospitals and individuals involved, it is not possible to generalise these findings to the entire population. However, the aim of the research is not generalisation, but rather gaining a deeper understanding of infection control perceptions and practices which the research methods used have helped achieve. A longitudinal study sampling more hospitals and recruiting a larger number of participants would be recommended for future studies when time and resources permit.

Finally, the findings of this research are subject to social desirability bias which can under or overestimate the results. For example, since perception and attitude of HCWs were measured using a personalised scale, there is a high likelihood some subjects may have offered the wrong information for fear of victimisation or being seen as individuals not committed towards the fight against infectious illnesses. However, while the researcher attempted to study the subjects within

their natural environments, they were aware of being under study. Future studies may consider using the participatory observation research to get a clearer picture of HCWs' perceptions.

6.8 SUMMARY OF CHAPTER SIX

In this chapter, the main research findings are discussed in relation to the research questions and the existing literature to understand in depth HCWs' perceptions of IPC and their role among other factors in influencing compliance with IPC in two healthcare facilities in KSA. The key finding indicates that HCWs have positive perceptions of IPC in their workplace, but their compliance with recommended policies and guidelines is suboptimal because of gaps and barriers which hindered implementing IPC practices. The findings show several institutional and individual factors which affected the implementation of IPC practices. Finally, the chapter identifies the strengths, challenges and limitations of the study. The next chapter provides the conclusions for this study and recommendations for practice, policy makers and future research.

CHAPTER 7: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

7.1 INTRODUCTION

In this concluding chapter, a concise summary of the main aims and findings of this study is provided. Based on the findings, some recommendations for practice, policy makers and future research are suggested. The chapter begins first with presenting the aims of the study and the main three questions this study answers. Next, the key findings which address these aims and answer the main research questions are briefly summarised. Finally, the chapter ends with a discussion of the study's recommendations for practice, policy makers and future research.

7.2 SUMMARY OF RESEARCH AIMS AND KEY FINDINGS

In KSA, the reported number of healthcare-associated infections among HCWs has been increasing which threatens the health of HCWs and patients as well as present a significant economic burden on the country (Balkhy et al., 2006; Gupta et al., 2017). Based on the literature, many institutional and individual factors can influence HCWs' adherence to safe IPC practices (Allegranzi and Pittet, 2009; Ayub et al., 2013; Bai, 2015; Tan and Jeffrey, 2015; Edet et al., 2017). However, the factors affecting HCWs' compliance with recommended IPC procedures are still under-researched in KSA healthcare facilities. Therefore, the main purpose of this study is to provide a comprehensive understanding of HCWs' perceptions of IPC and the role of these perceptions among other factors in affecting compliance with recommended IPC practices. The key questions this research answers are:

1. What are healthcare workers' perceptions of infection prevention and control practices within the two research hospitals in KSA?
2. What institutional factors influence healthcare workers' compliance with infection prevention and control practices within the two hospitals in KSA?

3. How do the individual factors influence healthcare workers' compliance with infection prevention and control practices within the two hospitals in KSA?

To achieve the identified aims of the study and address the research questions, HCWs' perceptions of IPC were critically examined, and their IPC practices were observed in two hospitals in KSA. Quantitative and qualitative data was collected and integrated in a concurrent mixed methods research design. In the quantitative phase of research, a structured questionnaire survey investigated HCWs' perceptions of IPC practices and the role of institutional and individual factors in influencing HCWs' compliance with IPC practices. In the qualitative phase, the attitudes of HCWs regarding the overall quality of IPC, IPC leadership, guidelines and policy, infection outbreak preparedness, IPC education and training, IPC supplies and resources, IPC surveillance and IPC culture at their ward, department or hospital were explored in semi-structured interviews. Furthermore, HCWs' compliance with recommended hand hygiene and respiratory cough hygiene as well as HCWs' use of PPEs were observed at the two research hospitals using non-participant structured observations.

In their questionnaire-based analysis of IPC in healthcare facilities in KSA, Rabaan et al., (2017) indicate that training, awareness and compliance of HCWs at all levels of the organisation are needed for effective implementation of IPC policies and procedures in healthcare facilities. However, the findings of this study indicate that effective measures to strengthen HCWs' training, awareness and compliance are not currently adopted which affects the quality of IPC in the two research hospitals involved in this study. Key research findings indicate that although HCWs showed positive perceptions of IPC, their observed compliance with recommended IPC practices was poor. Therefore, the findings suggest that a gap exists between HCWs' perceptions and actual application of IPC practices which HCWs are aware of as shown in their discussions of barriers and influencers on IPC practices in their wards or hospitals. Based on HCWs' perceptions, IPC leadership, guidelines and staff training positively influence compliance with IPC practices.

Nevertheless, the findings indicate that HCWs expressed their need for providing a more sustained high-quality IPC training to increase IPC compliance. Moreover, key findings show that the lack of supplies, shortage of trained IPC staff and inefficient surveillance mechanisms hinder compliance with recommended IPC practices.

Regarding the influence of individual factors on IPC compliance, key findings suggest that gender, profession, education and nationality affect HCWs' perceptions of the quality of infection control, leadership, guidance and surveillance. Compared to male HCWs, female HCWs in this study showed more positive perceptions of and compliance with IPC practices. In addition, nurses showed more positive perceptions of and compliance with IPC practices than doctors. The findings also indicate that nationality is the most significant factor influencing HCWs' perceptions of infection control practices.

All in all, despite indicating some improvements in infection control in KSA especially since the MERS coronavirus outbreak, the findings of this research show that a combination of organisational and individual factors influence compliance with recommended IPC policies and guidelines. There are still challenges and gaps which should be addressed to improve compliance with IPC policies and guidelines. The study suggests some areas of improvement particularly in terms of IPC training, culture, supplies, and surveillance.

7.3 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PRACTICE, POLICY MAKERS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Based on the research findings extensively discussed in the previous chapter, the following recommendations are proposed to facilitate translating HCWs' positive perceptions of IPC into compliance with IPC guidelines, and therefore, narrowing the gap between HCWs' perceptions of IPC and actual application of IPC practices in healthcare facilities in KSA and similar contexts world-wide. It is hoped that the research recommendations will help healthcare facilities to plan and implement IPC practices to protect the health of HCWs and patients.

7.3.1 Providing Continuous High-Quality IPC Training

The findings of this study indicate that HCWs showed awareness of the importance of following recommended IPC practices. Moreover, HCWs indicated that their healthcare facilities have provided appropriate policies, guidelines and support to prevent and control infections. HCWs indicated that one of the two research hospitals has been providing lectures, workshops, administering written exams and offering certificates to those who pass them to improve compliance with IPC practices. Nevertheless, HCWs indicated their need for more opportunities to discuss their needs for IPC training with MOH officials to improve infection control practices. The findings show that HCWs were observed using unhygienic practices which can put HCWs and patients at a high risk of acquiring healthcare-associated infections.

The triangulated findings suggest that there are several factors which hinder IPC compliance primarily including having insufficient consistent IPC training among HCWs which may have contributed to a lack of self-efficacy among HCWs and affected implementing recommended IPC guidelines. Strengthening IPC training is recommended to reduce healthcare-associated infections and protect the health of both patients and HCWs (Allegranzi and Pittet, 2009; Luo et al., 2010). Therefore, an important recommendation this study suggests is providing sustained high-quality training based on HCWs' needs particularly in relation to hand washing, cough hygiene practices and PPEs' storage and use in order to extend HCWs' knowledge about safe IPC practices. The provision of continuous training programmes which are based on HCWs' needs is suggested as one of the interventions which can contribute to creating an organisational environment that complies with the recommended IPC practices.

7.3.2 Providing Sufficient and Appropriate IPC Supplies and Equipment

To facilitate implementing IPC guidelines, it is recommended that the provision of sustained training is accompanied by ensuring the provision of adequate supplies of PPEs as the triangulated findings of this study highlight that HCWs perceived the need for appropriate IPC

supplies and equipment as a significant contributing factor influencing their IPC compliance. Most HCWs indicated having shortages of IPC supplies at their healthcare facilities such as hand washing supplies, culture bottles, gloves and masks which are critical for preventing infection outbreaks. Therefore, in line with the recommendations of Luo et al., (2010) and Efstathiou et al., (2011), allocating further investment in the provision of IPC supplies and equipment is proposed to facilitate the implementation of recommended IPC practices. Creating a good supply chain strategy, estimating volume of resources that would be required over a certain period, and creating an appropriate replenishment or restocking plan which ensures that supplies needed for infection control are always available are particularly recommended to help HCWs implement safe IPC practices at KSA healthcare facilities. Such intervention strategies are proposed not only to narrow the gap between HCWs' knowledge and practice, but also to help reinforce a supportive environment which promotes IPC compliance and addresses the identified barriers to HCWs' adherence to recommended IPC practices.

Storing PPEs at HCWs' disposal is another recommendation provided based on the findings of this study to facilitate HCWs' compliance with IPC guidelines and foster a culture of positive hygiene practices within KSA healthcare facilities. To improve hand hygiene compliance, there is an emphasis on adopting the "clean in, clean out" approach wherein HCWs are expected to wash their hands or disinfect them before they enter and after they exit a patient's room. Consequently, storing PPEs in the right place or near place of use as well as having easy access to running water, disinfectants and sinks for hand hygiene; for example, are specifically advised to support HCWs' adherence to recommended IPC practices.

7.3.3 Carrying Out Efficient Surveillance

The findings of this study indicate having ineffective monitoring of IPC practices which plays a role in affecting IPC compliance. The findings show a lack of infection control monitoring and feedback which are partly caused by the shortage of well-trained IPC coordinators whose role

involves supporting the evaluation of infection control measures and providing feedback to HCWs to improve compliance with IPC guidelines. Therefore, one of the most important recommendations this study proposes is ensuring the provision of an effective surveillance system by, for example, increasing the appointment of specially-trained IPC leaders in each department who regularly assess IPC practices, identify gaps in IPC provision, help HCWs identify certain infectious diseases, provide HCWs with constructive feedback, and enhance their positive perceptions of IPC practices and compliance with recommended IPC guidelines.

Evidence reviewed in this study suggests that electronic monitoring of handwashing greatly improves HCWs' compliance with IPC procedures (Allegranzi and Pittet, 2009; Walker et al., 2014). Therefore, hospitals in KSA may need to consider installing real-time electronic monitoring of hand hygiene to increase compliance with the IPC guidelines. It is recommended that hospitals implement and strengthen regular auditing and reviewing of HCWs' IPC practices and their adherence to IPC protocols, rules and regulations to develop and enhance desired teamwork among HCWs which is important to promote a positive IPC culture within healthcare facilities and facilitate implementing IPC guidelines.

7.5.4 Avenues for Future Research

Based on the findings of this research, it is recommended that future research considers patients and stakeholders' perspectives regarding infection prevention and control as nearly most of the studies reviewed are concerned with examining the views of HCWs. Studying infection control practices based on the perspective of patients, hospital management and HCWs may help develop a better understanding of the factors influencing compliance with IPC policies and guidelines. System analysis may provide future researchers with an appropriate framework for investigation.

Conducting longitudinal studies which involve more hospitals and recruit a larger number of participants is recommended for future studies to comprehensively understand influences and

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barriers hindering IPC compliance at a national level in KSA. A particular area for future research in KSA proposed here is hand hygiene as implementing proper hand hygiene practices is an essential and efficient method to prevent the spread of infectious illnesses. Surveying the literature shows that very few studies have examined hand hygiene practices in some healthcare facilities in KSA such as Mazi et al., (2013), Tan and Jeffrey (2015) Zabeeri et al., (2016) and Alshammari et al., (2018). Therefore, studying the implementation of safe hand hygiene practices is proposed as an avenue for future research in KSA.

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for turning the tide against the Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus and other zoonotic pathogens with epidemic potential.

APPENDICES

APPENDIX I: MEDLINE ON OVID: Search Form

Search History (8searches found)				
				<input type="button" value="View Saved"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	# ▲	Searches	Results	Type
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	Bacterial Infections/ or Anti-Bacterial Agents/ or Clostridium Infections/ or Hospital-acquired infections.mp. or Cross Infection/	373	Advanced
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	health care associated infections.mp.	2	Advanced
<input type="checkbox"/>	3	nosocomial infections.mp.	8	Advanced
<input type="checkbox"/>	4	methicillin resistant hospital infections.mp. or Personal Protective Equipment/ or Infection Control/ or "Delivery of Health Care"/ or Vancomycin-Resistant Enterococci/ or Iatrogenic Disease/ or Methicillin-Resistant Staphylococcus aureus/	157	Advanced
<input type="checkbox"/>	5	Disease Outbreaks/ or Cross Infection/ or Visitors to Patients/ or Health Care Surveys/ or hospital acquired infection outbreaks.mp. or Organizational Policy/ or Communicable Diseases, Emerging/	99	Advanced
<input type="checkbox"/>	6	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5	583	Advanced

<input type="checkbox"/>	7	((((((Infection control or infection control practices or hospital infection control practices or hospital infection control interventions or policy or infection control code of conduct or infection control committee or leadership or institutional support or training of new staff or education or hospital infection surveillance or training or supplies or equipment or availability of equipment or availability of supplies or availability of personal protective equipment or PPEs or availability of bins or physical environment or hospital layout or cohorting or proximity of hand dispensers or hand wash sinks or technological barriers or electronic hand wash monitoring system or environmental cleaning precautions or health care culture or health care institution infection control culture or organisational culture or being a nurse or being doctor or attitude) and perceptions) or demographic factors or demographic) and socio factors) or work experience or length of service or gender or sex or age or nationality or self-efficacy).mp. [mp=title, abstract, original title, name of substance word, subject heading word, floating sub-heading word, keyword heading word, organism supplementary concept word, protocol supplementary concept word, rare disease supplementary concept word, unique identifier, synonyms]	7251	Advanced
<input type="checkbox"/>	8	6 and 7	190	Advanced
<input type="button" value="Save"/> <input type="button" value="Remove"/>		Combine with: <input type="button" value="AND"/> <input type="button" value="OR"/>		

APPENDIX II: Wed of Science - Search History

Search History						
Set	Results	Save History / Create Alert	Open Saved History	Edit Sets	Combine Sets <input type="radio"/> AND <input type="radio"/> OR Combine	Delete Sets Select All Delete
# 6	<u>745</u>	#5 AND #4 <i>Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH, BKCI-S, BKCI-SSH, ESCI, CCR-EXPANDED, IC</i> <i>Timespan=All years</i>		Edit	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
# 5	<u>1,893,959</u>	TI=(Infection control or infection control practices or hospital infection control practices or hospital infection control interventions or policy or infection control code of conduct or infection control committee or leadership or institutional support or training of new staff or education or hospital infection surveillance or training or supplies or equipment or availability of equipment or availability of supplies or availability of personal protective equipment or PPEs or availability of bins or physical environment or hospital layout or cohorting or proximity of hand dispensers or hand wash sinks or technological barriers or electronic hand wash monitoring system or environmental cleaning precautions or health care culture or health care institution infection control culture or organisational culture or being a nurse or being doctor or attitude and perceptions or demographic factors or demographic and socio factors or work experience or length of service or gender or sex or age or nationality or self-efficacy) <i>Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH, BKCI-S, BKCI-SSH, ESCI, CCR-EXPANDED, IC</i> <i>Timespan=All years</i>		Edit	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
# 4	<u>6,172</u>	#3 OR #2 OR #1 <i>Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH, BKCI-S, BKCI-SSH, ESCI, CCR-EXPANDED, IC</i> <i>Timespan=All years</i>		Edit	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
# 3	<u>4,451</u>	TI=(nosocomial infection*)		Edit	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH, BKCI-S, BKCI-SSH, ESCI, CCR-EXPANDED, IC
Timespan=All years

2 **1,238** TI=(Hospital acquired infections) [Edit](#)
Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH, BKCI-S, BKCI-SSH, ESCI, CCR-EXPANDED, IC
Timespan=All years

1 **522** TI=(health care associated infection*) [Edit](#)
Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH, BKCI-S, BKCI-SSH, ESCI, CCR-EXPANDED, IC
Timespan=All years

<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="radio"/> AND <input type="radio"/> OR Combine	<input type="checkbox"/> Select All <input type="checkbox"/> Delete				
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APPENDIX III: CINAHL Via EBSCOHOST - Search History

<u>Search ID#</u>	<u>Search Terms</u>	<u>Search Options</u>	<u>Actions</u>
<input type="checkbox"/> S5	health care associated infection* OR Hospital acquired infections OR nosocomial infection* AND (Infection control or infection control practices or hospital infection control practices or hospital infection control interventions or policy or infection control code of conduct or infection control committee or leadership or institutional support or training of new staff or education or hospital infection surveillance or training or supplies or equipment or availability of equipment or availabilit ...	Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	View Results (7,205) View Details Edit
<input type="checkbox"/> S4	health care associated infection* OR Hospital acquired infections OR nosocomial infection*	Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	View Results (8,289) View Details Edit
<input type="checkbox"/> S3	health care associated infection* OR Hospital acquired infections OR nosocomial infection*	Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	View Results (8,289) View Details Edit
<input type="checkbox"/> S2	health care associated infection* OR Hospital acquired infections	Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	View Results (4,538) View Details Edit
<input type="checkbox"/> S1	health care associated infection*	Search modes - Boolean/Phrase	View Results (2,853) View Details Edit

APPENDIX IV: Critical appraisal of cross-sectional studies using the AXIS tool

Study name	Tan and Jeffrey (2015)	A Quantitative survey self-administered questionnaire to 87 health professionals in KSA
Study question	Response Yes = 1 No = 0	How is the question addressed in the study
1. Were the aims/objectives of the study clear?	1	The aim of the study was to assess the healthcare professionals' perception towards hand hygiene and their compliance with IPC procedures
2. Was the study design appropriate for the stated aim(s)?	1	The authors conducted a cross-sectional survey recruiting 87 HCWs of which 64.4% were nurses and 20% were doctors. They also used the World Health Organization standardized survey questionnaire. Acknowledging that generally there always more nurses than doctors in any hospital, it could be argued that the sample was representative of an expected distribution of doctors and nurses in most hospitals.
3. Was the target/reference population clearly defined? (Is it clear who the research was about?)	1	Hospitals, health care workers in hospitals. The authors clearly stated that the aim of the study was to support the WHO hand hygiene campaign against healthcare associated infections in hospitals
4. Was the cohort recruited in an acceptable way, such that the sampled participants could be said to be representative of the target/reference population under investigation?	0	A purposive sample was used, although the sample consisted of various healthcare professionals (doctors and nurses working in the hospital. Also this study was carried out at just one hospital therefore the perceptions reported might be influenced by the organisational culture of this particular hospital, and not necessarily representative of perceptions of HCWs across KSA.
5. Were the risk factor and outcome variables measured appropriate to the aims of the study?	1	The authors reported participant's perceptions on health care associated infections and hand hygiene. It also enquired on participants own performance of hand hygiene when situations requiring this arise and measured any correlations between perception and compliance

6. Were the basic data adequately described?	1	Details of the demographic and other profiles of respondents, the response rates, and outcomes on necessary variables reported
7. Does the response rate raise concerns about non-response bias?	1	Eighty five percent (85%) i.e. 87 of the 102 healthcare professionals eligible and were invited to participate and sent the survey questionnaire completed and returned the survey questionnaire. A response or participation rate of $\geq 80\%$ is generally considered acceptable Creswell (2003)
8. Have the authors taken account of the confounding factors in the design and/or analysis?	1	Authors reported on most of the important variables that affect compliance with IPC including institutional factors such as good leadership, training, but also investigated self-efficacy and personal or demographic factors such as knowledge (perception) about IPC.
9. Were the authors' discussions and conclusions justified by the results?	1	Authors touched on most of the results and compared their findings with other published studies. For example that 99% of HCWs in the survey were aware about the effectiveness of hand hygiene against health care associated infection, and that this awareness was attributed to formal training attended previously by the respondents. They relate this to Nteli et al. (2012) who also reported that educational activities were important factor to improve health-care workers hand hygiene practices.
10. Was ethical approval or consent of participants attained?	1	Authors indicate that Ethical considerations were addressed by seeking the ethical approval from the Infection Control and Prevention Committee of the hospital.
Total Score	9/10	Excellent
<p>Notes: Modified AXIS Tool to also include 10 of the 18 questions in the critical appraisal tool to assess the quality of cross-sectional studies (AXIS); Downes MJ, et al. <i>BMJ Open</i> 2016;6:e011458. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2016-011458. Similar assessment was done for other cross-sectional studies such as Rabaan et al. (2017), Ward 2013; Haridi, Al-Ammar& Al-Mansour (2016), Quan et al. (2015), and Auyb et al., 2013.</p>		

Risk assessment tool	Were the aims/objectives of the study clear?	Was the study design appropriate for the stated aim(s)?	Was the target/reference population clearly defined? (Is it clear who the research was about?)	Was the cohort recruited in an acceptable way, such that the sampled participants could be said to be representative of the target/reference population under investigation?	Were the risk factor and outcome variables measured appropriate to the aims of the study?	Were the basic data adequately described?	Does the response rate raise concerns about non-response bias?	Have the authors taken account of the confounding factors in the design and/or analysis?	Were the authors' discussions and conclusions justified by the results?	Was ethical approval or consent of participants attained?	Total Score
Author (Year)											
Amoran et al. (2013)	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	9
Mortada et al. 2014	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	9
Wetzker et al. 2016	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	5
Walker et al., 2014	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	6
Ayub et al., 2012	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	7
Quan et al., 2015	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	8
Carvalho et al., 2016	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	7
Herbert, 2013	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	8
Rabaan, 2017	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	N/A	9
Mazi et al., 2013	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	6
Offner et al., 2016	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	6
Haridi et al., 2016	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	8
Luo et al., 2010	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	9
Osazuwa-Peters et al., 2010	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9
Piai-Morais et al., 2015	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	9

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Hosseinial hashemi et al., 2015	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	9
Abdulraheman et al., 2012	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	9
Song et al., 2013	1	1	0	1	1	0	N/A	1	1	0	6
Tan and Jeffrey 2015	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	9

Key:

Yes: **1**

No: **0**

Not applicable: **N/A**

Total: A combination of all the '1' in a study

APPENDIX V: Critical appraisal of Qualitative studies

Study name	Shah et al. (2015)	A Qualitative survey of perceptions of Clinical staff at a National Health Service hospital group in London, UK
Study question	Response Yes = 1 No = 0	How is the question addressed in the study
1. Was there a clear statement of the aims of the research?	1	The authors indicated that the aim of the study was to identify how appraisals of IPC duties and social and environmental circumstances shaped and influenced non-compliance with IPC
2. Is a qualitative methodology appropriate?	1	As the study wanted to investigate how HCWs rationalize their own behaviour and the behaviour of others and to describe the context of the working environment that may explain inconsistencies in IPC practices. These concepts can only be explored through a qualitative study design
3. Was the research design appropriate to address the aims of the research?	1	The authors used Semi-structured interviews were conducted at three tertiary hospitals in London, UK. Eligible participants were doctors, pharmacists, nurses or midwives working in any of the hospitals, with regular contact with patients and/or prescription of antimicrobials.
4. Was the recruitment strategy appropriate to the aims of the research?	1	Potential participants were identified from staff lists provided by the Human Resources Department. Staff lists were used for sampling in order to achieve maximum variation. Recruitment was done through stratified sampling, staff were grouped by profession, hospital site and seniority. This must have helped to achieve good representation of different professionals in the hospital.
5. Was the data collected in a way that addressed the research issue?	1	Semi-structured interview questions were developed following the systematic reviews of the literature and guidance from experienced IPC practitioners. Study invitations were sent via e-mail, with a follow-up sent two weeks later. Topics included IPC, HCAIs, antimicrobial prescribing and catheter management, with questions on

		beliefs about HCAIs, rationalization of HCAI prevention activities, barriers encountered during practice, and definitions about the participant's role and the roles of others.
6. Has the relationship between researcher and participants been adequately considered?	1	Participants were coded using numbers, and interview data were anonymized using this coding system. All interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim.
7. Have ethical issues been taken into consideration?	1	Study procedures were approved by the UK National Research Ethics Service. Written informed consent was obtained prior to interviews. This seems to satisfy good clinical research practice guidelines.
8. Was the data analysis sufficiently rigorous?	1	An inductive approach was used to analyse the data. Participant's responses were coded using a deductive framework for data indexing. Initial concepts about HCWs' behaviour and sources of non-compliance were identified and categorized according to themes identified in systematic reviews.
9. Is there a clear statement of findings?	1	Key themes emerging from the analysis were: attribution of responsibility; prioritization and risk appraisal; and hierarchy of influence.
10. How valuable is the research?	0	Mitigating the risk of HCAI requires eliminating ambiguity through negotiation of personal responsibility, together with locally relevant policies. The results of the study could be used to design IPC interventions that achieve sustained behavioural change. Participants in this study were recruited from one organization and local norms may differ elsewhere.
Total Score	9/10	Excellent
Notes: Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (2018). CASP Qualitative Checklist. Similar qualitative quality assessment was conducted for other qualitative studies such as Edet et al. (2017), Efstathiou et al. (2011), Shah et al. (2015), Walker et al. (2014), Ward (2012), etc.		

APPENDIX VI: Critical appraisal of Mixed Methods studies

Study name	Ng, Shaban and van de Mortel (2017)	Healthcare professionals' hand hygiene knowledge and beliefs in the United Arab Emirates
Study question	Response Yes = 1 No = 0	How is the question addressed in the study
1. Was the aim of the paper clearly stated?	1	Hand hygiene compliance averaged 47.5% in the USA, despite it being clearly identified by the WHO as important in infection prevention, hence a challenge. The authors aimed at understanding the factors hindering compliance
2. Did the authors justify why a mixed methods design is the best strategy to convey the overall complexity of the topic or study phenomenon?	1	The authors argued that literature suggests that enhancing compliance is not simply related to effort, but is highly dependent on altering behavioural perceptions. Hence the need to understand the motivators and barriers to change and potential reasons for non-compliance. These concepts could not be understood by just conducting a quantitative study, therefore the study design they adopted is justifiable.
3. How was the sample (events, persons, times and settings) selected? (For example, theoretically informed, purposive, convenience, chosen to explore contrasts)?	1	The authors indicate that they conducted a mixed-methods study: an anonymous electronic survey of nurses (n = 550) and doctors (n = 250) working in the hospital, followed by qualitative focus group sessions with a subset of participants recruited through convenience sampling. The approach the authors used is the standard way of doing mixed-methods studies, as there is need for focus groups to represent all areas of intended study population, hence use of purposive sampling is standard way of achieving this.
4. Is the sample (informants, settings and events) appropriate to the aims of the study?	1	The study was survey of nurses (n = 550) and doctors (n = 250) working in the hospital, followed by qualitative focus group sessions with a subset of participants. As the aim was to understand barriers to non-compliance with hand hygiene, such reasons can only be obtained from practicing health care workers. So this choice of participants seems reasonable.
5. What data collection methods were used in the study? (Provide insight into: data	1	The quantitative survey employed a structured questionnaire, whereas the focus group discussion employed a series of

collected, appropriateness and availability for independent analysis)		open-ended questions based on work by O'Boyle et al. (2001)
6. What outcome criteria were used in the study?	1	Association between beliefs and attitudes and practice and thematic analysis of concepts from the focus group discussion to understand the barriers and facilitators to compliance with infection control.
7. How were the data analysed? Is there sufficient breadth (e.g. contrast of two or more perspective) and depth (e.g. insight into a single perspective)?	1	An independent-samples-t-test was used to compare the mean scores of hand hygiene beliefs by profession as the data were normally distributed based on the results of the Kolmogorov–Smirnov statistic and Levene's Test for Equality of Variances. Data from focus groups underwent content analysis, which enabled data to be categorized into specific themes and concepts, shifting from the general to the specific according to the range of likeness and disparities
8. Are the findings interpreted within the context of the studies aim and theory?	1	Both results for quantitative survey and focus group have been reported with tables and appropriate statistics for the quantitate analysis and thematic analysis summaries using tables including verbatim
9. How adequate is the data analysis? (For example, were important confounding variables controlled in the quantitative analysis and Are the researcher's own position, assumptions and possible biases outlined?)	1	All data was analysed properly and confounders controlled for.
10. To what setting are the study findings generalizable? (For example, is the setting typical or representative of care settings and in what respects? If the setting is atypical, will this present a stronger or weaker test of the hypothesis?)	0	The authors reported that the exact response rate is unknown as the population sample size had to be approximated. They also acknowledge that selection bias towards HCP with an interest in hand hygiene. There was a low response rate of doctors, high for nurses which means the views might mostly represent those of nurses. Participation into focus groups was sometimes forced by seniors.
Total Score	9/10	Excellent
Notes: Modified HCPRDU Evaluation tool for mixed methods studies. Long, A.F., Godfrey, M, Randall, T, Brettle, A and Grant, MJ (2002). Similar qualitative quality assessment was conducted for the other mixed methods study i.e. Bai (2015)		

Risk assessment tool	Was the aim of the paper clearly stated?	Did the authors justify why a mixed methods design is the best strategy to convey the overall complexity of the topic or study phenomenon?	How was the sample (events, persons, times and settings) selected? (For example, theoretically informed, purposive, convenience, chosen to explore contrasts)?	Is the sample (informants, settings and events) appropriate to the aims of the study?	What data collection methods were used in the study? (Provide insight into: data collected, appropriateness and availability for independent analysis)	What outcome criteria were used in the study?	How were the data analysed? Is there sufficient breadth (e.g. contrast of two or more perspective) and depth (e.g. insight into a single perspective)?	Are the findings interpreted within the context of the studies aim and theory?	How adequate is the data analysis? (For example, were important confounding variables controlled in the quantitative analysis and Are the researcher's own position, assumptions and possible biases outlined?)	To what setting are the study findings generalizable? (For example, is the setting typical or representative of care settings and in what respects? If the setting is atypical, will this present a stronger or weaker test of the hypothesis?	Total Score
Author (Year)											
Ng, Shaban and van de Mortel (2017)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	9
Bai, 2015	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	10

APPENDIX VII: Critical appraisal of Systematic Reviews

Study name	Smiddy et al. (2015)	Systematic qualitative literature review of Health professionals' compliance with hand hygiene guidelines
Study question	Response Yes = 1 No = 0	How is the question addressed in the study
1. Did the review address a clearly focused question?	1	Authors indicate that HCWs compliance with hand hygiene guidelines, reduces this risk. They argue that there are has been no previous attempt to summarise evidence from qualitative research in this area, and therefore aimed at systematically review the qualitative literature.
2. Did the authors look for the right type of papers?	1	Authors indicate that Based on the work of Sandelowski, they sought to systematically identify, explore, and describe similar qualitative studies so as to gain a better understanding of their shared meanings
3. Do you think all the important, relevant studies were included?	1	The authors reported that they conducted a systematically searching of literature
4. Did the review's authors do enough to assess quality of the included studies?	1	It is reported that two reviewers independently appraised the studies using a standard quality assessment tool and that differences of opinion were resolved through discussion, and appraisal was completed by a third reviewer.
5. If the results of the review have been combined, was it reasonable to do so?	1	Qualitative data regarding health care workers' compliance with hand hygiene guidelines were extracted and transcribed. Two researchers independently analysed the data by reading it repeatedly, identifying and coding recurrent themes as they emerged. The codes were compared and contrasted and agreed on through discussion and debate. Broader themes were identified and discussed until a consensus was achieved. It was reasonable and standard procedure to extract and group data into themes, as it is likely reasons for compliance would fall into many themes.
6. What are the overall results of the review?	1	The authors included 10 studies. Evidence from these studies showed that the factors that impact on health care workers' compliance with hand hygiene guidelines fall into 2 broad

		categories: 1). Individual factors that motivate health care workers' compliance, 2). Work environment characteristics that influenced how health care workers complied with hand hygiene guidelines. Individual motivational factors included: social influences, the acuity of patient care, self-protection, and use of cues. Institutional factors included: resources, knowledge, information, and organizational culture.
7. Were all important outcomes considered?	1	Covered both individual and institutional factors that could act as barriers or facilitators to compliance with infection control
8. How precise are the results?	1	Using a theoretical perspective provides the philosophical stance that informs the methodology of the research. It also provides a context, and grounds it in logic. The authors used a conceptual framework to building a cumulative understanding of the topic under investigation. They also systematically reviewed the qualitative literature on this subject.
9. Are the benefits worth the harms and costs?	1	The findings are in keeping with the larger body of quantitative research on health care workers' compliance with hand hygiene guidelines. Quantitative studies generally use a reductionist approach focusing on single dimensions, such as alcohol hand rubs or education, and their effect on health care workers' compliance with hand hygiene guidelines. The work presented here offers an inductive approach. It provides an opportunity to explore the phenomenon of interest with the potential for the data analysis to lead a theoretical understanding of the phenomenon of interest.
10. Can the results be applied to the local population?	0	The authors indicated that the quality of all the 10 included studies was poor and that there is generally a paucity of good quality empirical qualitative research in relation to health care workers' compliance with hand hygiene guidelines. The exclusion of studies published in languages other than English may have impacted on the richness of the data included in this review.
Total Score	9/10	Excellent
Notes: Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (2018). CASP Systematic Review Checklist. Similar quality assessment was conducted for the other Systematic Reviews, i.e. Allegranzi and Pittet (2009), Hessels and Larson (2016), and Hale et al. (2015).		

Risk assessment tool	Did the review address a clearly focused question?	Did the authors look for the right type of papers?	Do you think all the important, relevant studies were included?	Did the review's authors do enough to assess quality of the included studies?	If the results of the review have been combined, was it reasonable to do so?	What are the overall results of the review?	Were all important outcomes considered?	How precise are the results?	Are the benefits worth the harms and costs?	Can the results be applied to the local population?	Total Score
Author (Year)											
Smiddy et al. (2015)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	9
Hale et al. (2015)	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	8
Hessels and Larson (2016),	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9
Allegranzi and Pittet (2009)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10

APPENDIX VIII: Critical appraisal of Narrative Reviews

Study name	De Bono et al. (2014)	Organizational culture and its implications for infection prevention and control in healthcare institutions
Study question	Response Yes = 1 No = 0	How is the question addressed in the study
1. Was there a clear Statement of concrete aims or formulation of question(s)	1	To examine the inter-relationship between organizational culture and HCWs attitudes with compliance with infection control guidelines
2. Was the article's importance for the readership, justified?	1	The Geneva model for hospital infection control, has been the basis of most international initiatives aimed at improving hand hygiene compliance. However, its introduction within other healthcare institutions, using a similar methodology, have often failed to replicate success. The authors further argue that Gould et al. attribute this discrepancy to organizational culture.
3. Was the literature search strategy described including search terms and inclusion criteria	0	The authors indicate that previous literature is reviewed and synthesized, using both IPC journals as well as publications focusing on human behaviour and organizational change. However, like all if not most narrative reviews, details of how exactly literature was identified like search terms and databases, and the inclusion and exclusion criteria are not provided or described.
4. Were the Key statements supported by references	1	Examples: "Not surprisingly, low correlation is often reported between self-reported and observed compliance of IPC practices such as hand hygiene (57)" and "Effective IPC relies directly upon the successful interplay of multiple management systems, which in turn are strongly influenced by corporate culture (23)"
5. Are the referencing of key statements inconsistent throughout the manuscript	1	In most places there is good referencing, however as expected in a narrative review, there are places where the author expressed their opinion.

<p>6. Can you conclude that the articles arguments are based on sound scientific reasoning?</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>For example the authors referenced literature do support the assertion as in the statement: “On the other hand, there appears to be a consensus that OC is historically and socially constructed, holistic and difficult to change.²² As a result, changing OC elements that are uncondusive for effective IPC practice promises to be a formidable task.”</p>
<p>7. Is there evidence that Appropriate evidence is introduced selectively</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>No there is no selective reporting</p>
<p>8. Is data presented appropriately? For example if quantitative data are the relative risk estimates, such as Odds Ratios and their confidence intervals provided</p>	<p>1</p>	<p>There has been good use of diagrams to explain few theories used in the arguments of the manuscript</p>
<p>Total Score</p>	<p>7/8</p>	<p>Excellent</p>
<p>Notes: Modified SANRA-a scale for the quality assessment of narrative review articles. Baethge C, Goldbeck-Wood S, Mertens S. 2002. The review included only one Narrative review, therefore no Similar quality assessment was conducted for another narrative review study.</p>		

Risk assessment tool	Was there a clear Statement of concrete aims or formulation of question(s)	Was the article's importance for the readership, justified?	Was the literature search strategy described including search terms and inclusion criteria	Were the Key statements supported by references	Are the referencing of key statements inconsistent throughout the manuscript	Can you conclude that the articles arguments are based on sound scientific reasoning?	Is there evidence that Appropriate evidence is introduced selectively	Is data presented appropriately? For example if quantitative data are the relative risk estimates, such as Odds Ratios and their confidence intervals provided	Total Score
Author (Year)									
De Bono et al. (2014)	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	7

INTRODUCTION

This survey aims to explore healthcare workers' (in particular physicians and nurses) perceptions of regulatory implementation of infection prevention and control within Saudi Arabia. The findings of the survey will be used within a larger study to determine the extent of, and influencing factors on, the regulatory compliance-concordance relationship within the multinational context of infection prevention and control regulatory implementation.

You have been asked to take part in this survey as you are a physician or nurse currently working in HOSPITAL 1 or HOSPITAL 2 within the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Please ensure you have read the information sheet provided, and if you are happy to take part, then please continue to question 1 (of 31 questions). By completing and submitting the questionnaire/survey, you are consenting to participate in this part of the study.

The survey will take approx 15-30 minutes to complete - you require to give a response to each question.

Thank you for considering taking part.

Focus of interview/ schedule of questions: Core components for infection prevention and control programmes (WHO, 2011):

- Organisation of IPC programmes - CULTURE;
- Technical guidelines;
- Human resources (training, staffing, occupational health – STAFF DEVELOPMENT);
- Surveillance of diseases and of compliance with IPC practices - MONITORING;
- Microbiology laboratory support;
- Clean and safe environment - RESOURCES;
- Monitoring and evaluation of IPC programmes - MONITORING;

Links with public health and other services.

Use 5-point Likert scale where appropriate
(strongly agree/agree/neither agree nor disagree/disagree/strongly disagree)

QUESTIONNAIRE: The Regulation of Infection Control – KSA Survey 2016

SECTION 1: DEMOGRAPHICS

Section 1 of this survey aims to find out a bit about you and your work.

Please consider the following questions, and answer as instructed.

1. What is your profession? Choose the most appropriate response by selecting from the following options.

Answer by marking a cross against your chosen option. If you are not a physician or nurse, please do not continue with this survey.

- Nurse (registered/ licensed)
- Nurse (unregistered/ unlicensed)
- Physician

2. What is your gender? Choose the most appropriate response by selecting from the following options.

Answer by marking a cross against your chosen option.

- Male
- Female

3. What age band do you fit within? Choose the most appropriate response by selecting from the following options.

Answer by marking a cross against your chosen option.

- Between 20-34 years
- Between 35-49 years
- 50 years or over

4. What is the highest level of academic qualification you have achieved? Choose the most appropriate response by selecting from the following options.

Answer by marking a cross against your chosen option.

- Diploma
- Bachelor
- Master
- Board
- Ph.D

5. What is your country of origin/ home nationality? Respond by writing your answer in the text box below.

6. In which hospital do you currently work? Choose the most appropriate response by selecting from the following options.

Answer by marking a cross against your chosen option.

- HOSPITAL 1
- HOSPITAL 2

Section 2 of this survey aims to find out about your perceptions/views of infection control.

Consider your experiences of infection control/ infection control practices within your work at HOSPITAL 1/HOSPITAL 2 and share your views by reading and responding as instructed to each of the following statements.

7. Infection control in this ward/department is good.

Answer by marking a cross against your chosen option

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

8. Infection prevention and control in this hospital is good.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

9. Infection prevention and control in this ward/ department could be better

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

10. Infection prevention and control in this hospital could be better

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

11. This ward/ dept is prepared in the event of an infection control outbreak/ incident

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

12. This hospital is prepared in the event of an infection control outbreak/ incident

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

13. There is good infection prevention and control leadership within the ward/ dept

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

14. There is good infection prevention and control leadership within the hospital

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

15. The ward/ dept has a set of guidelines that I can access to support my infection prevention and control practices

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

16. I am offered sufficient levels of training to support good infection prevention and control practice

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

17. I need more education and training to support good infection prevention and control practice

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

18. I feel the need to attend the education and training sessions provided to me

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

19. I can provide good infection prevention and control without the need for further education and training

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

20. The hospital has a set of guidelines that I can access to support my infection prevention and control practices

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

21. No one checks on my infection prevention and control practice

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

22. The ward/ dept provides sufficient resources to enable me to prevent and control infection during care delivery

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

23. I am always aware of the infection prevention and control surveillance going on in the ward/ dept

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

24. I am always aware of the infection prevention and control surveillance going on in the hospital

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

25. There are staff who do not practice good infection prevention and control

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

26. There are never any gloves when you need them

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

27. Nursing staff are blamed if there is an outbreak in the ward/ dept

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

28. Nursing staff are blamed if there is an outbreak in the hospital

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

29. Medical staff are blamed if there is an outbreak in the ward/ dept

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

30. Medical staff are blamed if there is an outbreak in the hospital

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

31. Staff are supported to improve their infection prevention and control practice

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	2	3	4	5

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THANKS

You may be interested to know that this study also involves qualitative semi-structured interviews and non-participant observation - so watch out for the information on these aspects of the study and consider if you wish to participate.

Meantime, thank you for taking the time to complete this survey. Your support with this study is greatly appreciated, and your contribution will support better understanding of infection control/infection control practice within KSA.

Please submit your completed questionnaire to the sealed box within one of the following offices, where it will be stored confidentially until uplift by the researcher:

1. Hospital Infection Prevention and Control Unit office
2. Ward/department Supervisor or Coordinator office
3. Hospital Medical Director office

Draft Data Collection Tool

Thank you for agreeing to participate

- Information sheet re-cap
- Consent form
- Recording of interview
- Right to withdraw/ stop at any time
- Time – 1-hour approx.

Introduce self

- PhD researcher
- Study
- No right/wrong answers

Icebreakers

- Tell me a bit about yourself
- Tell me a bit about your work here at HOSPITAL 2/HOSPITAL 1?

Focus of interview/schedule of questions: Core components for infection prevention and control programmes (WHO, 2011):

- Organisation of IPC programmes - CULTURE;
- Technical guidelines;
- Human resources (training, staffing, occupational health – STAFF DEVELOPMENT);
- Surveillance of diseases and of compliance with IPC practices - MONITORING;
- Microbiology laboratory support;
- Clean and safe environment - RESOURCES;
- Monitoring and evaluation of IPC programmes - MONITORING;

Links with public health and other services.

Specific prompts

1. Tell me how you feel about infection prevention and control generally in the ward/ dept?
2. What do you know about the...or have you ever been involved in any infection prevention and control policy development?
3. Can you tell me a bit about the education and training (staff development) that takes place here to support infection prevention and control?
4. How might you describe the resources available to you for supporting good infection prevention and control practice?
5. Can you tell me how you feel about the monitoring of infection prevention and control?
6. How would you describe the organisational culture in terms of infection prevention and control?
7. How might infection prevention and control be better, if that is possible?
 - a. What makes you feel like that?
 - b. Why do you say that?
 - c. Can you explain that a bit more?
 - d. Etc
8. Anything else you would like to add/anything else you would like to ask?

Close - Thanks

**The regulation of infection control – A
comparison of infection control perspectives
(perceptions and compliance) across
Scotland and Saudi Arabia**

**Participant (Saudi Arabia) Interview Consent
Form (May 2016 – V1)**

Personal details withheld.

Please initial box

- 1 I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet (dated May 2016) for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions. c
- 2 I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason, or rights being affected. c
- 3 I understand that the information gathered during this interview will be recorded, analysed and used to report/publish on the issue of infection prevention and control. I give permission for my contribution to be utilised in this way and as part of the collective findings. c
- 4 I agree to take part in the above study. c

Name of Participant:

Signature:

Date:

Name of person taking consent (if different from researcher):

Signature:

Date:

Name of researcher:

Signature:

Date:

1 copy for participant and 1 for researcher

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APPENDIX XII: Observational Data Collection Tool

Ward/ Dept Demographics

Record notes on ward size/ bed numbers/ classification Record number of medical/ nursing staff on duty Any other initial field notes
--

Hand Hygiene Hours/Time (24-hour clock)	1-3	4-6	7-9	10-12	13-15	16-18	19-21	22-24	Comments
Before performing hand hygiene: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● expose forearms; ● remove all hand/wrist jewellery (a single, plain metal finger ring is permitted but should be removed (or moved up) during hand hygiene); ● ensure fingernails are clean, short and that artificial nails or nail products are not worn; and ● cover all cuts or abrasions with a waterproof dressing. 									
To perform hand hygiene: Alcohol Based Hand Rubs (ABHRs) must be available for staff as near to point of care as possible. Where this is not practical, personal ABHR dispensers should be used. Perform hand hygiene: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. before touching a patient; 2. before clean/aseptic procedures. If ABHR cannot be used then antimicrobial soap should be used; 3. after body fluid exposure risk; 4. after touching a patient; and 5. after touching a patient's immediate surroundings. 									
Wash hands with non-antimicrobial liquid soap and water if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● hands are visibly soiled or dirty; or ● caring for a patient with a suspected or known gastro-intestinal infection e.g. norovirus or a spore forming organism such as Clostridium difficile. 									
Respiratory and Cough Hygiene Hours/Time (24-hour clock)	1-3	4-6	7-9	10-12	13-15	16-18	19-21	22-24	Comments
Cover the nose and mouth with a disposable tissue when sneezing, coughing, wiping and blowing the nose. Dispose of all used tissues promptly into a waste bin. Wash hands with non-antimicrobial liquid soap and warm water after coughing, sneezing, using tissues, or after contact with respiratory secretions or objects contaminated by these secretions. Hand wipes should not be used by staff in the hospital or care home setting for hand hygiene unless there is no running water available. Staff may use hand wipes followed by ABHR and should wash their hands at the first available opportunity. Keep contaminated hands away from the eyes nose and mouth. Staff should promote respiratory and cough hygiene helping those (e.g. elderly, children) who need assistance with this e.g. providing patients with tissues, plastic bags for used tissues and hand hygiene facilities as necessary.									
PPE Hours/Time (24-hour clock)	1-3	4-6	7-9	10-12	13-15	16-18	19-21	22-24	Comments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● located close to the point of use; ● stored to prevent contamination in a clean/dry area until required for use (expiry dates must be adhered to); ● single-use only items unless specified by the manufacturer; and ● disposed of after use into the correct waste stream i.e. healthcare waste or domestic waste. 									

University of the West of Scotland

<p>Reusable PPE items, e.g. non-disposable goggles/face shields/visors must have a decontamination schedule with responsibility assigned.</p>										
<p>Gloves must be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● worn when exposure to blood and/or other body fluids is anticipated/likely;² ● changed immediately after each patient and/or following completion of a procedure or task; ● changed if a perforation or puncture is suspected; and ● appropriate for use, fit for purpose and well-fitting to avoid excessive sweating and interference with dexterity. <p>Double gloving is recommended during some Exposure Prone Procedures (EPPs) e.g. orthopaedic and gynaecological operations or when attending major trauma incidents.</p>										
<p>Aprons must be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● worn to protect uniform or clothes when contamination is anticipated/likely e.g. when in direct care contact with a patient; and ● changed between patients and/or following completion of a procedure or task. <p>Full body gowns/Fluid repellent coveralls must be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● worn when there is a risk of extensive splashing of blood and/or other body fluids e.g. in the operating theatre; and ● changed between patients and immediately after completion of a procedure or task. 										
<p>Eye/face protection (including full face visors) must be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● worn if blood and/or body fluid contamination to the eyes/face is anticipated/likely e.g. by members of the surgical theatre team and always during Aerosol Generating Procedures. Regular corrective spectacles are not considered eye protection 										
<p>Any other field notes/ observations</p>										

Reference: Derived from requirements of SICP (NHS Scotland) (NHS NSS, 2016)

Appendix XIII: Ethical approval, University of West of Scotland

Ref: MAC/JB

School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery
Hamilton Campus
Caird Building
HAMILTON
ML3 0QA
Tel +44(0)1698 283100
Fax +44 (0)1698 282131

20/05/2016

Adil Abalkhail

Dear Adil,

Outcome of School of Health Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee

Thank you for your recent submission to the above Committee.

I can confirm your submission (SEC/SHNM/MAY16/061) was reviewed by the Committee, where the outcome has been:

- **APPROVED - subject to External Body Approval(s)**
- **APPROVED - subject to required (compulsory) changes (under guidance of supervisor)**

This outcome requires you to refer to feedback, and address issues under guidance of supervisor.

Feedback from the Committee is attached for your information.

On behalf of the School Ethics Committee, I take this opportunity to wish you well with your study.

Yours sincerely,

Personal details withheld.

Appendix XIV: Ethical approval from MOH in Al- Qassim region KSA

Personal details withheld.

Appendix XV: Ethical Approval, Buraidah Central Hospital (Hospital 2)

Personal details withheld.

Appendix XVI: Ethical approval, King Fahd Specialist Hospital (Hospital 1)

Personal details withheld.

Appendix XVII: Observational study Notice

The regulation of infection control – A comparison of infection control perspectives (perceptions and compliance) across Scotland and Saudi Arabia

ATTENTION ALL STAFF AND PATIENTS

During the month of August 2016, observational research of healthcare workers will be conducted in this area

Information has been issued to:

- 1. Participating healthcare worker**
- 2. Patients who may be indirectly involved**

NOTE

At no point in this research is any patient being observed

Please ask the nurse in charge for information

Please alert the nurse in charge if you do not wish to be involved directly or indirectly

Thank you for your co-operation during this period.

Personal details withheld.

Appendix XVIII: Descriptive statistics of IPC section

Q	N	Missing	MIN	MAX	MEAN	Std. Deviation	1(Strongly agree)	2(Agree)	3(Neither agree nor disagree)	4(Disagree)	5(Strongly disagree)
Quality of Infection control services in the hospital/ward											
Infection control in this ward/department is good.	433	0	1	5	2.00	.733	93	272	46	21	1
Infection prevention and control in this hospital is good.	433	0	1	5	2.07	.780	84	265	54	27	2
Infection prevention and control in this ward/department could be better.	433	0	1	5	1.91	.682	110	261	53	8	1
Infection prevention and control in this hospital could be better.	433	0	1	5	1.91	.711	117	251	55	8	2
Preparedness about outbreaks											
This ward/department is prepared in the event of an infection control outbreak/ incident.	433	0	1	5	2.22	.841	64	258	69	37	5
This hospital is prepared in the event of an infection control outbreak/ incident.	433	0	1	5	2.24	.861	62	258	70	35	8
Hospital leadership on infection control											
There is good infection prevention and control leadership within the ward/ department.	433	0	1	5	2.16	.832	75	253	70	30	5
There is good infection prevention and control leadership within the hospital.	433	0	1	5	2.15	.811	75	257	67	31	3

Guidelines and policies											
The ward/ department has a set of guidelines that I can access to support my infection prevention and control practices.	433	0	1	5	1.97	.762	102	268	41	18	4
The hospital has a set of guidelines that I can access to support my infection prevention and control practices.	433	0	1	5	1.97	.701	97	270	51	41	1
Training and support											
I am offered sufficient levels of training to support good infection prevention and control practice.	433	0	1	5	2.14	.795	69	273	59	27	5
I need more education and training to support good infection prevention and control practice.	433	0	1	5	2.08	.744	76	271	61	24	1
I feel the need to attend the education and training sessions provided to me.	433	0	1	5	2.09	.735	71	278	60	22	2
I can provide good infection prevention and control without the need for further education and training.	433	0	1	5	2.79	.977	25	178	98	125	7
Surveillance, monitoring and evaluation of infection control											

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No one checks on my infection prevention and control practice.	433	0	1	5	3.36	1.027	23	72	101	200	37
I am always aware of the infection prevention and control surveillance going on in the ward/ department.	433	0	1	5	2.24	.833	54	274	60	39	6
I am always aware of the infection prevention and control surveillance going on in the hospital.	433	0	1	5	2.20	.808	57	278	60	32	6
There are staff who do not practice good infection prevention and control.	433	0	1	5	2.82	1.104	51	138	97	130	17
Supplies and infection control resources											
The ward/ department does not provide sufficient resources to enable me to prevent and control infection during care delivery.	433	0	1	5	3.30	1.037	16	105	81	197	34
There are never any gloves when you need them.	433	0	1	5	3.66	1.042	31	63	66	207	84
Supportive or blame culture on infection control at the hospitals											
Nursing staff are blamed if there is an outbreak in the ward/ department.	433	0	1	5	3.00	1.128	38	122	111	124	38
Nursing staff are blamed if there is an outbreak in the hospital.	433	0	1	5	3.04	1.104	34	116	116	131	36
Physicians are blamed if there is an outbreak in the ward/ department.	433	0	1	5	3.18	.983	20	87	148	149	29
Physicians are blamed if there is an outbreak in the hospital.	433	0	1	5	3.25	.988	18	81	142	157	35

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Staff are supported to improve their infection prevention and control practice.	433	0	1	5	2.09	.876	97	245	52	33	6
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